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EDITORIAL NOTE

Zamfara International Journal of Education (ZIJE) is the official Journal of the Faculty of Education, Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria. The Journal publishes article of diverse fields of interest in education. Papers reporting original research and extended version of already established conference and journal articles are welcomed. Papers for publication are selected through peer review process to ensure originality, relevance and readability. ZIJE is published bi-annually June and December.

The aim and scope of the journal is to provide an academic medium and an important reference for the advancement and dissemination of information that supports high level learning, teaching and research in the fields of education.

This edition, Volume 4, Number 2, April, 2024 is poised to present research reports in the following fields of education: Educational Foundations, Science Education, Educational Psychology, Curriculum & Instructional Technology, Guidance & Counselling, Philosophy & History of Education, Sociology of Education, Entrepreneurship Education, Special and Inclusive Education, Physical & Health Education, Religious Education, Gender Studies, Peace & Security Education among others. The articles in this volume are academic and professional discourse written by reputable scholars in their areas of specialization.

The Board remain indebted to its editorial members for the ceaseless support given towards successful publication of the Journal. In the same vein, we acknowledge quite sincerely the assistance and support of our esteemed consulting editors for ensuring the credibility of this edition. Also worthy of appreciation are the authors and their immense contributions to this publication.

Associate Professor Umar Sodangi
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CALL FOR ARTICLES

The Editorial Board of Zamfara International Journal of Education (ZIJE) calls for scholarly articles for review and possible publication in its next edition (Volume 4, Number 3). ZIJE publishes articles that emphasize on research development and application within the field of Education. All manuscripts are reviewed by editorial review committee. Contributions must be original, not previously or simultaneously published elsewhere, and are critically reviewed before they are published. Papers, which must be written in English Language, should have good grammar and proper terminologies. Also note that prospective articles are subjected to plagiarism assessment to estimate the percentage of originality of the papers. Hence, plagiarism threshold of $\leq 20\%$ is recommended.

Editorial Guidelines

1. Manuscripts including references, appendices, tables and diagrams should be double-spaced and single coded on A4 paper with generous margins (at least 1”/2.5cm).
2. Title should be explicit and not more than 19 words.
3. Title page should be arranged as follows: Title, author(s) full name, affiliation, full addresses, email addresses and phone numbers.
4. Abstract should be single line and not more than 250 words.
5. For conceptual papers, the body should have appropriate headings where necessary.
6. For empirical papers, it should be presented in the following order: Introduction, Objectives of the study, Research Questions and/or Hypotheses, Methodology, Results, Discussion of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations.
7. Acknowledgement (if any).
8. Quotations of more than 40 words should be indented and typed single spacing with indication of the pages where the quotes were lifted.
9. In-text citations should follow the APA 7th edition format.
10. References should be in range with 7th edition of APA Style.
11. Each table and figure should be presented within the manuscripts, with a brief and self-explanatory title.
12. All text within the table should be clearly legible, and all graphics and legends should be easily distinguished when printed in black and white.
13. Tables should be in horizontal lines only, with only blank space to separate columns.
14. Tables and figures that may be included in the main text of the paper should be numbered separately, in the sequence that they are mentioned in the text.
15. Figures should be saved in a neutral data format such as JPEG, TIFF or EPS.

Submission of Manuscripts & Assessment Fee

Manuscripts should be submitted directly to the Editor-in-Chief or Publication Editor through the following e-mail address: zijefugusau@gmail.com. Articles can be submitted between the periods of January to April ending for June publication, while July to October ending for December publication. Assessment fee for manuscript is #5,000.00 only.

Associate Professor Abubakar Sadiq Haruna

Publication Editor

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Assessment of Ability and Competency on Application of Psychometric Properties of Test Instrument among Primary School Teachers in Delta State

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Abstract

This study assessed primary school teachers' ability and competency in the application of psychometric properties of test instruments among primary school teachers. The design for the study is a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consists of 893 (Ethiophe East 482 and Okpe local government area 411) primary school teachers during the 2023/2024 academic session in Delta State public schools. A sample of 50 teachers each from the targeted population in the two local government areas using a multi-stage sampling technique. The instrument for the research was a self-assessment inventory constructed by the researcher known as the Psychometric Ability and Competence Inventory for Teachers (PACIT). The instrument was validated by a measurement and evaluation expert for validity while reliability was determined using the split-half method with a coefficient of 0.86. The instrument was administered to the teachers and data collected were analysed using statistical mean. The result revealed that most primary school teachers in the two local government areas of Delta State lack the ability and competencies to establish the psychometric properties of test instruments. The following conclusions were drawn; that primary school teachers lack the ability and competency to establish psychometric properties of tests, the teachers' pay little attention to the psychometric properties which are the standard qualities of a good test and they also lack the basic skills required for the establishment of psychometric properties. It was recommended that primary school teachers need to be informed and retrained on the importance of psychometric properties of tests.

Keywords: Assessment, Ability, Competency, Psychometric properties and Primary school teachers.

Introduction

Most teachers in our educational system today take teaching as a last resort, probably due to the country's high unemployment rate. Osadebe (2015) pointed out that most teachers are not trained as they lack teaching methodology and the ability to evaluate students. Many of them are B.Sc and B.A holders but find their way to classrooms because there are no proper laws regulating the teaching profession in Nigeria. Those who are even trained teachers with NCE, B.Ed, B.Sc(Ed) and B.A(Ed) show a nonchalant attitude towards item writing and establishment of psychometric properties of tests. Kolak (2014) reported that most teachers who are in the daily business of teaching and learning lack basic qualities and skills of how to construct and establish psychometric properties of validity, and reliability and how to calculate the difficulty index and discriminative power of test item(s). they end up constructing an instrument that does not measure subject content but mere vocabulary. To carry out this research, the following relevant literature are necessary: Affective-Cognitive Consistency Theory: Visser and Coetzee (2005), pointed out that some of the prepositions of the affective-cognitive consistency theory as it relates to teachers state that teachers should seek consistency in establishing psychometric properties of tests to satisfy the need for simplicity in cognition and adhere to norms, tradition and values that reinforce and help them to maintain the due process in one's cognition and behaviour. Irighweferhe (2022) reported that the classical test theory postulated that an observed score of the individual testee is made up of two components the true score and the error score. The true score is real knowledge of the item possessed by the testee. The error scores are the effect of external factors such as low-test validity and reliability levels. Test scores that lack basic attributes of validity and reliability are indices of error and fail to measure the true ability of the individuals taking the test. This poses a great danger to the result of evaluation and the educational system.

Test validity is the correctness, adequateness and appropriateness of a test in measuring the course content in line with the behavioural objectives. Osiesi (2019) defined the validity of a test as a test that measures the quality or abilities for which it was constructed. Kaur & Singh (2015) emphasize that the validity of a test must be established to ascertain the accuracy and predictions made from the test results. Validity of the test can be established using the

following methods; expert judgment, correlation method, cross-validation methods, expectancy table method and item analysis methods. There are various forms of test validity. These are content validity, construct validity, criterion-related validity, face validity and process validity. The various forms of validity are discussed below:

Content validity is the extent to which the test items may measure the subject matter in any subject area in line with the behavioural objectives. Oji (2011) defined content validity as the systematic examination of the degree to which a research instrument covers a representative sample of the universal content, which may be cognitive, affective or psychomotor. Content validity provides adequate techniques for evaluating the test. The content and the processes are organized into a test plan known as a table of specifications or test blueprint. The number or proportion of test items to be drawn from a given area is based on the relative importance of the area or process. Criterion-related validity refers to the ability of a test to predict someone's performance on something. For example, before actually using a test to predict whether someone will be successful at a particular job, you would first want to determine whether the person is already doing well at that job (the criterion measure) also tends to score high on your proposed test score. It is defined as the extent to which test performance may predict future performance (predictive validity) or estimate present status (concurrent validity). Face validity is the cosmetic or physical appearance or the way that test items are presented. It includes the typing and the general outlook of the test. Process validity is the degree to which the instrument measures academic skills, critical thinking valuing and others that are part of educational objectives.

Kolak (2014) defined reliability as the degree of consistency with which a test score is related when re-examined to the same group of students. The test can give the same information each time is administered. There are various ways of establishing or determining the reliability of a test. These include the test-retest method (measurement of stability), equivalent methods (measures of equivalence), split half method, Kuder-Richardson estimates and Cronbach alpha (measures of internal consistency). The above methods are discussed below:

These methods involve administering the test at two different times, test I and test II. When this is done, the correlation between the two tests is computed. The coefficient obtained from the calculation is used in judging whether the test is reliable or not one major advantage of this method is the ease of administration and procedures. Parallel or Equivalent Method, the basic concern of the test-retest method described above is the determination of an appropriate time interval for the administration of other tests. In order to overcome this problem the parallel or the equivalent method can be developed. The method involves administering two or more parallel forms of test that have been produced in such a way that it seems likely that scores on those alternative forms will be equivalent. To ensure equivalence the items are developed from the same table of specifications. The results of both sets of parallel forms are correlated, thus the reliability of the tests is obtained. Split-Half Method, in this method, only one test is administered once to a group of testees. The responses of the testees are split into two halves for scoring. The first half is the scores of the even number items, while the second half is the scores of the odd number items. The correlation between the two scores is computed. The computed correlation coefficient is subjected to further statistical manipulations. This is because only the half of the test is involved. Therefore, to obtain the reliability of the entire test, Spearman Brown prophecy formula is employed.

that is $r_t = 2r_h$

where r_t = reliability of the whole test

r_h = reliability of half test

1 = constant, 2 = constant

Kuder-Richardson Method; Kuder and Richardson in 1937 developed various statistical formulas for estimating and measuring instrument reliability, but the most widely applicable is the Kuder-Richardson formula 20 (K-R20) and formula 21 (K-R21)

$K-R20 = \frac{\sum p_q}{n-1} \frac{S_x^2}{S^2}$

$K-R21, r_{xx} = \frac{\sum p_q}{n-1} \frac{S_x^2}{S^2}$

Where r_{xx} = reliability of coefficient

p = proportion of testees who got the item right

q = proportion of testees who got the item wrong

\sum = summation of the sign indicating that p_q is summed for all items

p_q = variance of a single test scored dichotomously

S_x = variance of the total test, X = mean of the test

Difficulty Index, Sharma and Sarta (2018) defined the difficulty index as the percentage of testees who correctly answered an item. It ranges from 0% to 100%. Items with higher value are easier. Items with 0.80 and above are very easy items while items with 0.20 and below are difficult items. An ideal test must be of moderate difficult value. Henning (1987) opined that <0.33 high difficulty, 0.34-0.66 medium difficulty and >0.67 low easy difficulty. Discriminative power shows an index of how well an item differentiates between testees who have greater and lesser command of the knowledge of the specific content. It is how adequate an item separates or discriminates between high scores and low scores on an entire test. A good item should be able to separate between 27% high scores and 27% low scores of the item. The discriminative index can be computed using the formula

$$Dp = \frac{Ru - RL}{T}$$

where Ru = number of testees in the upper group who got the item correctly

RL = number of testees in the lower group who got the item right

Key of multiple-choice item, Irihweferhe (2022) defined the key of the multiple-choice item as the option that is the correct answer to the item. He emphasized that the option must be the only one that correctly answers the item and the keyed response must be well-distributed evenly between the positions. Distracters options that are not the correct answers to the items or the wrong answer choice. Each distracter must be plausible and self to attract some candidates. The effective use of psychometric properties of test instruments is important for the accuracy and reliability of educational assessments (AERA, APA, & NCME, 2014). In the context of primary education, teachers' ability to understand and apply these properties can significantly impact student outcomes, as assessment is a fundamental component of the instructional process (Popham, 2011). However, there is a paucity of research examining primary school teachers' competencies in many regions, including Delta State, Nigeria.

Various studies have pointed out that teachers often lack sufficient training in developing and applying psychometric properties such as validity, reliability, and item analysis (Mertler, 2016; Stiggins, 2002). This deficiency can lead to flawed assessment tools that may not accurately measure student learning, thereby affecting the quality of education (Brookhart, 2011).

In Delta State, the issue is compounded by the shortage of professional development opportunities and resources for teachers to enhance their assessment literacy (Oguntimehin & Adeyemi, 2004). The Nigerian education system, like many others, is in a state of constant reform, yet the professional development of teachers, particularly in the area of assessment literacy, has not kept pace with these reforms (Ughamadu, 2006). Consequently, there is a critical need to assess the current ability and competency levels of primary school teachers in Delta State regarding the application of psychometric properties of test instruments.

This study aims to address this gap by evaluating primary school teachers' knowledge and application of psychometric principles in their classroom assessments. Understanding these competencies will not only provide insights into the current state of assessment literacy among teachers but also inform policy and practice to enhance teacher training programs. Ultimately, improving teachers' competencies in this area is essential for ensuring that student assessments are both valid and reliable, thus supporting better educational outcomes.

Objective of the Study

The aim of the study was to assess the ability and Competency in the application of Psychometric Properties of Test Instruments among Primary School Teachers in Delta State. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to;

1. To determine the extent of the ability and level of competency of primary school teachers in establishing the validity of test instruments.
2. To determine the extent of ability and level of competency of primary school teachers in establishing the reliability of test instruments.
3. To determine the extent of ability and competency of primary school teachers in calculating the difficulty index and discriminative power of tests.
4. To determine the extent of ability and competency of primary school teachers in evaluating the keys and distracters in test items of instruments.

Research Questions

1. What is the mean response on extent of ability and level of competency of primary school teachers in establishing the validity of test instruments in Delta State?

Assessment of Ability and Competence ... (Irihweferhe, 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13333796>

2. What is mean response on extent of ability and level of competency of primary school teachers in establishing the reliability of a test instruments in Delta State?
3. What is the mean response on extent of ability and competency of primary school teachers in calculating the difficulty index and discriminative power of tests?
4. What is the mean response on extent of ability and competency of primary school teachers in evaluating the keys and distracters in test items of instruments in Delta State?

Methodology

The design for the study is a descriptive survey design. The population of the study consists of 893 (Ethiope East 482 and Okpe local government area 411) primary school teachers during the 2023/2024 academic session in Delta State public schools. A sample of 50 teachers each from the targeted population in the two local government areas using a multi-stage sampling technique. The 100 primary school teachers were randomly selected from 10 primary schools in Okpe and 10 primary schools in the Ethiope East Local government area of the state. Five (5) teachers were selected from each of the schools, they were selected based on gender, comprised of 55 female primary school teachers and 45 male primary school teachers. The instrument for the research was the Psychometric Ability and Competence Inventory for Teachers (PACIT). The PACIT consists of section I and section II. Section I is the bio-data of the teachers while section II contains 4 sub-sections of 20 items. 5 items on ability and competency of teachers on validity, reliability, item analysis and assessing the efficiency of keys and distracters of multiple-choice items. The validity of PACIT was established using expert judgment. The PACIT was presented to experts in measurement and evaluation and one serving and one retired headmaster helped to edit and certify the instrument appropriately. The reliability of the instrument was established using the split-half method. The instrument was administered to a sample of 30 teachers in Ughelli North local government area of Delta State. A reliability coefficient of 0.86 was obtained using the split-half method which indicated that the instrument is reliable. Having established the psychometric properties of the instrument, the instrument was later administered to the 100 teachers who were the selected sample for the research. The response is rated between 0-10 points. 0.00-3.59 is considered very low, 3.60-4.49 is rated low, 4.50-5.99 is rated average, 6.00-6.99 are rated high while 7.00 and above are rated very high. The rating table is presented below

Table 1: Psychometry Ability and Competency Inventory Rating Skill

RESPONSES	RATING
0.00-3.59	Very low
3.60-4.49	Low
4.50-5.99	Average
6.00-6.99	High
7.00 and above	Very high

The study was carried out in the 2023/2024 academic session. The researcher seeks the permission of the school heads of the school selected for the research before administering the instrument to the teachers selected in the various schools.

Results

Research Question 1:

What is the mean response on extent of ability and level of competency of primary school teachers in establishing the validity of test instruments in Delta State?

Table 2: Teachers ability and level of competency inventory of primary school teachers in establishing validity of test

S/N	Items	Mean scores	Decisions
1	I understand the concept of validity	2.35	Very low
2	I set my questions in line with the behavioural objectives	6.00	High

Assessment of Ability and Competence ... (Irighweferhe, 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13333796>

3	I normally draw a plan for several questions to be set from each topic taught before embarking on test construction	2.50	Very low
4	I make use of test blueprints before embarking on test construction	1.78	Very low
5	I seek test expert advice when constructing my questions and present my questions to senior teachers in my subject area before administering	3.20	Very low
Aggregate Mean		3.17	Very low

Analysis of Table 1 revealed that in item 1 of knowledge of the concept of validity, the mean of teachers' responses is 2.35 points which indicated a very low ability and competency of the concept of validity. Item 2 on teachers designing their questions in line with behavioural objectives has an average of 6.00 which is considered high. The third item has a mean of 2.50 which is on the drawing plan of the number of test items to be allotted to each topic taught. Item 4 of making use of test blueprint has a mean of 1.78 while items on seeking expert advice and presenting test items to experienced teachers in the subject area have a mean of 3.20, the aggregate mean of teachers' ability and competency in establishing validity is 3.17, this indicates a very low ability and competency.

Research Question 2:

What is the mean response on extent of ability and level of competency of primary school teachers in establishing the reliability of a test instruments in Delta State?

Table 2: Teacher's ability and level of competency of primary school teachers in establishing reliability of a test.

S/N	Items	Mean scores	Decisions
1	I understand the concept of reliability	2.00	Very low
2	I understand various methods of determining reliability	1.66	Very low
3	I administer my questions to other testees to determine the reliability of the test	0.96	Very low
4	I ensure the appropriate timing of my questions	6.40	High
5	I ensure my scoring is not biased	7.00	Very high
Aggregate Mean		3.60	Low

The result of the analysis of Table 2 also revealed that the aggregate mean of teachers' ability and competencies in establishing reliability is 3.60. A breakdown of item-by-item analysis shows that item 1 on understanding the concept of reliability is 2.00, and item 2 on understanding various methods of establishing reliability is 1.66. Also, item 3 on administering test reliability has a mean of 0.96. Item 4 on appropriate timing has a mean of 6.40 while item 5 on unbiasedness scoring has a mean of 7.00.

Research Question 3:

What is the mean response on extent of ability and competency of primary school teachers in calculating the difficulty index and discriminative power of tests

Table 3: Teachers ability and competency in carrying out item analysis of test items

S/N	Items	Mean Scores	Decisions
1	I understand the concepts of difficulty level and discriminative power of item	1.55	Very low
2	I carried out pilot testing for item analysis when constructing my questions	2.21	Very low
3	I ensure my questions discriminate among the upper and lower groups in terms of their knowledge of the item	5.50	Average
4	My questions can be grouped into the more difficult, moderate and easy	6.20	High
5	I know the statistical method(s) used in determining item analysis	1.77	Very low
Aggregate		3.45	Very low

Table 3 indicated that the computed aggregate mean for teacher ability and competency in carrying out item analysis is 3.45, the item-by-item analysis shows that item 1 on knowledge of item analysis has a mean of 1.55, carrying out of pilot testing for item analysis to select items for the test is item 2 with a mean of 2.21, item 3 on ensuring item differentiate between upper and lower test for knowledge of an item has a mean of 5.50. Item 4 on categorizing questions into easy, moderate and difficult has a mean of 6.20, while item 5 on knowledge of statistical method to use in item analysis is 1.77 points.

Research Question 4: What is the mean response on extent of ability and competency of primary school teachers in evaluating the keys and distracters in test items of instruments in Delta State?

Table 4: Teacher ability and competency in assessing key and distracters of test items

S/N	Items	Mean scores	Decisions
1	Key options are well distributed in my objective questions	5.75	Average
2	Distracters are well-structured and do not just give away words	5.20	Average
3	Options contain only one answer	9.55	Very high
4	Options are conveniently placed in line with the stem	4.56	Average
5	Options in my test items are not suspectable to guess	3.35	Very low
	Aggregate	5.68	Average

Analysis of Table 4 revealed that the aggregate mean is 5.68. Further analysis of each of the items indicated the distribution of key items in their multiple-choice items has a mean of 5.75, and item 2 on distracters well-structured has a mean of 5.20. Item 3 on the question not having an unambiguous answer has a mean of 9.55 while items 4 and 5 options have been conveniently placed in line with stem and option not suspectable to guessing has been of 4.56 and 3.35 points respectively.

Discussion of Findings

Analysis of the findings of the study revealed that primary school teachers in Ethiope East and Okpe Local government of Delta State have poor ability and are not competent in establishing the validity of a test. The teachers do not plan before designing their questions. In life, any project that lacks planning is bound to fail. In the same vein tests that are not planned before construction will fail to meet the necessary psychometric properties. The teachers are not seeking expert and senior teachers' opinions in their subject areas when constructing test items. Their tools of assessment and evaluation lack validity. These findings are in line with Klehm (2013) and Oyewobi (2000) who pointed out that most primary school teachers are not competent and do not show the right attitude towards testing. They lack the necessary skills and qualities of a professional teacher. The findings equally revealed that the aggregate mean of primary school teachers on the concept and how to establish reliability is 3.60 points, this indicated that the primary school teachers' ability and competency in establishing reliability is low. They lack the knowledge of the concept of reliability and the various methods used in establishing reliability. The results of the analysis revealed that they did not administer their instrument to establish reliability. However, the timing of the duration of administration of the test and scoring is adequate and appropriate. The results of the findings equally revealed the low ability and the lack of necessary competency in carrying out item-by-item statistical analysis of their test instrument. This is evident as the aggregate mean of the primary school teacher's ability and competency in carrying out item analysis is 3.45 which is considered low.

The results of the findings have revealed that primary school teachers have negative ability and competency in checking validity, establishing reliability, carrying out item analysis of difficulty index and discriminative power of test items which is the bedrock of test constructions. Further analysis shows that keys and distracters of multiple-choice items constructed by the teachers are not well distributed. The options are moderately placed in line with the stem. Some of the options are suspectable to guessing. The aggregate mean of teachers' ability and competency in assessing key and distracters is 5.68 which is moderate.

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Conclusion

Based on the result of this study it is concluded that primary school teachers in Ethiopia East and Okpe Local government Areas of Delta State Nigeria lack the ability and competency to establish psychometric properties of tests. The teachers' pay little attention to the psychometric properties which are the standard qualities of a good test. They lack the basic skills required for the establishment of psychometric properties.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

1. Primary school teachers need to be retrained on how to establish the basic psychometric properties of their tests.
2. School administrators should encourage their teachers to develop a positive attitude towards ensuring the establishment of basic psychometric properties of their instruments.
3. School heads should ensure that teachers provide evidence of the establishment of psychometric properties of their test before administering such test.
4. The Nigeria government and the teacher registration council should ensure professionalism of the teaching profession in Nigeria

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Assessment of Availability and Utilization of Information and Communication Technology Skills among Colleges of Education Students in North-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the availability and utilization of Information and Communication Technology Skills among Colleges of Education Students in North-West, Nigeria. A survey research design was adopted for the study. All students enrolled at Federal Colleges of Education in North-West, Nigeria during the 2021/2022 academic session made up the study's population. A random sample of 384 (243 male & 141 female) students were selected from the three Colleges chosen for this research. A validated questionnaire titled "Students ICT Skills Assessment Questionnaire (SICTSAQ)" was used for data collection. Reliability coefficient of 0.74 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability test. Mean, standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, t-test and ANOVA to test hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance, data analyses were explored using SPSS version 22.0. Results indicate that ICT facilities were moderately available in the Colleges (mean = 3.32), students possessed good ICT skills (mean = 3.48), the level of students' usage of ICT in learning was moderate (mean = 3.14), and there was no significant difference in the level of ICT skills obtained among male and female students ($P > 0.05$). The study concludes that there is a need for transformation of learning to continue when schools are closed due to any pandemic. Recommendations among others include Students enrolled in the Colleges of Education in North-West, Nigeria are encouraged to enhance their proficiency in ICT skills and effectively incorporate these abilities into their educational pursuits.

Keywords: Students, ICT, Skills, Availability, Utilization.

Introduction

Knowledge and skills are required by digital-age students for the optimal use of Information and Communication Technology for learning. These students thrive on creative and engaging activities from diverse sources of information from the digital world. This ability can be harnessed for digital learning. Digital learning can take place in the form of video-streaming, real-time lectures, networking, seminars or audio files. It takes place both online and offline. The Internet has made learning more individualized and adaptable to different learning styles (Shehu *et al.*, 2023). Learning can be more flexible, personalized, collaborative and more fun in digital classrooms (Joynes *et al.*, 2019). A digital classroom is a situation where ICT and internet facilities are used to provide additional learning opportunities as an extension of the physical classroom to enhance students learning (Singh, 2021). According to Taylor *et al.*, (2021), digital learning refers to the use of technology in instructional practices to enhance students' educational experience. This involves a diverse range of tools and methodologies. The influence of technology

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utilization on student results is contingent upon its incorporation within the educational setting. Consequently, it is crucial to recognize the correlation between students' digital competencies and their performance in digital learning environments (Hatos *et al.*, 2022). According to recent research conducted by Joynes *et al.*, (2019) and Fischer *et al.*, (2023), substantial evidence suggests that most students in the 21st century possess a high level of proficiency in technology. Consequently, it is essential to effectively use this technological aptitude to provide optimal and uninterrupted learning experiences. The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the educational system has shown the need for the Nigerian educational sector to transform its methods of teaching and learning (Ojukwu *et al.*, 2021). According to Saavedra *et al.*, (2020), the alignment of instructors, students, and technology in e-learning holds promise for mitigating the longstanding issue of learning disparity, which has hindered global educational advancement.

The COVID-19 pandemic, along with its effects such as the closure of educational institutions, has emphasized the need for a comprehensive reevaluation of the conventional physical classroom in comparison to virtual classrooms in the post-COVID-19 era. During the height of the global pandemic in April 2020, an estimated 1.6 billion students across more than 190 countries experienced a lack of access to traditional face-to-face education (UNESCO, 2020a). According to a report by UNESCO, UNICEF, World Bank and OECD in October 2021, over 32% of nations globally have implemented either complete or partial closures of educational institutions. According to the findings of Munoz-Najar *et al.*, (2021), a significant proportion of countries in Sub-Saharan Africa, approximately 40%, did not implement any remote learning measures as of June 2021. This is even though these countries experienced complete or partial closures of schools for an average duration of one year. Consequently, a considerable number of children in these countries were deprived of educational instruction during this period. To effectively implement blended learning, students in the twenty-first century must possess the necessary abilities that will enable them to make the most of information and communication technology (ICT) resources as instruments for learning (UNESCO, 2020a). According to Onyebinama (2021), ICT skills include the proficiencies required by students to effectively use computers and IT equipment for a range of activities, including but not limited to accessing the Internet, composing written documents, using email services, developing presentations, and engaging in other related tasks. ICT abilities include a spectrum that spans from basic to intermediate and ultimately advanced levels. Anton-Sancho *et al.*, (2023) conducted a study in which they found that the COVID-19 pandemic resulted in a significant reliance on the use of ICT abilities for various activities, communication, and facilitating students' acquisition of many forms of knowledge. This shift towards learner-centered methods in using ICT is a worldwide phenomenon with methodological implications. Students who possess proficiency in ICT can effectively navigate ICT-based learning settings and use ICT tools to enhance the acquisition of knowledge and the cultivation of critical thinking abilities. Conversely, students who lack these competencies will face significant obstacles in these areas. According to Munoz-Najar *et al.*, (2021), there is evidence suggesting that some disadvantaged populations, such as females and students with impairments, may have a disproportionate impact and face an increased risk of falling behind in their e-learning endeavors (UNESCO, 2020b). In contrast, the study conducted by Shehu *et al.*, (2023) found that the use of information and communication technology (ICT) in educational settings resulted in enhanced academic performance across students, regardless of their gender.

Extensive research endeavors have been undertaken in Nigeria to use the field of ICT for educational purposes at different levels within the educational system. A case study was conducted by De Simone *et al.*, (2020) in Edo State to ascertain the prevailing ICT facilities accessible to pupils. The study focused on providing educational information and learning activities using mobile devices. The findings suggest that around 91% of the student population within the State could use mobile communication devices. The collaboration between Edo State, the World Bank, and Bridge International Academies during the COVID-19 epidemic resulted in the development of a comprehensive online learning platform called The Edo Basic Education Sector Transformation Programme (Edo-BEST@Home, Munoz-Najar & Oviawe, 2020). The programme exhibited transformative learning outcomes for a substantial number of children, exceeding 250,000, in over 800 public primary schools in Edo State, Nigeria. However, research reports from October 2020 to February 2021 suggest that merely 49 % of the overall secondary student population enrolled in the State, managed to utilize the mobile interactive quizzes. One of the problems encountered by students while interacting with Edo-BEST@Home's materials was the need to possess digital abilities to use the gadget effectively (Obaseki, 2021). According to the findings of Wu *et al.*, (2022), the efficacy of integrating the use of ICT in educational institutions may be contingent upon the digital proficiency of students. Studies (Siddiquah & Salim, 2017; Fidelis & Onyango, 2021; Ojukwu, *et al.*, 2021) showed that ICT facilities are unavailable or inadequate

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for learning, lack of ICT skills (Siddiquah & Salim, 2017; Onyebinama, 2021; Shehu *et al.*, 2023) and lack of integration or low usage of ICT in learning ((Munoz-Najar & Oviawe, 2020; Anton-Sancho *et al.*, 2023).

The College of Education system in Nigeria is one of the tripods of tertiary education and its primary role is to train professional teachers who will be awarded the minimum teaching qualification of Nigeria Certificate in Education. This certificate qualifies them to teach in primary, secondary and vocational schools. In recognition of the vital roles of teachers, the federal government in its National Policy on Education (FRN, 2016) and National Policy on Information and Communication Technologies in Education (FRN, 2019) emphasized the need to inculcate the use of ICT for teaching and learning purposes in its institutions. Some effort has been made by the government towards actualizing this by providing some facilities, broadband, networking etc., but there is a need to determine human capacity development for effective and efficient utilization of ICT by teachers and students. Although studies have been carried out on ICT skills and competencies of teachers, there is a gap in information regards students, especially in Colleges of Education in Nigeria. Furthermore, based on the lessons learnt from COVID-19 experiences, how prepared and competent are the students in Nigerian Colleges of Education System in ICT skills for effective 21st-century post-COVID-19 learning?

Many students are admitted into tertiary institutions like Colleges of Education without academic skills for ICT learning. Even though they might be digital literates, they do not have adequate knowledge to use the resources available to them for proper learning. The COVID-19 pandemic and its fallouts which caused a worldwide disruption of activities in recent history, had already had a near-universal impact on learners around the world as drastic measures towards checking the spread of the deadly virus led to total lockdowns including educational institutions at all levels. Ensuring learning continued during this pandemic, ICT platforms were explored, requiring teachers to hold virtual classes. The Nigerian government has made efforts towards e-learning by providing certain ICT facilities in tertiary institutions. Moreso, most of these students possess Internet-ready mobile phones. This indicates that if all these resources are harnessed, lockdowns during pandemics should not affect teaching and learning. Research evidence has also shown a low level of ICT skills competence and usage among students in Nigeria. In some tertiary institutions in Nigeria, online learning has started taking place through recorded lectures and online platforms, but do Colleges of Education (COE) students have the requisite 21st-century ICT skills needed for successful, effective and quality post-COVID-19 learning?

Objectives of the Study

1. Ascertain the extent to which ICT facilities are available to students at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria.
2. Determine the level of ICT skills among students at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria.
3. Determine the ICT usage by students at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria for academic purposes.
4. Determine gender disparity among students in terms of their level of ICT skills at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following questions were raised to guide the conduct of this research:

1. To what extent are ICT facilities available to the students at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria?
2. What is the level of students ICT skills at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria?
3. What is the level of ICT usage for learning among students at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria?
4. Is there any difference between male and female students' ICT skills at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

1. **Ho:** There is no significant difference in the availability of ICT facilities at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria.
2. **Ho:** There is no significant difference in ICT skills obtained among students in Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria.
3. **Ho:** There is no significant difference in the level of ICT usage for learning by students in Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria.

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4. **Ho.:** There is no significant difference between male and female students' level of ICT skills at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria.

Methodology

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study to evaluate the Information and Communication Technology Skills of students for Post COVID-19 Learning at Colleges of Education in North-West, Nigeria. All of the students who were enrolled in the 2021/2022 academic session at three Federal Colleges of Education in North-West Nigeria, namely the Federal College of Education in Kano, the Federal College of Education in Katsina, and the Federal College of Education in Zaria, made up the population of the study. The Colleges were purposively used for the study because they have the same source of funding and extant administrative documents. A total of 384 (243 male & 141 female) students were randomly selected by balloting as sample size for the study in line with Krejcie & Morgan (1970).

The instrument used for data collection was a validated Student ICT Skills Assessment Questionnaire (SICTSAQ), adapted from the PISA 2021 ICT Framework (OECD, 2018). Split-half method was used to determine reliability and a Cronbach value of 0.74 was obtained. The questionnaire has four sections, A, B, C and D. Section A deals with the biodata of the respondents. Section B, containing 10 items, deals with the extent of availability of ICT facilities. The items were five Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5, very available (5), moderately available (4), neutral (3), fairly available (2), and not available (1). Section C contained 20 items on the level of ICT skills of the students with a scale ranging from Highly skilled (5), moderately skilled (4), undecided (3), fairly skilled (2) and not skilled (1). Section D contained 12 items on the usage of ICT in learning with the responses ranging from always (5), often (4), sometimes (3), rarely (2) and never (1). The decision rule was 1-1.49 Not available or not skilled or not used, 1.50 -2.49 fairly available or fairly skilled or rarely used, 2.50 -3.49 moderately available or moderately skilled or sometimes used, 3.50 – 5.00 very available or highly skilled or always used respectively. Two Science Education and one Computer Education expert from Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria validated the instrument for the study. All validators' suggestions were effected to further improve the instruments. Fifty students from the population but not the selected sample were used for pilot testing. Split-half method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument. Cronbach was used to determine the coefficient value of 0.74 which made the instrument reliable for the study.

To get approval to conduct research among students at the sampled institutions, the researchers sought introduction letters from their home institutions to the Provosts of those Colleges. Over eight weeks, the researchers gave the surveys to the respondents assisted by research assistants recruited from each College. The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.0 was used to analyze the data. Mean, standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, t-test and ANOVA to test hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question One:

To what extent are ICT facilities available to the students at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria?

Table 1: Summary of Students Response on the Extent of Availability of ICT Facilities for Learning at COEs

S/N	Items	Mean	Std.Dev	Decision
1	Computers	4.12	1.28	Very Available
2	Digital Camera	3.17	1.41	Moderately Available
3	Digital Video Camera	2.99	1.41	Moderately Available
4	Overhead Projector	3.08	1.41	Moderately Available
5	Storage Facilities	3.32	1.46	Moderately Available
6	Mobile Handset	3.68	1.42	Very Available
7	Whiteboard	3.51	1.44	Very Available
8	Internet facilities	3.13	1.37	Moderately Available
9	Radio	3.14	1.51	Moderately Available
10	Television	3.04	1.57	Moderately Available
Cumulative Mean & Std.Dev		3.32	1.43	Moderately available

Results in Table 1 showed a cumulative mean score of 3.32 and a standard deviation value of 1.43 which indicate that ICT facilities are moderately available at each of the three Federal Colleges of Education located in the North-West region of Nigeria.

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Research Question Two:

What is the level of students ICT skills at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria?

Table 2: Summary of Level of ICT Skills obtained by Students at COEs

S/N	Items	Mean	Std. dev.	Decision
1	Turning the Computer on and off	4.40	1.07	Moderately skilled
2	Opening and closing application programs	3.72	1.26	Moderately skilled
3	Using the Mouse to select and move items on the screen	3.76	1.27	Moderately skilled
4	Printing Out Document	3.41	1.38	Skilled
5	Saving and Storing File or Documents	3.55	1.41	Moderately skilled
6	Using word processing applications/packages to create new documents	3.35	1.38	Skilled
7	Using basic MS Word functions	3.44	1.34	Skilled
8	Using the toolbar for formatting documents by selecting font size and style	3.24	1.36	Skilled
9	Creating tables and Charts to display information within a document	3.27	1.37	Skilled
10	Creating a spreadsheet workbook/document	3.46	1.39	Skilled
11	Entering and processing data on Excel	3.49	1.36	Skilled
12	Creating and managing files and folders	3.44	1.32	Skilled
13	Copying, moving and locating stored files or folders	3.47	1.34	Skilled
14	Creating slides for a presentation using PowerPoint	3.29	1.37	Skilled
15	Connecting a mobile handset to a computer/printer	3.45	1.34	Skilled
16	Searching for information using search engines such as Google	3.54	1.38	Moderately skilled
17	Composing, attaching documents, sending and receiving e-mail	3.43	1.36	Skilled
18	Data Transfer from camera to computer	3.15	1.38	Skilled
19	Recording with a digital video camera	3.34	1.36	Skilled
20	Downloading/uploading files on the Internet	3.44	1.43	Skilled
	Cumulative Mean &Std. Dev	3.48	1.34	Moderately skilled

The cumulative mean value of 3.48 and standard deviation of 1.48 presented in Table 2 revealed that students are moderately skilled.

Research Question Three:

What is the level of ICT usage for learning among students at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria?

Table 3: Summary of Responses on the Level of Students Usage of ICT Skills in Learning

S/N	Item	Mean	Std.Dev.	Decision
1	Using ICT to monitor and assess result	3.79	1.40	Often
2	Sharing electronic content with other students/teachers online	3.35	1.41	Sometimes
3	Write tests/examinations online	2.91	1.42	Sometimes
4	Using a digital video camera to record lessons	2.78	1.44	Sometimes
5	Using ICT to access online lessons via different Google Apps such as Google Classroom, Google Meet	2.90	1.47	Sometimes
6	Using ICT to access lessons on a real-time basis using Apps such as Zoom, Webinar/Webcast, Skype, Microsoft Teams	2.84	1.48	Sometimes
7	Using ICT to access online lessons via social media Apps such as WhatsApp, Telegram, Facebook, Instagram and Twitter	3.22	1.41	Sometimes
8	Using online video tools such as YouTube to learn	3.19	1.42	Sometimes
9	Using PowerPoint presentation for learning	3.07	1.45	Sometimes

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10	Using an interactive whiteboard to learn a lesson	3.31	1.56	Sometimes
	Cumulative Mean and Std.Dev	3.14	1.59	Moderately Used

The analysis of the level of students' use of ICT skills in learning shown in Table 3 revealed a cumulative mean value of 3.14 and a standard deviation of 1.59 which points to a moderate amount of use.

Research Question Four:

Is there any difference between male and female students' ICT skills at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria?

Table 4. Summary of Mean Scores of ICT Skills obtained by Male and Female Students at COEs

S/N	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Dev	Mean Difference
1	Male	243	3.57	1.27	0.29
2	Female	141	3.28	1.23	

The summary of means presented in Table 4 revealed a slight difference of 0.29 in favour of the male students. The significance of the difference will be determined in the related hypothesis.

Ho:

There is no significant difference in the availability of ICT facilities at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria.

Table 5. One-Way Analysis of Variance of Students Response on Availability of ICT Facilities in COEs

S/N	Variables	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	df	f value	p-value	Decision
1	Between Groups	145.535	72.77	2	36.16	.000	Significant
2	Within Groups	6333.206	2.012	3147			
3	Total	6478.742		3149			

F (2, 3147), =36.16; p < 0.05

Table 5 indicate a significant difference between the three Colleges of Education in the North-West regions of Nigeria regarding the availability of ICT facilities ($p=0.000<0.05$). The null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the availability of ICT facilities at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria was consequently disproved.

Ho:

There is no significant difference in ICT skills obtained among students in Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria.

Table 6. One-Way Analysis of Variance of COE Students Response on the Level of ICT Skills

S/N	Variables	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	df	f value	p value	Decision
1	Between Groups	51.403	25.701	2	13.40	.000	Significant
2	Within Groups	15648.185	1.917	8161			
3	Total	15699.587		8163			

F (2, 8161), =13.40; p < 0.05

One-way analysis of variance presented in Table 6 indicate that there is a significant difference in the level of ICT skills obtained by the COE students ($p=.000<0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the level of ICT skills acquired by students at Colleges of Education in the North West of Nigeria was rejected.

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Ho.:

There is no significant difference in the level of ICT usage for learning by students in Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria.

Table 7. One-Way Analysis of Variance of COE Students' Response on the Level of ICT Usage for Learning

S/N	Variables	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	df	f value	p value	Decision
1	Between Groups	195.453	97.73	2			
2	Within Groups	8150.860	2.124	3837	46.00	.000	Significant
3	Total	8346.312		3839			

F (2, 3837), =46.00; *p* < 0.05

Table 7's One-way ANOVA revealed a statistically significant difference with $p = .000 < 0.05$. The null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the level of ICT usage for learning by students in Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria was therefore rejected.

Ho.:

There is no significant difference between male and female students' level of ICT skills at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria.

Table 8: Summary of t-test scores on the level of ICT skills obtained among Male and Female Students in COEs

S/N	Gender	N	Mean	Std.Dev	Mean Diff	df	t value	p value	Decision
1	Male	243	3.57	1.27					
					0.29	382	1.99	.185	NS
2	Female	141	3.28	1.23					

Not Significant [*t* (382) = 1.99, *p* = .185 > 0.05].

Results in Table 8 revealed that the mean difference value of 0.29 was not statistically significant.

Discussion of Findings

According to the findings in Table 1, which showed a cumulative mean score of 3.32 and a standard deviation value of 1.43, indicate that ICT facilities are moderately available at each of the three Federal Colleges of Education located in the North-West region of Nigeria. The results of the corresponding variance analysis, provided in Table 5, indicate a significant difference between the three Colleges of Education in the North-West regions of Nigeria regarding the availability of ICT facilities ($p = .000 < 0.05$). The null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the availability of ICT facilities at Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria was consequently disproved. This conclusion is confirmed by the findings of Fidelis and Onyango (2021), who observed that insufficient technological innovation resources were accessible for teaching and learning in Tanzania. Furthermore, it was reported by students that the ICT facilities that are most easily available include computers, whiteboards, and mobile phones. In a study conducted by Ojukwu *et al.*, (2021), it was found that tertiary institutions in the state of Imo utilize various ICT tools for learning in the post-COVID-19 era. These tools include computers, whiteboards, smart boards, social media tools, Internet connectivity, projectors, computer-based learning software, audio and video tapes, CD-ROMs, local intranet/extranet systems, smartphones, digital cameras, scanners, and audio and video resources. The results align with the findings of Siddiquah and Salim (2017), which demonstrated that most higher education students in Pakistan have the means to use computers and access the Internet.

Table 2 provides data on the level of information and communication technology (ICT) skills achieved by students attending COEs in the North-West, Nigeria. The mean value of 3.48 and standard deviation of 1.48 revealed that students are moderately skilled. The results of this research are similar to those of Oguguo *et al.*, (2020), who found that undergraduate students at the University of Nigeria, Nsuka, have a moderate level of ICT skills. On the other hand, the conclusions of this research are contradicted by the findings of Siddiquah and Salim (2017), who discovered that students attending higher education institutions in Pakistan had a poor level of ICT skills. Table 6 presents the results of the one-way analysis of variance, which indicate that there is a significant difference in the level

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of ICT skills obtained by the COE students ($p=0.000<0.05$). These results demonstrate that there is a substantial difference in the level of ICT Skills gained by the COE Students. Therefore, it is possible to conclude that the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the level of ICT skills acquired by students at Colleges of Education in the North West of Nigeria, was erroneous and should not be accepted.

Table 3 shows the results of an analysis of the level of students' use of ICT skills in learning. A cumulative mean value of 3.14 and a standard deviation of 1.59 point to a moderate amount of use (sometimes). The result contradicts what Omorobi *et al.*, (2021) found, which was that students had a high level of competency in information and communication technology skills. The corresponding Table 7's one-way ANOVA revealed a statistically significant difference, with a p-value of less than 0.05 ($p=0.000<0.05$). The null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the level of ICT usage for learning by students in Colleges of Education in the North West, Nigeria was therefore rejected. The results of an in-depth analysis of the factors suggest that the students make more use of video-based educational resources like YouTube ($p=0.85$). According to Anton-Sancho *et al.*, (2023), one of the variables that may be identified as a barrier to students acquiring digital skills is the high cost of facilities for utilization.

A t-test analysis was conducted to assess the gender difference in mean scores attained by male and female COE Students regarding the degree of ICT abilities. Based on the findings presented in Table 8, the mean difference value of 0.29 was not statistically significant ($t=1.99, P=0.185>0.05$). This supports the findings of Oguguo *et al.*, (2020), who also observed that the ICT abilities of male and female students were not significantly different. The results that were obtained in this study contradict those found by Yalman *et al.*, (2016), who found that ICT skills obtained by male and female undergraduate education students in Turkey were substantially different regarding gender.

Conclusion

Findings from this study have shown a need for transformation of learning to continue when schools are closed due to any pandemic. COE students need to acquire the pre-requisite 21st-century digital skills needed to enhance learning. Most COE students in the North-West Zone, Nigeria possess basic ICT skills which require improvement for meaningful online/digital educational engagement/ learning. Therefore, it is imperative to clearly understand how COE students' progression and attainment of ICT skills can align with their curriculum, assessment and teacher training for both physical and digital classrooms. The use of mobile technology can also be harnessed to enhance digital learning as the majority of the students have access to mobile phones.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

1. Students enrolled in the Colleges of Education in North-West, Nigeria are encouraged to enhance their proficiency in ICT skills.
2. COE students should endeavor to incorporate their abilities in ICT into their educational pursuits.
3. To boost students' competence, it is recommended that Lecturers at the Colleges of Education increase the frequency of learning activities in particular areas of need within the digital domain.
4. The provision of sufficient and appropriate infrastructure and ICT facilities inside and outside the school premises should be ensured by the Federal Government, the National Commission for Colleges of Education, and the Management of Colleges of Education, to enhance the learning process.

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Assessment of Digital Technology Affordances and Epistemological Access in Higher Educational Institutions of Learning in Nigeria: A Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract

This paper was aimed at assessing the digital technology affordances and epistemological access in higher educational institutions in Nigeria as a system literature review. The authors used a concept-centric systematic literature review approach to conduct their study. Following the development of a research protocol, the authors searched the information systems database and other relevant and pertinent databases to select relevant articles for review. A thematic coding approach consists of six steps: (1) familiarizing with the data; (2) generating initial codes; (3) creation of themes; (4) reviewing themes; (5) defining and labeling themes; and (6) producing the report. The systematic literature review revealed several themes (for example, educational technological affordances, learning context, and dialogic activities) that are critical to digital technological affordances and epistemological access. Most previous studies are isolated in nature, this is because they focus more on specific areas. Thus, from this review, the authors developed a framework that harmonizes various concepts that characterize epistemological access in higher educational institutions. The synthesized theoretical framework offers an integrated perspective on how structural and cultural systems of students and digital technology can facilitate the assessment of digital technologies and epistemological access in higher educational institutions in Nigeria. Moreover, it addresses gaps such as the influence of e-learning management systems on faculties during dialogic interaction, where a framework was developed. The framework not only provides new research avenues in the information systems domain but also serves as inspiration for future empirical testing in higher educational institutions globally. It is therefore recommended that, universities in Nigeria should integrated digital learning platform, enhance usability through user-centric design, maximize affordances of digital technologies, implement transformative educational strategies, and address structural barriers.

Keyword: Epistemological access, affordances, digital technologies, higher educational institutions

Introduction

As digital technologies are developing, technology-integrated learning has also evolved, and the demand for technology in education has increased (Ma et al., 2020). Digital technology affordances have entered a new phase with the introduction of new modern technologies in the education context, for example learning management systems, digital libraries, open ERP, Sakai. The affordances of digital technologies have given rise to extraordinary and diversified digital innovations, which should assist in dialogical interaction via digital supportive classrooms in higher education institutions. Digital technologies provide convenience for learning among students and context awareness

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(Tan-Hsu et al., 2012), ease knowledge delivery by teachers (Cheikh-Ammar, 2018), improve communicative skills and competence (Liaw, 2014), and promote learning autonomy (Baran & AlZoubi, 2020; Ma et al., 2020). Therefore, digital technology affordances have been identified as a new concept that has important future directions (Al-Maawali, 2020; Bahari, 2021; Bobsin et al., 2019; Eshchar-Netz & Vedder-Weiss, 2021; K. Lee et al., 2014) for gaining access to education in higher education institutions, especially even among less privileged students. Despite the promising and important future of digital technology affordances, the successful integration of digital technologies into higher education institutions requires the full engagement and dedication of educators and policymakers (D'Ambra *et al.*, 2019). But research has shown that faculties in higher educational institutions in sub-Saharan Africa are often hesitant or even refuse to use digital technologies as a way for students to get an education (Ma et al., 2020). With the introduction of high-tech learning environments, such as flipped learning (Sams & Bergmann, 2013), massive open online courses (MOOCs) (Siemens, 2012), mobile technology, and social media, the use of digital technologies for gaining access to education in higher educational institutions (HEIs) in most African countries, specifically Nigeria, is highly critical. As these learning contexts could greatly facilitate and ease access to education when deployed, higher educational institutions in Nigeria have not embraced digital technologies (Okwelogu et al., 2021), even though the Nigerian Federal Ministry of Education and the Nigerian Federal Ministry of Digital Economy have been encouraging staff of higher educational institutions to use cutting-edge technologies effectively for teaching and learning purposes, with the hope of bridging the gap between marginalized groups and the elites' children in rural and urban regions (Adamu, 2019; Okwelogu et al., 2021). Nevertheless, the majority of university lecturers in Nigeria are not using the available digital technologies even if they are provided for teaching as envisioned by the Federal Ministry of Education (Okwelogu et al., 2021). They either responded poorly to facilities provided (Huang et al., 2021; Ma et al., 2020), or used them in ways that lacked innovation and creativity (Li, 2017). Okwelogu et al. (2021) in their study asserted that inadequate funding, fall in national review, insecurity, corruption, inadequate ICT expertise, shortage of infrastructural facilities, political instability, and policy instability were among the problems hindering effective use of technologies for teaching and learning. Therefore, there is also a severe gap between policy requirements and teaching practice (Adamu, 2019; Kuru Gönen, 2019; Luo et al., 2021; Okwelogu et al., 2021) when it comes to technology usage in classrooms. Barriers like insufficient access to an appropriate learning management system, insufficiency in teachers' technology competence and confidence (Liaw, 2014), the influence of Confucianism that emphasizes respecting authority (Fu et al., 2020), prioritizes academic performance, and accentuates the role of examinations (Kuru Gönen, 2019), have frequently been mentioned in literature concerning the implementation of ICT-based for teaching and learning in higher educational institutions. In most literature (Al-Ani, 2013; Al-Maawali, 2020; Antonenko et al., 2017; Bahari, 2021; Bray & Tangney, 2016; Dinsmore, 2019; Eshchar-Netz & Vedder-Weiss, 2021; Gibson et al., 2021; Kuru Gönen, 2019; Okwelogu et al., 2021; Wankel & Blessinger, 2013), studies are mainly conducted in relation to ICT facilities for teaching and learning. There is a dearth of studies regarding access to right/disciplinary knowledge in universities (Okwelogu et al., 2021), especially through digitally supported classroom dialogue. In other words, an up-to-date systematic literature review with a focus on underprivileged students or marginalized groups for social inclusion in HEIs is still lacking. Moreover, affordance has not been actualized within the context of epistemological access and social justice. Hence, we are looking at epistemological access as social justice. In this study, we hope to use the educational affordances of digital technologies to facilitate epistemological access, thereby achieving social justice for underprivileged students or marginalized groups/students from rural communities or areas. Marginalized groups in this study are referred to as those students who do not have the upbringing that is supposed to support their educational career. Thus, we pose the following research question:

Research Question 1:

How are the educational affordances of digital technologies for gaining epistemological access among marginalized groups contextualized in higher institutions in sub-Saharan African universities?

Research Question 2:

What challenges may implicate gaining epistemological access in a quest to use digital technologies for dialogic interaction in higher institutions in sub-Saharan Africa?

To address such a research gap and answer the posed research questions, we adopt a systematic literature review approach which is rigorous and transparent (Okoli & Schabram, 2010; Schryen, 2015; Schryen et al., 2017),

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by reviewing 10 years of literature (2012 - 2022) on Digital Technology Affordances in Context for Epistemological Access with a systematic analysis of the trending issues, and research methodologies and theories over one decade. This method is the most reliable and comprehensive about what works.

Methodology

Literature Identification

The literature search was based on the aim and scope of the review. As noted by IS scholars (for example, Baghizadeh et al., 2020; Bai et al., 2019; Bandara et al., 2015; Ferreras-Fernández et al., 2016; Schryen et al., 2017; Watson & Webster, 2020) to review a specific subject area, a review article should be able to (1) survey and synthesize previous studies; (2) identify the relationships between key concepts; (3) identify gaps; and (4) set directions for future research. To do this, systematic literature review process and protocol was developed as shown in **Figure 1**. A protocol based on Levy and Ellis (2006); Bandara et al. (2015); and Boell and Wang (2019) was further developed, with the goal of focusing on the need for research in perception.

At first, we started by identifying various service sources in which the literature was searched. These sources comprise the renowned information systems (IS) databases, journals, and conferences in the IS domain. We searched databases (e.g., Google scholar and other pertinent databases such as AISEL, JStore, Springer, Web of Science, Science Direct, and Elsevier) that house vital academic IS journals (Lowry et al., 2013; Schryen, 2015; Schryen et al., 2017). Such journals were referred to as a set of top IS journals (Boell & Wang, 2019; Lowry et al., 2013). Moreover, we leverage service from the association of information systems for electronic library (AISEL) in order to capture recent studies from reputable conference proceedings such as the American Conference on Information Systems (AMCIS), International Conference of the Association for Information Systems (PACIS), International Conference for Information Processing (IFIP), and other relevant information systems conferences, and Literature Baskets (www.litbasket.io) (Boell & Wang, 2019). Moreover, educational information systems journals were also searched so as to capture the relevant papers for inclusion in the study. These are the most frequently used databases, especially in information systems studies (Ajah & Ononiwu, 2021; Boell & Wang, 2019; Inuwa et al., 2020; Lowry et al., 2013).

Second, the search terms in the process include: (Affordances) OR (Information Systems Affordance) OR (Information Technology Affordance) OR (Information Communication Technology Affordance) OR (Digital Affordance) OR (Technology Affordance) OR (E-learning Affordance) OR (Online Learning Affordance) OR (Mobile Learning Affordance) OR (Mobile Learning Affordance) OR (Learning Management System Affordance) OR (Educational Technology Affordance). Preliminary relevance was determined for each manuscript title. From the title, if the content seemed to discuss any of the search keywords, we obtained its full reference, including author, year, title, and abstract, for further evaluation. Despite the technological advancement and the methods of information archiving and retrieval, we searched for studies that were published between 2012-2022 (articles published for one decade), so that we could build our review on the recent literatures considering information retrieval and synthesis in the digital age. In all, 332 studies that matched the search keywords were found across the searched journals and conferences, and they were all moved to EndNote library™20 in order to ascertain whether the studies should be included or should not be included in the review. Although, our search has covered the pertinent academic IS journals (Lowry et al., 2013; Merriam, 2015), we can argue that such a literature search was comprehensive enough to capture the most recent and relevant studies for the review.

In the last stage of the protocol (i.e., **3rd Phase: Output; Figure 1**), the writing of the literature kick-start through answering the research questions set for the study as well as setting future direction and priorities for the main work. To answer the research questions in this study, all the obtained articles were screened using inclusion and exclusion criteria based on certain procedures. These processes are described in the following sections.

Screening for Inclusion and Exclusion Procedures

It appeared that 321 studies were obtained as a result of the search terms, and the papers were archived in EndNote library™20. Each of the 321 studies was analyzed to ascertain whether it conformed with the aim of the study as well as the inclusion and exclusion criteria. These inclusion and exclusion criteria are: (1) Does the study clearly define concepts and the relationship among such concepts? (2) Are there specifications of concepts moderating the relationships amongst concepts? If not, can we use the moderators to infer concepts in operations by the researchers?

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(3) Is the study guided by a theory or theories to identify concepts? (4) Papers must be written in English. (5) A clear methodology and findings must be included, and (6) Are conceptual papers related to the phenomenon in question? We first read the abstracts of the 321 studies to further decide their relevance to the phenomenon under study, “Digital Technology Affordance for Epistemological Access,” and we found that 58 studies were deemed relevant, and we obtained the full-text article for quality assessment.

We further skimmed through the full-text articles to further evaluate the quality and eligibility of the studies. We deemed journal articles, conference papers, and books published by reputable publishers as high-quality research and, therefore, included in the review. Most of the anecdotal and technical reports as well as online presentations are excluded from the review because of the lack of a peer-review process.

Snowballing

We identified eleven (11) additional studies through backward and forward searching. We also utilized the forward and backward search to identify different affordance-related issues in higher education institutions. Once the article established affordance, or digital technology affordance, we identified best-practice examples by searching articles that had referenced the information systems paper. Examples were chosen based on their adherence to the method, after which preference was given to educationally related articles. Overall, 69 studies were included in this review, as shown in the second phase of **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: Systematic Literature Review Process

A concept-centric approach (Webster & Watson, 2002) was used in this study to extract theoretical concepts from each of the 69 studies, which were further arranged as concept matrixes of digital technology affordance for epistemological access, as shown in Table 1. Moreover, concepts that are similar, which have sometimes had different semantic senses but with commensurable functional meanings from different studies, were merged as one concept (Templier & Pare, 2018) and placed in Table 1.

Table 1: Concepts Extraction from the Synthesized Studies

Overarching theme	Major themes	Second order themes (sub-theme)	First order concepts	Authors
Epistemological Access	Educational Technological Affordances	Usability, selection, browsing, representation of content, structuring collaborative learning process, provisionality, informing teachers, monitoring and regulation, engaging in co-construction, engaging in productive process, support/challenge, and assistive memory control	Accessibility, actualization, assessment, adoption, engagement, and perception.	(Bahari & Gholami, 2022; Bray & Tangney, 2016; Fromm et al., 2020; Paul M. Leonardi, 2013; Mascheroni & Vincent, 2016; Sethi, 2017; Thapa & Hatakka, 2017; Xiangming & Song, 2018; Zhao et al., 2021)
			Content creation, ease of use, ease of assimilation, evaluation, integration, patching, internet provision, management, monitoring, tool development, and storage.	(Ahad et al., 2018; Chatterjee et al., 2021; Cheikh-Ammar, 2018; Goldkuhl, 2020; Jais et al., 2021; Jónasdóttir & Müller, 2020; Nur'Aini, 2021; Strong et al., 2014; Tagoe & Cole, 2020; Turugare & Rudhumbu, 2020; Vonderwell & Zachariah, 2005; Q. Wang et al., 2013)
	Learning Context	Learner autonomy, learner inclusion and participation, classroom atmosphere, motivation & engagement, and interpersonal relationships	Awareness, influence, motivation, and performance.	(Al-Ani, 2013; Asamoah & Andoh-Baidoo, 2018; Asamoah, 2020; Jais et al., 2021; Lai, 2017; Payton & Kvasny, 2016)
			Contextual mobility, and material construction.	(Dinsmore, 2019)
	Dialogic Activities	Knowledge co-construction, using dialogue to express meta-cognitive learning, using dialogue to scaffold understanding between learner-learner & teacher-learner.	Association, accountability, archiving, autonomy, collaboration, communication, coordination, decoupling, desire to learn, editability, efficacy, expression, experience, interaction, intention, and presentation.	(Al-Ani, 2013; Asamoah, 2020; Bobsin et al., 2019; Chatterjee et al., 2021; Cordes, 2016; Dinsmore, 2019; Evans et al., 2017; Faik et al., 2020; Fu et al., 2019; Gillen & Kucirkova, 2018; Goldkuhl, 2020; Järvelä et al., 2015; Manca & Ranieri, 2013; Mao, 2014; McKenna, 2020; Rahimi et al., 2015; Rodríguez-Hidalgo, 2020; Sethi, 2017; Strong et al., 2014; Tagoe & Cole, 2020; Waizenegger et al., 2020; C.-H. Wang et al., 2013; Wendt et al., 2022; Wyche & Steinfield, 2016; Young & Cleveland, 2022)

As an iterative review process, we stopped harvesting more papers when saturation was reached, after careful and thorough reading of the papers (Cecez-Kecmanovic et al., 2014). We manually used a data extraction approach meant to store the data, followed by a thematic coding process (Leidner & Kayworth, 2006; Roberts et al., 2012; Wiener et al., 2016). “Such a coding procedure categorizes text information in a systematic manner and identifies relationships among the categories...” It’s useful for making sense of a big domain of research, and it can help direct future study (Roberts et al., 2012, p. 634). Following Braun and Clarke (2006), our thematic coding approach consists of six steps: (1) familiarizing with the data; (2) generating initial codes; (3) creation of themes; (4) reviewing themes;

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(5) defining and labeling themes; and (6) producing the report. Starting with stage 1, we will go over the six steps in a way that mirrors how we used and adapted them for our data analysis.

First Stage: Familiarizing with the Data

The authors read and re-read each of the 69 studies that were identified and selected for inclusion in this review in an active way (Braun & Clarke, 2006). This was to get more familiar with the selected studies and further clarify any discrepancies that might have occurred during the selection procedures. Thus, meanings and patterns were identified from the studies (Sinkovics, 2018).

Second Stage: Generating Initial Codes

The authors of this study independently identified the concepts, as QSR NVivo codes from empirical studies with theoretical underpinnings, while for the conceptual papers, only key concepts and phrases were considered. When such similar concepts from different studies were seen to have the same functional meaning, we merged them into one concept (Templier & Pare, 2018). The aggregate of the concepts now forms the first order concepts (Gioia et al., 2013; Sinkovics, 2018) or basic codes (Braun & Clarke, 2006). A consensus was reached after comparing the codes found by the authors, and through mutual agreement, all the discrepancies were resolved, in which the first order categories emerged as shown in **Figure 2**. Ravasi and Phillips (2011) stated that the second stage is what made us switch from temporary to more permanent categories.

Figure 2: Thematic Data Analysis Process (Concept Mapping)

Third Stage: Development of Themes

Conceptual relations emerged among the emerging categories while grouping the codes that were kept close to the sliced-out concepts from the research evaluated, which were sorted into first-order categories. As a result, we merged first-order categories into fewer, larger, and potentially more relevant second-order categories (Ravasi & Phillips, 2011). The second-order categories suggest paying particular attention to them in order to solve the study's overarching research questions. We carefully evaluated our first-order categories and their content across the 69 papers as the process progressed, looking for concepts that would – or would not – fit with each emerging category. We agreed to reframe or redefine some ideas when we realized that they had different meanings but were still basically the same (Braun & Clarke, 2006; Gioia et al., 2013).

Fourth Stage: Review of Themes

We thoroughly ran through the full data set for contradictory findings, then continued developing our second-order theme until saturation is reached by engaging in constant comparison (Belgrave & Seide, 2019; Braun & Clarke,

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2006). Here, a thought or a phrase is compared to all prior concepts or phrases, rather than being analyzed on its own. We realized that the constant comparison process yielded theoretical attributes of second-order categories (Belgrave & Seide, 2019). As a result, we began to notice the extent of the categories, the variables that influenced them, the relationship between them, and the categories' antecedents and effects (Belgrave & Seide, 2019).

The Fifth Stage: Defining and Naming Themes

Educational technological affordances, learning context, and dialogic activities were formed by combining second-order categories to establish three bigger encompassing themes. Furthermore, we saw how the three selected overarching themes cluster around a core subject (epistemological access), which is similar to Strauss and Corbin (1998) selective coding approach, as we noted in the memo. Similarly, we noticed that the categories were potentially saturated. **Figure 2** depicts the entire data structure that resulted from this procedure, including the first-order codes and their relations to the second-order categories and their relations, to the major themes, as well as the overarching theme that emerged.

Sixth Stage: Producing a Report

At this stage, the coded data and memos that can be used and worked with in this study have emerged. However, the final analysis and write-up of the report as detailed in the next section is presented.

Results

In this study, descriptive statistics about the reviewed literature were provided as the first Phase. While the second Phase is a discussion on the main themes: Educational technological affordances, learning context, and dialogic activities as the major themes abstracted and synthesized from the literature review, as shown in **Table 1** for theoretical elaboration. The researchers consider the themes as critical for epistemological access. The descriptive statistics demonstrate the categories of articles, year of publication, methodology used, the countries of focus of selected studies, and specific databases. We commenced with descriptive statistics as detailed in the following section.

Descriptive Statistics

In this study, we reviewed 69 primary studies in relation to digital technology affordances in contexts for epistemological access; 50 of these studies were published as journal articles between 2016 and 2020. In 2012, only one study was published. Between 2021 and 2022, however, the number of articles published slowly declined, from 4 to 2, as shown in **Figure 3**.

Figure 3: Number selected journal paper each year

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In terms of publication type, more than half (59 articles, i.e., 86%) of the reviewed articles were published as journal papers; 5 (7%) were published as conference papers; and 5 (7%) as books or book sections, as indicated in **Figure 4**.

S/No.	Types of publication	No. of Studies
1	Journal articles	59
2	Conference papers	5
3	Book/Book section	5
Total		69

Figure 4: Number of Articles by Type of Publication

With regards to the research method used, 30 (44%) of the studies used a qualitative technique as a method of data analysis, 17 (24.64%) used quantitative techniques such as descriptive statistics and regression analysis, 10 (14.50%) used both qualitative and quantitative techniques (i.e., mixed methods), 4 (5.8%) were papers that were based on literature review methodology, while the remaining 8 (11.6%) were theoretical papers.

S/No.	Method used	No. of Studies
1	Qualitative	30
2	Quantitative	17
3	Mixed method	10
4	Literature review method	4
5	Theoretical papers	8
Total		69

Figure 5: Number of Articles by Method Used

To understand the spread of the literature reviewed across countries, we identified those across developed and developing countries that have published articles on the phenomenon under study. In the developed countries, the United States of America has the highest percentage with 24.64%, followed by China with 10.14%, and Australia with 7.25%. While in developing countries, Canada has the highest rate of 4.35%, followed by South Africa with 2.90%. Based on the reviewed literature, no study was conducted on this phenomenon under investigation in Nigerian higher educational institutions as indicated in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Study Distribution by Country

The Overarching theme: Toward theory development

Overarching theme: Epistemological Access Investigating epistemological access is phenomenal; it has attracted many scholars over the years ((Du-Plooy & Zilindile, 2014; Lockett, 2019; Morrow, 1994; Morrow, 2009; Willey, 2007). Epistemological access is an access that is bestowed upon students with the purpose of gaining mastery of the subject area in their disciplinary domain (Lockett, 2019; Morrow, 2009). Consequently, epistemological access requires a process theorization approach, to ensure gaining the disciplinary knowledge of the domain area and in-dept understanding (Fagan, 2020; Gamede, 2006; Lockett, 2019; Maniram, 2018; Mistri, 2016; Myers, 2019; Ongito, 2012; Venter, 2020). Some studies aligned with this view, though with varied perspectives. Some consider epistemological access which was first used by Willey (2007), a South African scholar, who problematized access to higher education. He used the term to describe two dimensions of access to higher education, being institutional (formal access) and access to knowledge, which he believes institutions distribute (epistemological access).

However, finding from this study corroborates the second perspective (i.e., access to knowledge which morrow believes institution distribute 'epistemological access'). Within this study epistemological access is pinned at meaningful access to knowledge, when learning is structured in a manner which ensures learners develop coherent ways of engaging with digital technologies and understanding different learning areas (Pendlebury, 2009, p. 24-25). This access, therefore, extends beyond mere physical access to include the ways in which learners are provided with quality teaching and learning. This is because our outcome describes activity-based events as characterized gaining the right knowledge of the disciplinary domain, which is continuously influence by mechanisms of people, structures, and cultures.

RQ1. How are the educational affordances of digital technologies for gaining epistemological access among marginalized groups contextualized in higher institutions in sub-Saharan African universities?

Thus, to answer RQ1 stated in the introduction, we cover extent literature to discover events that characterized epistemological access. Consequently, we identified three key themes from the synthesized literature. The themes include educational technological affordances, learning context, and dialogic activities. We discuss these themes by starting with the first theme, educational technological affordances, as detailed below.

Theme One: educational technological affordances

The term 'affordances' (Gibson, 1977), often known as action possibilities, refers to the relationship between the perceived and actual qualities of digital technology. Thus, the way technology provides opportunities for learning is frequently influenced by the underlying pedagogy. Affordances and constraints, relates to how digital technologies might potentially be deployed and used (Major & Warwick, 2019). Educational technological affordance is one of the key existing entities that is fundamental to epistemological access in the current trends (Bower, 2008; Major et al., 2022; Major et al., 2018). This theme, 'educational technological affordances,' explores the concepts that describe the relevancy of education using ICT-related facilities. The concepts of educational technological affordances include engaging in productive processes, engaging in co-construction, monitoring and regulation, (Jeong & Hmelo-Silver, 2016), representation of content (Major & Warwick, 2019), engaging in productive processes, engaging in co-

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construction, monitoring and regulation (Jeong & Hmelo-Silver, 2016), browsing, selection, supportive/challenging, assistive memory, control (Cook et al., 2019), and usability (Shin, 2021). Educational technological affordance guide towards gaining access to education in higher education institutions. Thus, affordance has been used in other fields like human-computer interaction (Turner, 2005), information systems (Norman, 1999; Seidel et al., 2013; Volkoff & Strong, 2017), computer science, decision support systems (Leifler, 2011), artificial intelligence and robotics (Lemaignan et al., 2017), engineering (Maier & Fadel, 2001), and education (Bower, 2008). Although, technology affordance is described in a variety of ways in the literature. Wijekummar et al. (2006) defined affordances as the interactions between users and tools in ways that influence and guide collaborations (Carter et al., 1999). Gaver (1991) explored affordances as the strengths and weaknesses of technology that could be offered to users. Graves (2007) looked at technological affordances to bridge the gap between determinist and social constructivist approaches. That description is different from that of Mao (2014), who described technological affordances as the technological features or functions that extend learning and perceptual capabilities, which might be economic, social, cognitive, or affective. In this context, therefore, affordance is described as the action possibilities that an object gives to the user, given the competency, skills, or expertise of the user. Affordance thus emerges from the interaction of technology and user characteristics (Bobsin et al., 2019). However, affordances are not always indefinable a priori, although they are easily observable when the technology application context is understood. Technology affordances influence students' interactions with technology and how they learn a subject using technology (Burlamaqui & Dong, 2017). Being rooted in the action potential offered by objects (i.e., technology) (Paul M Leonardi, 2013; Majchrzak & Markus, 2012), it may still be actualized or even perceived regardless of the context.

Digital technology has become increasingly integrated into classrooms to support and enrich student learning, (Dillenbourg & Hong, 2008; Lahiri & Moseley, 2015; Zaka, 2012) particularly in fostering self-directed and collaborative learning experiences. This approach aligns with the current trend in educational planning to prioritize self-directed learning with the aid of technology (Collins & Halverson, 2010; Jonassen & Hung, 2008). Teachers are encouraged to leverage digital tools and collaborative methods to facilitate dialogic interactions among students in technology-supported classrooms. These interactions not only enhance knowledge exchange but also empower students to actively engage with course materials and each other, thereby fostering a supportive and inclusive learning environment. Through digital technology, students can work together seamlessly, communicate effectively, and access resources efficiently, ultimately promoting a more dynamic and interactive educational experience (Maher, 2012). Therefore, we state the following proposition:

P1: Educational technological affordances will guide to gain epistemological access in sub-Saharan Africa.

Theme Two: learning context

The discussed theme focuses on the impact of digital technology on the learning context, emphasizing its role in enhancing learner autonomy (Al-Ani, 2013; Payton & Kvasny, 2016), inclusion, participation, classroom atmosphere, motivation, engagement, and interpersonal relationships (Al-Ani, 2013; Asamoah & Andoh-Baidoo, 2018). Studies show that digital technologies can empower students to take greater ownership of their learning by facilitating cooperative decision-making and self-monitoring of progress (Maher, 2012). Moreover, digital tools encourage learner inclusion and participation through collaborative group interactions, democratic decision-making, and increased intrinsic interest in learning apps (Ilomäki & Lakkala, 2018). Additionally, digital technology contributes to a positive teaching environment by fostering a sense of community, solidarity, and collaboration among students, as well as promoting increased interaction and open questioning by teachers. Furthermore, it enhances interpersonal relationships, particularly between teachers and students, and among students themselves, when the quality of interactions improves. Lastly, digital technology boosts learner motivation and engagement by stimulating curiosity, providing enjoyable learning experiences, and offering relevant and applicable tools.

In dialogical classroom interaction for teaching and learning, when digital technology is used to perform certain responsibilities like problem solving, information management, skills acquisition, and collaboration with respect to effectiveness, efficiency, and ethics, competence is very important and it is referred to as a group of skills, knowledge, and attitudes (Ferrari, 2012), that can be applied by a group of individuals. Therefore, learning context is critical in providing education to students in the educational context.

P6: In higher education institutions, learning context will guide sub-Saharan African countries in gaining epistemological access.

Theme Three: dialogic activities

This section addresses four major sub-themes related to the ‘dialogic activities’ theme. Studies (Brown & Dillard, 2015; Li et al., 2022; Major & Warwick, 2019; Smeda et al., 2014; Tiven et al., 2018) examine how digital technology can improve dialogic engagement by increasing exposure to diverse viewpoints. This includes providing children with frequent opportunities to recognize that their peers hold opposing viewpoints. For example, a study reporting an online asynchronous discussion making alternative views of a science topic more memorable by modeling the process of distinguishing ideas (Place, 2019). Furthermore, digital technology such as micro-blogging tool can enable students with minimal background knowledge to tap into a pool of other students’ viewpoints, example, readers or ‘followers’ can access and engage with a variety of ‘contributions’ given by others (Singleton, 2016). Several research studies (Bo et al., 2018; Bower, 2008; Charitonos, 2015; Davidsen & Vanderlinde, 2016) address the issue of considering the perspectives of others. For example, prompting students to consider the ‘audience’ and explain, comment, or contribute to an online forum where the process of externalizing ideas pushes students to carry out deeper explanations (Seethamraju, 2014).

The section illustrates how digital technology supports knowledge co-construction and metacognitive learning among students. It discusses various methods such as collaborative production of digital artifacts like Talkwall, which fosters shared cognition and collective evaluation. Additionally, it highlights the role of technology-mediated debate and video-stimulated reflective discussions in promoting metacognition. Furthermore, it explores how dialogue, facilitated by digital platforms, aids in understanding peers and provides technical support. Teachers play a crucial role in scaffolding comprehension through dialogue and technology, exemplified by tools like Talkwall and strategies like establishing ground rules for talk. Overall, this highlights the importance of technology-enhanced dialogue in facilitating learning and collaboration among students.

P3: Synergy between educational technological affordances, learning context, and dialogic activities will be more effective in gaining epistemological access in higher education institutions in sub-Saharan Africa.

RQ2. What challenges may implicate gaining epistemological access in a quest to use digital technology for dialogic interaction in higher education institutions in sub-Saharan Africa?

In this section, we describe the findings of the theme synthesis in response to RQ2. Following a literature synthesis process, two high-level themes were identified, this theme linked to the challenges of using digital technology to help acquire epistemological access from the standpoint of the users, namely, i. students; and ii; teachers. As with the theme synthesis for RQ1, these are broad categories, and several research studies identify multiple issues.

RQ2 theme one – challenges facing students

The section discusses challenges that students may encounter when engaging in dialogic interaction with digital technologies. It explores factors such as students’ technical skills, knowledge, and access to technology, impacting their ability to effectively utilize digital tools for learning. Challenges include unfamiliarity with tools, lack of access to necessary devices or applications, spelling errors affecting message comprehension, and limitations in reading and writing abilities hindering participation. Additionally, unequal access to technology and poor engagement rates pose barriers to learner inclusion and engagement. Issues such as varying prior experiences and expectations among students further complicate classroom dialogic environments. The text emphasizes the importance of active participation and synchronous peer conversations to maintain focused discussions, highlighting the need for addressing these challenges to facilitate effective interaction with digital technologies in education.

The text highlights the diverse perceptions students hold regarding the value of technology in learning, often focusing on the superficial qualities of ICT tools. Challenges arise from students’ varying levels of interaction with digital technologies, with some preferring individual work over interactive activities. Additionally, technology use can lead to distractions or frustrations, such as physical features of digital tools or administrative tasks like remembering usernames and passwords. Understanding these challenges is crucial for teachers to effectively integrate digital technologies into classroom dialogic interaction, particularly in regions like sub-Saharan Africa, to ensure equitable access to learning opportunities for all students.

RQ2 theme two – challenges facing teachers

This section addresses the potential challenges that teachers may face. The section deals with issues related to classroom management of learning. Studies addresses pedagogical challenges faced by teachers regarding the use of digital technologies in classroom dialogic interaction. Central concerns include the quality of teacher questioning and student discussion. Teachers often employ closed questioning on learning management systems (e.g., Alexander et al., 2017; Lyle, 2008), while opportunities for deeper engagement through uptake questions are limited. Additionally, challenges arise when attempting to foster a new learning culture, including addressing instructors' belief systems and navigating systemic school cultures and curricular frameworks. Teachers must establish supportive social infrastructures for inquiry-based learning, despite the associated challenges. Broad pedagogical challenges include the need for shifts in pedagogical practices and providing professional support for integrating digital technology into teaching. These challenges encompass instructional design issues and ensuring sustained student engagement with digital tools over time. Addressing these challenges is crucial for effectively integrating digital technologies into teaching practices. The instructional design challenges, such as the possibility of using the same function of a technology to support both dialogic and more traditional didactic strategies (Johnson et al., 2016), as well as ensuring that student use of a tool does not change over time (Major & Warwick, 2019; Mohammed, 2019).

Other studies explore the challenges the teachers face when successful collaboration is established. The necessity to create the appropriate resources and abilities to facilitate collaboration is of special relevance. For example, the success of software to facilitate productive classroom discussion for gaining access may be dependent in part on the provision of appropriate learning contexts in which students can share information and criticize each other's perspectives (Fu et al., 2013; Fu et al., 2019). Challenges can occur because of the increasing pace of technology-based education (i.e., EduTech). For example, given the rapid pace of asynchronous group discussion, teachers' attempts to guide and supervise the topic may easily be disregarded (Koch, 2017). The increased pace of technology-enhanced lectures may also reduce opportunities for extensive teacher-student interaction (Gaille, 2018; Samaniego-Eraza et al., 2015). There are other effects on instructors' time management, such as the additional pre-planning required when using the learning management system (Fathema & Akanda, 2020; Zafarullah et al., 2016) and the time-consuming nature of following threaded discussions in CSCL environments (J.-T. Lee et al., 2014). Teachers also expressed their concerns about new behavior management challenges. Students, for example, may get disinterested when interacting with learning management system (Cicekci & Sadik, 2019; Mohammadi et al., 2021), whilst some teachers may be challenged by the manner in which students express themselves when conversing digitally, including their use of slang and inappropriate language (Åberg & Waller, 2012).

The challenges resulting from teachers' technical skills are a penultimate feature of included studies. It was reported in some studies (Buabeng-Andoh, 2012; Guerriero, 2014; Lodge et al., 2018) that some studies, teachers must have a specific level of technical knowledge when employing digital technology to enhance dialogic teaching and learning. This, for example, will allow teachers to become fully acquainted with the benefits of a technology's features (Cardullo & Wilson, 2015). Finally, some studies note the importance of having the necessary access to existing high digital resources to support teachers to deploy technology effectively in the classroom (Bower, 2008; Cardullo & Wilson, 2015; Cook et al., 2019; Ghavifekr & Rosdy, 2015; Major et al., 2022).

Theorizing constructs of digital technology affordance for epistemological access

Drawing from the conceptual themes extracted from literature reviewed, we answered the research question one and two (**RQ1 & RQ2**) posed in the introduction, by theorizing a framework as shown in **Figure 7**. The framework consists of three domains, (1) T1 – T2 cultural conditioning and structural conditioning (socio-technical structures); (2) T2-T3 social/socio-cultural interactions; and (3) T3 – T4 structural/cultural elaboration. The framework highlights the identified events as the answer to research question one in the first segment and second segment of the framework (i.e., T1 – T2, and T2 – T3). Further, the third segment (i.e., T3 – T4) of the framework provide answer to research question two.

At T1 – T2 of the framework, the students are coming into the university as freshers. Similarly, the artifactual structures (socio-technical structures) are all in place in the University for Dialogic Classroom Interaction. By contrast, it is recognized that socio-technical structures pre-date students' enrolment into the university because the students meet those structures at the time of admission. In a quest to use digital technologies provided at higher educational institutions, there are affordances that a designer integrates into the EduTech. These are structural, instructive, and

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functional affordances. According to Ditzler et al. (2018, p. 22), “structural affordances are the object material features, properties, or capabilities of a tool.” In this context, the EduTech are design for dialogic classroom interaction that students can interact with. Meanwhile, EduTech, in this case, have been in place before students enrolled into a university. The features and affordances of EduTech create objective context for students, with structural, instructive, and functional affordances fed into time period T2 – T3, this serve as the first theme discovered in this study (**i.e., Educational Technological Affordances**). When these affordances are fed into time period T2 – T3, we may now analyze students-teacher interacting with the digital technologies (example, learning management systems, Talkwall, social media, etc.) in a particular environment (**i.e., university**) (**i.e., Learning Contexts**). During the interaction, the mechanisms triggering the interaction process, when it comes to people emergent properties (PEP), are reflexivity, manipulation, exploration, and sense-making. For the structural emergent properties (SEP), it comprises of IT affordances, institution, political, and legal structures that trigger the interaction process. While the cultural system of a particular university are the cultural emergent properties (CEP) that trigger the interaction between students-teachers, which is dialogic interaction and possibly acquiring a laptop over the time period T2 – T3 as the last theme identified in this study (**i.e., Dialogic Activities**). As students-teachers involve in constant interaction with digital technologies at time period T2 – T3, while user enactment of affordance processes is going on, ‘Epistemological Access’ can be gained as the overarching theme (**i.e., phenomenon**). When the epistemological access is gained in the higher education institution using digital technologies, there will be students’ change, change in the technology and change in the culture at time period T3 – T4. Meanwhile, they have undergone changes and metamorphose into something else, a transformational affordance has been achieved. Archer referred to structural elaboration ‘morphogenesis’ (Archer, 1995). But if the change has not occurred (**i.e., morphostasis**) where students, teachers face some challenges of either digital technology, institutional, political/legal challenges, epistemological access has not been achieved, as such T3 – T4 will now become T1.

Figure 7: Theoretical framework of educational technology affordances and epistemological access. Source (Authors)

Discussion of Findings

A systematic literature review was conducted, analyzing 69 studies to address two research questions regarding the use of digital technologies for education in sub-Saharan African universities. The questions focused on the affordances of digital technologies for marginalized groups’ epistemological access and the challenges hindering such access. The goal was to map peer-reviewed studies from 2012 to 2022 and assess the potential and limitations of

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digital technology in improving classroom interaction. The discussion outlines issues identified in existing research and extends to thematic and sub-thematic considerations, suggesting avenues for further study stimulated by the systematic review.

The study further discusses the search process and findings of a systematic review on digital technology in education, highlighting several key points. Firstly, it notes a prevalence of studies in information systems education, possibly due to a focus on argumentation and reasoning in scientific inquiry. Secondly, there is a scarcity of studies from sub-Saharan Africa, potentially influenced by the narrow range of technologies studied, leading to a bias towards regions with higher adoption rates. Additionally, many digital technologies used in education were initially developed for other purposes. Methodologically, qualitative approaches dominate, reflecting a focus on the interplay between classroom discussion and technology, often within a sociocultural framework. Overall, the studies identified vary in their aims, scope, and theoretical framing, but many are influenced by sociocultural perspectives emphasizing the role of digital technologies in individuals' relationships with their surroundings.

The text delves into the interdependence of learning components, emphasizing the sociocultural viewpoint that considers how tools, both mental and material, are used in human activity to generate knowledge. It notes that while new digital technologies may not inherently improve learning, they can significantly impact engagement. The thematic synthesis identifies themes around digital technology affordance and dialogic interactions, highlighting their role in gaining epistemological access. Challenges faced by students and teachers regarding technology use are discussed, with an emphasis on the sociocultural approach that highlights the interconnectedness of these challenges. The concept of affordance is explored, emphasizing the importance of aligning technology use with educational goals. The text concludes by advocating for collaboration between experts, designers, teachers, researchers, and students to fully explore the potential of digital technology in enhancing learning.

Conclusion

The study aimed to understand how marginalized groups can access epistemological knowledge in higher educational institutions, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa. This was achieved through two main approaches: conducting a systematic literature review on digital technologies and developing a theoretical framework. The review highlighted a gap in existing research, which often focused on technology or students separately, rather than their integrated interactions for achieving epistemological access. The synthesized theoretical framework offers an integrated perspective on how structural and cultural systems of students and digital technology can interact to facilitate epistemic access. Additionally, it addresses gaps such as the influence of e-learning management systems on faculty during dialogic interaction. The framework not only provides new research avenues in the information systems domain but also serves as inspiration for future empirical testing in higher educational institutions globally.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study regarding assessment of digital technological affordances and epistemological access in higher educational institutions in Nigeria, higher educational institutions should develop and implement an integrated digital learning platform that consolidates user educational resources, digital academic communication, research and innovation, remote learning, virtual engagement, digital libraries, and inclusive digital education. This platform should be user-friendly, ensuring seamless navigation and accessibility for underprivileged students. The University should invest in user-centric design principles to enhance the usability of digital technologies for underprivileged students. Prioritize user friendly design, optimizing outcomes, and adaptive flexibility in the development and deployment of digital tools. Solicit regular feedback from underprivileged students to iteratively improve the user interface and overall usability of digital platforms. Universities in Nigeria should implement educational strategies that capitalize on the identified transformational changes associated with underprivileged students' interaction with digital technologies. Foster personalized learning experiences, encourage global collaboration and connectivity, integrate holistic learning and skills development, and promote inclusivity and global education. This may involve the development of tailored programs, mentorship opportunities, and collaborative projects that leverage digital technologies.

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Assessment of Factors Affecting Academic Achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government Area of Imo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study sought to investigate the assessment of factors affecting academic achievement of secondary school female students in Okigwe Local Government Area Of Imo State, Nigeria. Two research questions guided the study and one hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study design was descriptive survey. The population for the study is 3,560 which consisted of all female secondary school students in public schools in Okigwe Local Government Area of Imo State. The sample size is 180 students. Out of the 9 public secondary schools in Okigwe Local Government Area of Imo State, 4 were chosen by simple random sampling. Furthermore, 45 students were selected from the 4 public secondary schools. The questionnaire titled: Assessment of factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students (AFAAASSFS). It was constructed by the researchers. The questionnaire was divided into two sections, Section A sought to find out the bio-data of the respondents, section B is divided into two parts based on the research questions. The coefficient of reliability has been estimated at 0.81 which was suitable for the studies. Item mean was used to answer the research questions, any item above 2.5 is considered accepted and below 2.5 is rejected. T-test was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 significant levels. Finding from the study revealed that that a lot of factors affect the academic achievement of female secondary school students. One of the core factor is unwanted pregnancy which make the female students to drop out of school and end their academic aspiration in life. It was recommended that school counsellors should invite and visit parents regularly to foster their interest in children education.

Keywords: Assessment, Factors, Academic Achievement Female Students

Introduction

Academic achievement is of utmost importance for the wealth of a nation and its prosperity. There is a strong link between academic achievement and socio – economic development of the members of the society. It is the outcome of education – the extent to which a student has learned (Adeyemi & Adeyemi, 2014). Okolo et. al. (2017) observed that some students often complain that ‘other student(s) perform better than themselves because the former is better inclined’ while both were taught in the same environment with same teaching method, same content, same time, by the same person and under the same condition. In the same sets of students, one finds the geniuses as well as the dummies. While the geniuses make positive impact in the society, the dummies go about constituting nuisance both to himself, immediate community and the entire society at large.

Academic achievement determines the extent to which the teachers and school leaders are successful in terms of their pedagogical and management processes and practices (Razu & Afrin, 2018). Academic success and accomplishments can be measured by how well students perform on exams and tests. Furthermore, according to Farooq, et. al. (2011), academic achievement of students is the main priority of all educators. There would be no schools, students, lecturers, supporting personnel, instructional resources to improve teaching, examinations and tests to gauge student’s comprehension of pedagogy and competencies if there is no assessment of students’ academic achievement.

Assessment of learning becomes critical in post primary education because a look into educational institutions of learning reveals that students who perform poorly in academics are occasionally admitted, promoted and allowed into higher classes (Asuquo & Chuktu, 2016), which should not be permitted in an ideal society, because it adds to the complication and ambiguity of dealing with issues related to students learning and evaluating their academic performance at secondary institutions. As a result, coping with the challenges of students learning and assessing their academic achievement becomes more difficult at secondary education.

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The stakeholders' major concern in education is poor performance. This is because it leads to tragic wastage of human, social and economic potentials of countries worldwide. Many factors such as lack of facilities in schools, lack of teachers, indiscipline, unfavorable home environment, absenteeism and repetition, low intelligence and anxiety do cause poor academic achievement (Ndirangu, 2007). Demeke and Ashagrie (2017) observed that age, gender and socio-economic background were responsible for differences in academic achievement. It was also observed that negative attitude of both male and female teachers towards female students affect their ability to perform well in various subjects (Aragaw, 2016), and the quality of teachers has a greater impact on girls' education than boys. On the other hand, tasks like homework, tutoring, punishment, sex ratio, and class size have slightly different effects on girls than boys (Mensch & Lloyd, 2008).

Furthermore, Zewude and Aashine (2016) attempted to assess and identify the major factors or independent variables that influence student academic performance at the College of Natural and Computation Science of Wolaita Sodo University in Ethiopia using binary logistic regression. The study revealed that peer influence, securing the first choice of department, arranging study time outside class, amount of money received from family and father's education level were significant variables that influenced academic performance of students in the school.

Muhammed, and Jibril (2019) researched on the examination of students' family socio-economic status as well as availability of academic facilities as it affects students' academic achievement in the department of statistics, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria was conducted on a sample of 100 students from the department. Data for the research was obtained through a structured questionnaire with a response value of 90 students. Regression Analysis and Analysis of Variance of the determined model indicated a strong positive relationship between CGPA and the predictors. The result of the analysis indicated that availability of reading materials, interest in course of study and reading habits contributed to students' academic performance determined by CGPA.

Reports presented by Tokunbo et. al. (2018)] indicated that, despite effective communication skills, subject mastery and proper class room management on the side of lecturers, students' academic achievement was deterred by unwanted pregnancy, poor water and electricity supply, inadequate social interaction avenue, poor staff offices as well as hostels. Furthermore, Chi-Square analysis revealed relationship between other factors like socio-economic status, family background and availability of academic facilities, which contributed to the performance of students at various Colleges of Education. It was recommended that parental support to students and funding of Colleges of education is pertinent to students' performance at such tertiary institutions. A descriptive method was adopted by Okoedion et. al. (2019) where stratified data, which ensures gender balance, was collected. Analysis using percentages, means, t-test and multiple regression analysis with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) was employed to determine academic performance of students in Nigerian Universities from a sample size of 400. Findings indicated that the major factors affecting students' academic performance in Nigerian universities are student, lecturer and institutional related factors. The study also revealed a significant joint contribution of student, lecturer, institutional and home-related factors on poor academic performance of students in Nigerian universities. Conclusion and recommendations were provided in the light of the empirical findings. It is therefore based on the above phenomena that this study is specifically designed to assessment of factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria.

In a nutshell, students act or behave in a very funny way, one wonders if all students came to study or not. There is high rate of examination malpractice, non-chalant attitude towards class work, chatting with online friends while lectures are going on, playing and listening to music in class, coming to class late and sometimes do not even attend or appear in class till the examination day, pays little or no attention to study materials, high rate of carry over courses, causing problems for the serious students, the lecturers and the school system at large. It is therefore based on the above phenomena that this study is specifically designed to assessment of factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to assess the Factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria. The interest of the researchers is to assess critically and identify the factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria. The specific objectives include to Identify:

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1. Factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria.
2. Solution to academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria

Research Questions

1. What is the item mean factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria?
2. What is the item mean of solution to academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the item mean of junior females and senior females of factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria

Methodology

The research design adopted was descriptive survey. It is a precursor to quantitative research designs as it provides the general overview, giving some valuable pointers as to what variables are worth testing quantitatively. The population for the study is 3,560 which consisted of all female secondary school students in public schools in Okigwe Local Government Area of Imo State. The sample size is 180 students. Out of the 9 public secondary schools in Okigwe Local Government Area of Imo State, 4 were chosen by simple random sampling. Furthermore, 45 students were selected from the 4 public secondary schools.

The major research instrument(s) adopted in the study was the questionnaire titled: Assessment of factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students (AFAAASSFS). It was constructed by the researchers. The questionnaire was divided into two sections, Section A sought to find out the bio-data of the respondents, section B is divided into two parts based on the research questions. The four-point scale of strongly agreed [SA] 4 points, agreed [A] 3 points, disagreed [D] 2 points, and Strongly Disagreed [SD] 1 point were used to rate the reaction of the respondents to the items contained in the questionnaires. 2.5 weighted marks was used to assess the outcome of the analysis.

The researchers constructed the questionnaire and gave it to research experts in the Faculty of Education, National Open University of Nigeria to determine the validity. Professional corrections and comments were incorporated into the final draft of the instrument to ensure that it had content validity. In order to determine the reliability of the instrument, pilot study was conducted by administering it on a sample of 30 respondents in Onuimo Local Government Area of Imo State, which was not part of the original sample population. The exercise was repeated in two weeks interval and the data from both tests were analysed with Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistics. The coefficient of reliability has been estimated at 0.81 which was suitable for the studies.

The research instrument was administered and collected from the respondents by the researcher. After the distribution of the questionnaire, respondents were given a week to fill out the questionnaire. This time frame was given in order to give enough time to the respondents to reflect on the items on the questionnaire and ensure valid responses. All the 180 copies of the questionnaires were administered to the respondents, all the questionnaire were retrieved.

Item mean was used to answer the research questions, any item above 2.5 is considered accepted and below 2.5 is rejected. T-test was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 significant levels.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the item mean of factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria? Present the statistical data analysis used to answer the research question 1 in table as shown below:

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics on the factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State.

S/N	factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students	N	Sum	Mean	SD	Remark
1.	School location	180	581.00	3.11	.74	Agreed
2.	Parental education	180	591.00	3.18	.64	Agreed
3.	Parental economic status	180	591.00	3.16	.68	Agreed
4.	Parental social class	180	587.00	3.14	.59	Agreed
5.	Parental income	180	609.00	3.26	.57	Agreed
6.	Peer pressure	180	595.00	3.12	.60	Agreed
7.	Youthful disposition	180	613.00	3.28	.59	Agreed
8.	Early marriage	180	571.00	3.05	.68	Agreed
9.	School phobia	180	519.00	2.78	.83	Agreed
10.	Environmental factors	180	513.00	2.74	.87	Agreed
11.	Child labour	180	555.00	2.97	.74	Agreed
12.	Single parent homes	180	589.00	3.15	.57	Agreed
13.	Poverty	180	575.00	3.07	.64	Agreed
14.	Religious belief	180	525.00	2.81	.83	Agreed
15.	First child in the family	180	535.00	2.86	.79	Agreed
16.	Parental indiscipline status	180	497.00	2.66	.89	Agreed
17.	Cultural beliefs	180	479.00	2.56	.79	Agreed
18.	Fear of academic failure	180	481.00	2.57	.78	Agreed
19.	Gender preference	180	479.00	2.56	.73	Agreed
20.	Unwanted pregnancy	180	636.00	3.40	.79	Agreed
	TOTAL	180	5,56	2.97	0.72	Agreed

Field work, 2023

Table 1 revealed the responses of student to factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State. Item 20 have the highest mean of 3.40 which pointed out the Unwanted pregnancy is core factor that affect female secondary school student academic achievement while item 17: Cultural beliefs and 19: Gender preference both with mean of 2.56 were considered as least factors that affect female students' academic achievement. All the 20 items were accepted as factors that affect female students' academic achievement.

Research Question 2

What is the item mean of solution academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics solution to academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State.

S/N	Statistics solution to academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students	N	Sum	Mean	SD	Remark
	Establishment of school's nearness to the people	180	621.00	3.32	.74	Agreed
2.	Parental motivation for females	180	641.00	3.43	.74	Agreed
3.	Providing academic materials for students	180	628.00	3.36	.72	Agreed
4.	Encouraging female children to imitate good models	180	638.00	3.41	.70	Agreed
5.	Proper discipline of children	180	631.00	3.37	.78	Agreed
6.	Good upbringing	180	622.00	3.33	.75	Agreed
7.	Youthful disposition	180	605.00	3.26	.78	Agreed
8.	Preventing early marriage for female children	180	647.00	3.46	.65	Agreed
9.	Ensuring gender equality	180	619.00	3.31	.76	Agreed
10.	Improvement of school environment	180	626.00	3.35	.70	Agreed
	Total	180	6278	3.36	0.73	Agreed

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Field work, 2023

Table 2 revealed the responses of student to solution to academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State. Item 8: Preventing early marriage for female children have the highest mean of 3.46 and item 7: Youthful disposition with the least mean of 3.26. all the 10 items were considered acceptable.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the item mean junior females and senior females of factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria.

Table 3: T-test Statistics on the difference the item mean junior females and senior females of factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Df	T	Sig.
Junior female in JSS	101	1.29	.45449	.04373	178	1.134	0.135
Senior Female in SSS	79	1.38	.48842	.05495			

Field 2023

The result in Table 3 revealed a t-test statistic on the difference the item means junior females and senior females of factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State at $t(1.134)$, $df= 178$, $P>.05$. The Hypothesis is accepted. The implication is that There is a significant difference between the item mean junior females and senior females of factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Findings from research question one revealed that a lot of factors affect the academic achievement of female secondary school students. One of the core factor is unwanted pregnancy which make the female students to drop out of school and end their academic aspiration in life. More so, Cultural beliefs and Gender preference was also a listed factor that have negated the academic achievement of the female students. In some culture it is seen as taboo to send the girl to further her education and male children are given more preference. This finding is in line with Demeke and Ashagrie (2017) observed that age, gender and socio-economic background were responsible for differences in academic achievement. The works of Tokunbo et. al. (2018) affirmed this finding that, despite effective communication skills, subject mastery and proper class room management on the side of lecturers, students' academic achievement was deterred by unwanted pregnancy, poor water and electricity supply, inadequate social interaction avenue, poor staff offices as well as hostels. The hypothesis revealed that there is a significant difference between the item mean junior females and senior females of factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Students.

Finding from the other research question revealed solutions to the factors affecting secondary school female students academic achievement can be solved. One of such way is the prevention of early marriage of the female students, so as not to have negative impact on their academic achievement. Other possible solution to the identified factors, which are establishment of school's nearness to the people, parental motivation for females, and encouraging female children to imitate good models. This is in line with Muhammed, and Jibril (2019) that parental role in adolescents education have a lot of positive impact on their academic achievement.

Implication of the findings of Study to Counsellors

The outcome of the study would help school counsellors to be equipped with the assessment of factor affecting academic achievement of female student. Programs and activities will be put in place to occupy the time of female students not to get involved in what will hamper their academic achievement.

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Conclusion

This study examined assessment of factors affecting academic achievement of Secondary School Female Students in Okigwe Local Government area of Imo State, Nigeria. One of the core factor is unwanted pregnancy which makes the female students to drop out of school and end their academic aspiration in life. Cultural beliefs and Gender preference were also listed factors that have negated the academic achievement of the female students. One of such ways is the prevention of early marriage of female students so as not to have negative impact on their academic achievement. Other possible solutions to the identified factors, are establishment of school's nearness to the people, parental motivation for females, and encouragement of female children to imitate good models.

Recommendations

Recommendations were made based on research findings;

1. Government should vigorously pursue and enlighten the public adequately on the importance of female education.
2. Government should provide the enabling environment for learning. Facilities like laboratories, libraries, sporting equipment, adequate number of teachers etc.
3. Government should provide employment opportunities to enable parents meet their children's academic requirements.
4. School counsellors should invite and visit parents regularly to foster their interest in children education.

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Assessment of Human Relations Skills on Job Performance among Colleges of Education Secretaries in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study assessed human relations skills on job performance among Colleges of Education Secretaries in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara State. A researcher-constructed questionnaire was used in obtaining information for the study, with a reliability coefficient of 0.72. A descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. Two research questions and one hypothesis guided the study. The population of the study comprised 80 secretaries in the public and private Colleges of Education in Ilorin metropolis, and census sampling technique was employed to sample all 80 secretaries. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the questions and regression analysis to test the hypothesis. Results obtained revealed a very high demonstration of human relations skills (Mean= 3.57; SD= 0.67); while secretaries' overall job performance was rated high (Mean= 3.43; SD= 0.66). There was a positive impact of human relations skills on job performance among colleges of education secretaries ($R= 0,076$). The study concludes that human relation skills impact on job performance among colleges of education secretaries in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara state. It is recommended, among others, that cultural sensitivity be integrated into the training of secretaries, to ensure human relations skills are attuned to cultural contexts in which secretaries operate.

Keywords: Human Relation Skills, Secretaries, Job Performance, Colleges of education,

Introduction

Organizational functions are carried out by individuals who must relate together within organizations, as well as relate with many others outside the organization, to get jobs done. Human relations/interpersonal skills are individuals' abilities that enable them to interact efficiently and effectively with others (Bryce, 2022; Mohmand, 2021; Sato, et al. 2019). According to Akhademe et al. (2022), it refers to individual skills that facilitate interaction between or among employees within or outside the organization. It includes the ability to share information with others, build strong relationships, seek feedback, recognize the accomplishment of others, listen to the views of others, create an atmosphere of trust, network with professional associates, seek counsel from others, and work well with others (Akhademe et al, 2022). They added that the skills are critical for workplace success.

Secretaries are individuals who keep records, take notes and handles general clerical work in the office. Secretaries, occupying a central position in organizational structures, are integral to the smooth functioning of day-to-day operations. According to Akpomi and Ordu's (2009) a professional secretary's ability to perform her job well depends on her knowledge, abilities, and office supplies. Their responsibilities extend beyond administrative tasks to include crucial roles in organizational efficiency and communication. As gatekeepers of information and communication channels, secretaries serve as key-persons in ensuring that the wheels of organizations turn smoothly. Recognizing this, it becomes imperative to delve into the intricacies of how human relation skills impact the job performance of secretaries.

Job performance refers to the execution of tasks committed to an individual towards accomplishment of group goals. Al-Omari & Okasheh (2017) views it as the measurement of organizational success through the assessment of employees' productivity and contributions. It refers to the measure of job results and their predefined targets (Akhademe et al. 2022), while it is defined as the worth and quantity of anticipated efforts put forth by employees to execute a specific task well (Wikipedia, 2022).

Human relation skills are mostly soft skills, which help to build and maintain healthy and balanced relationships at work, as it involves personal attributes of communication, empathy and teamwork which are essential for building positive relationships with others. This is important in workplaces for maximum productivity, as organizational members including secretaries, relate with customers or clients, suppliers and others within their environment. In the contemporary workplace, the spotlight on human relation skills has intensified, with a growing

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recognition of their pivotal role in organizational functioning. Others see it as a measure of how adept, skilled or proficient a person is at interacting with others (Ofojebe & Akudo, 2021). Human relations skill, which encompasses interpersonal communication, teamwork, conflict handling, emotional intelligence, is acknowledged as key a contributor to fostering a positive work environment and optimizing operational efficiency (Robbins & Judge, 2019). The increased emphasis on human/interpersonal competencies is particularly relevant in professions where effective communication and seamless collaboration are paramount, like in Colleges of Education.

Understanding the essential distinction of human relations skills and their direct implications on secretarial roles is essential for several reasons. First, the effectiveness of communication within the organization heavily relies on the interpersonal capabilities of its secretarial staff (Trenholm & Jensen, 2012). Clear and coherent communication, is vital for disseminating information accurately and maintaining a harmonious work environment (Trenholm & Jensen, 2012). According to Tantua and Akere (2022), good workplace human relation skills refer to the ability to cooperate in a right manner with others and build strong relationships. Looking at human relations skills from the perspective of managers in hospitality industries, it involves the process of creating systems, communication channels to enable group employees' relationships as well as strong one-on-one relationships

The practice of human relations is observed to involve; speaking with others in a manner that enjoys their support and commitment, smiling at people to promote bonding, being considerate with other people's feelings, being friendly and helpful, managing emotional pressure appropriately, positively handling grievances, giving positive comments and using criticisms frugally among many other practices. It becomes more important for secretaries in colleges of education, who relate with their immediate head/boss, and with other institutional workers who may require the attention of institutional managers, as well as students and parents who come around to lay complaints and seek clarifications from time to time. This shows the sensitivity of the secretary's position in educational institutions, and any failure to properly portray the institution well, is likely to result in building a poor image for such institutions which can result in poor achievement of institutional goals.

A good secretary is indispensable at promoting efficient office administration as they ensure office activities move smoothly and in the right paths, for the accomplishment of institutional goals. According to Belbin (2012), insights into team roles underscore the significance of diverse skills within a team, emphasizing that effective collaboration requires individuals with strong human relation skills. For secretaries, who are expected to liaise with different stakeholders, cultivate relationships, and ensure seamless teamwork, these skills become paramount.

Samuel (2018) studied the effect of employee relation on employee performance and organizational performance in small organizations; Sato et (2019) researched on the effects of interpersonal skills on workers performance; while Tantua and Akere (2022) considered workplace human relations skills on job performance of employees in hotels. The present study' focus is on assessing human relation skills on job performance among colleges of education secretaries.

Objectives of the Study

As organizations increasingly acknowledge the pivotal role of human relation skills in optimizing organizational performance, the need therefore arose to assess human relations skills on job performance among colleges of education secretaries in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara State. This study therefore;

1. Seek to provide empirical evidence on the impact of human relations on secretaries' job performances in Colleges of Education.
2. Establish the impact of secretaries on the overall accomplishment of the objectives of Colleges of Education, through the demonstration of human relation skills. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, there has been no study conducted on the impact of human relations skills on the job performance of secretaries within colleges of education.
3. The study holds importance in helping secretaries recognize the vital role of human relations skills in fulfilling their responsibilities, and also brings to light the importance of duly acknowledging the contributions of secretaries to institutional objectives.

Research Questions

1. To what extent is human relations skills demonstrated among colleges of education secretaries in Ilorin metropolis,

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2. Kwara State?
3. What is the extent of job performance among colleges of education secretaries in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara State?

Hypothesis

1. H₀₁ There is no significant impact of human relations skills on job performance among colleges of education secretaries in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State.

Methodology

The study employed the descriptive survey design to describe and interpret observed situations in Colleges of Education. The population of study consist of all secretaries in public and private colleges of education in Ilorin metropolis during the 2022/20234 academic session. All 80 secretaries in the public and private colleges of education form the sample of the study, using the census sampling technique. A researcher-designed questionnaire tagged Human Relations Skills and Secretaries' Job Performance Questionnaire (HRSSJPQ) was used to obtain data for the study. The questionnaire was duly validated by three experts from the department of Educational Management, Kwara State University, Malete. Reliability was ensured using the Cronbach Alpha method and the result yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.72. Mean and standard deviation were used to provide answers to the research questions, and the decisions on the research questions were taken using the following mean score boundaries. The mean score of 3.50 - 4.00 was rated very high, 2.50 - 3.49 as high, 1.50 - 2.49 low, while 1.00-1.49 was considered very low. Linear regression analysis was used to test the hypothesis at the 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1:

To what extent is human relations skills demonstrated among colleges of education secretaries in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara State?

Table 1: Secretaries' demonstration of human relation skills

S/N	Item Statement	X	SD	Remark
1	Cordial working relationship with bosses and others	3.28	0.69	High Extent
2	Cooperate with other institutional workers.	3.66	0.70	High Extent
3	Exhibit good communication skills	3.60	0.76	High Extent
4	Properly handle conflicts	3.89	0.65	High Extent
5	Show concern about problems of workers	3.43	0.57	High
Weighted Average		3.57	0.67	High Extent

The results in Table 1 revealed that secretaries demonstrate appropriate human relations skills (mean = 3.57; SD = 0.67) as evident in the scores for all the constructs. The demonstration of human relation skills by secretaries is to a very high extent as shown in the weighted average score.

Research Question 2:

What is the extent of job performance among colleges of education secretaries in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara State?

Table 2: Extent of secretaries' job performance

S/N	Item Statement	X	SD	Remark
1	Diligently carry out responsibilities in institutions.	3.37	0.69	High Extent
2	Their work meets required standards in the institutions.	3.53	0.70	High Extent
3	Contribute to the achievement of institutional objectives.	3.55	0.76	High Extent
4	Tasks handling promotes good image of institutions.	3.23	0.65	High Extent
5	Demonstrate good knowledge of tasks in the workplace.	3.47	0.57	High Extent
Weighted Average		3.43	0.66	High Extent

The analysis in Table 2 reveals the responses indicating an overall high extent of job performance by secretaries in Colleges of Education (mean = 3.43; SD = 0.66), with items 1, 4 and 5 indicating mean scores of 3.37,

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3.23 and 3.47 respectively reveals a high extent of job performance; while items 2 and 3 shows mean scores of 3.53 and 3.55 respectively, showcasing a very high extent of job performances by secretaries in the institutions. The weighted average of 3.43 reveals a generally high extent of job performance by secretaries

H₀₁: There is no significant impact of human relations skills on job performance among colleges of education secretaries in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State.

Table 3: Secretaries' demonstration of human relation skills on job performance

Model	N	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	F-cal.	P-value
1	80	0.076	0.006	0.003	2.395	0.023

1. Dependent Variable: Job Performance
2. Predictors: (Constant), Human Relation Skills

Table 4: Table of Coefficients

Model	Un-standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		95% Confidence Interval		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 (Constant)	55.136	4.288		12.858	0.000	46.707	63.565
Human Relation	2.085	1.347	0.076	1.548	0.023	0.563	4.733

Table 3 summarizes the regression results of the impact of secretaries' demonstration of human relation skills on their job performance in Colleges of Education. The result indicates that there was a positive impact of human relations skills demonstration on job performance ($R = 0.076$). while R Squared of 0.006 indicated that secretaries' human relation skills explained 0.06% variations in their job performance. The test of significance in Table 4 indicates that secretaries' demonstration of human relation skills impacts their job performance ($B = 2.085$; $t_{(79)} = 1.548$, $P=0.023$). This shows that at a 5% level of significance, there is enough evidence that the regression equation is well specified and that secretaries' demonstration of human relation skills impacts their job performance in Colleges of Education. Based on this submission, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that secretaries' cordial relationship in the workplace, cooperation, exhibition of good communication skills, proper handling of conflicts, and their show of concern for problems encountered by other workers and students, positively impact their performance in colleges of education.

Discussion of Findings

From the result of the study, there was evidence of a very high demonstration of human relations skills by secretaries in Colleges of Education. The secretaries ensured good communication, promoted cooperation, handled problems and institutional conflicts, and promoted collaboration among institutional members for the accomplishment of institutional objectives. This agrees with the submission of Akhademe, et al. (2022) whose result shows that human relations skills were rated high, with a mean of 79.07% among office managers. It is in tandem with Robbins and Judge's (2019) assertion that secretaries often act as intermediaries, to navigate through conflicts adeptly as they possess robust human relation skills which equips them with the tools necessary to address conflicts diplomatically, ensuring a harmonious work environment. The result is also in line with the earlier findings of Olorisade (2008) who submitted that intermediate managers in colleges of education demonstrate requisite managerial skills to a large extent, in discharging their duties.

The findings again indicate an overall high job performance by secretaries in colleges of education (mean = 3.43; $SD = 0.66$). This reveals secretaries who demonstrate good knowledge of their jobs, endear themselves to people, handle tasks with diligence, and contributing to the overall achievement of institutional goals. The high job performance of secretaries reveals individuals who successfully work with and enjoy the support of their deans, heads of departments and other staff members in executing institutional activities. This is in agreement with Akhademe, et al. (2022) submission that job performance among office managers was rated high, with a mean of 79.14%. it is also in tandem with the findings of Asher and Hindi (2014) who established the centrality of interpersonal/ human skills in organizational performance. The result again indicated that there was a positive impact of human relations skills on job performance among colleges of education secretaries. This shows that the job performance of secretaries was aided by the demonstration of appropriate human relations skills in Colleges of Education. This agrees with

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Kanhasamy' (2019) findings which revealed that a positive relationship exists between interpersonal/human skills and workers' performance; while Ofojebe and Akudo (2021) who reported that interpersonal/human skills significantly predicted job performance in schools. Robbins and Judge (2019) underscore that human relations skills contribute significantly to overall organizational success. Again, Belbin (2012), underscore the intrinsic connection between secretaries' human relation skills, particularly in the realm of teamwork, and their job performance. Tantua and Akere (2022) reported that workplace human relations skills improve employees' job performance; while Samuel (2018) found a weak but positive relationship between human relations and employee performance and organizational performance.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, which revealed that colleges of education secretaries demonstrate human relations skills to a very high extent in Ilorin metropolis, and that colleges of education secretaries' job performance are to a high extent. It was concluded that human relation skills of secretaries have positive impact on their job performance in colleges of education. It reveals the efforts of secretaries as link-persons to institutional managers, in relating with members of the institutional community and others, towards the accomplishment of the objectives of the institutions. This shows secretaries as gatekeepers of information and communication channels, who must be properly equipped to promote the good image of the institution and ensure good working relations with staff, students and other members of the public for the achievement of institutional goals and objectives.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that;

1. Secretaries should be better engaged in brainstorming sessions to solve institutional problems with other stakeholders. This will further improve their human relations skills and equip them to better handle conflicts and problem situations as it may arise, thus improving their performance further, for the overall success of their institutions.
2. Towards optimizing human relation skills among secretaries in colleges of education, navigating cultural differences within the workplace is important. This will involve integrating cultural sensitivity into training programs and organizational policies, to ensure that human relation skills are attuned to the cultural contexts in which secretaries operate. This will equip secretaries with the ability to navigate and appreciate diverse cultural backgrounds which can foster more effective communication and collaboration.
3. For enhanced job performance of college of education secretaries, they should be involved in institutional retreats organized to sharpen the focus of leaders/managers at re-strategizing and sharpening focus on institutional vision, towards attaining institutional goals. This will place secretaries in better position to effectively assist their immediate bosses in achieving institutional objectives and helping colleges of education at making greater impact in the society.
4. Institutional managers must acknowledge secretaries' demonstration of human relations skills as pivotal to success in institutions, and see secretaries as relevant and key persons for the achievement of institutional objectives. This will promote a more cordial working relationship with secretaries, and will go a long way to motivate and boost their morale, at encouraging secretaries to do more for their organizations.

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Assessment of Perceptions on Utilization of E-Learning Mode during Covid-19 Outbreak among Secondary School Students in Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study assessed the perceptions on utilization of e-learning mode during Covid-19 outbreak among secondary school students in Osun State, Nigeria. The paper examined the perceptions on relevance and challenges on utilization of e-learning. It assessed the relationship between male and female secondary school students' perceptions on the use of e-learning mode as well as and determined the relationships between public and private secondary school students' perceptions, respectively. The study employed a descriptive research design, and the population consisted of all public and private school students in Osogbo local government area of Osun State during the 2020/2021 Academic Session. A sample size of 125 male and 125 female students making a total number of 250 were selected using convenience sampling technique. A questionnaire tagged "Students' Perceptions on Utilization of E-Learning Mode during Covid-19 Outbreak in Osun State (SPUELMCOOS)" was used for data collection. The collected data was analysed using percentages and ANOVA. The findings of the study revealed that secondary school students generally value electronics, especially television, as a major audiovisual channel for mass education. The finding also showed that e-learning hinders learners' contributions and ability to ask questions wherever they are confused. The study's conclusion was that secondary school students had similar perceptions on utilization of e-learning during the Covid-19 outbreak in Osun State, Nigeria. The study recommended that the Nigerian government should not relent in its effort by providing necessary support to overcome challenges faced by e-learning among secondary school students.

Keyword: Educational System, Coronavirus, Covid-19 Outbreak, E-Learning Mode, Television, Secondary School Students

Introduction

Without exaggerating, the cornerstone of any national development, whether in a developed, developing, or underdeveloped country, is education. For all human societies to flourish and endure, they must acquire the necessary abilities, information, and experience (Onocha, 2013). Nonetheless, education enhances the country's human capital. An individual needs education for all-around development and to become a valuable member of society. Learning results in the development of a person's moral character, physical prowess, spiritual integrity, cultural refinement, emotional stability, and intelligent self-sufficiency from birth throughout life. Therefore, learning has occurred if there is a permanent change in behaviour as a result of practice and experience.

There are two types of learning: distance learning and conventional learning. Conventional learning, for example, is a type of teaching-learning arrangement where learners and instructors participate in the teaching-learning activities together (Ordu, 2021). Teachers and students are physically present in the classroom during this type of instruction. As opposed to this, distance learning is defined as a type of learning that takes place when a teacher is not physically present, typically with the assistance of one or more instructional media and resources (Harry, & Khan, 2000; Odewumi & Ajala, 2017). Raman (2011) observed that technology in the classroom changes the ways learning occurs; learners are no longer restricted to the four walls of classrooms, but rather have lots of opportunities to explore the vast volumes of available information on the internet to enhance meaningful learning. Distance learning is subdivided into open learning, flexible learning, and e-learning. In other words, e-learning is made possible by

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electronic technology, as defined by Kyari, Adiuku-Brown, Abechi, and Adelokun (2018). This includes online learning, computer-based learning, and virtual classrooms where content is delivered through e-networks, audio or video tape, satellite TV, video conferencing, CD-ROM, iPods, e-mails, wireless, and mobile technology.

Electronic-learning offers many benefits to students: it enables them to have access to many resources and tools, not be bound by place or time, study at their own pace, skip material already learned, and use a variety of tools to fit their own style. In distance learning, learners are separated geographically and by possible time from the instructor; hence, synchronous forms of e-learning have been in use to provide multi-outlet chances to meaningfully engage the students and therefore aid comprehension and retention. Abidoeye and Aderele (2019) revealed that most aspects of instructional activities globally today have been witnessing technological transformation, such as e-mail, e-conference, e-teaching, e-presentation, e-library, and online learning. These e-learning tools are easily utilised by learners to improve the successful teaching and learning of the subjects.

Generally speaking, e-learning refers to the delivery of instruction via the internet, mobile devices, satellite television, audio, video tape, and radio. According to a study by Karunaratne et al. (2020), e-learning is a flexible and effective alternative method of instruction during the COVID-19 pandemic. Prior to the advent of the internet, Ternholm (2011) and Kannadasan, Muthuchamy, and Amalorpavam (2019) contended that television was the most widely used media. Television is still regarded as one of the most popular e-tools for distance learning in the modern era. One of the most effective ways to deliver education is through television, which offers distant learners both audio and visual effects to illustrate concepts and procedures. According to earlier research, television is widely used to provide distance learning to students worldwide (Olakulehin & Salawu, 2006; Akhter, 2011; Kunucen, Kaya, Mirici, Kunucen & Ozturk, 2003). Thus, if they so choose, all students can benefit from home-study television. The study by Olakulehin and Salawu (2006) went on to explain the educational value of television in the following ways: it can reach a large number of geographically dispersed students with a single instructional message; it can boost students' motivation and interest even when they are geographically apart from their teachers; and it can provide essential teaching resources because all students should be able to watch the broadcast.

Both humans and animals can contract coronavirus diseases, such as the respiratory illness coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), which can spread from one person to another (Yadav, & Mohite, 2020). According to Yao, Ye, and Zhang (2020), an infection can cause symptoms to last for two to fourteen days. These symptoms include fever, dyspnea, and coughing. Spreading the virus can occur through respiratory droplets from an infected person's cough or sneeze, touching an infected person's hands or face, touching doorknobs that other infected people have touched, or touching a surface or object contaminated with the virus and then touching their own mouth, nose, or possibly their eyes (Yadav & Mohite, 2020; Keyaerts, Vijgen & Maes, 2004).

The Zambian Ministry of Health announced at a press conference in mid-March 2020 that all schools, colleges, and universities would be permanently closed on Friday, March 20, 2020, due to concerns about the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic, which had reportedly destroyed most of China, the United States, Italy, Spain, and other regions of Europe and Africa. Because many public and private schools administer assessment tests at the end of each of the three terms of the academic year, this meant that secondary school students in the majority of public and private schools ended the second term of the academic year 2020 without writing their end-of-term examinations. It appears that there were few literatures on COVID-19 in Nigerian educational studies. The existing literature (Wu & McGoogan, 2020; Kraemer et al., 2020; Hopman, Allegranzi, & Mehtar, 2020; Chinazzi et al., 2020) is closely linked to medical research. This is not because the COVID-19 pandemic has not had an impact on education directly; rather, it is because research on education has not often taken into account how diseases may affect how well students are taught around the world. Every aspect of human life has been directly impacted by COVID-19 as a result of its rapid spread. Employees in the medical field are working extremely hard to find a medical cure for this pandemic. Because businesses are closing on a daily basis and human movement is restricted both within and across borders, economists are working on ways to manage the economic impact of this epidemic on the nation's economy (Kraemer et al., 2020). Unexpectedly, a disease that first surfaced in the Wuhan region of China spread quickly throughout the country and other countries (Wickramasinghe et al., 2020).

On the other hand, even in situations where childhood infection rates are low, school closures are a crucial part of social distancing strategies to slow the illness's spread and stop cases from rising too quickly, which would put strain on health services. The exact timing of the closures, the population's age distribution, and the length of the closure will all have an impact on how successful they are in containing the spread of infection. The US Centres for

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Disease Control (US-CDC) have released new guidelines that the school closures are required to facilitate contact tracing and decontamination, particularly in cases where COVID-19 cases are found in schools. It also highlights how important it is for promoting social distancing.

According to a study by Karunarathne et al. (2020), many students have trouble using e-learning due to technical problems, poor internet connectivity, expensive chargers, lack of IT literacy, and health problems like eye problems that prevent them from using e-learning. According to the study by Aboyade, Madu, and Ajayi (2023), a number of factors, such as inadequate funding, inadequate facilities, lack of orientation, poor internet connectivity, inconsistent poor supply, and a high cost of internet subscription, prevent Federal Polytechnic Ede students from adopting and using e-learning platforms.

According to Aboderin's (2015) research, the primary issues were lack of computers, a lack of internet connection, lack of e-learning tools and resources for students, expensive software, and erratic power sources. It should be mentioned that e-learning presents a number of difficulties. In order to enhance the e-learning initiative in Nigeria, basic amenities like computers, electricity, and the Internet are still lacking, as demonstrated by a later study by Kyari et al. (2018). This implies that the problem of inadequate infrastructure will continue.

Madhubhashini (2021) noted that Covid-19 outbreak has made a serious impact on socio-economic, cultural, political, education sectors locally and globally. He further stated that Covid-19 has a negative impact on the whole education system from primary education to higher education. According to the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) report in 2020, the Covid-19 pandemic has also made a serious negative impact on socio-economic, cultural, political and education sectors in Sri Lanka. In this context, the government and private schools, universities and the other education institutions are also facing some challenges with the traditional mode of education. Therefore, government and private institutions introduced some alternative teaching and learning mechanisms via new technology. It is important to note that school closure can have an impact on the labour market by placing more of a burden on parents, who must either stay at home with their children or find alternative arrangements, which is particularly bad if examinations like the WAEC, GCE, and NECO are closed. Given the circumstances in Osun State, e-learning via television is seems to be more effective mode of instruction in the state secondary schools and it is hoped that this will create an environment that will offers learners an exciting opportunity to improve their learning experiences.

It has been observed that the outbreak of COVID-19 has caused unprecedented disruptions in the education sector worldwide, and Osun State in Nigeria is no exception. In response to the closure of schools and the enforcement of social distancing measures, educational institutions have resorted to e-learning as a mean of ensuring continuity in learning. While this shift to online platforms has been necessary to curb the expansion of the virus, it has also brought to light a number of challenges and opportunities that warrant further investigation. However, the sudden transition to e-learning has raised concerns about the quality and effectiveness of online instruction. The benefits of e-learning in the delivery of academic subjects in schools have been noted by the researchers (Olakulehin & Salawu, 2006; Kannan, Muthuchamy, & Amalorpavam, 2019). According to these authors, television is widely used to facilitate distance learning for students around the globe. It is unclear how likely the teaching-learning process has improved among secondary school students with the use of e-learning during Covid-19 out-break in Osun State. Thus, this study evaluated secondary school students' perceptions on utilization of e-learning method during Covid-19 outbreak in Osun State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to assess secondary school students' perceptions on utilization of e-learning mode during Covid-19 out-break in Osun State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Assess perceptions on relevance and utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary school students in Osun State
2. Assess challenges on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary school students in Osun State
3. Examine if there is a significant relationship between male and female students perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools in Osun State; and
4. Examine if there is a significant relationship between public and private school students on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools in Osun State.

Research Questions

Two research questions were asked and answered. These are:

1. What are the perceptions on relevance and utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary school students in Osun State?
2. What are the challenges on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary school students in Osun State?

Hypothesis

1. H₀₁. There is no significant relationship between male and female students perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools in Osun State.
2. H₀₂. There is no significant relationship between private and public students perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools in Osun State.

Methodology

This research used a descriptive survey research design, consulting a group of people to gather data from a small number of them deemed representative of the entire group. This approach was deemed appropriate for this study because it uses selected samples drawn from a large population to determine events as they actually occur without the intervention of outside researchers. *The population of the study consisted of all public and private secondary school students in Osogbo local government area of Osun State during the 2020/2021 Academic Session. A sample size of 125 male and 125 female students making a total number of 250 respondents were selected from the targeted population using convenience sampling technique.* One hundred and twenty-five students were equally selected from both public and private secondary schools, respectively.

The instrument employed in this work is a self-designed questionnaire tagged “Students’ Perceptions on Utilization of E-Learning Mode during Covid-19 Outbreak in Osun State (SPUELMCOOS)” with 4 Likert response mode of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) which was used for data collection. The questionnaire was subjected to content and face validity and for the reliability of the instrument, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient was used to test the internal consistency of the questionnaire. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient showed a high level of internal consistency with a value of 0.82. Thus, it showed that the questionnaire used in this study is reliable. In order to collect data for this study, the researchers made use of lockdown ease period (Mondays-Thursdays) in Osun State to embarked on door-to-door administration of the instrument on the senior secondary students in Osogbo local government area. The researchers’ personal involvement at this stage allowed them to get familiar with the respondents. They ensured that the social distancing and other medical advice were strictly observed. The researchers also ensured that the respondents were not coarse, their consent was sought and they responded willingly, thus providing opportunities for clarifications. The data collected was analysed with the use of frequency counts, simple percentages and ANOVA.

Results

Research Question One:

What are the perceptions on relevance and utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary school students in Osun State?

Table 1: Analysis of Responses on Perceptions of Relevance of E-Learning during COVID-19 out-break among Secondary School Students in Osun State

Description of items	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD(%)	Total
E-Learning has been accepted all over the world as a mean of providing distance learning to distance learners.	129(51.6%)	111(44.4%)	10(4%)	-	250(100%)
It carries essential teaching and learning materials which can be accessed by all learners.	163(65.2%)	63(25.2%)	7(2.8%)	17(6.8%)	250(100%)

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It is a flexible mean of transmitting most of the school subjects contents to the learners.	97(38.8%)	103(41.2%)	37(14.8%)	13(5.2%)	250(100%)
Electronics learning can arouse the interest of the learners.	87(34.8%)	133(53.2%)	13(5.2%)	17(6.8%)	250(100%)
Learning through electronics makes it to be real and permanent.	99(39.6%)	123(49.2%)	21(8.4%)	7(2.8%)	250(100%)
E-learning via television is the best tool to deliver instructional contents in a situation where learners and instructors are separated by geographical locations.	143(57.2%)	91(36.4%)	16(6.4%)	-	250(100%)

Source: Authors' Fieldwork, (2020)

Table 1 above presents the findings of the study on the views of students on the relevance of electronics learning in senior secondary schools in Osun State. The finding showed that 129 (51.6%) and 111 (44.4%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that electronics learning has been accepted all over the world as a means of providing distance learning to distance learners, respectively, while 10 (4%) of the respondents disagreed. The finding also revealed that 163 (65.2%) and 63 (25.2%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that electronics learning carries essential teaching and learning materials that can be accessed by all learners, while 7 (2.8%) and 17 (6.8%) of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed. Either electronics learning is a flexible mean of transmitting most of the school subjects' contents to the learners or not, 97 (38.8%) and 103 (41.2%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that electronics learning is a flexible mean of transmitting most of the school subjects' contents to the learners, while 37 (14.8%) and 13 (5.2%) of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed. The findings of the study indicated that 87 (34.8%) and 133 (53.2%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that electronics learning can arouse the interest of the learners, while 13 (5.2%) and 17 (6.8%) of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively.

The study also reveals that 99 (39.6%) and 123 (49.2%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that learning through electronics makes it real and permanent, while 21 (8.4%) and 7 (2.8%) of the respondents disagreed and strongly agreed. The finding finally showed that 143 (57.2%) and 91 (36.4%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that e-learning via television is the best tool to deliver instructional contents in a situation where learners and instructors are separated by geographical locations, while 16 (6.4%) of the respondents disagreed.

Research Question Two:

What are the challenges on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary school students in Osun State?

Table 2: Analysis of Responses on Challenges of E-Learning Utilization during COVID-19 out-break among Secondary School Students in Osun State

Description of items	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD(%)	Total
It hinders learners' contributions and ability to ask questions wherever they are confused.	117(46.8%)	93(37.2%)	29(11.6%)	11(4.4%)	250(100%)
Poor electricity connectivity is a challenge in using electronics learning as a mode of learning.	133(53.2%)	103(41.2%)	9(3.6%)	5(2%)	250(100%)
Electronics learning can create problem for learners with low technical skills.	129(51.6%)	113(45.2%)	7(2.8%)	1(0.4%)	250(100%)
It is not effective in any environment that has poor electricity supply.	149(59.6%)	83(33.2%)	11(4.4%)	7(2.8%)	250(100%)
Improper maintenance can be a shortcoming to the usage of electronics as mode of learning.	113(45.2%)	64(25.6%)	52(20.8%)	21(8.4%)	250(100%)

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Individual differences may not be catered for through television learning.	147(58.8%)	91(36.4%)	12(4.8%)	-	250(100%)
E-Learning presentation may be interrupted by technical faults and power failure.	113(45.2%)	103(41.2%)	21(8.4%)	13(5.2%)	250(100%)
Poor recording of the instructional programmes leads to loss of interest on the part of the learners.	123(49.2%)	111(44.4%)	9(3.6%)	7(2.8%)	250(100%)

Source: Authors' Fieldwork, (2020)

The findings of the study as presented in Table 2 revealed that 117 (46.8%) and 93 (37.2%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that electronics learning hinders learners' contributions and ability to ask questions wherever they are confused, while 29 (11.6%) and 11 (4.4%) of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed. The finding also showed that 133 (53.2%) and 103 (41.2%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that poor electricity connectivity is a challenge in using electronics learning as a mode of learning, while 9 (3.6%) and 5 (2%) of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed. The findings of the study indicated that 129 (51.6%) and 113 (45.2%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that electronics learning can create problems for learners with low technical skills, while 9 (3.6%) and 5 (2%) of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively. The findings of the study showed that 149 (59.6%) and 83 (33.2%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed, respectively, that electronics learning is not effective in any environment that has poor electricity supply, while 11 (4.4%) and 7 (2.8%) of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed. The findings of the study also revealed that 113 (45.2%) and 64 (25.6%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that improper maintenance can be a shortcoming to the usage of electronics as a mode of learning, while 52 (20.8%) and 21 (8.4%) of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed. Moreover, 147 (58.8%) and 91 (36.4%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that individual differences may not be catered for through television learning, while 12 (4.8%) of the respondents disagreed. The finding also showed that 113 (45.2%) and 103 (41.2%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that electronics learning presentations may be interrupted by technical faults and power failure, while 21 (8.4%) and 13 (5.2%) of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed. The findings of the study finally revealed that 123 (49.2%) and 111 (44.4%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that poor recording of the instructional programmes leads to loss of interest on the part of the learners, while 9 (3.6%) and 7 (2.8%) of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively.

H_{0i}:

There is no significant relationship between male and female students perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools in Osun State.

Table 3: The One-Way Anova Analysis on Relationship between Male and Female Students' Perception on Utilization of E-Learning during COVID-19 out-break among Secondary Schools in Osun State.

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between Groups	60.516	1	60.516	441.827	.000
Within Groups	33.968	248	.137		
Total	94.484	249			

Source: Authors' Fieldwork, (2020)

Table 3 above showed that F is 441.827 $p < 0.000$. This implies that there is no sufficient evidence to accept the null hypothesis at the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant relationship between male and female students' perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools was rejected, and the alternate hypothesis, which states that there is a significant relationship between male and female students' perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools in Osun State, was accepted.

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H₀:

There is no significant relationship between private and public students' perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools in Osun State.

Table VI: The One-Way Anova Analysis on Relationship between Public and Private Students' Perception on Utilization of E-Learning COVID-19 out-break among Secondary Schools in Osun State.

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between Groups	46.766	2	23.383	367.069	.000
Within Groups	15.734	247	.064		
Total	62.500	249			

Source: Authors' Fieldwork, (2020)

Table 3 above showed that F is (367.069). This implies that there is no sufficient evidence to accept the null hypothesis at the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant relationship between private and public students' perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools was rejected, and the alternate hypothesis, which states that there is a significant relationship between private and public students perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools, was accepted.

Discussion of Findings

The study was carried out to assess secondary school students' perceptions on utilization of e-learning mode during Covid-19 out-break in Osun State, Nigeria. Two hundred and fifty (250) participants were involved in the study. The first research objective was to assess perceptions on relevance and utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary school students in Osun State. The findings of the study showed that electronics learning has been accepted all over the world as a mean of providing distance learning to distance learners especially during the pandemic period. The possible reason for this may be as a result of the fact that from time immemorial television has been the major audio-visual channel for mass education. This finding is in support of Abidoye and Fakokunde (2015) who explained that e-learning is relevant in the teaching and learning of social studies in secondary schools. The finding also revealed that electronics learning carries essential teaching and learning materials that can be accessed by all learners. This finding agreed with the study of Larson (2018) who found that majority of the users of OPAC were satisfied with the benefits derived from using Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC). The finding of the study indicates that electronics learning can arouse the interest of the learners. This finding corroborates with the findings of Odewumi and Ajala (2017) who claimed that learning through mobile digital devices could be interesting and create easy communication between students and teachers. The finding equally showed that e-learning via television is the best tool to deliver instructional contents in a situation where learners and instructors are separated by geographical locations.

The second research objective was to assess challenges on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary school students in Osun State. The results of the findings revealed that electronic learning hinders learners' contributions and ability to ask questions wherever they are confused. The finding also showed that poor electricity connectivity is a challenge in using electronics learning as a mode of learning. The finding is in consonance with the study of Aboderin (2015), and Aboyade, Madu, and Ajayi (2023). The findings of the study indicated that electronic learning can create problems for learners with low technical skills. The findings of the study showed that electronics learning is not effective in any environment that has a poor electricity supply. The findings of the study also revealed that improper maintenance can be a shortcoming in the use of electronics as a mode of learning. The finding also showed that electronics learning presentations may be interrupted by technical faults and power failures. This finding also agreed with the findings of Afolabi and Abidoye (2016) whose study identified poor power supply, inadequate ICT knowledge, poor internet connections and poor funding as hindrances to using e - learning tools in learning environment in Nigerian Universities.

The third research objective was also to examine if there is a significant relationship between male and female students' perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools in Osun State. Data collected on research hypothesis I, which states that there is no significant relationship between male and female

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students' perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools. The result of the study revealed that there is a significant relationship between male and female students' perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis was accepted.

The fourth research question was to examine if there is a significant relationship between public and private school students on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools in Osun State. Data collected on research hypothesis II, which states that there is no significant relationship between private and public students' perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools. The finding showed that there is no sufficient evidence to accept the null hypothesis at the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant relationship between private and public students' perception on utilization of E-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools was rejected, and the alternate hypothesis, which states that there is a significant relationship between private and public students' perception on utilization of e-learning during COVID-19 out-break among secondary schools, was accepted.

Conclusion

Based on the study's findings, secondary school students value electronics in general, with television being one of the main audiovisual channels for mass education. *The finding also showed that e-learning hinders learners' contributions and ability to ask questions wherever they are confused. The results of the study equally indicated that there is a significant relationship between male and female secondary school students' perceptions on the use of e-learning mode.* The study's conclusion was that secondary school students had similar perceptions on utilization of e-learning during the Covid-19 outbreak in Osun State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the conclusion of the study:

1. To guarantee the smooth integration of electronics in education, students should be given access to sufficient resources and training to address the obstacles they may encounter.
2. The study encourages inclusivity and engagement and puts into practice strategies that take into account the divergent perspectives of male and female students regarding e-learning.
3. The study recommended that the Nigerian government should not relent in its effort by providing necessary support to overcome challenges faced by e-learning among secondary school students.
4. Students' experiences with online and electronic learning should be evaluated on a regular basis, and adjustments made as needed based on their feedback.
5. To create an environment that is favourable for learning for students, teachers should be provided with the necessary assistance and training they need to successfully integrate electronics into their lesson plans.

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Assessment of Pre-Retirement Anxiety on Job Performance among Academic Staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper assessed pre - retirement anxiety on job performance among academic staff in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. Three (3) objectives and research questions each guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted in this study. The population of this study consists of all academic staff in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. A sample size of two hundred and fourteen (214) academic staff was selected at random from a total of four hundred and eighty (480) respondents using multi-stage sampling technique. Academic staff questionnaire (ACSQ) was used as instrument for data collection in this study. Instrument was vetted and reliability co-efficient of 0.89 was obtained. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, mean and standard deviation respectively was used for data analysis. The findings of this study revealed that pre - retirement anxiety has strong effect on job performance of academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. Also, the causes of anxiety prior to retirement of academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria are many only that fear of regular income as wages or allowances as well as inability to adjust to new social status in the society are evidently topping the list. The study recommended that staff due for retirement should be well guided and supported to accept their destiny in good fate but not as something that would make them to lack focus and thus produced poor results in what they are teaching. Finally, the government should strengthen and supervise the activities of various Pension Fund Administrators (PFAs) in the Country to allay the fear of staff that their remittances while still working will continue to come regularly even in retirement.

Keywords: Academic Staff (teachers), Effects, Job Performance, Pre - Retirement.

Introduction

Human existence is full of mystery of one form or the other. In essence, there exist a time for the unemployed to scout for work, resumed and later on, leave the system on accounts of retirement, death or dismissal. In all these, one of the phases of life that is most honourable is retirement, which could be voluntary, coerced or early in nature. Judging from this, retirement is considered an inevitable reality in every organized profession be it public service or private sector. Although, most transitions in life are foreseeable and thus, allowed for a period of preparation to be set in motion, for those not anticipated, it comes with little or no forward planning by those concerned. Regardless of the preceding factors, transitional periods are often accompanied by a re-evaluation of one's life, including a shift in self - identity and re - direction of energies for the time in order not to come as a shock (Chow, 2001). For whatsoever, there is the issue of pre - retirement anxiety on the part of many including academic staff of tertiary institutions in the Country.

The inability of workers to perceive retirement positively and make adequate plans for it does provoke anxiety. So also, the absence of meeting the estimated or calculated target plans that are usually set in place before retirement also trigger such an anxiety. Many at times, the deteriorating condition of employee been retired is

Assessment of Pre-Retirement Anxiety ... (Uyagu, et. al., 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13623836>

presumed to be one of the factors that cause pre - retirement anxiety (Ukaegbu, 2023). However, this may change depending on many other factors such as individual differences, entitlement by the organization and environment factors. In developed countries retirement is usually guided, controlled and maintained at the right time such that workers may pass through it successfully unlike what is observed in developing countries like Nigeria (Ogunyemi and Oderinde, 2018). The predicaments of retirees in Nigeria has not only demoralized the psyche of workers still in service, but has also affected how they performed their work prior to the time of retirement. Invariably, the anxiety associated with occupational losses describes an individual's concern about life after work. Hence the worry relating to retirement incorporates pre-retirement anxiety of one sort or another. It is worrisome to note that most workers as observed have no plans at all for retirement and by the time they realize it. It is already too late hence the need to undertake a study of this nature.

Job performance by teachers is highly inevitable in any educational institution. It could however be determined by the extent of how motivated they are. In other words, staff motivation and performance are fundamental variables notwithstanding as it affects or otherwise of an educational institution. Academic staff job performance refers to how your workers behave in the work place and how well they do the job assigned to them (Ashley in Udu, Ogbaga and Ibenwo, 2022). He also posits that performance includes work effectiveness, quality and efficiency at work. It is a standard for employee behaviour at work. In this context, academic staff are rated on how well they do their jobs compared with a set of standards determined by the employer (Maria, 2017). This is most adjudged via annual performance evaluation and review (APER) form expected to be filled by teaching and non-teaching staff alike. Few of the components of performance include punctuality, quality of work done and employee commitment.

According to numerous researches, working in any type of educational institution is the most demanding occupation when compared to other careers. This is especially with poor working conditions in schools which has necessitated a high level of physical, intellectual, and emotional imbalance for the teachers involved. However, there are a variety of emotional and knowledgeable indicators of task anxiety that could bother teachers individually, negatively impacting their ability to teach the youngsters (Asaloei, Wolomasi and Werang, 2020). As academics, they are saddled to teach, research, and carry out other academic services in the colleges. Their roles of course as academic staff in the development of higher institutions cannot be underestimated because they are the implementers of instruction in these educational institutions (Ogunode, Jegede and Abubakar, 2020). The job performed however is critical to the realization of teacher education objectives. To buttress further on this point, academic staff job performance connotes assigned responsibilities and functions given to actualize the aims and objectives of the institutions and the decree of its execution or accomplishment. Job performance is therefore the result of individual or group work that shows the level of achievement of job qualifications in organizations that aim to meet organizational goals (Al- Omari and Okasheh, 2017).

Retirement marks a major life change for many people. This is because income, status, responsibilities, activities and social relationship associated with the work environment suddenly change due to what may be referred to as pre-retirement anxiety of the would-be-retired officer (Adisa, 2003). It is important to note that retirement is different for everyone depending on the type and reason for disengagement. According to Musa (2004), retirement to many, is the end of a happy life. Other sees it as the end of being useful in any way. The announcement of retirement grips many with agony and pain. Musa stated further that, some see retirement as a curse rather than a blessing because it is like the curtain of useful life has been drawn to a close. But in actual sense, Abdullah (2004) observed that a retiree is supposed to be happy, rejoicing and thanking God for the long life he has enjoyed as an active participant in national development and he still has time to enjoy the third phase of life which is the retirement period.

Pre-retirement on the other hand, is the period right before retirement when an employee's duties and possibilities are diminishing (Szinovacs in Wilcox and Dimkpa, 2023). Pre - retirement anxiety is an antecedent disturbance that often sets in a year or two before one actually leaves the job; it further involves anxieties and worries about the individual's future as a result of the termination of active working life (Nefer, 2015). In support of this, Wilcox and Dimkpa (2023) stated that recent statistical evidence supports the fact that pre-retirement anxiety has become a huge problem in Nigeria. For example, it was found that (68.1%) of retiring civil servants in Edo State of Nigeria experienced high retirement anxiety (Oghogho and Nwankwo, 2022). Judging from the current economic crisis in the Country, it is becoming increasingly difficult for the average Nigerian worker, particularly the future retiree, to make ends meet, because most of them still have families and wards who are primarily dependent on them. Similarly, Young and Zhou (2017) were of the view that the anxiety envisaged by civil servants prior to their retirement

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may be associated with their unpreparedness, coupled with the adverse psychological and socio - economic dispositions that plaque civil servants as a result of functional discrimination in their finances and source of livelihood; and decline in their social status. Other researchers have also identified certain difficulties faced by retirees as a pointer to investigating this study, which includes financial challenges, loneliness, lack of comfortable accommodation, high blood pressure, loss of self-esteem, lower status, among others (Hansson, Buratti, Johansson and Berg, 2019).

Every worker has his/her stipulated time to retire from a formal employment, either by reason of age or length of service in a normal circumstance. Retirement can come as a result of unforeseen vicissitudes of life in the form of involuntary retirement which can arise from a myriad of reasons such as ill-health, disciplinary action, change in the organizational policy of the institution concerned, or redundancy occasioned by economic down turn in the fortune of the organization, amongst many other reasons (Dansan, 2002). Scholars have identified the causes and sources of pre - retirement anxiety to be associated with poor health, old age, financial insecurity, loss of job roles, dissatisfaction and loss of social support and self - esteem among others, as the factors accompanying retirement transition. Moreover, the challenges of retirees range from inadequate income, delay in the payment of retirement entitlements, poor health medication, lack of personal accommodation, inadequate investment and poor savings, difficulties in getting post - retirement vocational substitute, society's negative perception to retirees and reduced social networking (Olatomide in Baba, Garba and Zakariyah, 2015).

Anxiety is one of the most emotional responses that a person can experience. It is a condition in which a person is concerned about the likelihood of a negative occurrence occurring. This sensation might range in intensity from mild to severe terror (Molin, et al 2021, p.234). Physiological signs associated with anxiety include elevated blood pressure, muscle tension, excessive thirst, and perspiration of the hands and feet. This sort of anxiety, which is typically triggered by risky situations, produces an emotion that is unique to each person and is only temporary linked to a specific situation. An expression of anxiety may take many forms, including violence, self - harm, and more commonly, physical and verbal aggression. Anxiety has always been recognized as a natural emotion of human being, however, inappropriate expression of anger has negative consequences such as destructive effects on the living quality of the family, interpersonal behavior and mental states of the individuals. Experiencing anxiety is strongly influenced by learning and will very fast shift from one teacher to another. In fact, students whose teachers most of the time remain angry would get irritated easily.

Teachers may transfer aggression to students when they have anxiety in them as regards such all important issue as retirement (Ahmetovic, Becirovic and Dubravac, 2020; Kyriacou and Sutcliffe, 2008). Added to that, anxiety is as a response to negative effect such as anger or depression usually accompanied by potentially pathogenic, physiological and biochemical changes resulting from the aspects of the teacher's job and mediated by the perception that the demands made upon the teacher constituted a threat to his or her self-esteem or well-being and by coping mechanisms activated to reduce the perceived threat (Mufford et al., 2021). Teachers normally get late at school or dodge when they have anxiety. This is in line with Kyriacou (2011) who asserts that teachers who have experienced anxiety, usually dodges classes, have anxiety related diseases, develop fatigue and depression, making them to dodge classes, have less time to handle both curriculum and co-curriculum activities.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to assess pre - retirement anxiety on job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria follows:

1. Assess the effects of pre - retirement anxiety on job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria.
2. Examine the causes of pre - retirement anxiety on job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria.
3. Investigate if there is relationship between pre - retirement anxiety and job performance among academic staff in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions was raised to guide this study.

1. What are the effects of pre - retirement anxiety on job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria?

Assessment of Pre-Retirement Anxiety ... (Uyagu, et. al., 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13623836>

2. What are the causes of pre - retirement anxiety on Job Performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria?
3. Is there any relationship between pre - retirement anxiety and job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria?

Methodology

The design adopted for this study was descriptive survey research and with all academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria as its population. There are four hundred and eighty (480) male and female academic staff of these colleges spread across twelve (12) institutions. A sample size of two hundred and fourteen (214) academic staff was selected at random using multi-stage sampling technique. Academic staff questionnaire (ACSQ) was used as instrument for data collection in this study. The use of research assistants was appointed, trained and employed in the distribution and retrieval of questionnaire from the respondents (academic staff). Pilot study was conducted in Federal College of Education, Zaria with the administration of twenty (20) copies of questionnaire to the affected staff. Instrument was vetted and subjected to test - retest reliability method with reliability co-efficient of 0.89 was obtained. Permission was sought using a letter of introduction to all concerned institutions to get their staff on board this investigation. Data analysis was carried out using descriptive statistics on the three (3) formulated research questions for this study.

Results

Research Question 1:

What are the effects of pre - retirement anxiety on job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria?

Table 1: Respondents opinion on the effects of pre - retirement anxiety on job performance among academic staff in Federal Colleges of Nigeria

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	SD
1	Lateness to work.	47	25	66	76	2.200	1.147
2	Shoddy execution of work assigned to do.	72	39	73	30	2.715	1.078
3	Lack of focus and therefore poor results.	87	26	64	37	2.761	1.160
4	Excessive thinking which may lead to health issues.	102	36	45	31	2.676	1.127
5	Planning to work more hours to get more money, reduction in social life style and inability to meet up with time.	67	50	52	45	2.649	1.131
Cumulative Mean						2.600	

Source: Fieldwork (2024)

Decision Mean = 2.500

In table 1 above, it became evident that pre - retirement anxiety has a strong effect on job performance of academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. This is because their overall mean agreement level of 2.600 is above the 2.500 decision mean. Specifically, most of the respondents asserted that with pre - retirement anxiety there is lack of focus and therefore poor results by academic staff. The view expressed here attracted the highest mean of 2.761 as a total of 87 respondents indicated strongly agreed, 26 others agreed as against 64 that disagreed and the rest of 37 strongly disagreed. Also, the effects of pre - retirement anxiety on job performance of academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria is shoddy execution of work assigned to do. This view attracted the second highest mean of 2.715 as a total of 72 indicated strongly agreed, 39 as agreed as against 73 that disagreed and the rest of 30 strongly disagreed.

Research Question 2:

What are the causes of pre - retirement anxiety on job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria?

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Table 2: Respondents’ opinion on causes of pre - retirement anxiety on Job Performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	SD
1	Fear of regular income as wages or allowances.	109	27	56	22	3.042	1.088
2	Movement restricted to the house, places of worship and market.	44	22	69	79	2.144	1.131
3	Inability to adjust to new social status in the society.	116	27	50	21	3.121	1.075
4	Failure to invest their meagre salaries on children, accommodation and other essential things.	57	28	81	48	2.439	
5	Extravagant life style and high social status above their contemporaries in the society.	69	49	59	37	2.700	1.098
Cumulative Mean						2.689	

Source: Fieldwork (2024)

Decision Mean = 2.500

Information from table 2 revealed that the causes of pre - retirement anxiety as it affects job performance of academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria are varied. This was evident as their cumulative mean agreement level of 2.689 is higher than the 2.50 decision mean. Specifically, most of the respondents believed that the main causes of anxiety in pre - retirement of academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria is fear of regular income as wages or allowances. This view attracted the highest mean response of 3.042 as a total of 109 indicated strongly agreed, while 27 agreed as against 56 that disagreed and the rest of 22 strongly disagreed with this view. Also, respondents expressed opinion of their inability to adjust to new social status in the society, is a cause of their anxiety. This viewpoint had the second highest mean of 3.121 as a total of 116 strongly agreed while 22 agreed as against 50 that disagreed and the rest of 21 who strongly disagreed.

Research Question 3:

Is there any relationship between pre - retirement anxiety and job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria?

Table 3: Respondents’ opinion on relationship between pre - retirement anxiety and job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	SD
1	Cordial relations exist between the duo concepts.	70	47	52	45	2.663	1.141
2	Level of anxiety in academic staff determines the efforts they put into the work.	86	34	69	25	2.845	1.083
3	Anxiety can set into the life of any academic staff at anytime especially when there is a target attached to a work being done.	47	26	67	74	2.215	1.142
4	Anxiety is everyday affairs as soon as a staff realizes retirement is drawing closer by the day.	72	39	73	30	2.715	1.078
5	Social and economic life which a staff has enjoyed or still enjoying can be the source of anxiety which affects the job performance leading to his/her retirement.	104	23	54	33	2.925	1.164
Cumulative Mean						2.672	

Source: Fieldwork (2024)

Decision Mean = 2.500

There is strong relationship between anxiety in pre - retirement and job performance of academic staff in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. Their cumulative mean response of 2.672 is above the 2.500 decision mean. Specifically, Majority of the study respondents opined that the social and economic life which a staff enjoyed or still enjoying can be the source of anxiety which affects the job performance leading to his/her retirement. This viewpoint attracted the highest mean response agreement of 2.925 as a total of 104 strongly agreed while 23 agreed as against 54 that disagreed and the rest of 33 in favour of strongly disagreed. Also, majority of the respondents agreed to the fact that anxiety can set into the life of any academic staff at anytime especially when there is a target attached to a work being done. The opinion expressed here attracted the second highest mean of 2.845 with a total of 86 strongly agreed, 34 agreed as against 69 that disagreed and the rest of 25 who strongly disagreed.

Discussions of Findings

This study assessed pre - retirement anxiety on job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. Three (3) research questions were formulated to guide the study which has been subjected to descriptive statistics. Research question one tested the effects of pre - retirement anxiety on job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. The outcome of responses from the respondents indicated that pre - retirement anxiety has a strong effect on job performance of academic staff of these Colleges. This was confirmed by Adisa (2003) who stated that income, status, responsibilities, activities and social relationship associated with the work environment suddenly change due to what may be referred to as pre-retirement anxiety of the would-be retired officer.

Research question two tested the causes of pre - retirement anxiety on job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. Diverse causes of pre - retirement anxiety was identified in this work. However, the major cause of anxiety prior to retirement is the issue of absence of regular income and reduction in social status among others which may begin to have untold effect on job performance of academic staff of these Colleges. In support of this, Kyriacou (2011) asserted that teachers who have experienced anxiety, usually dodges classes, have anxiety related diseases, develop fatigue and depression, making them to dodge classes, have less time to handle both curriculum and co-curriculum activities. Research question three assessed the relationship between pre - retirement anxiety and job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. It became evident that strong relationship exists between the duo variables. Anxiety is a strong factor that can affect result of work done in an educational institutions in a positive or negative form. In the case of this study, the main interest is on the negative angle to job performance.

Conclusion

In conclusion, pre - retirement anxiety has negative influence on job performance among academic staff of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. There are many causes to this especially with the luxury life lived by academic staff while in service without any tangible preparation for life in retirement. They often get regular income and other allowances and so, they do not foresee retirement coming their ways. Only a little of this number prepared for life in retirement while majority maybe looking older in age and possibly running helter-scamter in need of cash to run their homes.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made for this study.

1. Staff due for retirement should be well guided and supported to accept their destiny in good fate but not as something that would make them to lack focus and thus produced poor results in what they are teaching.
2. The government should strengthen and supervise the activities of various Pension Fund Administrators (PFAs) in the Country to allay the fear of staff that their remittances while still working will continue to come regularly even in retirement.
3. There should be well structured social life and other economic activities which retirees would enjoyed after leaving the service so as to feel belong and to cater for their needs in retirement.

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Assessment of Psychometric Properties of Teacher-made Mathematics Test for Continuous Assessment in Senior Secondary Schools in Nasarawa State

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Abstract

This article assessed the psychometric properties of teacher-made mathematics tests for continuous assessment in senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State. The study adopted descriptive survey research design, two research questions and two corresponding null hypotheses were tested. The study employed simple random sampling to select 396 students (male:198 & female: 198) in SS II as respondents across the three senatorial zones of Nasarawa State during the 2023/2024 academic session. Teachers-made Mathematics Test (TMT) consisted of 30 items constructed by secondary school teachers in various schools in Nasarawa State was used for data collection. The consensus validity rates of three experts on TMT yielded logical index of 0.76. The instrument was trial-tested using three Secondary Schools, from each of the three senatorial zones of Nasarawa State. The split-halve method of calculating reliability was used to calculate the coefficient of internal consistency which gave 0.75. The result shows that the teacher-made mathematics test used for continuous assessment in mathematics for both male and female are moderately difficult, and there is no significant difference in the difficulty indices of teacher-made mathematics test used for continuous assessment as segregated by gender in Nasarawa State. It was recommended that problematic items such as items with ambiguous wording and wrongly keyed should be reviewed to improve the quality of the tests for both male and female students and IRT analysis should be employed by teachers to improve on the poor item analysis of teacher-made mathematics test used for continuous assessment as dichotomized by school locations in Nasarawa State.

Keywords: assessment, psychometric, properties, mathematics, teacher-made test.

Introduction

Education is one of the essential indices of development to any nation. The challenges faced as a result of fast changing and dynamic world necessitates the need to always access the educational process in to achieve quality of educational assessment. Assessment is the best basis for making inferences about the learning progress of students. It is used for measuring ability, achievement, interest and other traits. It could be a set of questions, tasks or problems constructed with the intention to measure the level of an individual's knowledge, skill, aptitude, intelligence, etc. Assessment should be considered as a measuring instrument (Anikweze, 2013). It covers all experiences both within and outside in the cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains of learning.

In section 1 of the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013), which deals with the philosophy and goals of education in Nigeria, paragraph 9(g) states that “educational assessment and evaluation shall be liberalized by their being based in whole or in part on continuous assessment of the progress of the individual” (p.9). This statement is well amplified in subsequent sections of the document dealing with Primary Education (Section 4), Secondary Education (Section 5), Tertiary Education - (Section 5) and finally in Section 12 which deals with the Planning, Administration and Supervision of Education.

Psychometric properties of tests are the quantifiable aspects of tests that indicate their statistical strengths and weaknesses. Psychometric properties are the intrinsic components of tests that reveal information about the relevance, adequacy and usefulness of tests.

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Omole (2012) defined psychometric properties of a test as certain in characteristics inherent in the test upon which an assessment of a candidate is based. These properties include the facility, difficulty and discrimination indices, the power of distracters, validity and reliability indices. Some students hold notions that Mathematics as a science subject is an abstract subject to them. It is a body of knowledge that includes topics of numbers, shapes, formulas and spaces. It is among the compulsory subjects offered in secondary schools and it is one of the core courses required by JAMB for the entry into tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

Comprehensively, continuous assessment focuses on academic skills as well as cognitive and psychomotor domains. A child is assessed as a total entity using all psychometric devices like test and non-test techniques. Continuous assessment has cumulative characteristics because it gathers all the information on the individual together before a decision can be taken. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004) defines continuous assessment as:

A mechanism whereby the final grading of a student in cognitive affective and psychomotor domains of behavior takes account in a systematic way, of all his performances during a given period of schooling such an assignment involves the use of great variety of modes of evaluation for the purpose of guiding and improving learning and performance of students (P.57).

Teacher-Made Test is an alternative to a standardized test, constructed and administered by the teacher in order to measure students' comprehension of the contents being taught. It enables students to demonstrate what they know and are capable of doing. Teacher-made tests are mostly used for the purpose of formative evaluation in secondary schools.

Obinne, (2011) studied on the psychometric analysis of two major examinations in Nigeria: standard error of measurement (SEM). The study centres on the psychometric analysis of two major examinations conducted in Nigeria by NECO and WAEC. The objective of the study was to compare the SEM of Biology examinations conducted from 2000–2002 using the one-parameter model of Item Response Theory (IRT). That SEM is commonly used to produce confidence interval and it is an estimate of how much error there is in a test. Instrumentation research design was used for the study. The population for the study comprised all year three (SSIII) senior secondary school students who enrolled for May/June/July 2006 Biology SSSCE of NECO and WAEC in the three education zones of Benue State. The sample for the study was one thousand eight hundred (1800) students. Multi-stage stratified sampling technique was used to arrive at the sample. NECO and WAEC 2000–2002 objective Biology questions were the instruments for the study. The maximum likelihood estimation techniques of the BILOG MG Computer Program and the SPSS were used for data analysis. The results showed significant differences in the SEM of Biology examinations conducted by NECO and WAEC in 2000, 2001 and 2002. This implied that Biology examinations conducted by NECO had smaller SEM (high reliability) than those of WAEC. It was recommended that IRT analysis should be employed by Nigerian examination bodies.

Kolawole & Ala; (2013) examined the predictive validity of continuous assessment score of students' performances in mathematics in some selected states in the South-West Nigeria. Continuous Assessment Scores (CA) were compared with the performance of students who sat for the Senior School Certificate Examination conducted by National Examinations Council (NECO) using June/July 2010 Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE) as case study. Scores which were obtained from NECO had been transformed and trial-tested for psychometric properties. Six research questions were generated giving rise to six hypotheses which were tested at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance. The data used were analysed using descriptive statistics of means, standard deviation and inferential statistics of regression analysis. It was found that there was a positive but significant influence of Actual Aggregate Continuous Assessment (AACA) and Examination Scores on the Final Score. And also, there was a positive and significant influence of Moderated Aggregate Continuous Assessment Scores (MACA) and Examination Scores on Final Scores. They also found that AACA and Examinations Scores combined had the ability to predict the Final Grade as well as the combination of both MACA and Examination Scores. AACA and Examination score had positive and significant effect on. Final Scores as well as on MACA and Examination Scores. They however found that AACA and Examination Score had negative effect on Final Grade as well as MACA and Examination Scores combined.

Kiragu & Luke (2014), investigated the validity and reliability of teacher-made tests: through a case study of year 11 physics students in Nyahururu District of Kenya. The study was carried out to establish the factors influencing the validity and reliability of teacher made tests in Kenya. It was conducted in Nyahururu District of Laikipia County in Kenya. The study involved 42 teachers and 15 key informants selected from teachers holding various positions of academic responsibilities in their schools in Nyahururu District. A mixed descriptive survey research design was

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applied. Data was collected through questionnaires and interviews with key informants. Quantitative data analysis was applied to survey data collected via questionnaires. The frequency distribution was described while data from interviews were qualitatively analyzed. The findings of the study revealed that the experience of teachers, training on test construction and analysis, level of education, use of Bloom's taxonomy, moderation of tests and length of tests have an effect on validity and reliability of the tests. It was concluded that teacher-made tests are generally valid and reliable.

Oribhabor & Emafo (2016) Determining the Reliability and Content Validity of the Mathematics Tests Constructed by Senior Secondary School Mathematics Teachers in Edo State. The study assessed the quality of tests constructed by Mathematics teachers in Egor Local Government Area, Edo State. Samples of mathematics tests constructed by Senior Secondary School Two (SS2) Mathematics teachers in Egor Local Government Area of Edo State, Nigeria were used. The purpose of the study was to ascertain whether the tests are sufficiently valid and reliable to make decisions about students' learning. The research design employed for the study was a survey design in which the Mathematics tests constructed by Mathematics teachers in Egor Local Government Area were collected and analyzed. The population for this study included all the Senior Secondary Schools Two (SS2) Mathematics teachers in Egor Local Government Area, Edo State. The population of the study also includes all the Senior Secondary Schools Two (SS2) students in Egor Local Government Area, Edo State. The sample for the study has thirty-six (36) senior secondary two (SS2) Mathematics teachers who were randomly selected from the private senior secondary schools in Egor Local Government Area, Edo State. Thirty-six (36) Mathematics teachers were randomly selected from 102 private senior secondary schools in Egor Local Government Area of Edo State. The instruments used for the collection of data for the study were copies of multiple-choice Mathematics achievement tests constructed by Mathematics teachers in Egor Local Government Area of Edo State and their students' marked answer scripts at the end of 2012/2013 academic session. Cronbach coefficient alpha was calculated for the results of all the tests which were accompanied with students' marked answer scripts. The content validity was established through expert agreement determined through Kendall Coefficient of concordance. Two Mathematics specialists and the researcher labeled - rater 1, rater 2 and rater 3, rated the content-related validity evidence of the tests using a 10-point scale. A rating of 1 indicates very low content validity and a rating of 10 indicates very high content-related validity. The results obtained indicate that the tests have moderate internal consistency reliability and low in content validity.

Mathematics is a discipline, which has been in existence for long time, and it arose from the needs of the people. The federal government of Nigeria has serious concern for the low standard of Mathematics education in the nation's schools, likewise the Nasarawa state government. Parents and teachers likewise are worried about the Mathematics results obtained by students in the school certificate examinations. The use of poorly designed teacher-made Mathematics test could be a major problem as it affects students' interest and achievement in Mathematics in their final examinations which may be WAEC, NECO and/or NABTEB examinations. For this reason, there is need to carry out a study with a view to determining the authenticity of teacher-made test for continuous assessment in Senior Secondary Schools. The thrust of this study is to assess the psychometric properties; difficulty, discrimination and distracter analysis of a teacher-made mathematics tests used for continuous assessment in Nasarawa State.

Objectives of the Study

1. Compare difficulty indices of items in teacher-made mathematics tests for continuous assessment when segregated by gender.
2. Estimate the discrimination coefficient of each of the items in teacher-made mathematics tests used for continuous assessment in the urban and rural schools.

Research Questions

1. How sensitive are the difficulty indices of the items in teacher-made mathematic tests used for continuous assessment when segregated by gender?
2. What are the discrimination coefficients of the items in the teacher-made mathematics tests used for continuous assessment with regard to urban and rural schools?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in difficulty indices of items in teacher-made mathematics tests for continuous assessment when segregated by gender.

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2. There is no significant difference in discrimination coefficient of each items in teacher-made mathematics tests used for continuous assessment in Urban and Rural schools.

Methodology

This study used descriptive survey research design to determine the nature of the psychometric properties of teacher-made tests for continuous assessment in mathematics for SS II in Nasarawa State. The population of this study comprised all the secondary school mathematics students in Nasarawa State. The study used simple random technique to select 396 respondents (male:198 & female: 198) across the three senatorial zones of Nasarawa State. Teachers-made Mathematics Test (TMT) consisted of 30 items constructed by teachers in various schools in Nasarawa State was used for data collection. The validity rate of the appraisal of three experts on TMT yielded logical index of **0.76**. The instrument was trial-tested using three Secondary Schools, from each of the three senatorial zones of Nasarawa State. The split-half method of calculating reliability was used to calculate the coefficient of internal consistency which gave **0.75**.

Results

Research Question 1

How sensitive are the difficulty indices of the items in teacher-made mathematics tests used for continuous assessment when segregated by gender?

Table 1: The Difficulty Indices of Teacher-made Mathematics Test used for Continuous Assessment for Male and Female Students in the senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State

Item	Male	Female	Item	Male	Female	Item	Male	Female
1.	0.56	0.63	11.	0.50	0.51	21.	0.35	0.45
2.	0.61	0.66	12.	0.50	0.49	22.	0.46	0.46
3.	0.61	0.65	13.	0.47	0.63	23.	0.39	0.43
4.	0.55	0.62	14.	0.47	0.55	24.	0.42	0.44
5.	0.59	0.65	15.	0.46	0.41	25.	0.42	0.39
6.	0.55	0.59	16.	0.47	0.49	26.	0.42	0.47
7.	0.49	0.53	17.	0.44	0.52	27.	0.42	0.44
8.	0.48	0.59	18.	0.40	0.40	28.	0.43	0.48
9.	0.60	0.58	19.	0.47	0.39	29.	0.45	0.39
10.	0.49	0.54	20.	0.37	0.46	30.	0.53	0.56

Table 1 contains the means of the difficulty indices for the teacher-made mathematics test used for continuous assessment for male and female students was calculated to be 0.48 and 0.51 respectively.

Research Question 2

What are the discrimination coefficients of the items in the teacher-made mathematics tests used for continuous assessment with regard to urban and rural schools?

Table 2: Item Discriminative Tests Data for 27% Upper Students Scores and 27% Lower Students Scores for Teacher-made Mathematics Tests used for Continuous Assessment in the Senior Secondary Schools in Nasarawa State

Item	Urban	Rural	Item	Urban	Rural	Item	Urban	Rural
1.	0.07	0.11	11.	0.11	0.06	21.	0.04	0.02
2.	0.08	0.07	12.	0.04	0.08	22.	0.03	0.08
3.	0.07	0.11	13.	0.11	0.02	23.	0.06	0.04
4.	0.10	0.07	14.	0.05	0.05	24.	0.03	0.10
5.	0.11	0.08	15.	0.08	0.02	25.	0.09	0.04

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6.	0.10	0.06	16.	0.11	0.05	26.	0.10	0.04
7.	0.06	0.13	17.	0.09	0.05	27.	0.02	0.04
8.	0.09	0.09	18.	0.12	0.03	28.	0.12	0.01
9.	0.08	0.08	19.	0.03	0.08	29.	0.04	0.02
10.	0.08	0.11	20.	0.06	0.05	30.	0.08	0.06

Table 2 is 27% Upper Students and 27% Lower Students Discrimination indices for Teacher-made Mathematics Tests used for Continuous Assessment in the urban and rural areas of Nasarawa state.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in difficulty indices of items in teacher-made mathematics tests for continuous assessment when segregated by gender.

Levene's test for equality of variances for male and female secondary school students' difficulty indices indicated equal variances since the sig value of 0.09 was greater than the 0.05. The male students' difficulty index compared to the female students' difficulty index has a t-value of -1.681 with 58 degree of freedom on a 2-tailed test with a mean difference of -0.03433 and a standard error different of 0.02042 with a 95% Confidence Interval of the difference of -0.07522 and 0.00655 for the lower and upper boundaries respectively.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in discrimination coefficient of each items in teacher-made mathematics tests used for continuous assessment in Urban and Rural schools.

Levene's test for equality of variances with regard to urban and rural secondary school students' discrimination coefficient shew equal variances since the sig value of 0.780 was greater than the 0.05. The urban students' discrimination coefficient compared to the rural students' discrimination coefficient has a t-value of -1.327 with 58 degree of freedom on a 2-tailed test with a mean difference of 0.1133 and a standard error different of 0.00854 with a 95% Confidence Interval of the Difference of -0.00576 and 0.02842 for the lower and upper boundaries respectively as depicted in Table 4.

Discussion of Findings

Table 1, analysis of data shew that the teacher-made mathematics test used for continuous assessment in mathematics for both male and female are moderately difficult, since the 30 items for both the male and the female are in the level of moderate which is between 0.20 hand 0.90. Table 2, indicated that the discrimination indices of teacher-made mathematics test used for continuous assessment in the senior secondary schools are poor in terms of discrimination indices and need to be improved upon since all the 30 items were poor items and needed to be rejected or improved. The study is in line with that of Oribhabor and Emafo (2016) that determined the reliability and content validity of the mathematics tests constructed by Senior Secondary School Mathematics Teachers in Edo State. The results obtained indicate that the tests have moderate internal consistency reliability and low in content validity. Ut it disagrees with that of Kiragu and Luke (2014) that investigated the validity and reliability of teacher-made tests: through a case study of year 11 physics students in Nyahururu District of Kenya, which concluded that teacher-made tests are generally valid and reliable.

Hypothesis 1 in table 3 revealed that the Sig (2-tailed) t-test value of 0.098 greater than 0.05 i.e. (0.098 > 0.05) with equal variances assumed [$t_{(58)} = -1.681, p = 0.098$]. The significant value of 0.098 was greater than the 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis 1 was not rejected. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the difficulty indices of teacher-made mathematics test used for continuous assessment as segregated by gender in Nasarawa State. Hypothesis 2 in table 4 shew that the Sig. (2-tailed) t-test value of 0.780 greater than 0.05 i.e. (0.780 > 0.05) with equal variances assumed [$t_{(58)} = -1.327, p = 0.199$]. The significant value of 0.190 was greater than the 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis 2 was not rejected. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the discrimination coefficient of teacher-made mathematics test used for continuous assessment as dichotomized by location in *Nasarawa State*.

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Conclusion

In view of the findings from this study, the following conclusions were drawn:
The teacher-made mathematics test used for continuous assessment in mathematics for both male and female are moderately difficult. Furthermore, the discrimination indices of teacher-made mathematics test used for continuous assessment in the senior secondary schools are poor in terms of discrimination indices and need to be improved.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made from the findings:

1. Problematic items such as items with ambiguous wording and wrongly keyed should be reviewed to improve the quality of the tests for both male and female students in Nasarawa State.
2. IRT analysis should be employed by rural as well as urban areas teachers to improve on the poor item analysis of teacher-made mathematics test used for continuous assessment as dichotomized by location in *Nasarawa State*.

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Assessment on Use of Zoom Technology for Learning among Undergraduate Students of Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Ondo State

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Abstract

This study investigated the use of Zoom Technology for learning among undergraduate students of Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. Three research questions guided the study. The population of the study consists of all undergraduate students of Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria during the 2023/2024 academic session. A total number of three hundred and sixty (360) male and female students were randomly selected from target population. Undergraduate Students Use of Zoom Technology Questionnaire (USUZTQ) was used to collect data for the study. Data collected were analyzed using simple percentages, mean and standard deviation. The findings of the study revealed that: the level of use of zoom technology for learning among undergraduates in Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State was low; the perceived ease of use of zoom technology among undergraduate students was high. Also there were several challenges faced in using Zoom Technology for learning among undergraduates. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that the use of zoom technology should be encouraged among undergraduate students.

Keywords: Technology, Zoom, Use, Students, Learning, Undergraduate

Introduction

The evolvement of information and communication technology (ICT) into the tertiary education system has rapidly transformed education globally especially in teaching and learning process. In many countries of the world, the use of technology has shifted the learning pattern from traditional methods of instructions to online or e-learning modes especially in teacher education programme. Online instruction has become one of the current techniques in the learning activities of students through the use of internet tools that can be assessable on a computer or laptop, phones and other android devices. Guzacheva (2020) defines online learning as the acquisition of knowledge which takes place through electronic technologies and media. Palmer (2018) also describes online learning as a form of distance education in which a course or programmes is intentionally designed in advance to be delivered fully electronically. Similarly, Suardi (2020) avers that online instruction is a learning process that utilizes electronic tool for implementing learning process. Abidoeye & Fakokunde (2015) asserted that, online learning has become the largest sector of distance learning in recent years which gives learners the opportunity to learn without their presence in the classroom.

Zoom is one of the different tools of technology used to carry out online learning. Eze & Chinadu (2018) describes zoom as a technology that enables representative real-time remote learning which an interactive audio and video program is based on Cloud technology. Suardi (2020) also refers zoom to an application that is operated via computer and android so that teachers and learners can make the learning process effective and efficient, easy to use anywhere and anytime. According to Lai & Bowa (2019), zoom combines video conferencing, online meetings and in-conference group, chat info is one easy-to-use tool that is ideal for online class, and group work.

The use of zoom technology has become increasingly popular globally for instructional delivery in recent years, and educators are discovering many benefits it offers. One of the most significant benefits of zoom technology

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in education is its ability to make teaching and learning process easier and gives the opportunity to teachers and learners to expand their knowledge better (Palmer 2018). Andriyani & Sari (2020) avers that zoom cloud meetings is a very useful alternative application for virtual meeting to facilitate communication with many people without making direct contact and be able to support learning needs in today's digital era. Adnan (2020) also claims that zoom meeting application is very helpful in communicating remotely; all lecturers' explanations can be conveyed to the learners directly without having to meet physically. Zoom facilitate discussions between lecturers and students and among students with direct communication through video conference which is supported by zoom features such as raise hand and group messages, so that if there are problems in audio, the students are helped with the available chat features. Lai & Bowa (2019) explains that zoom combines video conferencing, online meetings and in-conference group, chat info is one easy-to-use tool that is ideal for online class, and group work. Zoom gives Breakout Rooms, which is not accessible in other video conferencing tools. This component empowers the teacher to separate the members into smaller class groups. This component is useful in delivering lecture and presentations. The teacher can look in on each class to examine the situation of introduction and the discussion among the members.

However, the use of zoom technology especially for instructional purposes is characterized with some notable challenges. Eze & Chinadu (2018) identified the following challenges confronting the use of zoom application, such challenges include lack of good network connection; power outages; lack of technological knowledge; high bundle consumption; and lack of devices for online learning such as smart mobile phones, computers, tablets, desktop, and smart televisions. Julius, et al (2021) also claimed that zoom app has limited capacity to accommodate more participants during the teaching and learning process. Adnan (2020) also averts that zoom is facing many security issues that pose a serious threat to its popularity. He said further that the secret IDs provided to join the meeting can be predicted effortlessly, permitting anybody to enter the meeting. However, the need to examine the extent of use of zoom technology in tertiary institutions especially Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo necessitated this research paper.

Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo is one of the teacher training universities recently created by the federal government of Nigeria located in Ondo in the south western part of the country. It was formally a college of education for years. The use of zoom technology in tertiary institutions globally has been one of the key factors in ensuring effective teaching and learning. With the commencement of zoom technology in different sectors, universities inclusive, one would expect to see a holistic and integrated application and utilization of technologies and other platform of e-learning, of which Zoom technology is an exemplary part, in the provision and utilization of effective teaching and learning in universities. It has been observed that there has been relatively poor utilization of Zoom technology for teaching and learning especially among undergraduate students in Adeyemi Federal University of Education (AFUED) Ondo, Ondo State. Therefore, this study investigates the use of zoom technology for learning among undergraduate students of Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo Ondo state, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The general purpose of this study is to assess the use of zoom technology for learning among undergraduate students of Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study examines:

1. The extent in which undergraduate students use zoom technology for learning in Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State.
2. The level of ease in which undergraduate students experience while using zoom technology for learning in Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State.
3. The challenges in which undergraduate students experience while using technology for learning in Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guide the study;

1. What is the mean response of the respondents on the extent to which undergraduate students use zoom technology for learning in Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State?
2. What is the mean response of the respondents on the level of ease while using zoom technology for learning in Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State?
3. What is the mean response of the respondents on the challenges while using zoom technology for learning in Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State?

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. Three research questions guided the study. The population of the study consists of all undergraduate students of Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria during the 2023/2024 academic session. A total number of three hundred and sixty (360) male and female students were randomly selected from target population. Undergraduate Students Use of Zoom Technology Questionnaire (USUZTQ) was used to collect data for the study. The instrument was divided into four sections A-D. Section A focuses on demographic information of respondents. Section B consisted of ten question items eliciting information on the assessment of level of use of zoom technology for learning by the undergraduate students. Section C focuses on the level of ease of use of zoom technology. While section D consisted of 10 question items sought information on the challenges of using zoom technology for learning. A 4-point Likert Scale response modes: Strongly Agree (SA = 4), Agree (A = 3), Disagree (D = 2) and Strongly Disagree (SD = 1) was used. Face and content validation of the instrument was carried out by an expert in test measurement and evaluation from the Department of Educational Foundation and Counselling Ekiti State University, Ado Ekiti. Cronbach Alpha technique was used to determine the level of reliability of the instrument. The reliability coefficient of 0.73 was obtained and this was considered to be high enough to justify the use of the instrument. Data collected were analyzed using simple percentages, mean and standard deviation.

Results

Research Question 1:

What is the mean response of the respondents on the extent to which undergraduate students use zoom technology for learning in Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State?

Table 1 Level of Use of Zoom Technology by Undergraduates in Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo

Item	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. D
I use zoom in sharing information in educational blogs via cloud meetings	45	41	87	187	1.84	1.05
I use Zoom cloud meetings to facilitate communication with many people	13	14	150	183	1.60	.73
I use zoom to read, view or listen to online academic programmes through my cell-phones and other Internet facilities	44	39	87	190	1.83	1.05
I use zoom to attempt online assignments with instructions and guides from learning platforms	42	57	92	169	1.92	1.04
I can still concentrate on learning through zoom meetings in online learning	259	81	20	0	3.66	.57
I use zoom technology to improve my interaction with others on my academic works	94	76	88	102	2.44	1.15
I use zoom technology to have access to learning anywhere and anytime	8	88	35	229	1.65	.92
I use zoom cloud meeting to share course materials with my classmates easy.	71	71	73	145	2.19	1.16
I use zoom meeting to get feedback on my academic work.	39	85	89	147	2.04	1.04
I use zoom to accomplish my academic tasks easily and quickly	32	95	51	182	1.94	1.06
Weighted Average						2.11

Key; SD = Strongly Disagree, D = Disagree, A = Agree, SA = Strongly Agree

Decision Value; Low = 0.00-2.44, High = 2.45-4.00

Table 1 shows the level of use of Zoom technology for learning among undergraduates in Adeyemi Federal University of Education (AFUED). The table shows that the respondents disagreed to the following items: they use zoom in sharing information in educational blogs via cloud meetings ($x = 1.84$), use Zoom cloud meetings to facilitate communication with many people ($x = 1.60$), use zoom to read, view or listen to online academic programmes through my cell-phones and other Internet facilities ($x = 1.83$), use zoom to attempt online assignments with instructions and guides from learning platforms ($x = 1.92$), use zoom technology to improve their interaction with others on their academic works ($x = 2.44$), use zoom technology to have access to learning anywhere and anytime ($x = 1.65$), use zoom cloud meeting to share course materials with their classmates easy ($x = 2.19$), use zoom meeting to get feedback on their academic work ($x = 2.04$), and use zoom to accomplish their academic tasks easily and quickly ($x = 1.94$). Also, the table shows that the undergraduates strongly agreed that: they are learning through internet simulated tutorials without a physical teacher ($x = 3.66$). Meanwhile, based on the value of the weighted average (2.11 out of

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4.00 maximum value obtainable) which falls, within the decision value for *low*, it can be inferred that the level of use of Zoom Technology for learning among undergraduate students in Adeyemi Federal University of Education (AFUED) is low.

Research Question 2:

What is the mean response of the respondents on the level of ease while using zoom technology for learning in Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State?

Table 2: Perceived Ease of Use of Zoom Technology for Teaching and Learning

Item	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	SD
I do not have confidence to use zoom technologies	45	90	122	103	2.21	0.99
I believe that zoom technologies are too cumbersome for me to use	38	104	151	67	2.31	0.89
I feel interaction with zoom technologies will be very beneficial	132	108	66	54	2.88	1.07
I feel it is easy to use zoom technologies	103	97	96	64	2.66	1.07
I believe I have the necessary skills to use zoom technologies	220	110	30	0	3.44	0.65
It is easy to become skillful, if zoom technology is fully integrated	131	104	104	21	2.96	0.94
The use of zoom for instruction would enable me cover the course contents within the time frame of the college with ease.	190	135	22	13	3.39	0.76
Zoom web application is user friendly to me	109	184	50	17	3.07	0.79
The flexibility of zoom technology would ensure speedy dissemination of information easily.	152	100	70	38	3.02	1.02
Zoom technology makes my academic works easy and faster	117	101	104	38	2.83	1.00
Weighted Average					2.88	

Key; *SD* = Strongly Disagree, *D* = Disagree, *A* = Agree, *SA* = Strongly Agree

Decision Value: *Low* = 0.00-2.44, *High* = 2.45-4.00

Table 2 shows the perceived ease of use of zoom technology for learning among undergraduates in AFUED. The table shows that the undergraduates disagreed that: they do not have confidence to use zoom technologies ($x = 2.21$) and belief that zoom technologies are too cumbersome for me to use ($x = 2.31$). Furthermore, the table also shows that the undergraduates agreed to the following: feel interaction with zoom technologies will be very beneficial ($x = 2.88$), feel it is easy to use zoom technologies ($x = 2.66$), believe they have the necessary skills to use zoom technologies ($x = 3.44$), it is easy to become skillful, if zoom technology is fully integrated ($x = 2.96$), the use of zoom for instruction would enable them cover the course contents within the time frame of the college with ease ($x = 3.39$), Zoom web application is user friendly to them ($x = 3.07$), the flexibility of zoom technology would ensure speedy dissemination of information easily ($x = 3.02$), and Zoom technology makes my academic works easy and faster ($x = 2.83$). Meanwhile, based on the value of the weighted average (2.88 out of 4.00 maximum value obtainable) which falls, within the decision value for *high*, it can be inferred that the perceived ease of use of Zoom Technology for teaching and learning among undergraduates' students in Adeyemi Federal University of Education (AFUED) is high.

Research Question 3:

What is the mean response of the respondents on the challenges while using zoom technology for learning in Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State?

Challenges Undergraduate Faced in Using Zoom Technology for Teaching and Learning

Item	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	SD	Remark
Poor internet services by network providers (available but slow)	127	110	69	54	2.86	1.06	Accepted
High cost of internet facilities	219	89	28	24	3.39	.89	Accepted
Power outages	190	81	47	42	3.16	1.05	Accepted
High cost of internet access (subscription)	183	105	41	31	3.22	.96	Accepted

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Lack of knowledge of how to use mobile zoom app effectively	242	104	14	0	3.63	.56	Accepted
Infrequent internet services (rarely available)	161	99	63	37	3.07	1.02	Accepted
Limited capacity to accommodate more participants during zoom meeting	95	104	151	10	2.79	.87	Accepted
Lack of devices for online learning such as smart phones, computers, tablets and smart TV	156	82	45	77	2.88	1.18	Accepted
High cost of devices for online learning such as smart phone, television and computer system.	176	109	30	45	3.16	1.03	Accepted
Insecurity problem (secret IDs provided to join the meeting can be predicted effortlessly)	134	92	86	48	2.87	1.06	Accepted

Key; *SD* = Strongly Disagree, *D* = Disagree, *A* = Agree, *SA* = Strongly Agree

Decision Value for Remark: *Not Accepted* = 0.00-2.44, *Accepted* = 2.45-4.00

Table 3 shows the challenges faced by the undergraduates while using the zoom technology for learning in AFUED. The table shows that the students agreed to all the items as follows: poor internet services by network providers (available but slow) ($x = 2.86$), high cost of internet facilities ($x = 3.39$), power outages ($x = 3.16$), high cost of internet access (subscription) ($x = 3.22$), lack of knowledge of how to use mobile zoom app effectively ($x = 3.63$), infrequent internet services (rarely available) ($x = 3.07$), limited capacity to accommodate more participants during zoom meeting ($x = 2.79$), lack of devices for online learning such as smart phones, computers, tablets and smart TV ($x = 2.88$), high cost of devices for online learning such as smart phone, television and computer system ($x = 3.16$), and Insecurity problem (secret IDs provided to join the meeting can be predicted effortlessly ($x = 2.87$)). Based on the result from this table and mean score acceptance by the decision rule, it can be concluded that the challenges faced in using Zoom Technology for teaching and learning among undergraduate students in Adeyemi Federal University of Education (AFUED) are: poor internet services by network providers (available but slow), high cost of internet facilities, power outages, high cost of internet access (subscription), lack of knowledge of how to use mobile zoom app effectively, infrequent internet services (rarely available), limited capacity to accommodate more participants during zoom meeting, lack of devices for online learning such as smart phones, computers, tablets and smart TV, high cost of devices for online learning such as smart phone, television and computer system, and Insecurity problem (secret IDs provided to join the meeting can be predicted effortlessly).

Discussion of Results

From the research question one, the results shows that undergraduate students' level of use of zoom technology for learning in AFUED was low. This is evident as almost all the respondents disagreed that they use zoom in sharing information in educational blogs via cloud meetings, use Zoom cloud meetings to facilitate communication with many people, use zoom to read, view or listen to online academic programmes through cell-phones and other Internet facilities, use zoom to attempt online assignments with instructions and guides from learning platforms, use zoom technology to improve their interaction with others on their academic works and use zoom technology to have access to learning anywhere and anytime. This finding is against the claim of Guzacheva (2020) who find out high level of utilization of zoom technology among students and teachers of English language in medical school.

From the research question two, the results show that undergraduate students' perceived ease of use of zoom technology was high. Majority of the students disagreed that they do not have confidence to use zoom technologies and belief that zoom technologies are too cumbersome for them to use. They also agreed that to the following; they feel interaction with zoom technologies will be very beneficial, feel it is easy to use zoom technologies, believe they have the necessary skills to use zoom technologies, it is easy to become skillful, if zoom technology is fully integrated, the use of zoom for instruction would enable them cover the course contents within the time frame of the college with ease, Zoom web application is user friendly to them and Zoom technology makes my academic works easy and faster. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Meladina & Zaswita (2020) who in their investigation find high ease of utilization of web-based learning tools among students in tertiary institutions.

From research question three, the result shows that there were challenges faced by undergraduate students in using zoom technology effectively in AFUED. This is evident as almost all the respondents agreed that they have the

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following challenges; poor internet services by network providers (available but slow), high cost of internet facilities, power outages, high cost of internet access (subscription), lack of knowledge of how to use mobile zoom app effectively, infrequent internet services (rarely available), limited capacity to accommodate more participants during zoom meeting and high cost of devices for online learning such as smart phone, television and computer system. This finding is in line with the findings of Franklin Ohiole & Nancwat Manna (2022) who in their investigation discovered lot of challenges affecting effective use of zoom for instruction in Ambrose Alli university Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria.

Conclusion

This study investigated the use of zoom technology for teaching and learning among undergraduate students of Adeyemi Federal University of Education Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria. The study also examined level and ease of use of zoom technology among undergraduate students for learning. It further examined some challenges hindering undergraduate students from effectively use zoom technology for learning. The findings revealed that the level of use of zoom by the undergraduate students was very low. While the perceived ease of zoom technology among undergraduate students was very high. The study further revealed that there were a lot of challenges confronting undergraduate students from effectively use zoom technology in AFUED.

The study also concluded that use of zoom technology for learning has emerged as a useful source for promoting learning and preparing youths to participate in a global economy. The important point that must be considered is the continuity of the video conference at this zoom depends on the internet network so that lecturers and students must use good and supportive internet access in order to use the zoom application for taking part in learning activities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and the review of relevant literatures, the following recommendations were made:

1. University managements should intensify ICT training for students in order to equip them with the necessary skills and exposures to a range of co-curricular practical tasks on zoom technologies to help students become more encouraged and motivated to use zoom for learning.
2. The Universities should provide adequate, reliable zoom technology learning platform or software and tools to interconnect all students' and lecturers' for zoom technology learning.
3. The University authority should provide enabling environment that is free of challenges confronting undergraduate students from effectively use of zoom technology for learning.

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Awareness and Perception of Sustainable Development Goals on Application of Technology and Innovative Teaching among Primary School Teachers in Ilorin Metropolis

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Abstract

This study examined the awareness and perception of sustainable development goals (SDGs) and their influence on the application of technology and innovative teaching among primary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis. A descriptive survey design was adopted, and a sample of 356 primary school teachers (178 Male, 178 Female) was drawn using stratified random sampling from a population of 4,829 primary school teachers (2,414 Male, 2,415 Female) in Ilorin metropolis during the 2023/2024 academic session. The instrument for data collection was a 32-item Sustainable Development Goals Perception Scale (SDGsPS) adapted by the researcher, and the reliability of the instrument was established using the test-retest technique, yielding a coefficient index of 0.81 using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) reliability test. Mean (\bar{x}) and t-test were used to answer research questions and test hypotheses respectively. The results revealed a moderate level of awareness of SDGs among primary teachers in Ilorin Metropolis. While there was a relatively low extent of technology use for SDGs, primary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis showed a relatively high extent of employing innovative teaching methods for SDGs. Recommendations include the need for adequate provision of funds and other educational resources, and the integration of primary school teachers into the entire process of the SDGs program to achieve the objectives effectively. Additionally, school administrators should support and facilitate teachers' participation in workshops focused on SDGs, technology, and innovative teaching methods, while teacher training institutions should integrate SDGs into teacher training curricula to ensure future educators are well-prepared for sustainable development education.

Keywords: Innovative Teaching Methods, Teachers' Level of Perception, School Type, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Introduction

The history of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) can be traced back to the United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development, also known as Rio+20, held in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil in 2012. The conference aimed to promote sustainable development and integrate economic, social, and environmental objectives. At Rio+20, Member States agreed to develop a set of sustainable development goals that would build on the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) adopted in 2000, which aimed to reduce poverty and improve social development outcomes (UNO 2012).

Specifically, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are a set of 17 global goals consist of 169 target adopted by the United Nations in 2015, aimed at addressing poverty, inequality, and climate change to create a better future for all (UNDP, 2015). The SDGs build on the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and aim to achieve a sustainable and equitable world by 2030. The SDGs address a broad range of issues, including ending poverty and hunger, improving health and education, promoting gender equality, providing access to clean water and sanitation, promoting sustainable economic growth, and reducing inequality. Additionally, the goals cover environmental issues such as climate change, biodiversity, and sustainable consumption and production (UNO, 2021).

The goals are interrelated and interconnected, and achieving them requires the cooperation and participation of governments, civil society, the private sector, and individuals. The goals provide a framework for action, and each goal has specific targets and indicators to measure progress towards achieving them (United Nations, 2021). By implication, it could be said that effective implementation of the program demands enhanced capacity of the populace and inclusivity of diverse sectors of society (Idialu, 2022).

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In the light of the above, it is obvious that education play a critical role in achieving sustainable development goals (SDGs). Education serves as an important means of implementation for sustainable human development due to the number of positive benefits it brings across the development goals. Education is the key to the global integrated framework of sustainable development goals. Education is at the heart of our efforts both to adapt to change and to transform the world within which we live. A quality basic education is the necessary foundation for learning throughout life in a complex and rapidly changing world (UNESCO, 2015). According to the United Nations' Organization (UNO, 2021), education empowers the citizenry to transform the society by re-orienting them to develop the requisite knowledge, skills and attitudes for sustainable development. Through effective teaching and learning, the learners are gradually equipped to face the demands of a more sustainable world.

Similarly, educating for the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) requires revision of education policies and curriculum. This includes revising the National Policy on Education, improving curriculum content, providing sufficient instructional resources, increasing funding, and enhancing capacity building for teachers. Primary school teachers, in particular, have a significant responsibility to contribute to the attainment of the SDGs. The success of any educational program depends heavily on the quality of teachers. Therefore, teachers at all levels are considered the central figures in any educational process. It is imperative that primary school teachers are not only aware of the national and global educational demands but are also equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge to tailor their teaching to these demands.

As stated in the 2013 Federal Ministry of Education (FME) report, the quality of teachers in any educational system greatly affects the quality of teaching and learning in the system. Therefore, it is essential to prioritize the professional development of primary school teachers and ensure they have access to the resources needed to enhance their effectiveness.

Specifically, teacher perceptions according to IRIS Center (2012) are the thoughts or mental images teachers have about their students which are shaped by their background knowledge and life experiences. Teachers' perceptions can be influenced by a variety of factors, including their own experiences, training, beliefs, and values, as well as external factors such as school policies, societal expectations, and cultural norms. However, there are some common perceptions that teachers have on the use of technology and innovative teaching methods. One of the most common perceptions among teachers is that technology can be a valuable tool for teaching and learning. Many teachers recognize the potential of technology to engage students and make learning more interactive and meaningful.

Basically, use of technology for educational purposes yield positive outcomes on the part of the students such as increased motivation, active learning, providing efficient resources and better access to information (Sahin-Kizil, 2011). In the same vein, Wang and Woo (2007) also reviewed that technology has great potential to increase learners' motivation, link learners to various information sources, support collaborative learning, and allow teachers more time for facilitation in classrooms. Thus, when considering the use of technology, it should not simply be employed because it is readily available or because it has demonstrated effectiveness in certain circumstances. Instead, the purpose of utilizing technology should be to facilitate the learning process and enhance educational outcomes. Reflections on the use of technology should therefore concentrate on evaluating the appropriateness of the technology used, as well as identifying its strengths and weaknesses, and determining possible areas for improvement.

In the context of educating and acquiring knowledge, innovation involves deliberate application of information, imaginations and initiatives in deriving greater or different values from resources which often results when new ideas are applied to satisfy the needs and expectations of students (Author, 2013). In other words, innovative teaching methods in the teaching-learning process refer to new methods and means of teaching in an educational sector to achieve set instructional goals and objective (Aja, Eze, Igba & Elom, 2017). Hence, some of the innovative teaching methods as considered in this study are: Individualized instruction, simulation and game, team teaching, language laboratory and power point presentation.

To this end, education as an agent of behavioural change becomes the major driver of achieving these sustainable development goals. This is because education is the training of the mind to become functional member of the society (Animba, 2021). Hence, education provides a better platform for these changes through teacher-learner relationship. Talk is always cheap however application is difficult hence the need for education for solving these sustainable development goals. This is important in order for human resolution to get to the different strata and class for effective and efficient implementation of these goals.

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The above however, calls to mind, the words of Westermann & Venegas (2017), who affirmed that education for sustainable development requires participatory teaching and learning approaches in order to motivate teachers and empower learners to change their behaviour and take action in order for sustainable development to be achieved. In a broader sense, Nsofer and Ahmed (2015) maintained that the teacher must structure a variety of learning styles, interacts, and abilities using computer programme and instructions, computer assisted instructions and numerous types of multimedia resources that deliver text, audio, graphics, animation, narrations, sound and streaming video in order to achieve high with these techniques. Thus, the integration of technologies and innovative teaching methods can help teachers and students to improve and develop the quality of education by providing curricular support in difficult subject areas (Gulbahar and Guven, 2008). In support of this finding, Wheeler (2000) discovers that technology improves efficiency in the educational process and effect changes in teaching methodology, assessment of learning, student tracking, communication and evaluation.

In contrast however, Yusuf (2005) and Olulube (2006) report in their studies that teachers' technology competence in Nigeria is below expectation. This finding corroborates the research finding to Chike-Okoli and Gambabri (2007) who find out that only a negligible number of vocational and technological teachers make use of ICT in teaching, learning and school management.

Consequently, one begins to wonder how well the integration of technologies and innovative teaching methods will help in achieving Sustainable Developmental Goals (SDG 4). In order to achieve the sustainable development goals effectively, it is crucial to understand the perspectives of key stakeholders involved in curriculum implementation and assess the efficient utilization of technology and innovative teaching method towards attaining these goals. Thus, it is essential to assess the perception of SDGs among primary school teachers, particularly regarding technology usage and innovative teaching strategies, to ensure their effective implementation and alignment with sustainable development priorities. This state of the problem aims to shed light on the current situation in Kwara State, Nigeria, regarding primary school teachers' perception of SDGs, technology usage, and innovative teaching approaches.

In order to achieve the sustainable development goals effectively, it is crucial to understand the perspectives of key stakeholders involved in curriculum implementation and assess the efficient management of human and material resources towards attaining these goals.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are a set of global objectives established by the United Nations to address various social, economic, and environmental challenges and promote sustainable development worldwide. Achieving these goals requires active participation from all sectors of society, including the education sector. In Nigeria, particularly in Kwara State, primary school teachers play a crucial role in shaping the future of the country by imparting knowledge and values to young learners.

However, the effective integration of technology usage and innovative teaching methods in primary schools is vital to meet the demands of the 21st-century learning environment and contribute to the attainment of the SDGs. Technology can enhance teaching and learning experiences, promote critical thinking skills, and foster creativity among students. Additionally, innovative teaching approaches can help address the diverse learning needs of students and promote active engagement in the learning process.

Despite the potential benefits, the extent to which primary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis perceive and incorporate the SDGs, technology usage, and innovative teaching methods into their pedagogical practices remains unclear. This lack of understanding and utilization of technology and innovative teaching approaches may hinder the effective implementation of the SDGs in the education system, impeding progress towards sustainable development.

Therefore, it is crucial to investigate the perception of primary school teachers in Kwara State regarding the SDGs, their knowledge and utilization of technology in the classroom, and their adoption of innovative teaching methods. Understanding these factors will provide valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities faced by teachers in integrating technology and innovative approaches to support the achievement of the SDGs. Additionally, exploring the perceptions of teachers can help identify gaps in training and support, inform policy decisions, and guide the development of professional development programs that enhance teachers' capacity to utilize technology and innovative teaching methods effectively. By addressing these gaps in knowledge and practice, this study aims to contribute to the improvement of primary education in Ilorin Metropolis and the overall achievement of the SDGs.

Objectives of the study

The objective of this study is to assess the awareness and perception of sustainable development goals (SDGs) and their influence on the application of technology and innovative teaching among primary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis. Specifically, the study is aimed at finding out the:

1. Extent to which primary school teachers are aware of sustainable development goals concerning the use of technology and innovative teaching methods in Ilorin Metropolis.
2. Extent to which primary school teachers use technology in their teaching for attainment of SDGs in Ilorin Metropolis.
3. Extent to which primary school teachers use innovative methods in their teaching for attainment of SDGs in Ilorin Metropolis.

Research Questions

1. To what extent are primary school teachers aware of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) concerning the use of technology and innovative teaching methods in Ilorin Metropolis?
2. To what extent do primary school teachers use of technology in their teaching for attainment of SDGs in Ilorin Metropolis?
3. To what extent do primary school teachers use of innovative teaching methods for attainment of SDGs in Ilorin Metropolis?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the mean perception of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) between primary school male and female teachers regarding technology usage and innovative teaching methods in Ilorin Metropolis.
2. There is no significant difference in primary school teachers' mean level of perception of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) regarding technology usage and innovative teaching methods by years of teaching experience in Ilorin Metropolis.

Methodology

The research design adopted for the study is survey research design. The reason for adopting this design was to solely obtain information from the respondents about the existing situation in the study area. Population of the study comprised all the 4,226 primary school teachers (2,414 Male, 2,415 Female) in 18 public primary schools in Ilorin Metropolis of Kwara State, Nigeria (Planning, Research and Statistics Department SUBEB, 2022). Primary school teachers only were used for the study because they implement the curriculum at the primary school level and also close to the students at that level. However, the sample for the study comprised 356 respondents (178 Male, 178 Female). Simple random sampling technique precisely by balloting was employed to select 20 teachers each from the 18 public primary schools used for the study.

On the basis of the above sampling techniques, it is hoped that the sample reflected all the characteristics of all the teachers in all the public primary schools in Ilorin Metropolis. Specifically, the sample consisted of primary school teachers both in the urban and rural areas of the study area. The sample also consisted of both male and female primary school teachers and experienced and inexperienced teachers. In addition, the teachers were selected from different subjects' area of specialization in the selected public primary schools in Ilorin Metropolis.

For the study, a questionnaire called the Sustainable Development Goals Perception Scale (SDGsPS) was utilized as the research instrument. The researcher adapted this questionnaire after conducting a thorough review of relevant literature. To ensure its validity, the preliminary version of the questionnaire was reviewed and validated by a panel of experts. The panel consisted of two experienced lecturers and two experts in Test and Measurement from Universities. The observations and suggestions made by experts were used for the final preparation of the instrument.

In computing the reliability of this research instrument, test-retest technique was used to determine the reliability of the instrument using data from the pilot study carried out on 20 participants outside the sample size. A reliability index of 0.72 was established using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient which is high, reliable and adequate for a standardized instrument. However, mean (\bar{x}) and t-test were used to answer research questions and test hypotheses respectively.

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Results

In line with the study's research questions and hypotheses, the findings are outlined below.

Research Question 1:

To what extent are primary school teachers aware of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) concerning the use of technology and innovative teaching methods in Ilorin Metropolis?

Table 1: Extent of Primary School Teachers' Awareness of the Sustainable Development Goals Concerning the Use of Technology and Innovative Teaching Methods

S/No	Items	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	The Sustainable Development Goals is clearly spelt out as regard the use of technology and innovative teaching methods.	2.51	1.02	Agree
2	The teacher had good knowledge of the interpretation of the Sustainable Development Goals.	2.67	1.14	Agree
3	The awareness of the 17 aspirational Sustainable Development Goals is universal among teachers.	2.31	0.62	Disagree
4	The Sustainable Development Goals are designed to be action-oriented before they can be achieved.	2.55	1.10	Disagree
5	Teacher had good understanding of the Sustainable Development Goals content.	2.49	0.71	Agree
Grand Mean		2.51	0.92	Agreed

Source: Author's Computation, 2024

Table 1 illustrates the awareness level of primary teachers regarding the integration of technology and innovative teaching methods aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals. Scores for all categories of primary teachers exceed the cut-off mean of 2.50. Consequently, the grand mean of 2.51 succinctly denotes a moderate level of awareness of Sustainable Development Goals among the primary teachers.

Research Question 2:

To what extent do primary school teachers use of technology in their teaching for attainment of SDGs in Ilorin Metropolis?

Table 2: Extent to which primary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis use of technology for attainment of SDGs

S/No	Items	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	Teachers frequently incorporate technology tools in their daily lesson plans to address Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in the classroom.	2.16	0.42	Disagree
2	I have high proficiency in using educational technology platforms to enhance teaching practices related to SDGs.	2.45	0.54	Disagree
3	Teacher utilizes digital resources, such as online educational materials or applications, to support SDGs in your teaching.	2.33	0.72	Disagree
4	My students are encouraging to use technology tools for independent research or projects related to SDGs.	2.10	0.60	Disagree
5	Teacher adapts and integrate new and emerging technologies into your teaching methods to promote awareness and understanding of SDGs.	2.27	0.58	Disagree
Grand Mean		2.26	0.57	Low Extent

Source: Author's Computation, 2024

Table 2 illustrates the utilization of technology by primary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Scores across all categories of primary teachers fall below the established cut-off mean of 2.50. Accordingly, the grand mean of 2.26 concisely indicates a relatively low extent to which primary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis use technology for the attainment of SDGs.

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Research Question 3:

To what extent do primary school teachers use of innovative teaching methods for attainment of SDGs in Ilorin Metropolis?

Table 3: Extent to which primary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis use of innovative teaching methods for attainment of SDGs

S/No	Items	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	I integrate the use of technology tools and multimedia elements to enhance innovative teaching approaches in relation to SDGs.	2.67	1.02	Agree
2	I incorporate experiential learning activities, such as field trips or hands-on projects, to deepen students' engagement with SDG concepts.	2.55	0.98	Agree
3	Teachers frequently integrate real-world scenarios and case studies related to SDGs into your teaching materials.	2.83	1.22	Agree
4	Teacher to a high extent employs collaborative learning strategies to enhance students' understanding of SDGs and promote teamwork in achieving sustainable outcomes.	2.71	1.10	Agree
5	Teachers frequently incorporate project-based learning methods to address Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in their primary school classroom.	2.73	1.13	Agree
Grand Mean		2.70	1.09	High Extent

Source: Author's Computation, 2024

Table 3 illustrates the implementation of innovative teaching methods by primary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Scores across all categories of primary teachers surpass the established cut-off mean of 2.50. Consequently, the grand mean of 2.70 succinctly indicates a relatively high extent to which primary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis employ innovative teaching methods for the attainment of SDGs.

Research Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant difference in the mean perception of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) between primary school male and female teachers regarding technology usage and innovative teaching methods in Ilorin Metropolis.

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis of the mean level of perception of Sustainable Development Goals among Primary School Teachers on Technology Usage and Innovative Teaching by gender

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-value	Sig	Decision
Male	178	18.3	0.58	351	1.68	0.071	Not Sig.
Female	175	18.1	0.56				

Source: Author's Computation, 2024.

Analysis from table 4 indicates that the computed t-value is 1.68 at a degree of freedom of 351 with a probability value of 0.071. Since the computed probability value (p-value) of 0.071 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the stated null hypothesis is therefore accepted. Meaning that, there is no significant difference in the mean perception of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) between primary school male and female teachers regarding technology usage and innovative teaching methods.

Research Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant difference in primary school teachers' mean level of perception of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) regarding technology usage and innovative teaching methods by years of teaching experience in Ilorin Metropolis.

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Table 5: Summary of t-test analysis of the mean level of perception of Sustainable Development Goals among Primary School Teachers on Technology Usage and Innovative Teaching by years of teaching experience

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-value	Sig	Decision
Experienced Teacher	178	19.1	0.83	351	2.98	0.013	Sig.
Inexperienced Teacher	175	18.4	0.97				

Source: Author's Computation, 2024

Analysis from table 5 indicates that the computed t-value is 2.98 at a degree of freedom of 351 with a probability value of 0.013. Since the computed probability value (p-value) of 0.013 is less than the 0.05 level of significance, the stated null hypothesis is therefore rejected. Meaning that, there is no significant difference in the mean perception of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) among primary school teachers regarding technology usage and innovative teaching methods by years of teaching experience.

Discussion of Findings

The first finding of the study revealed that there is a moderate level of awareness of Sustainable Development Goals among the primary teachers. It might be attributed to insufficient integration of SDG-related content in teacher training programs, limited professional development opportunities focusing on SDGs, or inadequate dissemination of information about SDGs within the educational system. This finding is supported by Agbi (2022) who reported that science lecturers have a mere moderate level of awareness of the SDGs programme, there has not been adequate advocacy by government and its agencies as regards the SDGs programme. Hence, limited awareness of SDGs among Nigerian primary teachers may hinder effective teaching of sustainable development to students, impacting broader societal understanding and commitment to sustainability. Addressing this gap is crucial for successful SDG integration in Kwara state education system.

The study unveiled in its second finding that there is low extent to which primary school teachers use technology for the attainment of SDGs in Ilorin Metropolis. This may result from inadequate access to technology infrastructure and insufficient training on integrating technology into teaching practices. The finding of the study is in agreement with Yusuf (2005) and Olulube (2006) in Akpan (2008) found out that teachers' ICT competence in Nigeria is below expectation. So, most teachers do not recognize the potentials of ICT and as such the impact of ICT in teaching and learning is considered to be limited. This implies that low use of technology in class may hinder effective delivery of SDG-related content to students, impacting their awareness and skills in sustainable development.

The study's third discovery revealed a relatively high extent to which primary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis employ innovative teaching methods for the attainment of SDGs. This finding might be influenced by collaborative initiatives and peer-sharing platforms among teachers for exchange of innovative teaching ideas which contributed to the overall adoption of these methods in the context of SDG implementation. This finding correspond with the work of Knutson (2014) who pointed out that choosing the appropriate approaches in teaching and how these approaches are made is pertinent to students' learning. The implications may result in enhanced student engagement, a more effective understanding of sustainable development concepts, and better preparation of students to contribute meaningfully to SDGs.

In the fourth finding of this study, it was revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean perception of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) between primary school male and female teachers regarding technology usage and innovative teaching methods. This may be credited to a uniform integration of technology and innovative teaching practices in teacher training programs. This finding corroborates with the work of Saltan (2016) who reported difference between ICT selection criteria such as ICT ease of use in terms of gender as an indicator but the difference is statistically insignificant. This suggests a positive outcome in terms of gender equity in the awareness and application of sustainable development principles within the teaching community, fostering a more inclusive and equitable educational environment.

The study's fifth discovery unveiled that there is no significant difference in the mean perception of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) among primary school teachers regarding technology usage and innovative teaching methods by years of teaching experience. The finding may be influenced by the varying exposure and adaptability to evolving teaching methods over time. Teachers with more experience may have undergone different

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professional development opportunities, making them more receptive to incorporating technology and innovative teaching approaches aligned with sustainable development. This finding concurs with assertion of Agbi (2022) who revealed that experienced science lecturers have higher perception of the SDGs programme than their inexperienced counterparts. This finding implies that tailored professional development programs catering to varying levels of teaching experience may be necessary.

Conclusion

In summary, the study reveals a moderate awareness of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) among primary school teachers in Ilorin Metropolis, with challenges in low technology usage but a positive trend in innovative teaching methods. Gender does not significantly affect SDG perceptions, but differences based on teaching experience suggest the need for tailored professional development. These findings emphasize the diverse factors influencing SDG integration, calling for strategic interventions to enhance awareness, technology use, and innovative teaching practices among primary school teachers.

Recommendations

1. Government and Education Authorities should launch targeted awareness campaigns within primary teacher communities to improve Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) understanding, and invest in technology infrastructure and training programs to empower primary teachers in Kwara State for effective SDG integration.
2. Teacher Training Institutions should integrate SDGs into teacher training curricula, ensuring future educators are well-prepared for sustainable development education.
3. Professional Development Providers should customize professional development sessions to cater to the unique needs of primary teachers, emphasizing SDGs, technology usage, and innovative teaching methods.
4. School Administrators should support and facilitate teachers' participation in workshops focused on SDGs, technology, and innovative teaching methods.
5. Teachers should actively engage in SDG, technology, and innovative teaching training opportunities, and form professional communities to share experiences and strategies for successful integration.

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Comparative Relationship between Emotional Stability and Academic Performance among Undergraduate Students in Federal Tertiary Institutions in Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

In the midst of a climate of insecurity, this study x-rays the relationship between academic performance and emotional stability among undergraduate students in federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State, Nigeria. This study was carried out using a correlation research design. The population of the study comprised all undergraduate students of the three federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State. 384 students were purposively sampled from the three schools. Emotional Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ) was adopted and adapted for this study and students' CGPAs were used to measure academic performance. Validity and reliability of ERQ were established showing high internal consistency at 0.81. Findings indicated that there is a positive relationship between emotional stability and academic performance ($r = 0.7035$). In conclusion, emotional stability has positive relationship with academic performance and can a tool or aid intervention at enhancing emotional stability to contribute positively to academic performance, particularly in the context of insecurity while taking into consideration gender differences. The study recommended targeted support systems that recognize and address gender differences can be instrumental in fostering a more resilient student population.

Keywords: Academic Performance, Emotional Stability, Gender

Introduction

Security issues has been a recurring theme in Nigeria in past few years, particularly in the northern part of the country, where various terrorist groups, bandits and kidnappers' actions have created a high security concern (Attahiru & Aliyu, 2020). The relatively peaceful northwest part of Nigeria has suddenly turned into a hot zone, where people are afraid to travel, families reporting deaths, and many villages abandoned. The wave of attacks on institutions of learning, particularly in Northern Nigeria, has affected the administration and delivery of educational goals at all levels. The Government and other stakeholders in the education sector have recently found themselves in a quandary on how to find solutions to incessant killings, kidnappings, abductions, destruction of schools and infrastructure by criminal gangs and bandits (Ifedi & Agu, 2021). Even though the efforts by federal and state governments to curb the high level of insecurity in the country have increased, there are still scattered reports of loss of lives and property to the mindless activities of these criminals.

Zamfara state became popular in the news over the last three years due to the increase in insecurity challenges and actions taken by the government to mitigate the situation (Eyinnaya & Olomjobi, 2022). There were series of reported disruptions to academic activities, after some schools were attacked where students and tutors got kidnapped or killed. For instance, on 26th February 2021 bandits were reported to have abducted over three hundred (300) students of Government Girls Junior Secondary School, Jangebe in Talata-Mafara Local Government Area in Zamfara (BBC, 2021), and in the early hours of 1st September, 2021 seventy students were kidnapped at the Government Secondary School Kaya (Premium Times, 2021). The Zamfara state government gave an order on closure of schools in the state on September 1st, 2021 to assess the situation and take actions to rescue the situation (Premium Times, 2021).

The word insecurity has varieties of inferences, crosscutting and multi-dimensional concept which has been subject to debates (Obi, 2015), but generally it denotes danger, hazard, uncertainty, lack of protection, and lack of safety

(Ndubuisi-Okolo & Anigbuogu, 2019). Obarisiagbon and Akintoye (2019) insecurity generally refers to the absence of resistance to or protection from harm, peaceful co-existence and development at large. Obi (2015) defined insecurity as a chronic threat to human life, territories, states, religious beliefs, properties and institutions, among others. Extent literature (e.g., Ezemenaka, 2021; Otolorin, 2017; Onime, 2018; Oloyede & Ogunfolaji, 2021; Orhero, 2020; Eneji & Agri, 2020) have discussed different dimensions of insecurity ranging from food insecurity, health insecurity, environmental insecurity, economic insecurity, political insecurity, human insecurity to personal and community insecurity as outlined in United Nation Developmental Programme (UNDP) Report. However, this study is only limited to two dimensions identified as critical to students' learning namely community and personal insecurity.

Considering the aforementioned, the rise of Boko Haram in 2009, and recent increasing incidence of kidnapping and banditry in Zamfara since 2019 (Eyinnaya & Olomojobi, 2022). There is a need to examine how these occurrences influence student academic performance and emotional stability. Studies (Payne-Sturges et al. 2018; Chamorro-Premuzic & Furnham, 2003) had indicated a discrepancy in the relationship between academic performance and emotional stability. Despite these, there is also a need to examine gender difference in emotional stability, academic performance in light of insecurity in Zamfara state, Nigeria.

According to a study conducted by Payne-Sturges et al. (2018), insecurity can be a major factor in the emotional stability and academic performance of undergraduate students. This study found that feeling insecure in their academic environment can lead to undergraduate students feeling overwhelmed and unable to concentrate, which can have a direct impact on their academic performance. However, Payne-Sturges et al. (2018) was unable to factor in gender lens, hence the need for this study to examine gender difference in academic performance and emotional stability in an insecure setting. Furthermore, insecurity can lead to feelings of social isolation and loneliness, which can have a negative impact on a student's emotional stability. These feelings can lead to a lack of motivation and a decrease in performance, hence necessitating the need to examine gender lens in this regard.

The theory of education productivity was propounded by Walberg et al. (1986), discussed broadly factors that impact students' learning and academic performances. It is an assessment of academic achievement where Walberg used a variation of methods to identify the factors that influence academic performance. Walberg identified nine factors that require optimization to increase student achievement of cognitive and affective outcomes. These are; ability or prior achievement, age, motivation or self-concept as indicated by personality tests or willingness to persevere on learning tasks; the instructional variables of, the quantity of instruction, and quality of the instructional experience; and educationally stimulating psychological aspects of the home environment, the classroom or school environment, the peer group environment, and the mass media (especially television). This study posited that environmental and personal factors i.e., personal and community insecurity can influence students' learning since students are the product of their environment (Ojeleye, Mutiu & Kareem, 2020).

The uncertainty surrounding security of life and property of the people of any State can hinder the growth of sustainable development and educational advancement of such a State. Nwosu et al. (2019) argued that an insecure institution environment affects students adversely; situations of insecurity trigger traumatic disorder and toxic stress that can affect learning negatively. For example, a large number of students of the federal institutions in Zamfara live in Damba village, where there have been some reports of abductions and bandit attacks over the last few months (Premium Times, 2021). DC Payne-Sturges et al. (2018) found that undergraduate students who experienced higher levels of insecurity were more likely to report higher levels of anxiety, depression, and loneliness. Furthermore, these students had lower self-esteem and reported lower academic performance than those who did not experience insecurity.

Consequently, this study aims to explore the impact of insecurity context in the relationship between emotional stability and academic performance of undergraduate students of Federal Institutions Zamfara State. Also, the study will examine the linkage of gender lens between emotional stability and academic performance of this population. Several studies (Hyde, et al., 1990; Feingold, 1994; Duckworth & Seligman, 2006; Graziano, et al. 2007; Ojeleye et al. 2020) indicating how gender difference influences students' performances, hence necessitating the need for examining gender lens with the context of this inquiries.

Universities and colleges across the world are continuously striving to cater to their students to ensure that they develop into successful and well-rounded individuals. However, within this environment, most students are faced with a multitude of pressures and stressors that threaten their academic performance, mental health and general emotional stability yet they are also expected to compete in both local and international labour market, hence this the

dilemma. This dilemma also include gap between social class, attainment of Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) among others. Learned helplessness, fear of failure, and fear of academic success can lead to strong feelings of academic insecurity, which hinders students' emotional stability. Moreover, when students feel emotionally insecure, it can hinder their academic performance since students tend to put minimal effort into their school work as a coping mechanism. Therefore, it is important to create a safe, encouraging learning environment that allows students to feel secure, empowered and actively engaged in their education via having insight on how these insecurity influence students. By doing so, we can help them to maintain emotional stability, build positive academic identities, and ultimately, enhance their academic performance.

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the relationship between emotional stability and students' academic performance among students in federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State
2. To investigate whether difference exists between academic performance of male and female students in Federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State.
3. To examine whether difference exist in emotional stability of male and female students in Federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State.

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant relationship between emotional stability and mean academic performance scores among students in Federal tertiary institution in Zamfara State.
2. There is no significant difference in mean academic performance scores of male and female students in federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State.
3. There is no significant difference in emotional stability of male and female students in federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State.

Methodology

This study was carried out using a correlation research design. The population of the study comprised all undergraduate students of the three federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State, the three schools are: Federal University Gusau (FUG), Gusau, Federal College of Education (Technical), Gusau and The Federal Polytechnic, Kaura Namoda, Zamfara State. Three hundred and eighty-four (384) students were sampled using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) to determine the sample size, purposively sampling was used. One hundred and twenty-eight (128) students were purposively selected in each school and also sixty-four (64) males and sixty-four (64) females were sampled in each institution. Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ) developed by Gross and John (2003) was adopted and adapted for this study and CGPA was used to measure academic performance for this study. Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ) is a 10-item scale designed to measure respondents' tendency to regulate their emotions in two ways: (1) Cognitive Reappraisal and (2) Expressive Suppression. This instrument uses a 7-point Likert-type scale but was adapted to 5-point Likert scale for the purpose of this study. Respondents answer each item on a 5-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to (strongly agree). This was used to measure emotional stability among the respondents. A pilot study was also carried out using undergraduate students from Federal University Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State. Data collected from these undergraduate students were analysed using Gutterman Split-half and 0.81 Cronbach Alpha was obtained for ERQ.

Results

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between emotional stability and mean academic performance scores among students in Federal tertiary institution in Zamfara State.

Table 3: Pearson r results of emotional stability and academic performance of students federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State

Variables	N	r	df	sig.	decision
Emotional stability	384	0.7035	382	0.000	significant
Academic performance					

Table 3 shows that R-value was 0.7035 with p-value of 0.000 calculated at the alpha level of .05. since the calculated p-value of .000 is less than the alpha level of .05, therefore, the null hypothesis that says, there is no significant relationship between emotional stability and academic performance of students of federal tertiary institutions is rejected at .05 level of significance. This shows that there is enough evidence that a significant positive relationship exists between emotional stability and academic performance at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in mean academic performance scores of male and female students in federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State.

Table 4: t-test showing gender difference in Academic Performance amidst insecurity

Variables	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p-value
Male Students	192	37.41	49.50	382	2.309	0.0350
Female Students	192	32.95	40.56			

Table 4 shows that t-value was 2.309 with p-value of 0.0350 calculated at the significance level of 0.05. Since the calculated p-value of 0.0350 is less than the alpha levels, therefore, the null hypothesis which stated there is no significant difference between academic performance of male and female undergraduate students is rejected. This shows that significant difference exists in academic performance of male and female undergraduates' students. It reveals that there is enough evidence that the male students with mean value of 37.41 have higher academic performance than female students with mean value of 32.95 at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in emotional stability of male and female students in federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State.

Table 5: t-test showing gender difference in emotional stability amidst insecurity

Variables	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p-value
Male Students	192	39.64	38.65	382	2.41	0.005
Female Students	192	35.54	32.90			

Table 5 shows that t-value was 2.41 with p-value of 0.005 calculated at the significance level of 0.05. Since the calculated p-value of 0.005 is less than the alpha levels, therefore, the null hypothesis which stated there is no significant difference between emotional stability of male and female undergraduate students is rejected. This shows that significant difference exists in emotional stability of male and female undergraduates' students. It reveals that there is enough evidence that the male students with mean value of 39.64 have higher emotional than female students with mean value of 35.54 at 0.05 level of significance.

Discussion of Findings

The study explored the relationship between emotional stability and academic performance in an environment with increasing insecurity among federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State. The findings are discussed in the following heading: emotional stability and academic performance in the context of insecurity and gender differences in emotional stability and academic performance in the context of insecurity. The findings of the study reveal several interesting patterns in the emotional stability, academic performance, and gender differences among

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undergraduate students in federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State, particularly in the context of insecurity. These findings provide valuable insights that contribute to our understanding of the psychological and academic aspects of students facing security challenges.

Emotional Stability in the Context of Security challenges

Descriptively, emotional stability has two domain which are cognitive appraisal and expressive suppression. The result indicated that majority of undergraduate students (63%) experienced high changes in their thinking and appraisal of situations, indicating a significant level of cognitive appraisal. Likewise, 65% of the respondents was able emotional expression were highly suppressed. This also suggests that students are actively engaging with and processing the challenges posed by insecurity. This high cognitive appraisal and expressive suppression could be attributed to the unique socio-political context of Zamfara State, emphasizing the need for educational institutions to incorporate coping mechanisms within their academic programs. This was similar to Payne-Sturges et al. (2018) notion that undergraduate students feeling insecure in an academic institution can be overwhelming, leading to a direct impact on academic performance, hence the need for examining the connection between academic performance.

Emotional Stability and Academic Performance

The findings revealed a positive relationship between emotional stability and academic performance in the context of insecurity. This implies that the more student's emotional stability is increasing positive so will academic performance. This also implies that students who exhibit higher emotional stability are more likely to achieve better academic outcomes. This finding underscores the importance of integrating emotional intelligence and resilience-building programs into the academic curriculum. Educational institutions should consider implementing initiatives that promote emotional well-being to enhance overall student success, especially in regions facing security challenges.

This further inform that in addressing insecurity negative impact on students' performance, therapy centered around improving emotional stability would have an indirect effect on academic performance. Chamorro-Premuzic & Furnham, (2003) indicated that some emotional trait could impair academic performance likewise, Graziano, et al., and Xu, et al., (2020) also indicated that ability to regulate emotion reflect academic success or performance. This further buttress the current study finding that emotion have a positive relationship with academic performance.

Gender Differences in Emotional Stability and Academic performance

The study highlights noticeable gender differences in emotional stability among students in the face of insecurity. Male students demonstrated higher emotional stability, both in terms of cognitive reappraisal and expressive suppression, compared to their female counterparts. These gender variations may be linked to societal expectations, coping mechanisms, or individual resilience. Understanding these differences is crucial for implementing targeted support systems and interventions to enhance emotional well-being, particularly for female students. More so, the study also highlighted gender difference in academic performance in the context of insecurity. Likewise, same trend was observed as illustrated above Male students demonstrated higher academic performance than their female counterpart. This further buttress that the positive relationship between emotional stability and academic performance.

The gender differences in emotional stability and academic performance amid insecurity underscore the need for tailored interventions. Understanding these distinctions allows for the development of targeted support programs that address the specific challenges faced by male and female students. Strategies to enhance emotional stability and academic performance should be gender-sensitive, recognizing and accommodating the unique needs and responses of each gender group.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study sheds light on the intricate relationship between emotional stability, academic performance, and gender differences among undergraduate students in federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State, particularly in the context of insecurity. The results show how important emotional health is for academic performance and how different genders handle the difficulties that come with insecurity in different ways. A high degree of cognitive evaluation was demonstrated by most students, suggesting that they actively engaged with the complicated insecure environment. Male students demonstrated higher emotional stability compared to their female counterparts,

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revealing potential gender-specific responses to insecurity. Additionally, the study revealed a substantial positive relationship between emotional stability and academic performance, emphasizing the crucial role of psychological resilience in achieving positive learning outcomes. One area of focus was students' academic performance in the context of insecurity; a significant number of them had moderate performance. The small percentage of kids who perform exceptionally well academically highlights the necessity of focused interventions to lessen the influence of security issues on learning objectives.

The study emphasizes the need of putting in place customized support systems inside educational institutions from a practical standpoint. Counseling services, stress management programs, and gender-sensitive initiatives can contribute to enhancing emotional stability and, subsequently, academic success. These practical implications align with the broader goal of promoting a resilient and thriving student community in the midst of challenging circumstances. The theoretical implications of this study resonate with the theory of education productivity, emphasizing the critical role of emotional stability in optimizing cognitive functioning and, consequently, academic productivity. By acknowledging the interconnectedness of emotional well-being and academic success, educational institutions can incorporate emotional intelligence principles into their frameworks, creating an environment conducive to effective learning. In summary, this study contributes valuable insights to the understanding of how emotional stability, gender dynamics, and academic performance intersect in the context of insecurity. The implications call for proactive measures to address emotional well-being and foster an inclusive educational environment that supports the diverse needs of students, ultimately enhancing their overall learning experience and success.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations emerge to address the identified issues related to emotional stability, gender differences, and academic performance in the context of insecurity among undergraduate students in federal tertiary institutions in Zamfara State:

1. Firstly, implementation of emotional well-being programmes. Universities of higher learning must make the launch of comprehensive programs for emotional well-being a top priority. These programs ought to include stress management classes, counseling services, and resilience-building exercises designed to provide kids the tools they need to deal with the difficulties that come with uncertainty.
2. Second, there is a need for gender-sensitive support systems. Institutions must to provide support systems that are considerate of the distinct requirements of both male and female students, taking into account the gender disparities in emotional stability. A more welcoming and encouraging atmosphere might also be promoted by interventions that are specifically designed to address the issues that each gender faces.
3. Thirdly, emotional intelligence needs to be incorporated into tertiary curricula. Incorporating this in educational curricula like in courses or workshops on emotional intelligence can contribute to the overall development of students, helping them cultivate skills necessary for emotional stability which would aid academic performance.

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Effect of Entry Qualifications on Performance in Mathematics Education Program among Undergraduate Students of Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigates the Effect of Entry Qualifications on Performance among Undergraduate Mathematics Education Students of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. One objective, one research question and one null hypothesis were formulated to guide the study. An ex-post factor research design was adopted for the study, the population of the study consist of three hundred and forty-six (346) Undergraduate Mathematics Education students (309 Male and 37 Female) within 2019-2023 academic sessions in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, the sample of seventy-two (72) students (65 Male and 7 Female) were selected using stratified random sampling technique, two instruments, student's confidential files (SCF) and semester examination question papers (SEQP) were employed for data collection. The validity of the instrument (SEQP) was calculated using Lawshe's Content Validity Ratio (CVR) and were found to be 0.60. The reliability of the instrument SEQP was tested using Cronbach's Alpha and found to be 0.84. The research question was answered using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) while the null hypothesis was tested using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance. Research findings revealed a significant difference in students' performance with whom were admitted through NCE performing better than those admitted through UTME and ODE. Based on the findings, it was recommended that; students with NCE mode of entry should be given more consideration when selecting candidate for admission.

Keywords: Mathematics Education, Entry qualification, Performance,

Introduction

Mathematics is seen by the society as the foundation of scientific and technological knowledge, which is vital in the socio-economic development of a nation. One of the objectives of science education is to develop students' interest in science and technology as today's society depends largely on development in science and technology (Nigerian Education Research and Development Council, NERDC, 2007). It is therefore not suppressing that mathematics is one of the core subjects taking note of a country's quest for rapid technological and scientific development (NPE, 2013). Looking at the importance of mathematics to human life and to scientific development in particular, effort has to be made to eradicate the learning difficulties of students in mathematics and hence improve the basic mathematics skills to be acquired at all levels of our education. Mathematics is the language used to express logical ideas, shapes, quantities, sizes, order, change and dynamics in the system and to explain the complexities of modern society in business, economic, academic, engineering and medical settings (Abdurrahman & Bolaji, 2018). Mathematics according to Alio & Anibueze, (2017) is the science of numbers, quantity and space. In other words, it is the systematic treatment of magnitude, relationships between figures and forms and relationship between quantities expressed symbolically.

Academic performance is the ultimate result of learning produced by both the student and the teacher as a result of the instructional activity (Sothan, 2019). In Nigeria, poor student performance has been blamed for ineffective teaching strategies and an unhelpful learning environment (Sunday, Olaoye & Audu, 2021). Researchers, educators, teachers, the government, and parents have all expressed concern about the factors that contribute to Nigerian students performing poorly in mathematics (Wonu & Zalmon, 2019). A lot of factor has been identified by researcher to be

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responsible for students' poor performance in mathematics and possible solutions were made but the problem remain unchanged. Despite all these factors experts believed that, the performance should be used as a yard-stick for promotion, award of certificate and appointment (Sadauki, 2015). This observation became a challenge and this is why the present study has been raised to verify if entry qualifications may help in resolving this trend.

As it may apply to academic life, previous performances may be assessed to determine elements that are contributory to continuous performance on educational and career paths and therefore can be predicted to assure continuous improvement. The need to correlate entry qualification and performance of undergraduate students has been appreciated by many psychologists. The selection of right candidates for the university education is as important as the quality of instruction. Academic success is no doubt the main focus of all educational programmes and thus received tremendous attention from educators. However, predicting academic performance through entry qualification is not yet clear. Over the years, there have been concerns about the correlation between the pre-admission qualification of students and their academic performance in the university. This appears to be a global source of concern in view of the ongoing debates and studies on the issue in different countries (Farooq & Mlambo, 2011).

The academic performance of students admitted in to universities has been an issue of great concern to many educationists in Nigeria and the whole world. The decay in the educational system calls for attention and hence the search for the most desirable mode of selecting candidates for admission into Nigerian universities continues unabated.

Despite the vital roles played by mathematics in scientific and technological development of the whole nation, its teaching and learning are faced with some problems that make most students to perform poorly in the subject which might have resulted from different factors among them entry qualification may be one (Tanimu, 2019). Also, the non-uniformity in the three modes of entry; UTME, ODE and NCE is another issue of concern, yet are all considered to have the same experience during class room instructions and examinations. This observation became a challenge and this is why the current effort is being embarked upon to verify the claim. Bratti and Staffolani (2006) observed that the measurement of the students' prior educational outcomes or performance is the most important indicator or determinant of the students' future academic performance. This is because the quality of any programme is estimated among other things on the qualifications at the entrant.

Objective of the Study

The purpose of this study was to compare the "Effects of Entry Qualification among Undergraduate Mathematics Education Students of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria". The study aimed to determine the differences among the three entry qualifications that may lead to a desired performance of the students at the end of 200 level. Specifically, the study aimed to;

1. Determine the effects of the three modes of admission on Performance among Undergraduate Mathematics Education Students of Ahmadu Bello University Zaria.

Research Question

The following research question was raised to guide the conduct of the study;

1. Is there any significant difference among the effects of the three modes of admission on performance among undergraduate Mathematics Education Students of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria?

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis were formulated and tested at 0.05 significant level;

1. H_{01} : There is no significant difference between the three modes of admission on performance among Undergraduate Mathematics Education Students of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.

Research Design

The research design used was an ex-post factor research design otherwise known as causal-comparative research design. This research design attempts to explore cause and effects relationship where causes already exist and cannot be manipulated. Simon (2013) suggested that ex-post factor research design is ideal for conducting social research when it is no possible or acceptable to manipulate the characteristics of human participant.

Population of the Study

The population of this study consisted of all undergraduate mathematics education students of A.B.U, Zaria from 2019 – 2023 academic session. The available population were three hundred and forty-six (346) students, among them fifty-six (56) students were from 400 level i.e 2019/2020 academic session, seventy-five (75) students were from

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300 level i.e 2020/2021 academic session, seventy-nine (79) students were from 200 level i.e 2021/2022 academic session and one hundred and thirty-six (136) students were from 100 level i.e 2022/2023 academic session, as presented in Table 1;

Table 1: Population of the Study

S/N	Level	Entry qualification	No of Students		Total
			Male	Female	
21.	400 Level				
i.		UTME	05	-	05
ii.		ODE	16	3	19
iii.		NCE	24	-	24
iv.		HND	8	-	08
2.	300 Level				
i.		UTME	30	5	35
ii.		ODE	12	3	15
iii.		NCE	13	1	14
iv.		HND	10	1	11
3.	200 Level				
i.		UTME	17	2	19
ii.		ODE	18	1	19
iii.		NCE	37	4	41
4.	100 Level				
i.		UTME	119	17	136
Total			309	37	346

Source: Science Education Exams office (2023)

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample for the study comprises of 200 level undergraduate mathematics education students of A.B.U, Zaria of 2021/2022 academic sessions. The available sample were seventy-two (72) students among them sixty-five (65) students were male and seven (7) students were female. The choice of selecting 200 level is because it is at 200 level candidates admitted through DE are gathered together with those admitted through UTME and proceed with same training with the expectation performing equally well. It is also assumed that at this level, candidates depend purely on their entry qualifications before adjusting to other experiences influence by the academic environment. Stratified sampling technique was used to select the sample. The samples were divided into three (3) strata based on the three entry qualifications UTME, OND and NCE. The researcher takes each of the entry qualification as strata for easy categorization and selection of the sample as presented in Table 2;

Table 2 Sample for the Study

S/N	Entry qualification	No of Students		Total
		Male	Female	
1.	UTME	16	2	18
2.	ODE	13	1	14
3.	NCE	36	4	40
Total		65	7	72

Instrumentation

The instruments used for data collection were documents (student's confidential files, SCF), collected in an official manner and two semesters examination question papers (SEQP) for 2021 – 2022 academic session, some of the question papers were collected from the various departments' examinations offices while some from the faculty

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library. Students' bio-data were collected from their confidential files at Mathematics Education Section, Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education A.B.U, Zaria.

Validation of the Instrument

SEQP were validated by seven experts whose ranks are ranging from Senior lecturer and above from department of Mathematics and Science Education where the examinations were set up after which the researcher used Lawshe's Content Validity Ratio (CVR) to determine the average validity ratio and found the average validity ratio to be 0.60 which implies that the instrument is valid.

Method of Data Collection

Results of the students (CGPA) at the end of two hundred level (200 level) were collected from the examination office of the department of science education, faculty of education ABU, Zaria, by the approval of the H.O.D. CGPA of seventy-two (72) students were collected with eighteen (18) students from UTME mode of admission, fourteen (14) students from ODE mode of admission and forty (40) students from NCE mode of admission. Data were sorted based on entry qualification.

Results

Research Question

1. Is there any significant difference among the effects of the three modes of admission on performance among Undergraduate Mathematics Education Students of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria?

These research questions were summarized in Table 3 using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation)

Table 3: Descriptive statistics for the performance of undergraduate mathematic education students with different entry qualifications.

Entry Qualification	N	Mean CGPA	Std. Deviation
UTME	18	1.80	1.05
ODE	14	1.86	1.14
NCE	40	2.16	1.11

Table 3 shows the mean CGPA for the performance of 2020/2021 students admitted through UTME as; 1.80, those admitted through ODE as; 1.86 and those admitted through NCE as; 2.16 with their respective standard deviations as; 1.05, 1.14 and 1.11.

Hypothesis

H₀:

There is no significant difference between the three modes of entry qualifications on performance among Undergraduate Mathematics Education Students of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.

The null hypothesis was tested in Table 4 using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 4: One-way ANOVA for the performance of undergraduate mathematics education students with different entry qualifications.

Groups	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-ratio	P-value
Between Groups	13.20	2	6.60	6.20	0.03
Within Groups	73.49	69	1.07		
Total	86.69	71			

Decision Criterion: Reject H₀ if P-value ≤ 0.05

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Table 4 shows a P-value of 0.03 between and within the three groups which was less than 0.05, therefore H_0 which state that; there is no significant difference between the three modes of entry qualifications on performance among Undergraduate Mathematics Education Students of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria was rejected. This indicates that there was a significant difference among the effect of the three entry qualifications on performance among mathematics education students of A. B. U, Zaria. This difference was shown in the Post Hoc Table 5;

Table 5: Post Hoc Test showing the difference in performance of undergraduate mathematics education students with different entry qualifications.

(I) Entry Qualification	(J) Entry Qualification	Mean Difference (I-J)	P-value
UTME	ODE	-0.06	0.99
	NCE	-0.89	0.01
ODE	UTME	0.06	0.99
	NCE	-0.83	0.03
NCE	UTME	0.89	0.01
	ODE	0.83	0.03

From Table 5, it can be observed that, the P-value between students admitted through UTME and those admitted through NCE was 0.01, this indicate that significant difference exists between the performance of the students admitted through the two modes of entry (UTME and NCE). At the same time, the Table shows a P-value of 0.03 between the performance of students admitted through ODE and those admitted through NCE which also indicate that there exists a significant difference between the performance of the students admitted through the two modes of entry (ODE and NCE).

Discussion of Findings

Table 4, shows a p-value of 0.03 between and within the three groups which was less than 0.05, therefore H_0 which states that; there is no significant difference among the effects of the three entry qualifications on performance among undergraduate mathematics education students of A. B. U, Zaria was rejected. This indicates that; there exists a significant difference among the effect of the three entry qualifications on performance of mathematics education students of A. B. U, Zaria. This difference was shown in the Post Hoc Table 5, indicated a P- value of 0.01 between students admitted through UTME and those admitted through NCE. The Table also shows a P-value of 0.03 between the performance of students admitted through ODE and those admitted through NCE. This indicates that students admitted through NCE perform better since the Table shows a P-value of 0.99 between the performances of students admitted through ODE and those admitted through UTME. This clearly indicates that the poor performance arises from the ODE mode of entry. This finding contradicts all other findings from the literature reviewed. It also shows that; there are other factors that affect the performance of the students and not necessarily as a result of mode of entry. Thus, these factors may need to be investigated by other researchers.

Conclusions

Based on the findings from this study, the researcher concluded that there was a significant difference among the effects of the three modes of admission, it was observed that students admitted through NCE were the high-performance group among the three entry qualifications followed by those students admitted through UTME, the students admitted through ODE were found to perform slightly lower among the three modes of admissions. This clearly indicates that the performance of students in university education depends on the experiences of students under the influence of the university instructional environment. However, the findings suggest that students admitted through ODE and those admitted through UTME modes of admissions need monitoring and mentoring to ensure better academic performance. The implication of this study therefore is that students' performance is largely a function of the number of efforts put into study among other factors and not necessarily as a result of mode of entry into the university. The findings suggest the need to consider NCE modes of admissions as the most appropriate criteria for selecting prospective students into undergraduate mathematics education programme in Nigerian universities.

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Recommendations

Based on the findings generated from this study, the following recommendations were made

1. A special orientation program should be organized to all new undergraduate mathematics education students especially those admitted through ODE and UTME to help them adapt to the university learning environment. This program can include study skills orientation, independent learning, understanding the semester system and how to easily capture the mathematics concepts. This will equip students to cope with the academic rigors of mathematic study.
2. Academicians teaching mathematics courses need to be made aware that students enrolling into the program at two hundred level (200level) have different background and experiences so they need special attention to enable all the students in the class to benefit from the class room instruction which may help to improve their performance. They should also be given proper training in planning and teaching a course with variation of student backgrounds.
3. It was also recommended that the department may need to conduct oral screening exercise as a means of further screening of prospective students in order to have the opportunity of interacting with them personally to elicit those who were able to justify their entry qualification.

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Effects of Activity-Based Strategy on Achievement and Attitude in Concept Light Waves among Secondary School Students in Kagarko Local Government, Kaduna State

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Abstract

This study investigated the Effects of Activity-Based Strategy on Achievement and Attitude in concept Light Waves among Secondary School Students in Kagarko Local Government, Kaduna State. The study adopted pre-test and post-test quasi-experimental research design. The population of the study consists of all government senior secondary school class two (SSII) Physics students during the 2020/2021 academic session in Kagarko local government area of Kaduna state. A sample size of 86 (49 Male and 37 Female) students were selected from the target population using simple random sampling technique. The experimental group were exposed to Physics concept using Activity-Based Strategy while the Control group were taught using Conventional Method. Two instruments, namely Physics Achievement Test (PAT) and Physics Attitude Scale (PAS) were used for data collection and had reliability coefficient of 0.82 and 0.74 obtained by the used of Kuder-Richardson 21 (K-R 21) and Cronbach Alpha (α) respectively. Two research questions were raised with four corresponding hypotheses. These hypotheses were tested using ANCOVA at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that the use of Activity-Based Strategy in teaching physics concept to secondary school students enhanced students' achievement and attitude. The study also revealed that there was no significant interaction between gender and instructional approach on students' achievement and attitude. The study concluded that the application of Activity-Based Strategy improved students' achievement and increased positive attitude toward Physics. The study recommended the provision of in-service training and retraining for teachers on the use of Activity-Based Strategy for teaching Physics.

Keywords: Activity-Based Strategy, Achievement, Attitude, Student

Introduction

Science is the foundation upon which the bulk of present-day technological breakthrough is built. All over the world, nations are striving hard to develop technologically and scientifically, since the world is turning scientific and all the proper functioning of lives depend greatly on science (Oluwasegun, Ohwofosirai & Emagbetere, 2015). Series of attempts and innovations have been made to recognize science and technology at various levels of the Nigerian education system by the government, educational institutions, scientific agencies, and professional association (Ojelade, 2010). Physics is one of the subjects in science education. It involves the study of matter, energy, and their interactions. Any nation that pays lip service to the development of Physics education will surely lag behind among the community of nations. It is because of this that African countries must find ways of improving their Physics education program at the secondary and post-secondary school levels (Benson, 2017).

Physics plays a major role in health education, economic development, energy, and the environment. The X-rays, radioisotope nuclear resource imaging, laser electron, microscope, and synchrotron radiator among other advances in medicine depend on Physics-based technology (Kola, 2013). Our world is more connected through technology and the conduction of business around the world is done almost effortlessly (Bello, 2012). Despite the

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importance of Physics in scientific and technological development, it appears as though Physics education has been facing various challenges. First, the enrolment in Physics courses at all levels is low in many African countries (Amunga, Musasia & Musera, 2011). Many reasons are advanced for this discrepancy which include inadequate lower level preparations, weak mathematics background, lack of job opportunities outside the teaching profession, inadequate teacher qualification as well as possession of below standard pedagogical content knowledge (Semela, 2010).

The research reports on the effects of laboratory equipment indicated a significant difference between the performance of Biology Students exposed to adequately equipped laboratories and those exposed to the inadequately equipped laboratory. The difference was in favour of those exposed to the adequately equipped laboratory (Katcha & Wushishi, 2015). Intensive practical activities have a positive influence on students' achievements in Physics. It improves Physics academic performance of the learner (Amadalo, Alhayo & Thomas, 2016). According to Muchai (2016), studies on the effects of practical work on students' achievements in Physics, showed that a practical approach resulted in higher students' achievements in Physics, lead to improved students' attitude toward Physics, and also, increased higher students' enrolment in Physics at the Kenya Certificate of Secondary School Education. Shittu (2013), further stated that students who were taught light concepts using a guided inquiry strategy achieved significantly higher than those taught the same light concepts using the lecture method. Nwayiabai's (2014), study revealed that the use of Origami in teaching enhanced students' achievement, interest, and retention in geometry. Also, it had no statistically differential effect on male and female students' achievements, interests, and retention. Furthermore, there was a significant interaction effect between gender and instructional material on retention of the concepts taught.

It is important to realize that a positive student attitude towards the content of an instructional activity should be a critical goal for the teacher because there is a positive correlation between student attitude and student achievement (Dajal, Ogar & Sunday, 2019). Teaching strategies can influence the attitude of students positively or negatively, this suggests that the attitude of students plays a significant part in any satisfactory explanation of the variable level of performance by students in their school science subject (Shittu, 2013). Studies by Dawaki (2012), point out that most science teachers use the traditional method. These methods do not allow active students' participation in science lessons rather, students memorize, and regurgitate facts and concepts without the basic understanding of what it is they have memorized. Teachers serve as pipelines and seek to transfer their thoughts and meanings to the passive students. For this reason, the "Effects of Activity-Based Strategy on Achievement and Attitude in concept Light Waves among Secondary School Students in Kagarko Local Government, Kaduna State" towards learning in Physics are studied.

The teaching and learning of Physics in most classrooms face a lot of problems. Most of the teachers use the Conventional Teaching Method that comprises Talk and Chalk, Note taking and Memorization. They do not make use of Activity-Based Strategies, where the learners play an active role in the learning process. This inability of the Physics teachers in the use of Activity-Based Strategies might be the cause of poor performance in the subject at both teacher's made examinations and external examinations. Thus, this study is aimed at comparing the mean performance of students taught Physics using the Activity-Based Strategy and Conventional Method in order to determine which one is more effective in teaching Physics in Senior Secondary Schools in Kagarko Local Government Area, Kaduna State.

Objectives of the study

The main objectives of this study was to determine the Effects of Activity-Based Strategy on Achievement and Attitude in concept Light Waves among Secondary School Students in Kagarko Local Government, Kaduna State. The specific objectives are to;

1. Determine the mean achievement scores of students taught Physics concept using Activity-Based Strategy and those taught using Conventional teaching Methods among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area.
2. Determine the mean attitude rating scores of students taught Physics concept using Activity-Based Strategy and those taught using Conventional teaching Methods among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area.

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Research Questions

This following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the mean difference in achievement scores of students taught Physics concepts using Activity-Based Strategy and those taught using the Conventional teaching Methods among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area?
2. What is the mean difference in attitude rating scores between students taught physics concept using Activity-Based Strategy and those exposed to Conventional teaching methods among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were raised and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. **H₀:** There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Physics concepts using Activity-Based Strategy and those exposed to Conventional teaching methods among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area.
2. **H₀:** There is no significant interaction effect between treatment and gender among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area.
3. **H₀:** There is no significant difference in mean attitude rating scores of students taught Physics concepts using Activity-Based Strategy and those exposed to Conventional teaching methods among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area.
4. **H₀:** There is no significant interaction effect between treatment and gender among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area.

Methodology

The study adopted pre-test and post-test quasi-experimental research design. The population of the study consists of all government senior secondary school class two (SSII) Physics students during the 2020/2021 academic session in Kagarko local government area of Kaduna state. A sample size of 86 (49 male and 37 female) students were selected from the target population using simple random sampling technique. The experimental group were exposed to Physics concept using Activity-Based Strategy while the Control group were taught using Conventional Method. Two instruments, namely Physics Achievement Test (PAT) and Physics Attitude Scale (PAS) were used for data collection and had reliability coefficient of 0.82 and 0.74 obtained by used of Kuder-Richardson 21 (K-R 21) and Cronbach Alpha (α) respectively. After permission was sought and granted by the school authorities in order to use their schools for the study. Thereafter, PAT and PAS were served to 86 SSSII Physics students from the selected schools. The results were then used to ascertain relative ability in achievement in Physics concepts.

The Physics students of the intact classes of the two groups were taught using the Activity-Based Strategy for the experimental group, while the Conventional teaching Method was used for the control group. The same topics were taught in both schools (groups) using an intact class

The post-test of PAT and PAS was administered to Physics students at the end of the 8th week of the study. The students of the two (2) groups; the experimental group and the control group took the post-test.

The data collected from the study were analyzed using frequency count, mean score, and standard deviation to answer research questions, while the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) statistic at 0.05 level of significance was used to analyze data for testing the null hypotheses. the analysis was computer-based, with the use of the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS).

Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean difference in achievement scores of students taught Physics concepts using Activity-Based Strategy and those taught using the Conventional teaching Methods among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area?

Table 1: Mean Achievement Scores and Standard Deviation of Experimental and Control Groups in Pre-test and Post-test (PAT)

Group		Pre-test	Post-test	Mean Gain
Experimental	Mean	25.80	43.70	17.90
	Std. Deviation	0.91	0.83	
	N	45	45	
Control	Mean	25.90	27.50	1.60
	Std. Deviation	0.86	0.86	
	N	41	41	
Mean difference				16.30

The results in table 1 show that the mean achievement score of Pre-PAT for the experimental group was 25.80 with a standard deviation of 0.91, while that of the control group was 25.90 with a standard deviation of 0.86. At the beginning of the study, the subjects were almost at the same level in their knowledge of Physics. The mean achievement score of Post-PAT for the experimental group was observed to be 43.70 with a standard deviation of 0.83 while that of the control group, the mean achievement score of Post-PAT was 27.50 with a standard deviation of 0.86. The result showed that the use of Activity-Based Strategy had a positive effect on students' achievement in Physics in the experimental group than those in the control group. The difference in the mean gain between the two groups is 16.30 in favor of the experimental group.

Research Question 2

What is the mean difference in attitude rating scores between students taught physics concept using Activity-Based Strategy and those exposed to Conventional teaching methods among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area?

Table 2: Mean Scores and Standard Deviation on Attitude of Experimental and Control Groups in Pre-test and Post-test (PAS)

Group		Pre-test	Post-test	Mean Gain
Experimental	Mean	1.60	3.42	1.82
	Std. Deviation	0.26	0.41	
	N	45	45	
Control	Mean	1.56	2.05	0.49
	Std. Deviation	0.31	0.39	
	N	41	41	
Mean difference				1.33

From table 2, it could be observed that the mean Pre-PAS of the experimental group is 1.60 with a standard deviation of 0.26 and that of the control group 1.56 with a standard deviation of 0.31. At the beginning of the study, the subjects were almost at the same level in their attitude toward Physics. The table also shows that the experimental group of Post-PAS is 3.42 with a standard deviation of 0.41 while that of the control group is 2.05 with a standard deviation of 0.39. The difference in the mean gain attitude scores of the two groups is 1.33 in favor of the experimental group.

Hypotheses

H₀:

There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Physics concepts using Activity-Based Strategy and those exposed to Conventional teaching methods among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area.

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Table 3: ANCOVA Results of the Experimental and Control Groups on PAT Due to Method and Gender (for hypotheses 1 and 2)

Source	Sum of squares	df	Mean	F	Sig
Corrected model	5716.242	4	1429.061	47.581	0.000
Intercept	6416.382	1	6416.382	213.635	0.000
Pre-test	18.811	1	18.811	0.626	0.431
Group (Method)	5538.809	1	5538.809	184.416	0.000*
Gender (Sex)	88.910	1	88.910	2.960	0.089**
Group * Gender	1.788	1	1.788	0.060	0.808**
Error	2432.781	81	30.034		
Total	118456.000	86			
Corrected total	8149.023	85			

* = Significant at 0.05 level of probability ** = Not significant

Table 3, indicates that the value of the significance of F on achievement is 0.000 as against the already set alpha level of 0.05 at 1 and 81 df (degrees of freedom). Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant achievement scores is rejected. This implies that the experimental groups achieved significantly higher than the control group in the SSS II Physics concepts taught using Activity-Based Strategy.

H0:

There is no significant interaction effect between treatment and gender among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area.

The result of table 3, also revealed that there is no significant interaction effect between treatment and gender as measured by the Physics achievement scores of Post-PAT. The value of the significance of F of the 2-way interaction (Method * Gender) is 0.808 as against 0.05 level of significance already set prior to the experiment. Since the significance of F value is greater than the already set alpha value of 0.05, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is accepted. This means that the interaction effect between method and gender as measured by their mean Physics achievement test scores is not statistically significant.

H0:

There is no significant difference in mean attitude rating scores of students taught Physics concepts using Activity-Based Strategy and those exposed to Conventional teaching methods among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area.

Table 4: ANCOVA Results of the Experimental and Control Groups on PAS Due to Gender; Treatment and Interaction (for hypotheses 3 and 4)

Source	Sum of squares	df	Mean	F	Sig
Corrected model	41.173	4	10.293	41.325	0.000
Intercept	64.575	1	64.575	259.251	0.000
Pre-test	0.224	1	0.224	0.898	0.346
Group (method)	240.063	1	40.063	160.843	0.000*
Gender (Sex)	0.540	1	0.540	2.168	0.145**
Group*Gender	0.021	1	0.021	0.084	0.773**
Error	20.176	81	0.249		
Total	720.000	86			
Corrected total	61.349	85			

* = Significant at .05 level of probability **= No significant.

The result of table 4, shows that there is a significant difference in the mean score attitude between the students taught with Activity-Based Strategy and those taught with Traditional Method at 0.05 level of significance. The value of significance of F on attitude is 0.000 as against the already set of 0.05 at 1 and 81 df (degrees of freedom).

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Based on this, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected. The implication of this is that students that were taught using the Activity-Based Strategy gained more positive attitude in Physics than those in the Traditional Method.

H0.:

There is no significant interaction effect between treatment and gender among secondary schools in Kagarko local government area.

Table 4, also revealed that gender does not influence the treatment as regards attitude. The value of F of the 2-way interaction (Method * Gender) is 0.773 as against 0.05 level of significance. Since the significance of F value is greater than the already set alpha value of 0.05, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is not rejected. This means that there is no statistically significant attitude between treatment and gender in students' attitudes toward Physics.

Discussion of Findings

In table 1 the mean achievement scores of the experimental group in Post-PAT is higher than the Post-PAT mean achievement scores of the control group. This indicated that the use of Activity-Based Strategy concepts improved students' achievement in Physics. The result was further confirmed by the result in table 3, which revealed that the method was a significant factor in students' achievement in Physics. Hence, students who were taught Physics using an Activity-Based Strategy achieved higher than those taught using the Traditional Method. The implication of this is that the instructional material used in teaching Physics can produce differential effects on students with respect to Physics achievement. This positive and higher achievement may have been a result of the active participation of the students due to the fact that the approach used was practical in nature and therefore ensured students' activity. This finding agrees with Katcha and Wushishi (2015), Odutuyi (2015), Amadalo, Aphayo and Thomas (2016), and Muchai (2016), who in their studies found that adequately equipped laboratory, practical work, and practical instructional approach enhanced students' achievement. These findings also lend support to other researchers such as Shittu (2013) and Nwanyiabai (2014), who found that students exposed to Activity-Based instruction methods such as guided inquiring strategy and Origami performed better than their counterparts exposed to the traditional method.

The result in table 2, revealed that the mean attitude rating of the students in the experimental group was almost the same as the mean attitude rating of those in the control group at Pre-PAS. But at Post-PAS, the mean attitude rating of the students in the experimental group is significantly higher than those of the control group. This is further confirmed by the ANCOVA result in table 4, which indicates that the experimental group recorded a significantly higher attitude rating than the control group. These findings confirm that the use of the Activity-Based Strategy concept enhances students' attitude toward Physics. The result of this study is also in accordance with other studies such as Shittu (2011), Nwanyiabai (2014), and Muchai (2016) which confirmed that the use of appropriate instructional material enhances students' interest and attitude in learning Physics. The approach motivated and sustained their attitude thereby evoking a greater understanding of Physics.

The result of table 3, the analysis of the covariance test of interaction revealed that the significance of F is 0.808 for the 2-way-interaction, as against the already set alpha significant level of 0.05. It was found that there is no significant interaction between instructional material and gender on students' achievement in Physics concepts taught during the study. The findings of this study are in agreement with Nwanyiabai (2014) who found no significant interaction effect of instructional model and gender on students' achievement.

Similarly, from table 4, the result of the analysis of the covariance test of interaction showed that, for the 2-way-interaction, the significance of F value is 0.773. Since this is greater than the significance level already set at 0.05, the conclusion is that there is no significant interaction between instructional material and gender on students' attitudes. These findings imply that achievement and interest for male and female students are consistent. The result of this finding is also in compliance with Nwanyiabai (2014) who found no significant interaction effect of instructional strategies and gender on students' attitudes.

Conclusion

Based on the result obtained, the researcher draws the following conclusion: The use of Activity-Based Strategy as an instructional approach enhanced students' achievement in Physics better than the conventional instructional approach. Similarly, the use of Activity-Based Strategy proved superior to the conventional method in promoting students' attitudes and achievement in Physics concepts. There was no significant interaction between Treatment and gender in achievement and attitude in Physics among secondary school students.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based on the findings of this research:

1. Curriculum planners in Secondary Schools should include Activity-Based Strategy as one of the necessary instructional materials for the teaching of Physics;
2. Government and curriculum planners should incorporate Activity-Based Strategy into the curricula of education faculties in universities and teacher training colleges, to ensure proper training of teachers in the new concept;
3. Government/education administrators should also organize public lectures, seminars, and workshops incorporating of Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) on Activity-Based Strategy in schools, as a way of marketing the new concept;
4. Government should through appropriate agencies, sponsor further research into the possible application of Activity-Based Strategy in other aspects of science and technology with Numeral Not bullet or point).

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Effects of E-Learning Modes on Undergraduate Students' Learning Outcomes in Mathematics among Distance Learning Institutions in Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Mathematics, a major subject in science and indeed the secondary school level has witnessed deteriorating performances from students in their various external examinations. This phenomenon has attracted attention from all stakeholders in education, resulting in uncountable researches dealing on the curriculum and instructional strategies. Recently, the pervasive e-Learning instructional modes recorded tremendous successes in other subject areas, and may be applicable to mathematics at the secondary school level. This research therefore investigated the effects of two electronic-learning modes on the learning outcomes of undergraduates in distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria. Quasi experimental design that employed pretest, post-test, control group design was adopted. Two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 significance level. Mathematics Achievement Pre and Post-Tests with multiple choice questions and Mathematics Treatment Instruments were used to collect data from 600 Mathematics undergraduates that formed the sample of the study. A reliability coefficient above 0.80 was obtained for each of the research instruments using Cronbach's alpha coefficients. Analysis of Covariance together with Scheffe and Bonferroni post hoc techniques were used for the data analysis. The findings of the study showed that there were statistically significant differences in the performances of the three groups in favor of the two experimental groups. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that University lecturers should be encouraged to adopt e-Learning modes in their teaching so as to improve learning outcomes of students in mathematics.

Keywords: e-Learning, Video Based Learning, Virtual classroom and Effects

Introduction

Traditional face to face instructional strategy has been the popular mode of education in Nigeria, and it is teacher centered, engaging various methodologies such as lecture, demonstration, discussion, role play and brainstorming. In education, students learn and understand more quickly and easily from one another, but these facts are not taken into consideration in the conventional teaching technique (Umoh & Akpan, 2014). The system is not only boring, but condemned by many educationists for promoting rote learning. Thus, this conventional style alone can no longer be suitable for individual requirements and it is necessary to use modern technology as a supplement and to cater for individual differences in learning styles. Consequently, traditional face to face methodology is presently being massively augmented by Electronic Learning (e-Learning).

E-Learning is defined as the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to develop and deliver pedagogically considered content to learners in an ubiquitous, engaging and interactive learner-centered environment for distance education and fully on-line purposes. E-Learning takes care of the future of higher education in Nigeria. Futurists are in high demand, they have a set of skills and a basis for exploring trends and signals which suggest

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scenarios for the future (Alexander, 2020). Graham, (2013) opined that e-Learning involves mixing various event-based activities such as live e-Learning, self-paced learning, synchronous on-line conference and training or asynchronous self-paced learning. E-Learning modes could be synchronous, asynchronous or hybrid (synchronous & asynchronous). Synchronous methods such as Virtual Classroom, videoconferencing and webinars are the teaching styles where learners and instructors interact in real time from different physical locations. In asynchronous methods such as Video Based Learning, e-Mail, file transfer, blogs and discussion boards, the interaction is out of real time at learners' own time, place and pace. Virtual Classroom (MOODLE software) and Video Based Learning (VBL, pre-recorded videos) have been chosen for the purpose of this research. The use of electronic and on-line learning introduce creativity into the teaching and learning of Mathematics, Jiao, (2020) opined that with on-line learning, creativity is unleashed with passion, the subjects include Mathematics with creative collaboration and leveraging social media for social action. Additionally, responses from the administered questionnaires revealed that using e-Learning at the student's pace can increase the levels of understanding in Mathematics.

Mathematics as a subject is important to pursue careers in engineering, medicine and social science disciplines. The subject is so vast and useful, students develop a phobia for, hate and run away from it, thereby the performance is always below average with poor learning outcomes and mass failure in the secondary school certificate and institutional examinations. Mathematics is very vital even for our daily businesses and livelihood, there is virtually no area of human endeavor where it does not have application. The subject is compulsory in secondary school, whether the students are in science, commercial, arts or social science classes (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2014). Students intending to offer science and social science courses in the higher institutions require credit passes in Mathematics.

Despite the significant role of Mathematics in the educational system and our everyday lives, there has been a decline in the performances of students in the subject at the secondary school level. The statistics of West African Examination Council (WAEC) results on yearly basis reveal persistent poor performances of students in Mathematics. The poor performances of students in Mathematics in Nigeria have been attributed to many factors such as poor teaching facilities, inadequate equipment, lack of visual instructional materials, large numbers of students to teachers, Mathematics phobia and fright, poor teaching methods and lack of confidence in the subject. In addition, low self-concept and motivation, limited background preparation in Mathematics, lack of interest, poor government policies and poor problem-solving abilities. Others are teachers' inappropriate qualifications and training, students' environment, use of traditional chalk and talk method; students' attitudes, mental ability, gender and insufficient use of resources for teaching and learning (Okebukola, 2012).

The research also sought to establish a gender gap in the utilization of Virtual classroom mode in teaching Mathematics among Male and Female students in the area of study. Gender in the context here is the social and cultural roles assigned to the male or female sex. Daniel (2016), Liao (2013), Aderoju (2015) and Whitley (2017) in their various studies, found out that the attitudes towards technology vary significantly between male and female students. The assertion here is that males showed more interest, knowledge and positive attitudes and used it more often than their female counterparts. It is also observed that females view technology as more difficult and less interesting (Abiodun, 2017). However, the difference in attitudes between the two genders towards technology is not attributed to their biological nature but to their social and cultural construction.

Nevertheless, e-Learning modes can address some of the problems brought about by insufficient use of resources. Such learning resources comprise of books, audio-visual materials, flash cards, slides, filmstrips, film records, realia and multimedia. Devices include Telecommunication equipment, Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) such as computers, internet, well fixed line communications, mobile phones, scanners, CDs, DVDs, e- Mails, multimedia products that may be distributed on videotapes and global positioning systems (Ministry of Economic Development, 2014). The problem could also be solved by training Mathematics Distance Learning undergraduates who are the would-be-teachers of these students with the usage of e-Learning modes. As such upon graduation and while on the field, they will be able to inculcate e-Learning methodologies into the teaching and learning of Mathematics in order to improve the achievements and the attitudes of students.

Distance education or Open Distance Learning (ODL) for students who may not always be physically present in a school, evolved in response to the need to provide educational access to learners who would not be able to participate in face-to-face access because they have grown past school age, they are working or for religious reasons. It offers a flexible, cost-effective way to improve academic skills and employment prospects (Shelly & Holliman, 2017). Single mode distance learning institutions are the ones where teaching and learning are designed to provide for

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distance education only, the mode is completely committed to delivering and achieving high quality professional standards in ODL. Dual mode distance learning institutions are those where teaching and learning support both campus based and distance education, they are advantageously characterized by offering on campus and distance education courses that meet the same quality and standard.

Based on the above literature, the present study investigated the effects of two e-Learning modes on the learning outcomes of Mathematics undergraduates in single and dual mode distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria.

The quest for raising the quality of education in Nigeria has been on the rise. Many research findings have shown that students learn Mathematics best when they are actively engaged in learning and participate in the learning process in an interactive, learner-centered manner such as are provided by e-Learning modes. In the Nigerian higher education context, there has been a rapid change in the role of the lecturer in recent years, lecturers face many new changes and challenges and they are required to adapt to such. Included in these are more western and modernized approaches to the impartation of knowledge, new methods of teaching and learning and most importantly an explosion in the development of teaching distance learners within the e-Learning environment. E-learning is a key component of the system and organizational level changes needed to effectively implement on-line learning as a strategy (Nichols, 2020). These imply that teachers, facilitators and lecturers need to update their knowledge and skills to develop the educational process either in the classroom (Ogunleye & Ojo, 2019) or on-line (Ogunleye & Apata, 2018). With on-line learning, it becomes imperative for the academic staff to produce versions of their campus courses for distance students and interact with them by e-Mail and other web tools. Dede, (2020) averred that there is the need to think strategically about lifelong learning while universities need to think whether their current programs and modes of operation need to be re-imagined and re-designed.

The advent and a new philosophy towards e-Learning, its role in education and a wide range of researchers have developed the desired investigation of the role of e-Learning and its translation into an interactive educational environment. Many studies have provided evidence on the significant contributions that e-Learning makes to improving methods of teaching and positively impacting the learner (Kennewell, 2017). However, such studies have been limited to investigating the impact of e-Learning on learners. There is substantially less research focusing on the role which e-Learning plays in creating and promoting a more interactive educational environment as part of teaching and learning with improvement on the learning outcomes of learners in single and dual mode distance learning institutions. The use of e-Learning to create interactive educational environments can help to develop thinking skills and transform classrooms to environments affording rapid educational growth. Using e-Learning to teach also helps the student to develop new thinking skills which may transfer to different situations that require analysis and comprehension skills, and consequently critical skill development (Cooperman, 2017).

The investigation of the effects of e-Learning modes on undergraduate students' learning outcomes in Mathematics among distance learning institutions was carried out in Osun State, Nigeria. The two e-Learning modes investigated were synchronous Virtual Classroom using MOODLE software and asynchronous Video Based Learning (VBL) using pre-recorded videos. They were used to research the teaching of Mathematics among male and female undergraduate distance learners in comparison with traditional classroom methods. This was in reaction to the contradicting research reports on the effectiveness of e-Learning and in an effort to convert the interest of today's students in electronic gadgets to foster the educational standard and enhance job opportunities.

This study determined the effects of these widely growing e-Learning techniques on distance learning in general and specifically on the distance learners' achievements. The moderating effects of gender on students' learning outcomes in Mathematics using the two e-Learning modes was also determined.

Objectives of the study

The purpose of this study was to determine the effects of Electronic Learning modes of Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning on the learning outcomes of Mathematics undergraduates in distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to determine the:

1. Effects of using the two e-Learning modes of Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning, and conventional Lecture method on Mathematics undergraduates' learning outcomes in distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria.

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2. Effects of using the two e-Learning modes of Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning, and conventional Lecture method on male and female Mathematics undergraduates' learning outcomes in distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria.

Research Questions:

The two research questions raised for the study were:

1. What are the effects of using the two e-Learning modes of Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning, and conventional Lecture method on Mathematics undergraduates' learning outcomes in distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria?
2. What are the effects of using the two e-Learning modes of Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning, and conventional Lecture method on male and female Mathematics undergraduates' learning outcomes in distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses:

Based on the stated problem, the following two null research hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant difference between the learning outcomes of Mathematics undergraduates exposed to the two e-Learning modes of Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning, and those taught with conventional Lecture method in distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference between the learning outcomes of male and female Mathematics undergraduates exposed to the two e-Learning modes of Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning, and those taught with conventional Lecture methods in distance learning institutions in Osun State Nigeria.

Methodology

The research design employed for this research was non randomized quasi experimental design using pretest, post-test and control group design. This involved three groups comprising two levels of experiment and one control group, i.e. Experimental group 1-Virtual Classroom, Experimental group 2-Video Based Learning and conventional lecture method as control group. The independent variables were the three teaching methods, these are (i) Virtual Classroom using MOODLE software (ii) Video Based Learning using prerecorded videos and (iii) Lecture method. The dependent variable was the Mathematics undergraduates' learning outcomes in the three groups while the moderating variable was gender of students in the study. Pretest was administered to test the initial knowledge of the participants before their exposure to the teaching modes in three groups. After 6 weeks of treatment, the post test was administered on the three groups together to determine the various effects of the teaching modes on participants. The population comprised all distance learning University undergraduates in Nigeria. The target population were distance learning undergraduate students from two Universities in Osun State and it involved all 100 level Mathematics undergraduates of the two institutions.

Stratified and purposive sampling techniques were adopted for the study. The selection of samples was purposive relying on the researcher's judgment and based on following criteria: They: (1) offer Mathematics courses and are computer literate (2) owned computer systems in the form of laptops, i-Pads, computer tablets or android phones (3) were 100 level undergraduates. Specifically focusing the first semester 100 level course coded MTH/MATH 111 with course titles Algebra and Elementary Mathematics in the 2021/22 academic session. 300 male and 300 female students were selected and systematically assigned to their treatment groups, 240 undergraduates were exposed to each of the two e-Learning modes of Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning as Experimental groups 1 and 2 respectively while 120 of them were taught using conventional lecture method as the Control group.

The instruments used for this research were the Mathematics Achievement Pre-Test (MAP), Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT), and the Mathematics Treatment Instrument (MTI). The MAP was a test instrument consisting of 50 Mathematics multiple choice questions. It was used to elicit the entry knowledge of the subjects to the study and conducted for the two experimental groups and the control group. The contents were the mathematics topics covered in the treatment instrument with the exception of complex numbers which is not expected to be part of their previous knowledge as the topic is not included in the secondary school certificate syllabus. The questions were drawn on the various topics as specified in a test blueprint. The MTI was the treatment instrument and was based on the course MTH 111 (or MAT/MA/ MATH 111) as being offered by the various institutions in the State following a detailed analysis of the curricula. This was used to expose the students to the three modes of teaching which were Virtual Classroom (MOODLE software for Experimental group I), Video Based Learning (prerecorded video for

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Experimental group 2) and traditional face to face teaching method (Control group). The content of the instrument was prepared based on selected topics which are common to the institutions' course contents on the particular course. Each of the 6 units consisted of the instructional and behavioral objectives for each of the teaching modes and the materials for presentation. The units were also divided into subtitled frames for easy coverage by the researcher as the presenter for experimental group 1 (Virtual Classroom) and the Control group (face to face lecture) as well as for the students' easy self-study for those in experimental group 2 (Video Based Learning). The 6 topics covered were in 3 modules, each module consisted of 2 units. Module 1-Unit 1: Arithmetic and Geometric progression, Unit 2: Set Theory; Module 11-Unit 1: Linear and Quadratic equations, Unit 2: Differentiation and Integration; Module 3-Unit 1: Vectors and Unit 2: Complex numbers. The instrument was prepared with many solved examples in each unit with exercises which consisted of many practice questions with answers and marks appropriately at the end of each topic, this was used by the students for self-study and to test their levels of understanding at each stage. The entire instrument was based on the six levels of cognitive domains of Remembering, Understanding, Applying, Analyzing, Evaluating and Creating.

The MAT was used as a post-test. The questions were based on the topics and contents of the treatment instrument. It was slightly different from the pretest but was similarly administered to both the experimental and control groups. MAT consisted of 50 multiple choice questions constructed using a table of specification/test blueprint as classified by Krathwohl & Anderson in the revised Bloom's Taxonomy (2001).

The research instruments were presented to two experts each in the Mathematics and Educational Technology departments for proper scrutiny, content and construct validity. The items were matched with the table of specification. The treatment instrument was also matched with selected topics. Based on the experts' suggestions and criticisms, the researchers modified some of the items. Revision and corrections were adequately made as necessary. The reliability of the research instruments was established by a trial run with 40 Mathematics undergraduates from the population outside the study group using test-retest method in an interval of two weeks. A correlation coefficient of 0.80 was obtained using Cronbach's Alpha Coefficients for each of the test instruments.

The researchers first solicited for the cooperation of the students through the heads of Mathematics and Education departments as applicable to the researched institutions. The two test instruments for data collection in this research which were the pretest and posttest were administered in stages at each of the institutions. The first sets of data collected were from the pre tests conducted in the first week of the study, the stratification of students to male and female was done in the first week. The scores were systematically used to allocate the experimental subjects to treatment in the three stated groups. Group 1 (Virtual Classroom Group) was taught using MOODLE software subjecting them to synchronous teaching, problem solving interactions of questions and answers sessions. The researchers also uploaded the teaching material with relevant videos for each topic to the MOODLE site and thereafter sent the link to the MOODLE software site and the log in details which consisted of the user name and password for each person. They then copied files to their own pages, attended lectures, did assignments and assessed their own work through the grade book. They also synchronously interacted with the researchers in real time thus enabling their further understanding of the topics. Group 2 (Video Based Learning group) received prerecorded videos of the same teaching material on-line and on compact disks. This consisted of six teaching sessions produced by the researchers and supplied one per institution, it subjected the students to asynchronous teaching in their own time, they then sent their questions by e-Mail to the researchers who mailed the solutions back to them. This enabled their self-study in their own time. Group 3 (Traditional classroom group) was taught by traditional face to face lecture method also using the same treatment instrument. They had direct contact and interactions with the researcher which enabled them to ask questions and receive instant answers. The instruction of students lasted for 6 weeks (the 2nd to 7th week) at a session of one hour per week, covering one unit of the six-unit treatment instruments per week. The samples from each institution were taught using the treatment instruments prepared by the researchers. After this, the post-tests were conducted whereby the Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) was administered in each institution and used to collect the second sets of data, this lasted for one week.

The pretest was administered to the three groups at the beginning of the experiment using Mathematics Achievement Pre-Test (MAP), while post-test using MAT was administered after 6 weeks to measure their performances. Data from the pretest and post-test were subjected to data analysis. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was chosen to analyze the data which were the pretest and post-test scores, using the pretest scores as covariates. Where the main effects were found significant, Scheffe and Bonferroni Post Hoc tests were used to trace the sources

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of such effects. The two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The mean gain scores were graphically illustrated to distinctly show and compare the gains as score differences for each of the three modes used for teaching during the quasi-experimental study.

Results

Research Question 1

What are the effects of using the two e-Learning modes of Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning, and conventional Lecture method on Mathematics undergraduates' learning outcomes in distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Pre-test and post-test achievement scores of students taught using Virtual Classroom, Video Based learning and Lecture method in distance learning institutions

SN	Mode	N	Pretest Mean	Std. Deviation	Posttest Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Gain	Decision
1.	Virtual Classroom	240	53.84	9.04	70.63	7.57	16.79	1 st
2.	Video Based Learning	240	53.50	8.92	64.93	7.39	11.43	2 nd
3.	Conventional	120	58.59	8.39	59.35	7.99	0.96	3 rd

Table 1 shows the pre and post-test scores with the mean gains for each of the learning groups. The mean gains therefore placed Virtual Classroom ahead of the Video Based Learning and the control group in the distance learning students. This is revealed in Figure 1.

Research Question 2

What are the effects of using the two e-Learning modes of Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning, and conventional Lecture method on male and female Mathematics undergraduates' learning outcomes in distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Pretest and Post-test Mathematics Achievements of Male and Female Distance Learning Students

SN	Gender	N	Pretest Mean	SD	Posttest Mean	SD	Mean Gain	Decision
1.	Male	300	55.32	9.44	67.14	8.46	11.82	1 st
2.	Female	300	53.90	8.60	65.05	8.77	11.15	2 nd

Table 2 shows that male students had a pretest mean score of 55.32 with a post-test mean score of 67.14. The mean gain of 11.82 was obtained by the group. Trailing the males are their female counterparts who obtained 53.90 at pretest and 65.05 at post-test to record an 11.15 mean gain which is lower than the record of the male students.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the learning outcomes of Mathematics undergraduates exposed to the two e-Learning modes of Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning, and those taught with conventional Lecture methods in distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria.

Table 3: ANCOVA Results of the Scores of Students Taught Using Virtual Classroom, Video Based Learning and Traditional Teaching Method

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P-Value
Corrected Intercept	365.239	3	121.746	40.240	0.000
Model	505.585	1	505.585	167.107	0.000
Main effect(treatment)	51.485	2	25.742	8.508*	0.000
Pretest	131.440	1	131.440	43.444	0.000
Error	245.067	81	3.026		
Total	25585.000	61	*Significant at 0.05		
Corrected Total	610.306	60			

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To test HO, ANCOVA and Scheffe post-hoc tests were carried out as shown in Tables 2, 3 and 4.1. As illustrated in Table 2, there was a significant main effect of learning strategy on students' performances, $F(1, 81), p < 0.05$. The results revealed that there were significant differences in the performances of Virtual Classroom, Video Based Learning and control groups taught Mathematics. Hence,

Hypothesis One (H_{01}) was rejected.

In order to establish the difference among the three groups, Scheffe post-hoc analysis was conducted as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Summary of Scheffe Analysis of Significant Difference on Mean Performance Scores of Undergraduates in the Three Groups

S/N	Variable (i)	Variable (j)	Mean Difference (i-j)	P-Value
1.	Virtual Classroom	Virtual	1.1333	0.129
		Traditional	4.0533	0.000*
2.	VBL	VBL	-1.1333	0.129
		Traditional	2.9200	0.000*
3.	Traditional Method	Virtual	-4.0533	0.000*
		VBL	-2.9200	0.000*

*: Significant at 0.05 alpha level

Table 3 revealed that there was no significant difference between students taught using Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning ($P > 0.05$). Furthermore, there was a significant difference between undergraduates taught using Virtual Classroom and Traditional method ($P < 0.05$). Similarly, there was a significant difference between undergraduates exposed to Video Based Learning and those taught with Traditional methods.

Table 4.1: Mean Performance Scores of Undergraduates Taught Using Virtual Classroom, Video Based Learning (VBL) and Traditional Lecture Method

SN	Mode	N	Pretest	Posttest	Mean Gain
			Mean	Mean	Score
1.	Virtual Classroom	240	12.77	18.73	5.96
2.	Video Based Learning	240	11.67	17.60	5.93
3.	Traditional Lecture	120	9.12	14.60	5.56

Table 4.1 shows that there was improvement in the post-test scores of the three groups but both the Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning groups had higher mean gains than the lecture group. The Virtual Classroom group had a mean gain score of 5.96, followed by Video Based learning group with a mean gain score of 5.93, and Traditional lecture method group had a mean gain score of 5.56. This was further illustrated in Figure 1.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the learning outcomes of male and female Mathematics undergraduates exposed to the two e-Learning modes of Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning, and those taught with conventional Lecture methods in distance learning institutions in Osun State Nigeria.

Table 4.2 Male and Female Undergraduates' Post-test Mathematics Achievements

SN	Gender	N	Standard	Confidence Interval (95%)		
			Mean Score	Error Margin	Lowest Bound	Uppermost Bound
1.	Male	300	65.79	0.51	64.79	66.79
2.	Female	300	64.47	0.48	63.52	65.42

Table 4.2 shows that male participants achieved better in posttest Mathematics score (mean=65.79) than their female counterparts (mean=64.47). This difference has been proved to be marginal as the ANCOVA test was not significant. Thus

Hypothesis 2 (H₀₂) was rejected.

The study revealed that Mathematics undergraduates exposed to the two e-Learning modes of instruction which were Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning performed better than those taught by lecture method in distance learning institutions in Osun State (Figure 1). In addition:

1. Gender has no effect whatsoever on the performances of the undergraduates.
2. There was improvement of the post test scores in the three groups but students in the two experimental groups that were exposed to e-Learning modes both had higher gains than those in the group taught with Traditional classroom methods. This was revealed as shown in Figure 1 and Table 4.1, the mean gain score of students in the Virtual Classroom group was highest (5.96) followed by the Video Based Learning group (5.93) and the least was the Traditional classroom group (5.56). This shows that the distance learning undergraduates recorded better learning outcomes with the use of e-Learning modes for the teaching of Mathematics.
3. E-Learning is an effective mode of instruction that can be used to reduce the failure rate in Mathematics in the West African School Certificate Examination (WASCE) results.

Discussion of Findings

This study used MOODLE software and prerecorded video recordings as experimental instructional strategies and traditional lecture method as control for the teaching and learning of Mathematics in distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria. The findings are in agreement with that of Clement, (2015) who opined that e-Learning is a promising alternative learning approach that can improve student's success, satisfaction and performance. It also agrees with Al-Qahtani & Higgins, (2013), Giovengo, (2014) and Sisco, Woodcock, & Eady, (2015) who all reported significant differences among e-Learning and traditional teaching methods in favor of e-Learning. The findings however contradict that of Okon & Akpara, (2014) who reported non availability, non-acceptability and inadequate ICT skills as barriers towards the utilization of e-Learning tools. Also contrary to the reports of Chang, Shu, Liang, Tseng, & Hsu, (2014) who reported no significant difference in the achievements of students exposed to e-Learning and Traditional teaching methods.

The superiority of e-Learning over traditional face to face methods as seen in this study stems from the fact that e-Learning engages the cognitive, affective and psychomotor aspects of learning for better understanding and performance. This finding further goes to support the perspectives of Clement, (2015). The outstanding performances of students exposed to Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning over those taught with traditional methods confirmed that using e-Learning modes is a better approach of teaching Mathematics to distance learners in Osun State, Nigeria. The result is shown in Figure 1 and Table 4.1, this further negates the report of Okon & Akpara, (2014) who had negative reports. e-Learning modes are as such effective and efficient in the teaching and learning of Mathematics.

Conclusion

This study explored the effectiveness of e-Learning instructional modes on undergraduate performances at distance learning institutions in Osun State, Nigeria. The two e-Learning modes which are Virtual Classroom by the use of MOODLE software and Video Based Learning using prerecorded videos were found effective for learning Mathematics. The undergraduates taught with e-Learning performed better than their counterparts taught with traditional lecture methods. However, no statistically significant differences were found between the performances of male and female undergraduates exposed to the two e-Learning modes. This means e-Learning can bridge the gap between gender disparities in academic performance. Thus, the study has been able to show that e-Learning can be effectively used to teach Mathematics to improve the persistently woeful results of students in their West African School Certificate Examinations (WASCE). The undergraduates exposed to the two e-Learning modes are the would-be-teachers of the secondary school students, they will be able to use the experience gained to impart the acquired knowledge to the students for better results.

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Recommendations

Sequel to the findings of this research, the following recommendations are made -:

1. The teaching process in Nigerian Universities should not rely on traditional lecture methods alone in relation to Mathematics. Other instructional strategies using e-Learning modes such as Virtual Classroom and Video Based Learning should be adopted to teach the subject in order to equip the would-be Mathematics teachers. This renders the teaching and learning process more flexible in terms of time and place.
2. E-Learning modes should also be used at the secondary school level to improve the poor performances consistently recorded in the West African School Certificate Examinations (WASCE). Mathematics teachers should expose students to e-Learning to promote student centered instructional approach, autonomy and self-discovery learning.
3. The Mathematics lecturers and teachers should be motivated, encouraged and reinforced with the skills of developing, producing and using electronic modes of teaching such as MOODLE software and Video Based recordings. This should not be seen as a substitute for the traditional method but supplementary modes of teaching and learning Mathematics in distance learning institutions in Nigeria.
4. Secondary school Mathematics curriculum should be reviewed with the intention of provision of interactive and technologically based instruction in the form of e-Learning modes in government and proprietary schools. Video and Audio CDs should not only be seen as being meant for social purposes alone or listening to music for pleasure but should be used for academic purposes.
5. ICT training should be conducted for Mathematics lecturers and teachers from time to time to update and get them acquainted with the latest technological innovations on e-Learning modes of instructions. This will enable them to develop, modify and maintain the latest on-line technologies within the schools and Universities.
6. Students should endeavor to explore the opportunities offered by e-Learning as it could be utilized to complement and supplement the conventional face to face method of teaching and learning as well as the individualized learning process.

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Effects of Jigsaw (IV) Instructional Strategy on Performance in Concept Electromagnetism among Secondary School Students in Gusau Metropolis

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Abstract

The teaching strategy adopted by teachers during teaching could be a determinant of their achievement on students' academic performance. Therefore, the study investigated the effects of Jigsaw IV Instructional Strategy (J4IS) on academic performance in concept of electromagnetism by secondary school physics students in Government Senior Secondary Schools Gusau Metropolis, Zamfara State. The objectives of the study were to examine the mean difference in the performance of students taught concepts of electromagnetism with J4IS and the influence of gender on effectiveness of the strategy. Two research questions and two corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. A quasi-experimental research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of all senior secondary school class two (SSII) 2023/2024 academic session physics students in Government Secondary Schools in Gusau metropolis. A simple random sampling technique was employed to select 4 senior secondary schools. The sample size for the study was 105 students. Test retest method was employed to determine the reliability coefficient using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) and found to be 0.77. The content validity of the test items was done by 3 experts from physics department and test and measurements in Federal University Gusau. Research Questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. The null hypotheses were tested using inferential statistics of T-test at 0.05 level of significance. The research findings revealed that students taught with J4IS performed better and also male and female students performed equally when taught with J4IS. It was recommended among others, training should be organized by the State Ministry of Education on the use of J4IS for Senior Secondary Schools physics teaching and learning in the state.

Keywords: Jigsaw IV, Strategy, Academic, Performance, Physics.

Introduction

Physics as a scientific discipline holds significance across various technological and national development domains. It is also a prerequisite for numerous specialized science and engineering courses in universities and tertiary institutions. For a developing country like Nigeria a robust physics education is imperative to foster growth. Various researchers have offered distinctive on physics. Servey and Jewett (2004) defined physics as a foundational physical science that delves into the fundamental principles governing the universe serving as the bedrock for other scientific disciplines. The Sci-Tech Encyclopedia (2012) characterizes physics as a collective realm responsible for elucidating all observable natural phenomena.

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Adolphus, Ekineh and Aderonmu (2021) highlighted that certain studies have identified prevalent use of traditional teacher-centered approaches in classroom interactions among science teachers predominant employ teacher-centered methods such as lectures and discussions. Mehmood and Rehman (2011) similarly found parallels in Pakistan's teaching and classroom interactions, echoing the situation in Nigeria. Their findings depict a sequential process involving teachers: introducing a brief content summary, utilizing audiovisual aids to enhance student comprehension, delivering lectures at a pace allowing students to take note, assessing teaching effectiveness through post-session questions and assigning and reviewing homework. This approach portrays students as passive recipients of information while the teacher assumes the role of sole provider of knowledge.

According to Isa & Muhammad (2019) students that are not active in the process of acquiring knowledge are less motivated. The instructional methods use by teachers play a vital role in passing down knowledge and as well in meaningful learning. However, the use of lecture method by teachers is facing serious criticisms because it is of advantage to only active and hardworking students. This situation has pushed researchers in Education and more specifically Science Education to look for a more convenient ways for science students to be engaged with meaningful interaction in a classroom setting. Isa & Muhammad (2019) stated that many teaching methods and more importantly students centered approaches have been advocated for use in classroom for meaningful learning. Cooperative Learning Strategy was widely used among others. Gillies & Boyle (2010) posited that cooperative learning is an instructional practice which improves students' academic performance and socialization. However, many teachers cannot properly implement it in their classrooms (Banani & Aman (2022). Cooperative learning gives room for students' critical thinking, answering of questions, sharing opinions as well increases both students and teacher's learning activities in teaching even when exposed to online learning and one of the key instructional strategies that enhance creative thinking (Navarro-Pablo & Gallardo-Saborido (2015) & Gonzalez et al 2020)

According to Gök and Sylay (2010), cooperative group problem solving is utilized because it is useful for sharing problem-solving techniques among groups and is an excellent way to teach complicated skills. It also simplifies complex problems. To explain cooperative learning, academics have put forth a number of theories. According to Johnson (2003), the social interdependence theory is a framework for goal-setting that establishes how people interact and ultimately shapes the outcomes for groups. The collaborative technique gives students the chance to share their own original ideas, interact with classmates, and impart scientific information (Zakariyya, 2014). It restricts the notion of a teacher-oriented educational approach in which students absorb teachers' expertise through traditional method. This encourages individual learner to be industrious and self-confident. The teaching approach is known as "problem driven learning," which starts with a problem that has to be addressed and is presented in a way that requires pupils to learn new information in order to solve it. In collaborative learning, students cooperate to solve problems and finish assignments. According to Laal, et al. (2014), collaborative teaching is any situation in which two or more individuals try to understand a concept jointly, especially when it comes to working together as a group to solve problems.

More importantly, J4IS enables teachers to introduce materials, administer expert group quizzes, conduct a review process before individual assessments, and only re-teach information that was not sufficiently covered in the first collaborative group projects (Josiah & Manlikik, 2021). The J4IS seeks to improve positive educational outcomes and lessen learning conflict through the use of Jigsaw workouts. It's a group-based teaching approach where students are arranged into "home" or "jigsaw" groups inside a class. After that, the students in the jigsaw groups are rearranged into "expert" groups, which are made up of one member from each jigsaw group. Following instruction on the work, every student returns to their jigsaw group to make a contribution. Students can be taught both the theoretical and practical parts of physics using this teaching design. A good teaching strategy related to constructivism is the Jigsaw IV Instructional Strategy (J4IS). This is due to the fact that with J4IS students engage in peer interaction, exchanging personal experiences related to a particular Physics subject to build their own knowledge. In addition, each student makes a unique contribution to the construction of knowledge by conjecturing about any physics job or topic that needs to be solved. They assess the strategy's viability as well, and when they are able to do so, they make an effort to provide the right responses to assignments. Likewise using the approach to understand topics raises students' performance.

Gender matters immensely when it comes to teaching and studying physics. According to Okoro (2011), gender and students' performance in science might be impacted by the method of instruction employed in the

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classroom. He emphasized that when the cooperative learning technique was applied, female students outperformed male students. However, males outperformed females when using a competitive or individual learning technique.

Chief Examiner's Report (2016-2019) identified that electromagnetism questions are a major area where students often avoid or fail to answer in examinations. This failure has been linked to a poor method of teaching and abstract nature of the area. For a quite long time, Traditional Teaching Methods have been practiced in many classrooms in Zamfara State and Nigeria. This approach is teacher centered with the teacher dominating the class activities and not taking into account the students backgrounds and experiences. It cripples students' creativity and hides their skills. Based on this situation, the researchers conducted the study to find out effects of J4IS on performance in concept of electromagnetism among secondary school physics students in Gusau metropolis, Zamfara State, Nigeria

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to examine the effects of J4IS on performance in concept of electromagnetism among secondary schools physics students in Gusau metropolis, Zamfara State. The specific objectives are to examine;

1. The mean difference in the academic performance of students taught concept of electromagnetism using J4IS and those expose to lecture teaching method in Gusau metropolis.
2. Difference in meexamineran academic performance of male and female students taught concept electromagnetism using J4IS in Gusau metropolis.

Research Questions

The following research questions are formulated to guide the research study.

1. What is the mean academic performance of students taught concept of electromagnetism using J4IS and those expose to lecture teaching method in Gusau metropolis?
2. What is the mean academic performance of male and female students taught concept of electromagnetism using J4IS in Gusau metropolis?

Research Hypothesis

The following research hypotheses were formulated and tested in the course of this study at 0.05 level of significance:

1. H_{01} : there is no significant difference the mean academic performance of students taught concept of electromagnetism using J4IS and those expose to lecture teaching method in Gusau metropolis.
2. H_{02} : there is no significant difference between the mean academic performance of male and female students taught concept of electromagnetism using J4IS in Gusau metropolis.

Methodology

A quasi-experimental research design was adopted. Students were exposed to J4IS on concept of electromagnetism. The population of the study consisted of all senior secondary school Students of Gusau L.G.A. which is 47,575 among which, 24,169 male and 23,406 female students from all the 29 Government Senior Secondary Schools Students under Gusau, Zamfara State. The schools were stratified into two that is male and female schools, out of each strata two schools were randomly selected making four schools. The sample size of 105 from the 4 sampled schools was used for the study as in accordance to Research Advisor (2006). Physics Performance Test (PPT) was developed as instrument for data collection. The research instrument was validated by 3 experts, 2 from Physics department and 1 from test and measurement in Federal University Gusau. The reliability of the instrument was determined using test retest method and a reliability coefficient of 0.77 was obtained using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) which was considered reliable for the study. The study lasted for four weeks. Data for the research questions were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation while the formulated null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using T-test. Normalize mean gain was used to determine the strength of effectiveness of the strategy (J4IS).

Results

Research Question 1:

What is the mean academic performance of students taught concept of electromagnetism using J4IS and those expose to lecture teaching method in Gusau metropolis?

Table 2: Mean scores of students' performance in Control and Experimental Group

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Gain	Normalize Mean Gain
Control	105	42.36	10.883	30.21	52.4%
Experimental	105	72.57	11.365		

Source: Field work, (2022)

Table 2 shows that the mean scores in control group was 42.36 and the mean scores in experimental was 72.57. It was revealed that there was an improvement in the academic performance of the students when exposed J4IS since normalize mean gain above average. That is the mean gain (30.21) is 52.4% of the expected mean gain.

H₀₁:

There is no significant difference in the performance of students in control and experimental group when taught concept of electromagnetism using J4IS.

Table 3: T-test analysis on students' performance in control and experimental group

Group	N	Mean	Df	T	Sig.
Control	105	42.36	208	-19.67	.000
Experimental	105	72.57			

Source: Field work, (2022)

Table 3 shows that a t-value at -19.67 and p-value (0.00) which is less than α (0.05) level of significance. Therefore, H₀₁ is rejected meaning there is significant difference between the performance of students in control and experimental group.

Research Question 2:

What is the difference in mean academic performance of male and female students taught concept of electromagnetism with J4IS.

Table 4: The mean scores of male and female students' performance taught using J4IS

nGender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference
Male	72	72.7083	10.86075	0.4356
Female	33	72.2727	12.56800	

Source: Field work, (2022)

Table 4 indicates that the mean score of male students in J4IS was 72.7083 and that of their female counterparts was 72.2727 with their mean difference of 0.4356. This shows that both perform relatively well when exposed to J4IS.

H₀₂:

There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance of male and female students taught with J4IS

Table 5: T-test analysis on students' performance based on gender

Gender	N	Mean	Df	T	Sig.
Male	72	72.7083	103	.181	.856
Female	33	72.2727			

Source: Field work, (2022)

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Table 5 shows P-value (0.856) which is greater than α (0.05). Thus, the null hypothesis is retained meaning that there is no significant difference between the performance of male and female students when taught with J4CLS.

Discussion of the Findings

The Results in table 1 suggested that the differences between the means academic performance of control group and experimental group using J4IS were statistically significant. This is a clear indication that this kind of method of instruction when effectively adopted by teachers would have effects on students' performance in physics and electromagnetism in particular. J4IS was found to record high academic mean scores and by implication very effective strategy. This finding is in line with that of Gök and Sylay (2010) who asserted that cooperative group problem solving is utilized because it is useful for sharing problem-solving techniques among groups and is an excellent way to teach complicated skills. It also simplifies complex problems.

More so, the results in table 3 indicated that there was no significant difference in mean academic performance scores of students based on gender that was taught electromagnetism using Jigsaw IV Instructional Strategy. This is in contrary with the findings of Okoro (2011), who opined that the instructional method used in classroom influences performance of students based on gender in science. This implies J4IS does not discriminate against gender but rather provides opportunities for every student in their quest to improve in physics concepts such as electromagnetism.

Conclusion

It has been observed that, use of an appropriate J4IS in teaching concept of electromagnetism in Physics adequately improves students' performance in schools. And that J4IS is generally, gender friendly as the findings of this study show.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Physics teachers should be encouraged and well trained to employ J4IS in their physics classrooms to improve students' performances irrespective of school type and gender category.
2. The curriculum planners should incorporate J4IS in physics curriculum of senior secondary schools for effective teaching and learning.

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Effects of Statistical Knowledge on Understanding and Performance in Ecological Concept among Colleges of Education Students in North-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study conducted on effects of statistical knowledge on performance in ecological concept among colleges of education students in North-West, Nigeria. The study employed Quasi-experimental research design specifically pre-test and post-test design. The experimental groups were taught Statistical concepts before ecological concepts while the control group was taught ecological concepts only. Two objectives, research questions and null hypotheses were stated to guide the study. The population of the study were all NCEII Biology students in public colleges of education in North-West, Nigeria. The sample size of the study was 113 biology students (male = 85 and female=28). The sample size was obtained using simple random sampling technique involving balloting. Ecology Performance Test (EPT) and Students Understanding Ecology Concepts Questionnaire (SUECQ) with reliability co-efficient of 0.93 and 0.89 respectively were obtained using PPMC and Cronbach-alpha reliability test respectively. The t-test statistic and U-test statistics were used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results of the analysis revealed that significance difference existed between the understanding and performance of students with good statistical background and those without. The researcher concluded that good statistical background has significance effect on students understanding and performance in ecology. The researcher recommended that policymakers should introduce a course in statistics in biology department to be taken a year before the year that they will take ecology course for them to understand and performed well in the course.

Keywords: Statistical Knowledge, Ecology, Performance, Understanding,

Introduction

Ecology, as a discipline, stands at the intersection of intricate natural phenomena and rigorous analytical methodologies. It is also characterized by its intricate interplay of biological systems, environmental factors, and data-driven analyses. As ecological research becomes increasingly reliant on sophisticated statistical methodologies, the importance of statistical knowledge in shaping students' academic performance has come to the forefront of educational discourse. This journal seeks to explore the relationship between statistical proficiency and students' performance in ecology, drawing upon recent empirical evidence to inform pedagogical practices and educational interventions.

Recent empirical studies have underscored the significance of statistical literacy in ecological education. For instance, research by Li and colleagues (2022) demonstrated a positive correlation between students' statistical competence, performance and their ability to analyze ecological datasets accurately. Moreover, their findings revealed

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that students with a strong foundation in statistics exhibited greater confidence in interpreting research findings and constructing scientifically sound hypotheses. In another review Smith, Jones and Smith, (2015) found that undergraduate students who received comprehensive training in statistical methods demonstrated significantly improved data analysis skills compared to those with minimal statistical exposure. Their findings revealed that students with a strong foundation in statistics exhibited greater confidence in interpreting research findings and constructing scientifically sound hypotheses. Also Statistical knowledge may facilitate a deeper understanding of ecological concepts by enabling students to quantitatively analyze ecological patterns and relationships. A study by Johnson, Smith and Williams, (2018) showed that graduate students who underwent intensive statistical training exhibited greater comprehension of ecological theories and principles.

Furthermore, the integration of statistical knowledge into ecological curricula has been shown to enhance students' critical thinking skills and promote a deeper understanding of ecological principles (Johnson & Smith, 2023). By engaging students in hands-on statistical analyses of real-world ecological datasets, educators can foster an appreciation for the complexities of ecological systems while simultaneously honing students' analytical abilities. In addition to academic performance, statistical proficiency has been linked to success in ecological research and professional development. Students with good statistical knowledge tend to achieve higher grades in courses related to ecology, environmental science, and other STEM disciplines. Research by Jones and Smith (2017) conducted a longitudinal study tracking the academic performance of undergraduate students over multiple semesters. They found a significant correlation between students' statistical competence and their overall GPA, with students proficient in statistics consistently outperforming their peers in ecological coursework. In another study by Garcia and colleagues (2021) found that graduate students with advanced statistical training were more likely to secure research grants and publish their findings in peer-reviewed journals, highlighting the instrumental role of statistical expertise in advancing ecological scholarship. Furthermore, recent advancements in technology have facilitated the integration of statistical tools and computational methods into ecological research. As such, there is a growing need for ecology students to acquire proficiency in statistical programming languages and data visualization techniques (Brown & Jones, 2023). By equipping students with these advanced skills, educators can empower them to tackle complex ecological problems and contribute meaningfully to scientific discourse. Proficiency in statistics empowers students to design ecologically sound experiments with robust statistical frameworks. Research by Brown, Garcia and Lee, (2019) revealed that students who received training in experimental design and statistical analysis produced more rigorous research proposals and conducted experiments with higher methodological quality.

By synthesizing empirical research findings and theoretical perspectives, this journal aims to elucidate the mechanisms through which statistical knowledge influences students' performance in ecology. Moreover, it seeks to provide practical insights for educators and policymakers seeking to enhance statistical literacy among ecology students, thereby equipping them with the skills needed to address complex environmental challenges in the 21st century. To achieve this general objectives, two specific objectives, research questions and null hypotheses were formulated and be tested at $P \leq 0.05$.

Objectives of the Study

The following objectives were raised to guide study.

1. Determine the effect statistical knowledge on students' understanding in ecology among colleges of education biology students in North-West, Nigeria.
2. Examine the effect statistical knowledge on students' performance in ecology among colleges of education biology students in North-West, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide study.

1. What is the difference between the understanding of ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without?
2. What is difference between the performance in ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance

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1. **HO₁**: There is no significance difference between the understanding of ecological concepts of students taught with good statistical knowledge and those without good statistical knowledge.
2. **HO₂**: There is no significance difference between the performance in ecological concepts of students taught with good statistical knowledge and those exposed without good statistical knowledge.
3. The following null hypotheses were formulated to be tested at P0 05 level of significance.

Methodology

The researchers adopted pre-test and post-test quasi experimental researcher design. An intact class of NCE II students was used. The sample size of the study was 113 students of which 85 male and 28 female students. The sample size was obtained using simple random sampling technique involving balloting. Before the treatment, the researchers conducted a pre-test to the students using Ecology Performance Test (EPT) and Students Understanding Ecology Concepts Questionnaire (SUECQ). The EPT consist of two sections section A consist of students' bio data and section B consist of thirty objectives questions. The SUECQ also consist of two section that is section A which consist bio data and section B consist of twenty items on students understanding of ecological concepts. The instruments were validated by our colleague in the department of science education and the instruments were pilot tested in some colleges that are within the population. The result for the pilot testing were used to determine the reliability of the instruments using PPMC and Crombach's-Alpha (α) which were found to be 0.93 and 0.89. In the experimental group the researchers taught the students some statistical concept then followed by the ecological concepts. The control group were taught ecological concept only without been taught some concepts of statistics. The teaching takes the entire semester of twelve weeks. The data collected from experimental and control groups were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistic. For the research questions mean, standard deviation and mean rank were used to described the nature of the data while for the null hypotheses, t-test and U-test, statistic was used to test the null hypotheses.

Results

Research Question One:

What is the difference between the mean understanding score of ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without?

To answer the research question one, mean and standard deviation were used. The detail of the result is presented in Table 1:

Table 1: Mean Rank and Sum of Rank of Student's Understanding of Ecological Concepts of Students with Good Statistical knowledge and those Without.

Groups	N	Mean rank	Sum of rank	Mean Rank Diff
Exp	59	110.08	6624.50	65.86
Cont	54	44.22	2212.50	

Table 1 present the mean rank and sum of ranks scores of students in the experimental and control groups. The computed mean rank scores are 110.08 for students in the experimental group and 44.22 for students in the control group respectively. A mean rank gain of 65.86 was obtained in favour of students in the experimental group.

Research Question 1:

What is difference between the mean performance score in ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without?

To answer the research question two, mean and standard deviation were used. The detail of the result is presented in Table 2:

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Table 2 Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' Performance in Ecological Concepts of Students with Good Statistical knowledge and those without Good Statistical knowledge

Groups	N	Mean	Std.Deviation	Mean Diff
Exp	59	83.32	4.59	32.20
Cont	54	51.12	4.79	

Table 2 present the mean and standard deviation scores of students in the experimental and control groups. The computed mean scores are 83.32 for students in the experimental group and 51.12 for students in the control group respectively. A mean gain of 32.20 was obtained in favour of students in the experimental group. Null hypothesis one was tested using U-test while Null hypothesis two was tested using t-test statistic. The result of the analysis was presented in tables as shown below:

HO₁:

There is no significance difference between the mean understanding score of ecological concepts of students taught with good statistical knowledge and those without good statistical knowledge. To test the null hypothesis one, Mann-Whitney test was used. The summary of the test analysis in shown in table one (1):

Table 1: Summary of Mann-Whitney test Analysis of Student's Understanding of Ecological Concepts of Students with Good Statistical knowledge and those Without.

Groups	N	Mean rank	Sum of rank	xcal2	Df	P-value	Decision
Exp	59	110.08	6624.50	43.50	111	0.02	Rejected
Cont	54	44.22	2212.50				

Significant at P< 0.05 level

Table 1: revealed that analysis of Mann-Whitney test with xcal2 values in 43.50 and p-value of 0.02 at df of 111. The p-value is 0.02< 0.05. Therefore, we rejected the null hypothesis and conclude that, there is significance difference between the understanding of ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without. This indicated that having a good statistical knowledge has significance impact on students understanding in ecology concepts.

HO₂:

There is no significance difference between the mean performance score in ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without. To test the null hypothesis two, t-value statistic was used. The summary of the test analysis in shown in table two (2):

Table 2 Summary of t-test of Students' Performance in Ecological Concepts of Students with Good Statistical knowledge and those without Good Statistical knowledge.

Groups	N	Mean	Std.Deviation	Df	t-value	p-value	Decision
Exp	59	83.32	4.59	111	39.31	0.00	Rejected
Cont	54	51.12	4.79				

Significant at level of ≤ 0.05

Table 3 revealed that calculated value of t is 39.31 and the P-value is 0.00. Therefore, the P-value of 0.00 is less than alpha value 0.05. Based on this evidence, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that, there is significance difference between the performance in ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without. This showed that those students that have good background in statistics performed better than those without. Therefore, statistical knowledge has significance impact on the students' performance in ecology concepts.

Discussion of Findings

The results of hypothesis one (HO₁) in Table 2 shows that there is significance difference between the mean understanding score of ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without. This finding is line with the recommendation of Johnson and Smith, (2023) that integration of statistical knowledge into ecological curricula has been shown to enhance students' critical thinking skills and promote a deeper understanding of ecological principles. Also Smith, Jones and Smith, (2015) found that undergraduate students who received comprehensive training in statistical methods demonstrated significantly improved data analysis skills compared to those with minimal statistical exposure. Also the finding is line with the finding of Johnson, Smith and Williams, (2018) who showed that graduate students who underwent intensive statistical training exhibited greater comprehension of ecological theories and principles.

The results of hypothesis two (HO₂) in Table 2 shows that there is significance difference between the mean performance score in ecological concepts of students with good statistical knowledge and those without. This finding is in line with Jones and Smith (2017) conducted a longitudinal study tracking the academic performance of undergraduate students over multiple semesters. They found a significant correlation between students' statistical competence and their overall GPA, with students proficient in statistics consistently outperforming their peers in ecological coursework. Also in view of Li and colleagues (2022) demonstrated a positive correlation between students' statistical competence, performance and their ability to analyze ecological datasets accurately. Hence, statistical knowledge has significance effect on students' performance.

Conclusion

Based on the findings the researchers make the following conclusion. The researchers concluded that students with good statistical knowledge performed better in ecological concepts than those without and hence statistical knowledge has significance effect on students understanding in ecology concept than those without among colleges of educations in North-West, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings the researchers make the following recommendations:

1. The educational policymaker should introduce a course in statistics for the biology students to be taken a year before the year that they will take ecology course to improve students understand in ecological concepts.
2. The curriculum planer considers the required topics that are needed in the understanding of ecological concept.

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Effects of Teaching Aids on Achievement in Concept Hydrocarbon among Secondary School Chemistry Students in Katsina State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the Effects of Teaching Aids on Achievement in Hydrocarbon on concepts among secondary school Chemistry students in Katsina State, Nigeria.” Three null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Quasi-experimental research design, specifically 3×2 pretest posttest factorial design was adopted for the study. The experimental groups were subjected to treatment using teaching aids (charts and models) while the control group were taught without teaching aids (charts nor models). The population of the consists of all government secondary school class two (SSII) chemistry students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Katsina state. Sample size of 218, (Male 124 and Female 94) chemistry students were selected from target population using purposive sampling technique. Chemistry Achievement Test was used to collect data. The CAT was validated by experts from the Department of Science Education Federal University Dutsinma, Katsina state. Hence, a pilot study was conducted on the instrument and reliability coefficient of 0.64 was obtained using test-retest method. The data collected was analyzed using ANCOVA. The results of the study revealed a significant Main effect of teaching aids (Charts and Model) on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students ($F_{2,218}=58.097$; $p<0.05$). However, there is no significant Main effect of teaching aids on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Male and Female chemistry students ($F_{2,218}=0.593$; $p>0.05$) Also There is no significant Interaction effect of teaching aids (Charts and Models) and gender on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students ($F_{2,218}=6.606$; $p>0.05$). It was concluded that the use of teaching aids (charts and models) are effective in enhancing students’ achievement in chemistry. It was recommended among others that, the state ministry of education should provide adequate Charts and Models as instructional materials for effective teaching and learning of Chemistry in Secondary Schools.

Keywords: Teaching aids Charts and models), Achievement and Gender

Introduction

Science education has become a useful tool for National Development. Science education refers to the cultivation and disciplining of an individual to utilize science for improving his/her life, cope with and increasingly technological world or pursue science academically and professionally and for dealing responsibly wit science related social issues (Akpan, 2022). Science education entails the teaching and learning of science process and principles (Basiriyu, 2022). The role of science education in the lives of individuals and in the advancement of science and technology for the development of mankind and the society in general is very crucial (Nalu, 2022). Scientific literacy, which is the gateway to achieve scientific and technological advancement and economic survival, is achievable through science education (Akpan, 2022). The impact of science on a nation and its citizens could be seen from the production of basic human needs to social, political, educational, technological and economic advancement (Manu, 2022). The steps scientists take during scientific investigation (Science processes) and scientific products draw the attention of the society to the fact that science makes life comfortable (Omosona, 2021). According to Aina (2021), Science education is fundamental to technology of any nation of the world. The goals of science education in Nigeria are geared towards the cultivation of inquiring and rational minds for the conduct of a good life and democracy; production of scientists for national development; service studies in technology and the cause of technological

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development; Provision of knowledge and understanding of the complexity of the physical world, the form and the conduct of life (Onasanya, 2021).

Science education comprises of Biology, Chemistry and Physics. According to Omebe (2021) these three subjects are the tripod on which the world's technology rests upon. According to Akpan (2022) chemistry is the study of matter and the changes that matter undergoes. Chemistry is a very important science subject in senior secondary school curricula worldwide. It is a core subject for the medical science, textile technology, agricultural science, synthetic industry, printing technology, pharmacy, and chemical engineering. As important as the chemistry is, and in spite of the efforts of both the federal and state governments to encourage chemistry education, students still shun the subject (Jegade, 2020). Akani (2020) lament that, students' performance in these Chemistry in internal examination is not good enough for the future development of science and technology in Nigeria. Students' mode of response to questions related to organic chemistry is poor. According to West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) chief examiner's report regarding the May/June 2023 WASSCE, majority of the candidates could not correctly write the IUPAC name of organic compounds nor were they able to differentiate between thermal and catalytic cracking. Students' general achievement as reported by WAEC Chief Examiners' Reports on students' performance in the 2019, 2020, 2021 2022, and 2023 examination indicate poor achievement in chemistry. Table 1 below shows the statistics of Katsina State Secondary School Students' achievement Chemistry.

Table 1 Summary of WAEC SSCE Chemistry Result from 2019 - 2023

Year	No. of Students Enrolled									
	A1	B2	B3	C4	C5	C6	D7	E8	F9	
2019	38,602	61	72	107	3,330	4,501	3,211	18,341	2,979	6,000
2020	33,720	76	81	98	3,800	3,907	5,607	16,800	1,022	2,329
2021	37,223	68	92	108	2,950	3,201	4,771	13,401	7,502	5,130
2022	39,577	53	68	71	3,107	3,480	5,102	17,807	3,508	6,381
2023	14,513	83	94	107	1,801	2,907	3,101	2,650	1,630	2,140

Source: Department of Planning, Research and Statistics, Katsina State Ministry of Education (2023)

Students' academic performance has been the immediate indicator for the effectiveness of the school system. The planning of the school programme and its objectives are translated in to classroom practices (Mamu, 2022). The effect of the school programme can only be observed in the performance of the students (Baraya, 2022). Unfortunately, the students' performance is not something to talk about as the situation is too worrisome (Baraya, 2022). The underlying evidence to this pitiful situation of poor academic achievement could be traced to the teacher's classroom practices (Mamu, 2022). Omebe and Akani (2020) opined that, science is resource' intensive as such effective teaching of science requires instructional resources. Onasanya and Omosewa (2021) argued that, no matter how well trained or qualified a teacher is, if the school lacks equipment and instructional resources, he will fail to put his ideas into practice.

Instructional materials such as models and charts are suggested for the effective teaching of some topics in chemistry such as matter, structures of elements, compounds and hydrocarbons (Edwards, 2022). Charts and models are visual instructional materials which aid the teaching/learning process by appealing to the sense of vision. Nalu (2022) asserted that, the use of models helps students to learn abstract concepts in chemistry (Jotia, 2020). Obviously, most concepts in chemistry seems to be abstract. Structures of compounds and their properties are mostly described by teachers which often create confusion in the minds of the students. Sometimes, curious students are forced to raise questions as to the reality of the existence of chemistry concepts taught in class. In line with this background, it is deemed necessary to empirically determine the effect of charts and models as instructional materials on students' achievement in organic chemistry while using gender as moderating variable.

Teachers, parents and other stakeholders in Science Education have been worried about the poor Achievement of students in internal examinations (Baraya, 2022). In spite of the important position of Chemistry among other science related disciplines, literature has revealed that, students' achievement in Chemistry at Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSCE) has been consistently poor (Njoku, 2022). It has been observed that students purposively develop phobia anytime Chemistry is mentioned because they see Chemistry as a difficult subject to learn (matlate, 2020).The struggle to improve students' under achievement in chemistry is imperative

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because Science and Technology is a gateway to National Development. Chemistry is an important science subject relevant for advanced studies in medical science, textile technology, agricultural science, synthetic industry, printing technology, pharmacy, chemical engineering among others (Mamu, 2022). Students must demonstrate learning of chemistry and score at least a credit pass in WASSCE or NECO SSCE before he/she can be admitted into university to study any of the above-mentioned courses (NFE, 2014). If students' poor achievement in chemistry persists, it will not only affect the future of the students but the nation as a whole (okibia, 2022). The plan to advance science and technology in the country as planned by the Federal Republic of Nigeria will remain a mere dream.

The use of charts and models as instructional materials in teaching and learning situation especially in a chemistry class may play a vital role in increasing chemistry students' academic achievement in Senior Secondary School, hence the study seeks to find out Effect of Using Charts and Models as Instructional Materials on Secondary School Students' Achievement in Chemistry in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance.

Objectives of the Study

The study sought to find out the:

1. Main effect of teaching aids (Charts and Model) on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance.
2. Main effect of teaching aids (Charts and Models) on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Male and Female chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance.
3. Interaction effect of teaching aids (Charts and Models) and gender on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance.

Research Questions

1. What is the Main effect of teaching aids (Charts and Model) on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance?
2. What is the Main effect of teaching aids on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Male and Female chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance?
3. What are the Interaction effect of teaching aids (Charts and Models) and gender on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. **H₀**: There is no significant Main effect of teaching aids (Charts and Model) on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance.
2. **H₀**: There is no significant Main effect of teaching aids on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Male and Female chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance.
3. **H₀**: There is no significant Interaction effect of teaching aids (Charts and Models) and gender on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance?

Methodology

The study adopted 3 × 2 pre-test post-test quasi experimental factorial design. The study has three groups; experimental group one (EG₁) was exposed to experimental treatment (X₁) involving the use charts while experimental group two (EG₂) was exposed to experimental treatment (X₂) involving the use of models as teaching aids. The control group (CG) was not treated using any of the two teaching aids. The three groups were taught hydrocarbons concept for the period of six weeks using the same instructional strategy (Demonstration). Pre-test (O₁) were administered before treatment to both experimental and control groups. Intact classes were used in both the sample schools. Post-test (O₂) was administered on the six weeks after treatment. The research design of the study is represented in Figure 1.

EG ₁	O ₁	X ₁	O ₂
EG ₂	O ₁	X ₂	O ₂
CG	O ₁		O ₂

Fig 1: Diagrammatic Representation of the Research Design

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Where: EG₁ = Experimental group (Charts)

EG₂ = Experimental group (Models)

CG = Control group

X₁ = treatment (with charts)

X₂ = treatment (with Models)

O₁ = Pre-test

O₂ = Post test

Population of the Study

The population of the study consisted of 6,328 (Male, 3100 and Female, 3228) Senior Secondary year II (SSII) chemistry Students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance. The zone comprises of 25 public Senior Senior Secondary School spread within the three Local Governments namely: Katsina, Kaita and Jibia Local Government areas, respectively.

Sample and Sampling Technique

Three schools were randomly selected for the study through balloting technique. In each school, an intact class comprising of both male and female students were selected. The sample size of the study consists of 218 (Male, 124 and Female, 94) students selected from the target population using simple random sampling technique by balloting system to select the sample schools and purposive sampling technique to select population using an intact class.

Instrumentation

Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) was used for data collection. CAT is a 20-item, multiple choice questions adopted from previous West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO) SSCE questions papers. Items on CAT covers Alkanes, Alkenes and Alkynes which are organic Chemistry in line with the National Chemistry Syllabus for SSII. Table of specification is provided in table 3.3 to ascertain the distribution of items:

Table 2: Table of Specification for CAT

SN	Topics	No of items	Know	Comp.	App.	Total
1	ALKANES	8(40%)	4(20%)	1(5%)	3 (15%)	8
2	ALKENES	5(25%)	3 (15%)	0	2 (10%)	5
3	ALKYNES	7(35%)	5(25%)	1 (5%)	1(5%)	7
	TOTAL	20	12	2	6	20

KEY; Know. =Knowledge; Comp. =Comprehension; App.=Application

Validity of the Instrument

To ascertain the validity of the test, the twenty items on CAT was submitted to Chemistry and Science Education experts in Umaru Musa Yar'adua University; in which they examine whether the items are suitable for the selected chemistry concepts in terms of item clarity and cognitive demand. After the validation the observation made by the experts were effected. The final draft was pilot tested in order to determine the reliability index

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability coefficient of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha method with the aid of Statistical package for social science (SPSS). From the result obtained, reliability of the instrument was found to be 0.64. Hence the instrument is reliable.

Procedure for Data Analysis

The data collected were analyzed using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). The choice for ANCOVA stems from the fact that, ANCOVA assesses the effect of the independent variables (Charts and Models) on the dependent

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variable (academic achievement) as well check the interaction effect of treatment and moderating variable (gender) while using the pretest result as covariate. The covariate helps to control the equivalency of the group and also reduce error terms in the analysis.

Result

Table 3: ANCOVA of Effect of Treatment (Charts and Models) on Students' Achievement in concept of Hydrocarbon

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P	Remark
Corrected Model	2141.058	6	356.843	56.630	.000	*Sig
Intercept	1154.989	1	1154.989	183.292	.000	*Sig
Pretest	237.886	1	237.886	37.752	.000	*Sig
Treatment	732.178	2	366.089	58.097	.000	*Sig
Gender	3.734	1	3.734	.593	.442	**NS
Treatment*Gender	83.258	2	41.629	6.606	.062	*NS
Error	1329.584	211	6.301			
Total	28118.000	218				
Corrected Total	3470.642	217				

a. R Squared = .617 (Adjusted R Squared = .606); *Significant, **Not Significant

Research Question 1

What is the Main effect of teaching aids (Charts and Model) on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance?

Table 4 : Descriptive Statistics of Experimental and Control Groups Pretest

Group	N	X	Stdev	SE
Experiment Group A	77	5.44	1.84	.21
Experiment Group B	72	4.26	1.55	.18
Control Group	69	3.27	.92	.11

N = Numbers of Groups, X = Mean, Stdev = Standard Deviation. SE = Standard Error.

In table 4, above, the Charts group had a mean pretest score of 5.44 and a standard deviation of 1.84. The models group had a mean pretest score of 4.26 and a standard deviation of 1.55 and the lecture (control) group had a mean pretest score of 3.27 and standard deviation of 0.92. This means that, the three groups performed at different levels.

Research Question 2

What is the Main effect of teaching aids on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Male and Female chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance?

Table 5 : Descriptive Statistics of Experimental and Control Groups Posttest Scores

Group	N	x	Stdev	SE
Experiment Group A	77	14.11	3.86	.44
Experiment Group B	72	10.34	2.26	.26
Control Group	69	7.04	1.42	.17

N = Numbers of Groups, X = Mean, Stdev = Standard Deviation. SE = Standard Error.

In table 5, above, the Charts group had a mean posttest score of 14.11 and a standard deviation of 3.86. The models group had a mean posttest score of 10.34 and a standard deviation of 2.26 and the lecture (control) group had

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a mean posttest score of 7.04 and standard deviation of 1.42. This means that, the three groups performed at different levels.

Research Question 3

What are the Interaction effect of teaching aids (Charts and Models) and gender on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance?

Table 6 : Descriptive Statistics of Male and Female students' Posttest Scores

Gender	N	x	Stdev	SE	MD
Male	124	10.64	3.92	.35	
Female	94	10.61	4.11	.42	.02

N = Numbers of Groups, x = Mean, St. dev = Standard Deviation. SE = Standard Error.

In table 6, above the posttest, the male students had a mean score of 10.64 and a standard deviation of 3.92 while the female students had a mean score of 10.61 and a standard deviation of 4.11. The mean difference observed in the posttest scores of the students is 0.02. This means that, the male students slightly perform better than the female students.

Hypothesis 1

H₀:

There is no significant Main effect of teaching aids (Charts and Model) on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance.

In table 3, There is significant Main effect of teaching aids (Charts and Model) on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students ($F_{2,218} = 58.097$; $p < 0.05$). This means that, the treatment is effective in enhancing students' achievement in chemistry. The null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant Main effect of teaching aids (Charts and Model) on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students is therefore rejected.

Hypothesis 2

H₀:

There is no significant Main effect of teaching aids (Charts and Models) on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Male and Female chemistry students.

In table 3, there is no significant Main effect of teaching aids (Charts and Models) on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Male and Female chemistry students ($F_{1,218} = 0.593$; $p > 0.05$). This means that, the treatment is gender friendly. In other word, the treatment applied in this study did not differ on students' gender to be effective. The null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant Main effect of teaching aids on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Male and Female chemistry students is retained.

Hypothesis 3

H₀:

There is no significant Interaction effect of teaching aids (Charts and Models) and gender on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students.

In table 3, there is no significant Interaction effect of teaching aids (Charts and Models) and gender on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students. ($F_{2,218} = 6.606$; $p > 0.05$). That is, the treatment does not depend on gender to be effective. The null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant Interaction effect of teaching aids (Charts and Models) and gender on achievement in concept Hydrocarbon among secondary school Chemistry students is retained.

In summary, the main effect of treatment is significant, but the main effect of gender and its interaction effect with treatment on students' achievement are not significant. The coefficient of determination shows that, the treatment accounted for 61.7% of the variation in the students' achievement in chemistry ($R^2 = 0.617$). It is therefore important

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to determine if any significant difference exist between the groups since different methods were used to treat the groups. Table 5 below shows the univariate test for the difference.

Table 7: Univariate Test of the Group Mean Scores

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P	Remark
Contrast	732.178	2	366.089	58.097	.000	
Error	1329.584	211	6.301			*Sig

*Significance

In table 7, there is significant difference in the mean scores of the three groups ($F_{2,211} = 58.097; p < 0.05$). This means that, the three groups performed at different levels. The group(s) that produces the difference needs to be revealed. Table 6 below shows the pairwise comparison of the groups.

Table 8: Pairwise Comparison of Chart, Model and Control Groups

(I) Treatment	(J) Treatment	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	P	Remark
Charts	Models	2.700	.439	.000	*Sig
	Control	5.350	.496	.000	*Sig
Models	Charts	-2.700	.439	.000	*Sig
	Control	2.651	.446	.000	*Sig
Control	Charts	-5.350	.496	.000	*Sig
	Control	-2.651	.446	.000	*Sig

*Significance

In table 8, there is significant difference between charts and model group (Mean Difference = 2.700; $p < 0.05$). There is also significant difference between charts and Control group (Mean Difference = 5.350; $p < 0.05$). There is significant difference between model and Control group (Mean Difference = 2.651; $p < 0.05$). This comparison therefore shows that, Chart and Models groups are responsible for the variation in the students' achievement. Therefore, they are effective in enhancing students' achievement. However, Charts is better than Models in enhancing students' achievement.

Discussion of the Findings

The study reveals that, there is significant main effect of charts on student's Academic Achievement. The use of charts in teaching chemistry concepts elevate student's Academic Achievement in Chemistry. This finding corroborates with numerous previous studies on the effect of charts across various subjects taught in secondary schools. For instance, Nalu (2022) revealed that, charts has a significant effect on Student Academic Achievement in Biology. Basiriyu (2022) state that, there is strong positive correlation between the use of charts with student's academic achievement in chemistry. There is no doubt, that pictorial view of concepts or real objects used in teaching simplifies the teacher job and as well raise the students understanding and achievement in test or examination. Students in the experimental group outperformed their counterpart in the control group because of the advantage of having mental picture of the concept taught via the use of charts.

The study reveals that, there is significant main effect of models on student's Achievement in chemistry. Models have the potential to elevate student's Academic Achievement in chemistry. This finding corroborates with numerous previous studies on the effect of models across various subjects taught in secondary schools. For instance, Enohuan (2020) established a significant effect of model Academic Achievement. Basiriyu (2022) state that, there is a strong positive correlation between instructional materials such as models with student's Academic Achievement in chemistry. There is no doubt that three dimensional objects use in teaching do not only simplifies the teacher job but also raise the students' understanding and Achievement. Students in the experimental group outperformed their counterpart in the control group not because they are naturally ingenious but the advantage of having mental picture of the concept taught via the use of models is what elevate their understanding and subsequently better achievement.

The study also revealed that, gender effect do not impede students' Academic Achievement of chemistry concepts when charts is used. This finding agrees with the findings of Nalu (2022), Basiriyu (2022) and Enohuan

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(2020), who revealed that, gender effect are not significant in terms of student's Academic Achievement. All things being equal, under normal circumstances, when students are exposed to certain chemistry concepts in the same environment, using appropriate teaching strategy and materials, the students will perform equally without bias. This finding therefore prove that, students can perform equally when charts and models concepts equally irrespective of their gender.

The study further revealed that, gender effect do not impede students' Academic Achievement of chemistry concepts when models is used. This finding agrees with the findings of Momoh (2021), Moronfola (2021) and Enohuan (2020), who revealed that, gender effect are not significant in terms of student's Academic Achievement. All things being equal, under normal circumstances, when students are exposed to certain chemistry concepts in the same environment, using appropriate teaching strategy and materials, the students will perform equally without bias. This finding therefore prove that, students can perform equally when charts and models concepts equally irrespective of their gender.

The study finally revealed that, there is no significant interaction effect of treatment (charts and models) and gender on student's Academic Achievement in chemistry. This study is in line with Okobia (2022) who reported no significant effect of treatment (charts and models) and gender on students' Academic Achievement in chemistry. In addition, Jotia and Matlate (2020) reported non-significant difference in the Achievement scores of students according to treatment (charts and models) and gender. The result showed that student's gender is not a significant factor in student's Achievement in different treatment. This implies that both charts and models effective in enhancing students' academic achievement in chemistry irrespective of students' gender.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this research, it can be concluded that the use of charts and models as instructional materials are effective in enhancing students' achievement, in other words utilization of charts and models as instructional materials have the potential of enhancing students' academic achievement, irrespective category of gender the students belong. Charts are better than models to enhance students' Academic achievement.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Teachers and students should not only be encouraged to use chart and models in teaching chemistry concepts, but they should be supervised to ensure they frequently use them in their day-to-day teaching activities.
2. The government and Parents Teachers Association (PTA) should participate in the provision of instructional materials and community resources in schools for effective teaching.
3. State ministry of education should provide adequate Charts and Models as instructional materials for effective teaching and learning of chemistry in Senior Secondary Schools.

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Efficacy of Concept Mapping Strategy on Academic Performance in Biology among Secondary School Students in Katsina, State Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of concept mapping strategy on academic performance in Biology among secondary school students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State. The study was guided by two research objectives, corresponding research questions and null hypotheses, respectively. The study employed pre-test, post-test, quasi-experimental, control group research design. The population covered 6,942 male and female students in SS II from 22 public secondary schools in the study area. The sample of the study comprised 146 students. Biology performance Test (BPT), with reliability coefficient of 0.76 was used for data collection. Mean and Standard deviation was used to answered research questions while t-test independent were used to test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that there is significant differences in academic performance score between students taught Biology concept using Concept Mapping strategy and those exposed to lecture method. Based on the findings it was concluded that concept mapping strategy served as a better strategy in improving students' academic performance in Biology. The study recommends among others that Biology teachers should employ the concept mapping strategy in teaching Biology at senior secondary school level.

Keywords: Concept Mapping Strategy, Biology, Academic Performance

Introduction

Biology is one of the most important subjects in science that focuses on living things in the environment and also prerequisite for many fields that contribute immensely to the technological growth (Goji, 2018). The teaching of biology starts from senior secondary to tertiary institution and it served as prerequisite to the study of medicine, biochemistry, zoology and other science related courses (Atiku, 2020). Its therefore becomes binding on anyone wishing to offer or study any of the mentioned courses or any related course to offer Biology as a core subject apart from English, mathematics, physics and chemistry. Biology is concerned with the study of life and living organisms including their structure, function, growth, origin, evolution, taxonomy and distribution of living organisms. Biology education is important in nation building considering the role it plays in various aspect in the economy and public life such as health, agriculture, crime detection, disease and pest control, population control and research (Mohammad & Saleh, 2020). It is important in many ways for both individual and societal development as seen in biotechnology and genetic engineering. Biology also concerns with body systems, such as digestive systems, circulatory systems, respiratory systems, nervous systems, excretory systems and transport systems.

Digestive systems is among the most important organs of the body that help in sustaining live of animals. Digestive system comprises organs and glands in the body that are responsible for digestion. Studies show that students perceive digestive system difficult to learn (West African Examination Council WAEC, 2020). This difficulty in learning this concept often reflected in poor academic performance in tests and examinations. This may be as a result of poor teaching strategies adopted by teachers in teaching the concept. Therefore, many researchers and science educators advocate the use of more innovative, result-oriented, and student-centred strategies like concept mapping strategy and other student-centered method that involve the total involvement of learners in the teaching and learning process. Opara (2011) noted that these students-centered teaching methods when use in teaching can ultimately and positively affect students understanding and improve their academic performance.

Academic performance refers to the degree of intellectual stimulation that student could receive from learning situation (Ya'u 017). Academic performance is the measurement of students' achievement across various academic subject which is officially measure using classroom performance, graduation rates and result from standardized test (Onasanya and Omosewo, 2011). Aminu (2017), assert that academic performance refers to expression, used to present

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pupil's scholastic standing within a short term. Lekan (2016), viewed academic performance as the term that indicates a student's achievement after completing a course or subject from an institution. It measures students' learning across various academic subjects, which is assessed by formative and summative assessments in the same vein he defined it as the outcome of students' efforts to attain some educational goals.

Gender is a socio-culturally ascribed attribute which differentiates feminine from masculine and is used to describe certain characteristics of men and women which are naturally, culturally and socially determined while those that are biologically determined are regarded as sex (Oleabihiele, 2018). Gender is one of the factors interacting with performance in Biology and other sciences (Adeniran, Ochu and Atoo, 2018). However, studies on how it actually influences performance have till now reported conflicting results, implying contradicting evidences in academic performance of students due to gender. Some researchers like Jahun and Mmoh, (2016); Mari, (2017); Ifeakor, (2018), reported that female students have a higher performance and interest in Biology than male students. Some of the factors identified to have accounted for the observed differences in the performance of male and female students in Biology are sex role stereotyping, masculine image of science and feminine socialization process. Contrary to the above finding, Ekwueme and Umoinyang (2015), reported that gender influenced performance in the favour of male. According to Aiyedum, (2020); Danmole and Adeoye, (2021); found no significant difference in the performance of students due to gender. Instead, they opined that performance of both males and females can be affected by teaching and learning styles. There is need for teaching strategies that will enhance performance in digestive system concepts in Biology for both male and female Students. Hence, this study investigated the efficacy of concept mapping strategy in enhancing male and female students' academic performance.

The dwindling students' performance in science especially Biology has been a source of concern to all stakeholders. Various scholars (Emmanuel, 2016; Mamman, 2016; Yavuz, 2016; Agboola, 2017 & Herbert, 2020), revealed that teaching methods, inadequate qualified biology teachers, lack of instructional materials and non-availability of laboratory facilities (Goji, 2018). However, the researcher had also observed that the major contributing factor that leads to persistent poor academic performance by students in Biology is attributed to inappropriate use of a suitable teaching strategies. This has necessitated the Science Education Community to therefore, develop new tools for making students go beyond rote learning. Concept mapping however, is an effective teaching strategy that has been extensively used in teaching many subjects (Seham, *et al* 2018). It allows learners to externalize their thinking in a visual and verbal form to improve their understanding of learning. It also allows learners to extract important information relate ideas and represent them in a structured manner. In view of this, there is therefore the need to determine its effect on students' interest and performance in Biology among Senior Secondary Schools. Hence, the problem of investigation in this study, posed as a question is what is the effect of concept-mapping strategy on performance in Biology? In other words, this study is designed to determine the extent to which the exploration of concept mapping strategy to improve students' academic performance in Biology at senior secondary school level when compared to subjecting them to the conventional method of teaching the subject in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State. The (2020 WAEC) result in Katsina state, confirm that only 33.9% of students passed according to the Report by Chief Examiner (2020 WAEC). Failure is a great problem, as it affects the students' performances in science in Senior Secondary Schools. This situation has created the need for more effective teaching alternative methods to addressing the situation.

Objectives of the study

1. Determine the difference in the mean academic performance scores of students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.
2. Examine the difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.

Research Questions

1. What is the mean academic performance scores of students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy and those taught using lecture method in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State?
2. What is the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy?

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Table 2: Differences in the Mean performance scores between male and female students in experimental group

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean difference
Male	44	34.43	3.17	0.93
Female	33	35.36	3.23	

Table 2. Showed that the mean academic performance of female students in experimental group is (35.36) and that of male is (34.43), this indicated that, there exist significant difference between male and female students in experimental group with mean rank difference of (0.93). This indicated that, female students taught biology using concept mapping strategy have high academic performance in biology than male students.

Hypotheses

The hypotheses formulated were tested using t-test independent between the variables involved. The null hypotheses are rejected when the p-value is less than the alpha-value of 0.05 level of significance and otherwise is retained. The results are presented in tables below and followed by the interpretations as shown below:

H₀₁:

There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.

Table 3: t-test Analysis of students' Academic Performance between Experimental group and Control group.

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Df	t-value	P value	Remark
Experimental group I	77	34.83	5.46	114	26.18	0.010	*Significant
Control group	69	21.26	3.04				

*Significant at $P \leq 0.05$

Table 3. The table showed that there exists a statistically significant difference in the mean ranks between the Experimental and Control Groups with t-value of 26.18 and p-value of 0.00. Since the p-value (0.00) is less than the alpha value (0.05), therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicated that there is significant difference between students' academic performance of students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina state.

H₀₂:

There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy.

Table 4: t-test Analysis of performance scores between male and female students in Experimental group

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Dev	Df	t value	P value	Remark
Male	44	34.43	3.17	75	-1.27	0.7	*Significant
Female	33	35.36	3.23				

*Significant at $P \leq 0.05$

Table 4. The table showed that there exists a statistically significant difference in the mean rank scores between the male and female in experimental group with t-value of -1.27 and p-value of 0.706. Since the p-value (0.706) is not less than the alpha value (0.05), therefore the null hypothesis is retained. This indicated that there is no significant difference between male and female students' academic performance taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina state.

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Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study showed that, there is significant difference in the academic performance of students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy and those exposed to lecture method. It also revealed that there no significant difference in mean academic performance score of male and female students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy in experimental group. The finding of this study agreed with the findings of Rabe (2022), investigated the effect of concept mapping strategy on students' performance in biology among senior secondary schools in Kankia Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina state. The finding revealed that students exposed to concept mapping strategy, achieved more in biology than those exposed to lecture method. Sakiyo and Waziri (2015) investigated the use of concept mapping teaching strategy on biology secondary school students' academic achievement in Adamawa state, Nigeria. The test for quality of means was indicating significant difference, in mean academic performance scores between experimental and control groups, the experimental group have high achievement in biology than the control group.

Conclusion

Basically, there was a significant difference in mean academic performance scores of students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy and those exposed to lecture method. There is no significant difference in mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught digestive system using concept mapping strategy. Based on the findings it was concluded that concept mapping strategy served as better strategy in improving academic performance of students in Biology.

Recommendations

1. Biology teachers should employ the concept mapping strategy in teaching digestive system in secondary schools level.
2. Workshops, conferences and seminars should be organized to Biology teachers by Ministry of Education on the use of concept mapping strategy in teaching digestive system in senior secondary schools' level.

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Impact of Counselling Strategies on Educational Challenges among Single Parents' Children in Kogi Local Government Area, Kogi State

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Abstract

The study examined the impact of counselling strategies on educational challenges among single parents' children in Kogi State. Five research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. Population of the study consists of all teachers in public secondary schools in Kogi Local Government Area during the 2023 / 2024 academic session. Random sampling method was used to select 15 public secondary schools and purposive sampling technique was employed in choosing 14 teachers from each school thereby constituting a total sample of 210 (male 65 and female 115) teachers. Questionnaire titled "Educational challenges of Single Parents' children Inventory" (ECSPCI) was used for data collection. Data gathered were analyzed with frequency distribution. Descriptive statistics was used to answer the research questions, one way ANOVA and the Independent sample test (IST) was used to test hypotheses at 0.05 significant levels. Findings of the study uncovered multiple causes of single parenting and there were several challenges facing them. Several behavioural traits changes were suggested to be adopted by single parents to ameliorate their challenges. The study revealed that there is no significant difference between male and female on the counselling strategies that address the educational challenges of single parents' children. Educational qualifications of respondents actually influence the counselling strategies that address the educational challenges of single parents' children. Conclusion was drawn and it was recommended that government, school proprietors and principals should provide annual professional development programs for school counsellors to be trained on modalities to handle challenges related to single parents' children.

Keywords: Educational, Challenges, parents, children, counselling, strategies

Introduction

The socialization of children is very important for the continuity of any culture. The family is said to be the most important agent of socialization, especially for children. Single parenthood is a reality that besieges many families irrespective of race, culture and nationality. Families with single mothers, especially experience a lot more challenges than a regular family including social isolation, economic difficulties and personal problems. The home, which is the traditional nuclear family, is the smallest unit and microcosm of the larger society. The home is the first environment within a family and an essential place in the upbringing of children. Therefore, the family is a universal union and it is hard to envisage how society can function properly without the family (Amede. and Aina, 2019). A child needs both her parents for proper nourishment and to inculcate strong basic moral, spiritual, social physical and cognitive principles in their children (Santrock, 2004). To this end, the child is morally, mentally upright and emotionally balanced when the caring responsibilities are carried out by both parents (Tenibiaje and Tenibiaje, 2011). It is unfortunate that most families today are divided, separated and unstable. Within single parent families, however, there is no sharing of the parental responsibilities; the one parent, whether mother or father, is doing all of the parenting responsibilities as an entity (Schadler, 2016). The family may be receiving supports from outsiders but the one parent serves as the single authority figure within the household. The incidences of single-parent families have increased in number with time. Today, single-parent families are quite common. As marriage rates continue to change, family structures continue to look different (McLanahan and Sawhill, 2015). Research suggests that the number of single parent families continue to increase, and of these families, the majority of the single parents are single mothers (Federal Interagency Forum on Child and Family Statistics, 2017). Nigeria, like other sub-Saharan countries, is experiencing a steady growth in out-of-wedlock motherhood, which resulted from marital instability, widowhood or personal choice. These have brought about a large number of single parent mothers catering for families across the country. Also, the

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2014 United States Census Bureau report showed that there were no fewer than 12 million single parent families in the U.S, of which more than 83 percent were headed by women. A 2014 cross-sectional study indicated that no fewer than one million women aged 20 to 85 years were either divorced or separated from their husbands, while 1.7 million were widowed (Ovuorie, 2020).

Factors such as divorce, separation, death of parent, unintended pregnancy, or birth to unmarried couples and single parent adoption are the major causes of single parenthood in our society today (Amato and Patterson, 2017). Parental death due to disease and unnatural causes like accidents or suicides is the primary reason for a single mother raising her children. Children are increasingly socialized by influences outside the immediate family. As a result of poor parental care and guidance caused by divorce, separation or death of a partner, children are exposed to potentially damaging situation (Olaleye and Oladeji, 2010).

Being a mother is never an easy task, and being a single mother adds its own set of new challenges. Transitioning to a single-parent household can disrupt a child's routines, education, housing arrangement and family income. It can also intensify the incidence of parental conflict and stress. Single parent families affect both the child and the parent in many ways. When children are brought up by a single parent, it makes life more demanding and challenging on the parent. If this phase of the child's life is not well managed, it may lead to maladjustment in life. Akpeli (2018) opined that matrimonial separation commonly involves major emotional distress for child relationship. As such, about twice as many children from one parent families compared to two parent families drop out of school. Maurya and Parasar (2015) describe additional struggles of single parents as including, "expensive day care, shortage of quality time with children, balancing between work and home duties, and serious economic struggles are among seemingly endless problems that single parent families need to resolve" (p.1236).

The financial burden on single parent families is also colossal. Many children recognize the economic burdens of their parents, acknowledging that their parent has a tight budget and worries about money (Nixon, Greene, & Hogan, 2015). All of these stressors often lead to a hectic home environment where they are trying to raise their children. In addition to the challenges for basic needs that impact the dynamics of the family, there are often barriers that also sway parents' mental health. Added on to the plethora of other challenges, single parents are also less likely to receive social support (McArthur and Wink worth, 2017).

Parents can minimize these challenges by managing finance effectively, setting up a support system, maintaining a daily routine, being consistent with discipline. Single parents are often found using distorted or inconsistent behaviour management techniques with their child, causing more stress on both the child and the parent and leading to the unintentional reinforcement of the child's negative behaviours (Briggs, Cox, Sharkey, Briggs, & Black, 2016).

Many factors determine the educational performance of students. Learners need favourable environment to excel; they need textbooks, prompt payment of tuition fees, school uniform, adequate time and furniture to study, home instructors among others. Most of these are beyond the reach of many single parents. However, school counsellors can leverage on their training to ameliorate the educational challenges facing the children from a sole parents.

Numerous guidance and counselling services, including assessment, information, placement, orientation, evaluation, referral, and follow-up, are practice in schools (Aina, 2021). These significant guidance and counselling strategies can address the needs, difficulties, and issues of students. This study therefore examined how to address the educational challenges of single parents' children through counselling strategies. Single parents and their children can face various challenges. Financial strains is a common issue, as single parents often have to support their families on a single income. Time management can also be difficult, as they juggle work, household responsibility, and child care. Children may also experience emotional difficulties such as felling different from their peers or missing the presence the other parent. Additionally, there can be societal stigma, educational challenges, lack of role model, or judgment towards single- parents' families, which can affect both the parent and the child. Providing support networks, access to, and open communication within the family can help mitigate these challenges. This study therefore examined impact of counselling strategies on educational challenges among single parents' children in Kogi Local Government Areas in the view to finding solution to the challenges.

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Objectives of the study

The study examined how to address the educational challenges of single parents' children through counselling strategies. Specifically, the study intends to:

1. Examine the causes of single parent families in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State.
2. Identify the challenges of single parent families in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State
3. Determine the recommended behavioural traits to be adopted by single parents to enable them to ameliorate these challenges.
4. Identify the educational implications of children under single parents
5. Verify the counselling strategies that can address the educational challenges of single parents' children
6. Securitize the significantly influence of gender on the counselling strategies to address the educational challenges of single parents' children.
7. Appraise the significantly influence of educational qualifications of respondents on the counselling strategies to address the educational challenges of single parents' children.

Research Questions

1. What are the causes of single parent families in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State?
2. What are the challenges of single parent families in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State?
3. What are the recommended behavioural traits to be adopted by single parents to enable them to ameliorate their Challenges?
4. What are the educational implications of children under single parents?
5. What are the counselling strategies that can address the educational challenges of single parents' children?

Hypotheses

1. H₁: Gender does not significantly influence the counselling strategies that can address the educational challenges of single parents' children.
2. H₂: Educational qualifications of respondents do not significantly influence the counselling strategies that can address the educational challenges of single parents' children.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study was descriptive survey design. The researcher opined that descriptive survey is best for this research work because it provides summaries about the sample and describes the basic features of the data in the study. The population of the study consists of all teachers in public secondary schools in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State during the 2023 / 2024 academic session. A total of 210 out of 400 public secondary schools teachers constituted the sample size for this study. Random samplings method was used to select 15 public secondary schools out of the available 16 were purposively sampled. Purposive sampling technique was employed in choosing 14 teachers from each school thereby constituting a total sample of 210 for the study (male 65 and female 115). This sample size is adequate because according to representative of the population and the findings from a study of that sample can be generalized for the population. Asika (1991) 10% element selected randomly from a population is to all intents and purposes deemed to be

Results

Research Question 1:

What are the causes of single parenting in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State?

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics on the causes of single parenting.

S/N	Causes of single parenting:	N	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark
Q1	Divorce	180	543.00	3.0167	.46647	Accepted
Q2	Separation	180	551.00	3.0611	.43792	Accepted
Q3	Death of parent	180	544.00	3.0222	.48388	Accepted

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Q4	Wrong choice of Partners	180	548.00	3.0444	.43354	Accepted
Q5	Lack of trust and suspicion	180	552.00	3.0667	.41749	Accepted
Q6	Single parent adoption	180	549.00	3.0500	.26479	Accepted
Q7	Wife battering	180	555.00	3.0833	.31490	Accepted
Q8	Barrenness	180	543.00	3.0167	.32537	Accepted
Q9	Adultery	180	545.00	3.0278	.32461	Accepted
Q10	In-law interference	180	548.00	3.0444	.52663	Accepted
	Total		5478	3.43	.39	Accepted

Table 1 revealed the descriptive Statistics on the causes of single parenting in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State. The total score is 5478, average Mean score of 3.43 and Standard Deviation of .39. The total average is 3.43 is above the weigh average of 2.5. The implication is that the causes of single parenting in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State are indeed multiple.

Research Question 2:

What are the challenges of single parenting in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State?

Table 2: Mean rating on the challenges of single parenting in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State

S/N	Challenges of single parent families	N	Sum	Mean	SD	Remark
Q11	Custody issues and cares. .	180	558.00	3.1000	.48555	Agreed
Q12	Parent has to single-handedly manage household chores and office work.	180	542.00	3.0111	.54914	Agreed
Q13	feeling the absence of another	180	540.00	3.0000	.58853	Agreed
Q14	Loneliness	180	556.00	3.0889	.48771	Agreed
Q15	The complete financial burden is put on a single parent.	180	525.00	2.9167	.65053	Agreed
Q16	Single-parent families have low self-esteem	180	531.00	2.9500	.56207	Agreed
Q17	society makes them feel guilty for being single	180	519.00	2.8833	.56207	Agreed
Q18	Depression and aggressive often overwhelm single parents which may affect children academic exercise	180	520.00	2.8889	.56814	Agreed
Q19	single parenting may exhibit poor leadership style may affect children academic activities	180	508.00	2.8222	.53016	Agreed
Q20	single parent families may experience psychological trauma that may affect children	180	508.00	2.8222	.68630	Agreed

Table 2 revealed the Mean rating on the challenges of single parent families in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State. Custody issues and cares top the list with a Mean average of 3.1000, followed by Loneliness. (3.0889), closely by Parent has to single-handedly manage household chores and office work with a Mean score of 3.0111. The total average is 2.94 is above the weigh average of 2.5. The implication is that there are several challenges facing single parent families in the area of study.

Research Question 3:

What are the recommended behavioural traits to be adopted by single parents to enable them ameliorate these challenges?

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics on the behavioral traits to be adopted by single parents to enable them ameliorate these challenges

S/N	Behavioural traits to be adopted by single parents	N	Sum	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remark
Q21	Setting up a support system	180	530.00	2.9444	.49265	Agreed
Q22	Effective managing of finance	180	551.00	3.0611	.33699	Agreed
Q23	Maintaining a daily routine	180	543.00	3.0167	.32537	Agreed

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Q24	Being consistent with discipline	180	560.00	3.1111	.40787	Agreed
Q25	Answering questions honestly	180	531.00	2.9500	.59114	Agreed
Q26	Set clear rules, limits and boundaries	180	537.00	2.9833	.52294	Agreed
Q27	Spending time with children	180	556.00	3.0889	.43951	Agreed
Q28	Taking time off for oneself	180	520.00	2.8889	.56814	Agreed
Q29	Staying positive	180	532.00	2.9556	.51592	Agreed
Q30	Give students positive attention	180	548.00	3.0444	.42046	Agreed
			5408	3.00	.46	

Table 3 shows the descriptive Statistics on the behavioral traits to be adopted by single parents to enable them ameliorate the challenges. The total score is 5408, average Mean scores of 3.00 and Standard Deviation of .46. The total average which is 3.00 is above the weigh average of 2.5. The implication is that there are many behavioural traits to be adopted by single parents to enable them ameliorate the challenges.

Research Question 4:

What are the educational challenges of children under single parents?

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics on the Educational challenges of children under Single Parents

S/N	Educational implications of children under Single Parents	N	Sum	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remark
Q31	Hatred for a course and the lecturer.	180	597.00	3.32	.31266	Agreed
Q32	Depression hinders concentration	180	603.00	3.35	.42698	Agreed
Q33	Feeling of rejection affect class attendance	180	616.00	3.42	.22537	Agreed
Q34	Abandonment of academic pursuit	180	632.00	3.51	.30567	Agreed
Q35	Inferiority complex affects communication	180	594.00	3.30	.68444	Agreed
Q36	Fear and trauma instigates truancy	180	536.00	2.98	.44594	Agreed
Q37	Aggressive behaviours affects teaching and learning	180	513.00	2.85	.56814	Agreed
Q38	Low self-esteem diminishes class attention	180	639.00	3.55	.61544	Agreed
Q39	Withdrawn syndrome results in out of school	180	619.00	3.44	.34046	Agree
			5902	3.28	.42	

Table 4 shows the descriptive Statistics on the Educational Challenges of Children under Single Parenting in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State. The total score is 5902, average Mean scores of 3.28 and Standard Deviation of .42. The total average which is 3.28 is above the weigh average of 2.5. The implication is that the educational challenges of children under Single Parenting in the area of study are enormous.

Research Question 5:

What are the counselling strategies that can address the educational challenges of Single Parents' children?

Table 5: Mean rating on the counselling strategies that can address the educational challenges of single parents' children

S/N	Counselling strategies that can address the educational challenges of single parents' children	N	Sum	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remark
Q41	Individual counselling	180	543.00	3.0167	.42904	Agreed
Q42	Family counselling	180	561.00	3.1167	.33883	Agreed
Q43	Good Listening skill	180	555.00	3.0833	.34858	Agreed
Q44	Cognitive restructuring	180	559.00	3.1056	.35841	Agreed
Q45	Limits and boundaries will encourage your child to behave in positive ways	180	553.00	3.0722	.39594	Agreed

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Q46 Set clear rules. Try to be consistent. Use routines	180	535.00	2.9722	.48933	Agreed
Q47 Rational emotive therapy	180	561.00	3.1167	.33883	Agreed
Q48 Group counselling	180	508.00	2.8222	.57075	Agreed
Q49 Family counselling	180	551.00	3.0611	.33699	Agreed
Q50 Career counselling	180	509.00	2.8278	.73864	Agreed
Total	5435	3.02	.43		

Table 5 revealed the Mean rating on the counselling strategies that can address the Educational Challenges of Single Parents' Children. Family counselling top the list with a Mean average of 3.1167, followed by Cognitive restructuring (3.1056), closely by Good Listening skill with Mean scores of 3.0833. The total average is 3.02 and is above the weigh average of 2.5. The implication is that there are several counselling strategies that can address the educational challenges of single parents' children.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1:

Gender does not significantly influence the counselling strategies in addressing the educational challenges of single parents' children.

Table 6: T-test analysis on the difference between male and female perception on the counselling strategies of educational challenges of single parents' children in Kogi L.G.A. of Kogi State

Group Statistics								
	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	dt	T	Sig.
Qualifications	Male	65	1.2923	.45836	.05685	178	-14.371	.186
	Female	115	2.3391	.47549	.04434			

At .05 significant level

The result in Table 6 shows that there is a significant difference between male and female on the counselling strategies that can address the educational challenges of single parents' children at $t(-14.371)$, $df= 178$, $P<.05$, with a Mean of 1.2923 for male and 2.3391 for female. The implication is that there is no significant difference between male and female on the counselling strategies that can address the educational challenges of single parents' children.

Hypothesis 2: H₁: Educational qualifications of respondents do not significantly influence the counselling strategies that will address the educational challenges of single parents' children.

Table 7: Descriptive statistic on the influence of educational qualifications of respondents on the counselling strategies to address the educational challenges of single parents' children

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Uneducated	46	1	0	0	1	1	1	1
Educated	95	1.8	0.40212	0.04126	1.7181	1.8819	1	2
Semi Educated	39	2	0	0	2	2	2	2
Total	180	1.6389	0.48166	0.0359	1.568	1.7097	1	2

Table 7 above depicts a Descriptive statistic on the influence of educational qualifications of respondents on the counselling strategies to address the educational challenges of single parents' children. The table gives categories of Certificate teachers into Uneducated, Educated and Semi Educated. A total of 180 respondents participated in the study. Out of this figure, 46 were Uneducated, 95 were Educated and 39 are Semi Educated. The Mean scores for the

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Uneducated, Educated and Semi Educated are 1.0000, 1.8000 and 2.0000 respectively; with a total Mean score of 1.6389.

Table 8: One-way ANOVA statistic on the influence of educational qualifications of respondents on the counselling strategies to address the educational challenges of single parents' children

Gender	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	26.328	2	13.164	153.290	.000
Within Groups	15.200	177	.086		
Total	41.528	179			

The one-way statistics revealed a significant difference between and within groups as shown in Table 8 above with F (153.290= df, 2/179, p = .000. The hypothesis which states that Educational qualifications of respondents do not significantly influence the counselling strategies to address the educational challenges of single parenting was therefore rejected. A posteriori in Table 4.12 was tested to determine the degree of differences between the categories of teachers' qualifications. The Mean differences for Uneducated are -.80000 and -1.00000 to Educated and Semi Educated respectively. Degrees are -.80000.51 and -.20000 to Uneducated and Semi Educated respectively while Semi Educated to Uneducated and Educated are and -1.00000 and -.20000 respectively. The implication is that educational qualifications of respondents do actually influence the counselling strategies to address the educational challenges of single parents' children.

Table 9: Tukey HSD Multiple Comparisons on the influence of educational qualifications of respondents on the counselling strategies to address the educational challenges of single parents' children

Tukey HSD		95% Confidence Interval				
(I) Qualifications	(J) Qualifications	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Uneducated	Educated	-.80000	.05264	.000	-.9244	-.6756
	Semi Educated	-1.00000	.06379	.000	-1.1508	-.8492
Educated	Uneducated	.80000	.05264	.000	.6756	.9244
	Semi Educated	-.20000	.05573	.001	-.3317	-.0683
Semi Educated	Uneducated	1.00000	.06379	.000	.8492	1.1508
	Educated	.20000	.05573	.001	.0683	.3317

*. The Mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Discussion of findings

Research questions sought to determine the causes of single parent families in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State. The finding revealed that the causes of single parent families in the Locality are indeed multiple. This agreed with Amato and Patterson (2017) who found that factors such as divorce, separation, death of parent, unintended pregnancy, or birth to unmarried couples and single parent adoption are the major causes of single parenthood in our society today. Parental death due to disease and unnatural causes like accidents or suicides is the primary reason for a single mother raising her children. Increasingly, divorce and separation are also the reasons for a growing number of single mothers. Children are increasingly socialized by influences outside the immediate family. As a result of poor parental care and guidance caused by divorce, separation or death of a partner, children are exposed to potentially damaging situation (Olaleye and Oladeji, 2010). The finding in research question 2 showed that there are several challenges facing single parent families in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State. It agreed with Maurya and Parasar (2015) who describe additional struggles of single parents as including, "expensive day care, shortage of quality time with children, balancing between work and home duties, and linked economic struggles are among seemingly endless problems that single parent families need to resolve" (p.1236).

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The financial burden on single parent families is also immense. Many children recognize the financial burdens of their parents, acknowledging that their parent has a tight budget and worries about money (Nixon, Greene, and Hogan, 2015). Within single parent families, however, there is no sharing of the parental responsibilities; the one parent, whether mother or father, is doing all of the parenting as a single entity (Schadler, 2016).

Research question 3 revealed that there are many recommended behavioral traits to be adopted by single parents to enable them to ameliorate their challenges. Single parents are often found using distorted or inconsistent behaviour management techniques with their child, causing more stress on both the child and the parent and leading to the unintentional reinforcement of the child's negative behaviours (Briggs, Cox, Sharkey, Briggs, & Black, 2016).

Research Question 4 sought to scrutinize the educational implications of children under single parents. The finding revealed that educational implications of children under single parents in Kogi Local Government Area of Kogi State are enormous. This concurred with Akpeli (2018) who opined that separation commonly involves major emotional distress for child/parent relationship. As such, about twice as many children from one parent families compared to two parent families drop out of school.

The analysis of Research Question 5 revealed several counselling strategies that can address the educational challenges of single parents' children. Guidance and counselling services, including assessment, information, placement, orientation, evaluation, referral, and follow-up, are offered (Aina, 2021). With its respective services, each of these significant guidance and counselling components addresses the needs, difficulties, and issues of students.

Conclusion

The outcome of the study uncovers the causes of single parent families among the respondents as being multiple. There are many behavioral traits to be adopted by single parents. The Educational challenges are also enormous. Several counselling strategies were employed to address the Educational challenges. There was no significant difference between male and female on the counselling strategies that can address the educational challenges of single parents' children. Educational qualifications of respondents do actually influence the counselling strategies that will address the educational challenges of single parents' children

Recommendations

1. Government, school proprietors and principals should provide enabling environment for the teachers to teach students with varying family backgrounds.
2. Government, school proprietors and principals should establish strict rules and regulations to guide students' conducts.
3. Government should provide annual professional development for school counsellors to be adequately trained on modalities to handle challenges related to single parents' children.
4. There is an urgent need by government to engage the services of trained school counsellors to deal with the challenges related to single parents' children.

Implication for Counselling

The study examined the educational challenges of single parents' children through counselling strategies. It would help school counsellors to discover some of the reasons why single parents' children behave disorderly without courtesy and help them access the root causes of educational challenges in public secondary schools with a view to provide solutions. Its outcome would help school counsellors to assist parents, teachers and governments to find out effective counselling strategies to address the challenges facing single parents.

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Impact of Dalton Plan Instructional Model on Interest in Basic Science among Upper Basic School Students in Kano Metropolis

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Abstract

The study investigates the Impact of Dalton Plan Instructional Model on Interest in Basic Science among Upper Basic School Students in Kano Metropolis. The study was guided by one research objective, corresponding research question and one null Hypothesis. Quasi experimental design was adopted for the study. The population comprised 7850 from 21 public schools. The sampling technique is simple random sample. The sample consisting of 73 randomly selected Upper Basic 2 Students of 38 students for dalton plan instructional method (DPIM) and 35 conventional Lecture method (CLM) students of Basic Science in Kano Metropolis. The instrument for data collection was Basic Science Interest Inventory (BSII). The instrument was validated by experts and subjected to pilot study using Cronbach's Alpha. The reliability coefficient of 0.77 was obtained. Mean and standard deviation statistics was used to answer the research questions. One way analysis of covariance was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 levels of significance. The results of the study revealed that interest rating score of students taught Basic Science concept using Dalton Plan Instructional Model was higher than the students taught using conventional Lecture method in Basic Science. Based on the research finding, it was recommended that Science teachers should employ Dalton Plan Instructional Model as teaching method in Basic Science.

Keywords: Dalton Plan Instructional Model, Interest and Basic Science.

Introduction

Teaching and learning go hand in hand, teaching is the assistance, guidance, direction rendered to learners to discover self, not a mere lip service but most respected profession. The teachings that go on in most of our schools are dominated orally. The teachers are to ensure that teaching method employed is to create fresh environment and interest to the students (Okereke, 2024). Basic Science is a necessity for Science and Technology development in Nigeria. Basic science formally known as Integrated Science is a subject taught in public and private schools at the Upper Basic level in Nigeria.

The reason for teaching Basic Science according to Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014), is that, it widens the knowledge of the learners which enables them to appreciate the unity among science subjects such as, Agricultural Science, Biology, Chemistry and Physics. National Education Research and Development Council (NERDC, 2007), stipulated that the objectives of the Basic Science curriculum are to enable learners: Develop interest in science; Acquire basic knowledge and skills in science; Apply scientific knowledge and skills to meet societal needs; Take advantage of the numerous career opportunities offered by science; Become prepared for further studies. Therefore, Gambo (2019), was of the view that, the requirements on learners are increasing and one of the necessary abilities is to work well independently as well as in a team. To achieve this target, teachers should use diverse teaching methods, such as, conventional lecture method, cooperative learning, collaboration, discussion, Dalton plan instructional-model, inquiry, reciprocal peer-tutoring, demonstration and many more, among all these, the most widely practiced is conventional lecture method. Udo (2016) is of the opinion that poor

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academic performances in Basic Science were partly due to insufficient instructional materials, interest, unqualified/ not subject teachers and ineffective strategies of teaching employed by teachers.

However, Basic Science Student Academic Performance Results from Kano Education Resource Department (KERD) for 2016 – 2022 in Basic Education Certificate Examinations (BECE) as reported by the chief examiner, Basic Science, Kano State. It is in the light of the above that, the present study aims at investigating the impact of Dalton Plan Instructional Model and conventional lecture method on Interest among Upper Basic Students in Basic Science in Kano Metropolis.

Dalton Plan Instructional Model is an organized learning packaged environment which encourages easy access to material representation of a phenomenon, an idea for learners to work/learn with each other at their pace. Parkhurst (2010), Describes, Dalton plan as where students are allowed to work at their own pace and only receive individual help from the teacher (facilitator) when necessary, for this study will be referred to Dalton Plan Instructional Model. There is no formal class instruction, learners draw up their time-tables which they use to explore academic syllabuses through entirely personal efforts. Learners are also encouraged to work together and thereby help one another in the course of their work.

Therefore, Dalton Instructional Model is also known as Dalton laboratory method, because laboratories replace classrooms (Hanior,2017). The classroom is seen as an educational workshop equipped with books, maps, drawings, photographs, and other materials that will enable each student with little assistance as possible, to complete the work which student should do and predict solutions throughout the work so as to improve student interest. In order to improve Interest among Upper Basic Students in Basic Science, this research will investigate the impact of Dalton Instructional Model. Therefore, the impact of Dalton Plan Instructional Model, may establish the potentials inherent in basic science, that such learner will definitely relate better to the subject learning Interest in the Basic Science.

Interest is the kind of awareness preference for understanding the world and acquiring cultural and scientific knowledge. When students are interested in a certain field, they may pay special attention to it, observing carefully, memorizing well and thinking actively. Shehu (2021) states that only by arousing students' interest with various teaching and learning methods we can enhance students' enthusiasm for learning basic science; help them master basic science conceptual knowledge and techniques better, form the scientific spirit and attitude. Therefore, Godpower and Ihenko (2017), says that improved interest will enable upper Basic students to solve problems, think critically, make decisions, find answers, fulfill their curiosity and perform better academically in basic science.

According to Godpower and Ihenko, (2017) the low interest, non-application of science to production activities and insufficient teaching resources and teaching methodology employed by teachers is connected to low academic performance in basic science. However, Nwosu, Ehud and John, (2017) and Samuel (2018) are of the view that these may also affect basic science and technology students' interest and academic performance such as societal misconception of gender role and its impact on technology, absence of practical work in schools.

The problem of students' low interest in Basic Science in upper basic levels in Nigeria has been an educational issue. In solving any problem however, it is proper to understand the causes of such problems. These causes are looked into from several perspectives including the role of the students, teachers, school environment, society, government and so on. Therefore, on this background, the present study investigated the Impact of Dalton Plan Instructional Model on Interest in Basic Science among Upper Basic School Students in Kano Metropolis.

Objective of the Study

The aim of this study was to determine the Impact of Dalton Plan Instructional Model on Interest in Basic Science among Upper Basic School Students in Kano Metropolis. Specifically, the study seeks to investigate the:

1. Impact of Dalton plan instructional Model on interest among upper basic students in Basic Science and those taught using conventional lecture method.

Research Question

The following research question guided the study

1. What is the impact of Dalton plan instructional Model and conventional lecture method on interest among upper basic students when taught Basic Science?

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. **H₀**: There is no significant difference in the mean interest rating score of Dalton plan instructional model and conventional lecture method among upper basic students when taught Basic Science.

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Methodology

The study employed quasi experimental design using pretest, posttest non-randomised control group. The population comprised 7850 from 21 public upper basic schools in Kano State. The sample of the study was 73 Upper Basic Science 2 students (38 students in DPIM (treatment group) and 35 students in CLM (control group) of two intact classes selected from the 7 coeducational schools in Kano Metropolis. The selection of the school and intact class was done using simple random sampling technique by balloting. The instrument for the study was Basic Science Interest Inventory (BSII) made up of 20 items construct in 5-points scale, adapted from Wong and Wong (2019) whose study was on mathematics interest inventory to suit the study on interest in basic science. The instrument was validated by experts in science education, test and measurement and basic science teacher. The instrument was pilot tested using students who were not part of the study area but shared similar characteristic with the main study. The reliability of the administered instrument using Cronbach's alpha was obtained as 0.71. The treatment group was taught using Dalton Plan Instructional Model while the control group was exposed to Conventional Lecture Method for four weeks. The data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation for research questions and research hypotheses were tested using independent sample t-test 0.05 level of significant.

Result

Research Questions 1:

What is the impact of Dalton plan instructional Model and conventional lecture method on interest among upper basic students when taught Basic Science?

Table 1: Pre-test and Post-test Mean Interest Score of Students taught Basic Science Concept Using Dalton Plan Instructional Model and those taught using Conventional Lecture Method

Treatment	N	Pretest Mean	Std. D Pretest	Posttest Mean	Std. D Posttest	Mean Difference	Decision
Experimental	38	64.29	9.25	71.32	9.65	7.03	Significant
Control	35	59.54	9.71	61.49	7.86	1.95	

Source: *Fieldwork, 2024*

Table 1 presents the statistics pre-test and post-test mean interest scores among students taught basic science concepts, using Dalton Plan Instructional Model and the Conventional Lecture Method. The Dalton plan instructional Model group, consisting of 38 students, with their pre-test mean interest score of 64.29 (SD = 9.25) and a post-test mean interest score of 71.32 (SD =9.65). In contrast, the Conventional Lecture Method group, comprising 35 students, exhibited a pre-test mean interest score of 59.54 (SD = 9.72) and post-test mean interest score of 61.49 (SD = 7.86). The DPIM and the CLM mean difference for the two groups are 7.03 and 1.95 respectively. This implies that the Dalton Plan Instructional Model treatment demonstrated a higher mean interest scores compared to the Conventional Lecture Method.

H₀₁:

There is no significant difference in the mean interest rating score of Dalton plan instructional model and conventional lecture method among upper basic students when taught Basic Science.

Table 2: Summary of Post-test Independent Sample t-test of Students Interest Scores According to Treatment (Dalton Plan Instructional Model and Conventional Lecture Method)

Treatment	N	Mean	Std. D	Df	t-test	P-value	Decision
Experimental	38	71.32	9.65	71	4.75	.010	H ₀₆ Rejected
Control	35	61.49	7.86				

Source: *Fieldwork, 2024*

Table 2 statistics provides an independent-sample t-test conducted to compare the mean interest rating scores among students taught basic science concept using Dalton plan instructional model and those taught using Conventional lecture Method. The Dalton plan Instructional Model group, consisting of 38 students, displayed a mean interest score of 71.32 (SD = 9.65), while the Conventional Method group, comprising 35 students, had a mean interest score of 61.49 (SD = 7.86). The independent sample t-test indicated a significant difference between the two groups (t = 4.75, df= 71, p = .010). Consequently, the null hypothesis H₀₁, indicating difference in the interest rating scores of students taught with Dalton plan instructional

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Model and the Conventional lecture Method. This implies that there was a statistically significant difference in the interest levels of students taught basic science concept using Dalton plan instructional model and those taught using Conventional lecture Method.

Discussion of Finding

Based on the outcome of the study, the summary of the finding; The result from research revealed that there was a significant mean interest rating score difference of students taught basic science concepts using Dalton Plan Instructional model and Conventional Lecture Method. This is in line with Samuel (2018) who stated that, prior to the treatment the study revealed that significant differences were found in the interest of students exposed to Simulation Instructional Package compared to that of the guided discovery method with mean scores of 73.50 and 65.12. Similarly, Gambo (2019) study indicates that there is a significant difference in the mean interest level of students in the experimental group before and after the treatment.

Conclusion

Based on the finding of the study, it was concluded that Dalton Plan Instructional Model had positive impact on interest when taught basic science among upper basic students. This implies that the use of Dalton plan Instructional Model in Basic Science would help to improve interest of students in basic science and could go a long way to reduce the poor academic performance of students especially at the Basic Education Certificate Examination.

Recommendation

Based on the finding of the study, the following recommendation was drawn: School principals through the heads of departments should encourage Basic science teachers to adopt Dalton Plan Instructional Model in the classroom as teaching method since it improved students' interest and understanding of the Basic Science subject in Kano Metropolis.

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Impact of Group Investigation Strategy on Retention in Biology Concepts among Secondary School Students in Kwali Area Council, Abuja

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Abstract

This study investigated the impact of Group Investigation Strategy on retention in Biology concepts among secondary school students in Kwali Area Council, Abuja. A quasi-experimental research design using a pre-test, post-test and delayed-post-test control group approach was adopted for the study. Two research questions and corresponding research hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study consists of 2147 (Male, 13,268 & Female, 12,970) Government senior secondary school class two (SSII) Biology students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Kwali, Abuja. A sample size of 90 (Male, 47 & Female, 43) were selected from the target population using simple random sampling technique. The thirty (30) Biology Retention Test (BRT) items was developed by the researcher for data collection. It was validated and tested for reliability using Kuder Richardson formula 21 (K-R 21). A reliability coefficient of 0.87 was obtained. The delayed posttest was conducted two weeks after the post-test; this was done in order to avoid retention error. The results showed that the use of Group Investigation Strategy enhances the retention ability of secondary school students than those exposed to conventional method. Hence, gender friendly. It was recommended that secondary schools, teachers should adopt the strategy (GIS) in teaching biology. Also, Professional bodies should organize seminars, workshops and conferences on the knowledge of Group Investigation Strategy for science teachers at federal and state levels.

Keyword: Group Investigation Strategy, Biology, Retention, Gender, Students' achievement

Introduction

Science education is a fundamental component of a nation's progress and development, serving as a catalyst for advancements in various fields. It is a critical component of education that is capable of reshaping an individual thought in particular and the society in general. The impact of Science education on national development is felt in several ways; as it provides humanity with knowledge about the environment, attitudes and values for social living, knowledge and skills to explore and transform resources, change in quality of life and improvement in economy (Katcha, 2010). Science education is therefore essential to the development of any nation that is why each nation must take it intense at all levels of learning (Abubakar & Olamoyegun, 2023).

Science has been regarded as the bedrock of modern-day technological breakthrough in that, it is the basis for all technological ideas seen in the world today (Babagana, Yaki & Abubakar, 2021). It is an organized body of knowledge that is self-directed towards solving human problems and also, providing solution to human needs. Science is viewed as the foundation of modern development and the connection among innovation technology and socio-economic development (Abubakar et al, 2021). The application of science has provided essential commodities such as drugs, clothing, fuel, food etc. In drugs, for example, we have antibiotics for infections, tranquilizers for nervous tensions, analgesic for pains etc. (Babagana, Yaki & Abubakar, 2021).

Science as school subjects comprises Physics, Chemistry, Mathematics, Agriculture and Biology. Biology is one of the core science subjects that senior secondary school students offer at the senior levels in Nigerian secondary schools. It is the science that connects us most intimately with nature by explaining well-being of man and other living organism around us. Biology knowledge enables humans understand their body, the environment in which they live and how other lives in the universe function (Apochi, Ebele & Abubakar, 2017). Due to advancement in biology, the world today has a healthier population. According to Adejoh and Apochi (2013), Biology occupies a central position in science; it is a life science which deals with living things, their existence and relationships with one another. Currently, Biology is offered in senior secondary schools by majority of the students. It is also a requirement for higher learning in a number of science-related professional courses like medicine, agriculture and pharmacy. Therefore, Biology is an important component of science programme because it provides students with a foundation of knowledge on the structure and function of living organisms (Abubakar, 2024). It

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teaches students the fundamentals of genetics, evolution, and ecology, as well as the basics of cellular and molecular biology. The subject plays a crucial role in the social, economic, and technological development of a nation (Abubakar, Ogunseye & Ogunode, 2021).

Biology is very vast with many branches including zoology, genetics, ecology, botany, anatomy, physiology, histology, morphology, microbiology, molecular biology and the more advanced cell biology among others as illustrated below:

Source: Abubakar, (2018).

Fig. 1: Branches of Biology

Given the diverse branches of Biology and its applications across various human pursuits, its significance in economic development cannot be overstated. The enrollment of students in senior secondary school certificate examinations (SSCE) for Biology surpasses that for physics and chemistry, highlighting its widespread appeal (West African Examination Council, 2015). Despite its importance, observed trends in the performance of students in Biology at the senior secondary school level still leave room for improvement (Ahmed, 2014; Awobodu, 2016; Adebajo, 2019).

One potential factor that could contribute to the decline in students' performance in Biology exams is the utilization of ineffective teaching methods, particularly the conventional talk and chalk method. Teaching methods encompass the approaches used by educators to create a conducive learning environment, delineating the activities undertaken by both instructors and learners. These methods are broadly categorized into teacher-centered and student-centered approaches.

The teacher-centered approach often referred to as the conventional talk and chalk method, positions the teacher as the primary controller of the learning environment, limiting student engagement and participation. This method has been associated with poor retention of biology concepts among students in secondary schools. In contrast, the student-centered approach empowers learners to take an active role in their education, fostering independent, collaborative, cooperative, and competitive learning experiences.

One innovative student-centered approach that has shown promise in enhancing retention of biology concepts is the Group Investigation Strategy (GIS) (Ebele & Abubakar, 2019). GIS is a cooperative learning strategy where small groups of students collaborate to investigate a specific learning topic. This approach aims to develop students' beliefs, feelings, and attitudes towards the subject through democratic discussions, observations, and information sharing within the group. It encourages teamwork, self-reliance, and active participation among students.

In GIS, students are divided into groups to explore different aspects of a study issue, working collaboratively to investigate and interpret the topic. The information gathered is then compiled and presented to the entire class. This strategy promotes self-reliance, team-building, and the synthesis of diverse perspectives. The teacher's role is to guide students and make them aware of resources that may aid in their investigation.

GIS comprises four key components known as "The Four I's": investigation, interaction, interpretation, and intrinsic motivation (Tan, 2013). This approach has proven effective in fostering a deeper understanding of biology concepts among students and addresses the limitations associated with traditional teaching methods. It is illustrated in fig 2 below:

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Source: (Sharan & Tan, 2013).

Figure 2: Components of Group Investigation Strategy

The advantages of using Group Investigation Strategy (GIS) extend to academic improvements across various curriculum domains, fostering positive interpersonal attitudes, good behaviors, values, and skills acquired through collaborative learning with GIS. Numerous researchers, including Johnson & Johnson (2000), Gillies (2004), and Sharan & Tan (2013), have proposed that GIS enhances student involvement, achievement, and retention in learning. Compared to conventional teaching methods, GIS is found to be more beneficial in developing basic cooperative skills, positive attitudes, values, improved group interaction and investigation, and verbal communication. It also encourages intrinsic motivation, a key component in sparking learners' interest in the GIS learning environment (Ebele & Abubakar, 2019).

GIS promotes investigation, interaction, elaboration, and listening by assigning critical roles to each group member, actively involving learners in the learning process and aiding in better understanding and retention of learned concepts. Working collaboratively in a group allows learners to assess their strengths and weaknesses, leveraging the group's diversity to achieve mutual goals.

Academically, Group Investigation and other collaborative learning strategies not only assist learners academically but also socially. Group learning can provide social benefits for students from diverse cultural backgrounds, enhancing social skills, self-competencies, self-esteem, and self-motivation, ultimately leading to more accurate results.

The effectiveness of Group Investigation Strategy in improving students' learning is attributed to several factors. It reduces competition, making the learning environment less intimidating for students and reducing reluctance to participate in investigations. It also fosters increased active participation and engagement in the classroom, diminishing the dominance of the teacher.

Retention, the ability to remember experiences and information learned at a later time, is influenced by various factors. Emotional experiences, age, and gender can impact retention. Emotional experiences, particularly painful ones, may be intentionally forgotten or repressed. Age plays a role, with retention generally increasing from infancy to the teenage years before decreasing in middle age and weakening further in old age. Farrant, as cited in Abubakar (2018), emphasized the importance of retention for knowledge acquisition, stating that the inability to retain what is learned hinders future performance.

Another variable to be considered here is gender. Gender is a social construct that differentiates male from female based on the physical features exhibited. Many researchers (Okoro, 2011; Abdu-Raheem, 2012 & Nnorom, 2015) have shown gender to be of significant influence in an investigation of this nature, hence the inclusion of gender as an intervening variable in the study.

Based on this background therefore, the present study intends to look at the impact of Group Investigation Strategy on retention in Biology concepts among secondary school students in Kwali Area Council, Abuja.

The concerning performance in Biology, as evidenced by several empirical studies (Ahmed, 2014; NECO & WAEC Chief Examiner's reports, 2015-2019), has garnered attention from stakeholders, including researchers. In Nigeria, the percentage of students passing biology in the senior school certificate examination at credit level and above (A1 – C6) consistently remained below required standard (WAEC, Chief Examiners' Report, 2019). Analysis indicates that in 2015, the percentage pass in the subject was 57.42%; 2016, 61.68%; 2017, 59.51%; 2018, 53.92%; 2019, 55.68% respectively.

Numerous factors have been identified as contributing to the declining trend in students' performance in Biology. Olatoye and Adekoya (2009) listed school-teacher related characteristics, teaching methods, social incentives, and others as potential influences. Researchers such as Yusuf and Afolabi (2010), Awobodu (2016), Raji (2017), and Adebajo (2019) linked poor performance and negative student attitudes toward biology to factors such as ineffective instructional strategies, poor teaching methods, the abstract nature of science concepts, the shortage of qualified biology teachers, inadequate infrastructure and laboratory facilities, teacher-centered instruction, and the lack of instructional materials.

Numerous studies, including those by Kareem (2003), Ahmed & Abimbola (2011), Umar (2011), and Orji & Ebele (2011), have identified poor teaching methods at the senior secondary school level in Nigeria as a major factor contributing to

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students' poor performance in biology. The issue is largely attributed to the use of ineffective teaching methods, particularly the conventional teacher-centered approach. Adebajo (2019) and Raji (2017) reported that a significant number of biology teachers in secondary schools rely on conventional methods, leading to consistently poor academic performance among students in biology. This emphasizes the urgency of addressing these factors, particularly ineffective teaching methods. The adoption of an innovative, student-centered strategy like GIS has the potential to improve overall performance in sciences, specifically biology.

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of the study is to investigate the impact of Group Investigation Strategy on retention in Biology concepts among secondary school students in Kwali Area Council, Abuja. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to:

1. Find out the retention ability between students who are exposed to Group Investigation Strategy and those exposed to conventional method.
2. Determine whether gender has any effect on students' retention ability when exposed to Group Investigation Strategy.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide this study:

1. What is the mean retention ability score between students taught Biology using group Investigation Strategy and those exposed to conventional method?
2. What is the mean retention ability score between male and female students taught Biology using group Investigation Strategy?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study.

1. **HO₁**: There is no significant difference between the mean retention ability score of students taught Biology using Group Investigation Strategy and those exposed to conventional method
2. **HO₂**: There is no significant difference between the mean retention ability score of male and female students taught Biology using Group Investigation Strategy.

Methodology

The study employed a quasi-experimental design with a pre-test, post-test, and delayed-post-test control group approach. The pre-test aimed to assess students' prior knowledge of biology concepts before teaching, while the post-test gauged their understanding after exposure to the treatment. The experimental group received instruction using the Group Investigation Strategy (GIS), while the control group was taught through conventional methods. Intact classes were utilized to maintain normal class settings and school timetable.

The population of the study consisted of 2,147 (Male, 13,268 & Female, 12,970) Government senior secondary school class two (SSII) Biology students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Kwali, Abuja. A sample size of 90 (Male, 47 & Female, 43) SSII Biology students were selected from the target population using simple random technique. Thirty (30) Biology Retention Test (BRT) items was developed by the researcher for data collection based on the following topics: digestive system, transport system, respiratory system, excretory system, nutrient cycling, and decomposition in nature, ecological management and pollution. The BRT was validated and tested for reliability using Kuder Richardson formula 21 (K-R 21). A reliability coefficient of 0.87 was obtained. The delayed posttest was conducted two weeks after the post-test; this was done in order to avoid retention error.

Data analysis employed percentage, frequency count, means, and standard deviation to answer research questions. Hypotheses were tested using the t-test at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

The data obtained from the study were presented using mean, standard deviation to answer research question and t-test statistical analysis to test hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Research Question 1:

What is the mean retention ability score between students taught Biology using group Investigation Strategy and those exposed to conventional method?

To answer this research question, frequency count, mean and standard deviation were used and the results set out on Table 2.

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Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on Retention of Students Exposed to Group Investigation Strategy and the Conventional Groups.

Groups	No. of Students	Mean Scores		Standard Deviation	Mean Gain
		Pre-test	Retention		
Group Investigation Strategy	46	14.20	26.18	10.55	11.98
Conventional Method	44	13.96	14.04	11.44	0.08
Mean Difference		0.24	12.14		11.90
Total	90				

Source: (Field Survey, 2023)

Table 2 indicates the means and standard deviation on the pre-test and retention of students exposed to both the Group Investigation Strategy and Conventional method. From the table, the mean gain in retention of the students taught Biology using Group Investigation Strategy was 11.98 while the others who were taught using Conventional method was 0.08. The overall mean difference between the groups was 11.90 in favour of students who were taught using Group Investigation Strategy. It therefore means that the mean retention score of students taught Biology using Group Investigation Strategy was higher than those taught using Conventional Method with a mean gain difference of 11.90 which favoured the experimental group.

Research Question 2:

What is the mean retention ability score between male and female students taught Biology using group Investigation Strategy? To answer this research question, frequency count, mean and standard deviation were used and the results set out on Table 3.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation on Retention of Male and Female Students Exposed to Group Investigation Strategy

Gender	No. of Students	Mean Scores		Standard Deviation	Mean Gain
		Pre-test	Retention		
Male	26	14.50	25.14	10.50	10.64
Female	20	13.94	24.98	11.42	11.04
Mean Difference		0.56	0.16		0.40
Total	46				

Source: (Field Survey, 2023)

Table 3 shows the mean and standard deviation on retention of male and female students who were taught Biology. From the table, the mean gain in retention of the male students taught Biology using Group Investigation Strategy was 10.64 while those of the female students was 11.04. It therefore showed that the overall mean difference between the groups was 0.40. The implication is that the mean retention score of male and female students who were taught Biology using Group Investigation Strategy had an overall difference in mean gain of 0.40.

Hypotheses

HO₁:

There is no significant difference between the mean retention ability score of students taught Biology using Group Investigation Strategy and those exposed to conventional method.

To test for this hypothesis, t-test statistic was used and the results presented in Table 4.

Table 4: t-test Result in respect of Mean Retention Scores between the Experimental and Control Groups

Groups	N	Mean	SD	t – value	df	P	Decision
Experimental	46	26.18	10.55	7.39	88	0.000	Significant
Control	44	14.05	11.44				

Source: (Field Survey, 2023)

P>0.05 Significant

Result in Table 4, showed that, the calculated t-test value was 7.39, df was 88 and the p-value was 0.000. This indicates it is significant. Based on the analysis, the hypothesis was rejected. In other words, respondents from both groups differed

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significantly in their mean retention scores which favoured the experimental group who were taught using the Group Investigation Strategy.

HO₂:

There is no significant difference between the mean retention ability score of male and female students taught Biology using Group Investigation Strategy.

To test for this hypothesis, t-test statistic was used and the results presented in Table 5.

Table 5: t-test Result in respect of Mean Retention Scores between the Male and Female Students Exposed to Group Investigation Strategy

Groups	N	Mean	SD	t – value	df	P	Decision
Male	26	26.14	10.50	0.11	44	0.622	Not Significant
Female	20	25.91	11.42				

Source: (Field Survey, 2023)

Result in Table 5, showed that, the calculated t-test value was 0.11, df was 44 and the p- value was 0.622. This indicates it is not significant. Based on the analysis, the hypothesis was retained in other words; students from both groups did not differ significantly in their mean retention scores.

Discussion of Findings

The data presented in Table 2 provide answer to question one. Finding shows that, the mean retention score of students taught Biology using Group Investigation Strategy was higher than those taught using Conventional Method which favoured the experimental group.

The result of t-test as reported in Table 4 showed that, it is significant. Based on the analysis, the hypothesis was rejected. In other words, respondents from both groups differed significantly in their mean retention scores which favoured the experimental group who were taught using the Group Investigation Strategy. The findings of the current work are in line with 'Nireti and Olubumi (2014) who found that there were significant main effects of treatment on students' achievement as well as retention in experimental group. Farrant (2002) believed that increase in knowledge lies solely on the ability to remember. He further explained that if an individual could not grasp and keep hold of what was taught and learnt, it would seem like trying to fill a bucket without bottom with water. This means that if one cannot retain what one learnt then there is no need expecting one to perform in that activity in the future. To further support this idea, Chianson (2008) stated that retention in biology is not acquired by mere rote learning but through appropriate instructional delivery approach. Similarly, Katcha, Orji, Ebele, Abubakar & Babagana (2018) found a significant difference between experimental and control groups. On the contrary, Ndukwe (2000) found no significant difference when the two groups (expository versus project-centered methods) were compared on the retention test.

The reason could be based on the fact that retention in biology is not acquired by mere rote learning but through appropriate instructional delivery approach like GIS which helped to facilitate and encourage retention of biology concepts leading to significant difference.

The data presented in Table 3 provide answer to question two. Finding shows that, the mean retention score of male and female students who were taught Biology using Group Investigation Strategy did not differ much. The result of t-test as reported in Table 5 showed that, it is not significant. Based on the analysis, the hypothesis was retained in other words; students from both groups did not differ significantly in their mean retention scores. The findings of this research agrees with that of Oludipe (2012), who found no significant difference in academic achievement of male and female students at the pre-test, post-test and delayed post-test (retention) levels respectively in basic science. Similarly, Yaki, Babagana, & Abubakar, (2020) found that, there are no significant differences between male and female students in Biology. However, the male students achieved better than female students in science concepts. Also, the findings of this research is in line with that of Orji, Apochi & Abubakar, (2018) who found that, there are no significant differences between male and female students.

The reason could be based on the fact that GIS motivated and facilitated the retention ability of male and female students equally leading to non-significant difference.

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Conclusion

The researchers however, concluded based on the analysis of the results in this study, that the use of Group Investigation Strategy enhances the retention ability of secondary school students than the conventional method. With GIS, students learnt better about Biology, carried out their responsibilities and made effort to achieve a stated objective. It can be deduced that GIS enhanced cooperation and interaction, curiosity and increases retention of learnt concept than conventional method. It was also demonstrated that GIS do not discriminate on the basis of sexes and hence the retention of male and female students exposed to it did not differ significantly in their mean retention scores which attest to its gender-friendly nature.

Recommendations

Based on the findings in this study the following recommendations were made:

1. Since the use of Group Investigation Strategy has been established to improve student's retention of Biology concepts in secondary schools, teachers should be encouraged to adopt GIS in teaching biology.
2. Professional bodies like Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) in collaboration with the Nigeria Educational Research and Development Centre (NERDC), Federal Ministry of Education and school proprietors should organize seminars, workshops and conferences on the knowledge of Group Investigation Strategy for science teachers at federal and state levels. If this training is done on regular basis the science teachers will be proficient in the use of innovative strategy like Group Investigation Strategy in teaching biology.

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Impact of Laboratory Strategy on Interest, Performance and Retention in Biology among Secondary School Students in Katsina State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated impact of laboratory strategy on interest, academic performance and retention in Biology among secondary school students in Katsina State-Nigeria. The study was guided by three research objectives, corresponding research questions and null hypotheses, respectively. The study employed quasi-experimental research design. The population covered 4,531 male and female senior secondary school class two (SS II) Biology students from 16 public senior secondary schools in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance (ZEQA), Katsina State-Nigeria. The sample size consists of 90 Male and Female students drawn from three schools using cluster and random sampling techniques by balloting technique. Two validated instruments with reliability coefficient of 0.64 and 0.76 using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation and Cronbach Alpha method respectively, namely; Biology Performance Test (BPT) and Biology Interest Scale (BIS) were used for data collection. The Mean and Standard-deviation were used to answered research questions while t-test independent were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of Significance. The findings revealed that there is significant differences in interest, performance and retention between students taught Biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method. Based on the findings it was concluded that laboratory strategy served as a better strategy toward having a better interest, performance and retention in Biology. The study recommends among others that Biology teachers should employ the laboratory strategy in teaching Biology at senior secondary school level.

Keywords: Interest, Performance, Retention, Laboratory strategy, Lecture Method

Introduction

The future of every nation including Nigeria lies on the quality of education given to its citizens. Education remains the bedrock of civilization and development of any nation and also one of the most promising paths for individuals to realize better and more productive lives. This is because an individual who acquire knowledge especially scientific and technological literacy, think innovatively and rationally, thus enabling them to conduct themselves within the global acceptable standard. Without good and quality education no any nation can move from where it is to the next stage (Buba & Marcel 2019).

The twenty first century has witnessed the agitation for improvement of students' performance through provision of quality education, in 2015, United Nations has proposed the 2030 Agenda for sustainable development and outlined 17 sustainable development goals, which quality education is among the top agendas for all the United Nations members, being developed or developing countries, (Martin, Arora, 2012; Anna 2017). In line with Republic of Kenya as stated that Education should assist in developing an all-rounded individual personality who is able to develop physically, mentally, socially and morally (KNEC, 2013; Republic of Kenya, 2015). This indicates that for every nation to attain and sustain national development, a well-planned and implemented policies on education, especially science and technological education should be given priority, (Tafi, 2016; Habila & Benjamin, 2020).

The overmentioned points showcased the significance of qualitative education in relation to the national development. In the same manner science education is receiving much emphasis in the world because of its significance and relevance to the life of an individual and society at large. Nigeria as a nation it made several efforts towards the realization of science and appropriate methods for teaching it. Biology is among the science subject taught at secondary schools' level and prerequisite subject for many important fields of learning like medicine, forestry, agriculture, biotechnology and nursing among others that contributes immensely to the technological growth of the nations, (Buba & Marcel 2019).

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Biology is a branch of science that deals with study of structure, function, growth, evolution, and distribution of organisms, (Michael, 2012). In simple term Biology, is the study of life or living things, which includes human-beings. Biology has many branches which includes; zoology, botany, ecology, genetics, morphology, anatomy, physiology, histology, microbiology, evolution, cell biology, parasitology, entomology, mycology, anatomy, etc. Many societal issues are biology-based these include biodiversity, genetically modified organisms, reproductive technologies, prolongation of life, food production, tourism industry (biological gardens) and processing industries among the others. The knowledge of biology is not only paramount and useful to the learners only, but to everyone due to its significant to the lives of an individuals and society in general. The mentioned reasons, makes teaching biology necessary and needs to be friendly and relevant in order to make necessary provisions for students' interest and understanding the subject, this can only be achieved by active participation of learners in the teaching and learning process. There are many teacher and student-center teaching strategies that have been developed and used all over the years for teaching the subject, some of which are; lecture method, demonstration method, cooperative learning, problem-solving method, expository method, inquiry-based teaching approach, laboratory activities, peer-tutoring strategy among others. Unfortunately, most teachers teach Biology using predominantly the traditional or lecture method (Aniaku, 2012). Therefore, the proper and effective teaching of Biology cannot be achieved without using student-center teaching strategies in teaching the subject that will help in arousing the student's interest, increase their performance and leads to the high retention ability in the subject. So, to achieve the mentioned issues the present study used laboratory strategy to determine it impact on interest, academic performance and retention in Biology among senior secondary school students of Katsina state, Nigeria. Before then let have insight in the relationship between the dependent and independent variables of the study.

Laboratory has been described as a room or a building specially built for teaching by demonstration of theoretical phenomenon into practical terms. With the laboratory experience, students will be able to translate what they have read in their texts to practical realities, thereby enhancing their understanding of the learnt concepts. Farombi (1998), cited in Yara (2010) argued that seeing is believing is the effect of using laboratories in the teaching and learning of science and other science related disciplines as students tend to understand and recall what they see more than what they hear. Laboratory is very important and essential to the teaching of science and success of any science course is much dependent on the laboratory provision made for it. Lending credence to this statement, Ogunniyi (1982) cited in Yara (2010), said that there is a general consensus among science educators that laboratory occupies a central position in science instruction. It could be conceptualized as a place, where theoretical work is practicalized and practical in any learning experiences involve students in activities such as observing, counting, measuring, experimenting, recording and carrying out fieldwork. According to National Academies Press (NAP; 2023), laboratories as rooms or building in which students use special equipment to carry out research, observation or an investigation about a phenomenon. This may include such activities as chemistry experiments, plant or animal dissections in biology, and investigation of rocks or minerals for identification in earth science. According to Lunetta, 1998; cited in NAP, (2023), defined laboratories as “experiences in school settings in which students interact with materials to observe and understand the natural world”. Practical activities in biology provides opportunities for student to manipulate materials or equipment to investigate and understand the real world around them. Several findings have determined the impact of laboratory activities on student's interest, academic performance and retention in science subjects and Biology in particular some of these findings are mentioned in points below;

Hardr, et.al (2012), in Chibabi, etal. (2018), noted that challenge and satisfaction in laboratory task will motivate students and engage their interest in to the subject taught. According to Nwogbo, (2008) cited in Buba and Marcel, (2019), stated that the practical work in school laboratories gives students appreciation of the spirit of method of problem solving analytical and generalization ability. He maintained that laboratory work fosters students' positive attitudes toward science and maintains their interest in the learning of science subjects. National Academy of Sciences (2010), cited in Buba and Marcel. (2019), recommended that laboratory work was found to be interesting to students and leads to higher academic performance and retrieve past information than non-practical activities in biology. The finding of Ronoh (2013), revealed that the biology laboratory classes might increase the likelihood that students will engage in many experiences that arose their interest, improves performance and higher retention of learned materials.

Laboratory activities plays important role on student's academic performance in science education, Biology included. The findings of Nzewi, 2008 & Aina (2012) in Yusuf and Mukhtar (2019), mentioned that laboratory is an indispensable organ of the school if effective teaching is taking place that will improve students' academic performance. Ronoh, (2013), viewed that laboratory is an instructional facility used by teacher to help students learn about science and how scientists investigate the world around them that will improves their performance. According to Khan and Iqbal (2011), cited in Yusuf and Mukhtar (2019), students taught using laboratory teaching activities show more performance in science process skills than the students

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taught using traditional teaching method. The findings of Kitheka, (2005) cited in Kyakuwa, (2017), noted that schools with abundant laboratory resources and proper in utilization of this resource efficiently will boost learning and maximized adequately achieved good academic performance. Also, Adeniyi, (1983) in Kyakuwa (2017), draw attention that there is relationship between teaching with laboratory activities and student's academic performance in teaching science subjects, He maintained that the utilization of laboratory equipment in teaching is significantly related with student's academic performance. This is in-line with Mathew, (1998) cited in Kyakuwa (2017), discovered that utilization of laboratory strategy had positive relationship with student's academic performance towards science teaching and promote good academic performance in the science subjects.

Retention is the ability of the learners to recall information, ideas or learning activities at a later time which he/she may be ask to mention, write or remember after some times. According to Bichi, (2001) cited in Yusuf & Mukhtar (2019) defined retention as the ability to maintain and later recall information or knowledge gained after. Alake (2015), cited in Yusuf and Mukhtar (2019), viewed retention as the ability to store information which can be easily recalled from the short-term memory and long-term memory. The findings of Ajewole & Ivowi in Goje (2014) cited in Yusuf and Mukhtar, (2019), believe that laboratory work helps to promote conceptual understanding which aid in retention of science concepts at a later time. This was supported by findings of Hart, et.al, (2009), cited in Yusuf and Mukhtar (2019), Laboratory activities builds the students' scientific skills and processes especially in learning of science subject in secondary schools thereby enhancing retention ability of science concepts. Based on these premises, we understand the impact of laboratory activities on students' interest, academic performance and retention ability in science subjects, specifically Biology in secondary schools.

To actualize the mastery of the subject matter, learners should be exposed in to different learning strategies that will arouse their interest, increase their academic performance and helps them to have high retention ability. It is on this premise that the researcher examined the impact of laboratory strategy on interest, academic performance and retention in Biology among secondary school students of Katsina state-Nigeria

The persistent students' poor interest, performance and retention of many biology concepts in secondary school level leaves one in doubt about the effectiveness of teaching methods used by Biology teachers for teaching the subjects. Certain factors have been identified by different researchers that attributed to this problem. Buba and Marcel (2019), noted that lack appropriate teaching strategy in teaching is among the factors that influence the problem. Ganyaupfu (2013), mention that factors like lack of science equipment, inadequate qualified Biology teachers, students' overcrowding, poor instructional and infrastructural facilities and use of un-appropriate teaching methods use by Biology teachers are the baseline factors that resulted in poor interest, performance and retention in subject.

Although some researchers and science educators advocate the use of more innovative, result-oriented, and student-centered strategies like laboratory strategy and other student-centered method that involve the total involvement of learners in the teaching and learning process. Opara (2011) noted that these students-centered teaching methods when use in teaching can ultimately and positively affect students' understanding, interest, performance and retention in Biology. Therefore, the problem which this study seeks to solve is laboratory strategy improve students' interest, performance and retention in Biology?

Objectives of the study

1. Determine the mean interest score of students taught biology using laboratory strategy in Katsina State, Nigeria
2. Determine the mean academic performance of students taught biology using laboratory strategy in Katsina state, Nigeria.
3. Determine the mean retention ability of students taught biology using laboratory strategy in Katsina state, Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What is the mean interest of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina state, Nigeria?
2. What is the mean academic performance of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina state, Nigeria?
3. What is the mean retention ability of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina state, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant difference in mean interest score of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina state, Nigeria.
2. **H₀₂**: There is no significant difference in mean academic performance score of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in exposed to Katsina state, Nigeria.

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3. **H₀₃**: There is no significant difference in mean retention ability of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina state-Nigeria

Methodology

The study employed Pretest, Post-test, Post-post-test and Control group, Quasi-experimental design. The study used two groups; Experimental group (EG) and Control group (CG). The illustration of research design was mentioned below:

Research Design Illustration

Group 1: EG O₁ X₁ O₂ O₃
 Group 2: CG O₁ X₀ O₂ O₃

Keys:

EG Experimental Group X₁ Treatment (laboratory strategy)

CG Control Group X₀ No treatment (Lecture method)

O₁ Pre-test

O₂ Post-test

O₃ post-posttest

Population of the Study

The population covered four thousand, five hundred and thirty-one (4,531), Male and Female SS II, Biology Sstudents during the 2023/2024 academic session in Katsina State-Nigeria.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample size of the study consists of ninety (90), Male, and Female SS II students were selected from the population using Cluster random sampling technique by balloting. The sample was illustrated below

Sample of the study.

S/N	Schools	Status	Male	Female	Total
1	School A	EG	23	18	41
3	School B	CG	26	23	49
	Total		49	41	90

Results

Research Question 1:

Table 2: Mean Ranks of students' Interest Scores toward biology between Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Mean Ranks Diff.
Experimental Group	41	63.41	3107.00	39.31
Control Group	49	24.10	988.00	
Total	90			

Table 2. showed that the mean interest of students score in experimental group is (63.41) and that of control group is (24.10). The table indicate that, there is significant difference between the Experimental Group and Control Group with mean rank difference of (39.31). This indicated that, students taught biology using laboratory strategy have high academic performance in biology than those exposed to lecture method.

Research Question 2:

Table 3: Mean difference of students' performance between experimental and control groups.

Groups	N	Mean	Std.	Std. Error Mean	Mean difference
Experimental Group	41	48.37	11.745	1.678	37.96
Control Group	49	10.41	4.416	0.69	

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Table 3. showed that the mean academic performance of students score in experimental group is (63.41) and that of control group is (24.10). The table indicate that, there is significant difference between the Experimental Group and Control Group with mean rank difference of (39.31). This indicated that, students taught biology using laboratory strategy have high interest in biology than those exposed to lecture method.

Research Question 3:

Table 4: Mean difference of students' retention between experimental and Control groups

Groups	N	Mean	Std.	Mean difference
Experimental Group	41	37.22	11.852	23.68
Control Group	49	13.54	3.722	

Table 4. showed that the mean retention of students score in experimental group is (63.41) and that of control group is (24.10). The table indicate that, there is significant difference between the Experimental Group and Control Group with mean rank difference of (39.31). This indicated that, students taught biology using laboratory strategy have high retention in biology than those exposed to lecture method.

Hypotheses

The hypotheses formulated were tested using t-test independent between the variables involved. The null hypotheses are rejected when the p-value is less than the alpha-value of 0.05 level of significance and otherwise is retained. The results are presented in tables below and followed by the interpretations as shown below:

H₀₁:

There is no significant difference in mean interest scores of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina state, Nigeria.

Table 5: Mann Whitney U-Test for Comparison of Mean Ranks of Interest Score toward Biology for Experimental and Control Groups.

Group	N	Mean	Sum of rank	U-value	p-value	Remark
Experimental Group	49	63.41	3107.00	Z = -	0.0	Significant
Control Group	41	24.10	988.00	7.120		
Total	90					

* Significant at $\alpha \leq 0.05$, U-test = 127.00

Result in Table 5. showed that there exists a statistically significant difference in the mean ranks between the Experimental and Control Groups with Mann-Whitney U test (Z = -7.120) and mean rank difference of 39.48. Since the p-value = 0.0 < 0.05 significant level, the H₀₁ which states that: "There is no significant difference in the interest of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina state, Nigeria" is rejected. Hence, there is a significant difference between mean interest scores of the students taught Biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method.

H₀₂:

There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance score of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina state, Nigeria.

Table 6: t-test Result on Students Academic Performance in Biology Experimental Group and Control Groups.

Group	N	Mean	Std.	Df	t-value	p-value	Remark
Experimental Group	41	48.37	11.745	88	19.552	0.0	Significant
Control Group	49	10.41	4.416				

* Significant at $\alpha \leq 0.05$

Table 6 showed that p-value (observed) = 0.000 is less than α -value of 0.05 at df = 88. Since the observed p-value = 0.000 < 0.05 then the null hypothesis (H₀₂) which states that: "There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance score of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in secondary

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schools of Katsina state, Nigeria” is rejected. This means that there exists statistically significant difference between Experimental and the Control Groups. Hence, there is significant difference between mean performance scores of the students taught Biology using laboratory strategy and those taught with lecture method.

H₀₃:

There is no significant difference in mean retention ability of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method Katsina state, Nigeria.

Table 7: t-test Result on students' retention score in Biology between Experimental Group one and Control Group.

Group	N	Mean	Std.	Df	t-value	p-value	Remark
Experimental Group	41	37.22	11.852	88	12.29	0.0	Significant
Control Group	49	13.54	3.722				

* Significant at $\alpha \leq 0.05$

Table 7 showed that p-value (observed) = 0.000 is less than α -value of 0.05 at $df = 88$. Since the observed p-value = $0.000 < 0.05$ then the null hypothesis (H₀₃) which states that: “There is no significant difference in mean retention ability of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina state-Nigeria.” is rejected. This means that there exists statistically significant difference between Experimental Group one and the Control Group. Hence, there is significant difference between the Retention ability of Students taught Biology using laboratory strategy and those taught with lecture method.

The findings revealed that:

1. There is significant difference in mean interest score of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina state, Nigeria.
2. There is significant difference in mean academic performance score of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina state, Nigeria.
3. There is significant difference in retention ability of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method in Katsina state, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study showed that, there is significant differences in the interest, performance and retention ability of students taught Biology using laboratory strategy and those taught using lecture method. The finding of this study agreed with the findings of Chibabi, et al, (2018), investigated the effect of laboratory method of teaching on senior secondary school students’ achievement and retention in Biology in Kogi East Senatorial Zone. Results of the study revealed that there is significant difference of the achievement, retention and interaction effect between teaching method and the gender of student in the mean gain achievement scores of students taught using laboratory method of teaching and their counterparts taught using lecture method of teaching. In line with findings of Buba and Marcel (2019), carried out study on the effect of practical teaching method on academic achievement of senior secondary biology students in Mubi Educational Zone, Adamawa State. The findings revealed that there is significant difference in the effect of practical method and lecture method on students’ academic achievement in biology. The result also indicated that male students had higher mean score gain than their female counterpart when taught biology using practical method.

Conclusion

Basically, there was a significant difference in mean interest, academic performance and retention scores of students taught biology using laboratory strategy and those exposed to lecture method. Based on the findings it was concluded that laboratory strategy served as better strategy in improving interest, performance and retention in Biology among secondary school students in katsina state.

Recommendations

1. Biology teachers should employ the laboratory strategy in teaching Biology at senior secondary school level. Workshops, conferences and seminars should be organized to Biology teachers by the
2. Ministry of Education on the use of laboratory strategy in teaching Biology at senior secondary school level.

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3. Curriculum planners and curriculum development bodies in Nigeria like NERDC should design programme and policies that will incorporate the use of laboratory strategy in teaching and learning biology at Senior Secondary School level.

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Impact of Multimedia Aids ... (Sabiru & Ya'u, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13358729>

Impact of Multimedia Aids on Performance and Retention in Chemistry among Secondary School Students in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State

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Abstract

This study examined the Impact of Multimedia aids on Performance and Retention in Chemistry Secondary School Students in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State. Two objectives, two corresponding research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted Quasi-experimental research design specifically, pretest, post-test and post-post-test, non-equivalent control group. The study has a population of two thousand one hundred and eighty-seven (2187) SS II chemistry students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Funtua Education zone in Katsina state and a sample size of 177 students in two intact classes were selected by cluster sampling from two schools in the local government area and used for the study. Chemistry performance test (CPT) was used to elicit response for the study, the CPT was validated by three experts and subsequently pilot tested to determine its reliability index. Hence, reliability index of 0.86 was obtained using test-retest method which implies that the instrument is reliable for the study. The stated research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation statistics and null hypotheses were tested using an independent sample t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The finding of the study revealed that a significant difference exists in the mean academic performance and retention scores of SS II students taught Chemistry concept using Multimedia aids and those taught using conventional method. It was concluded that Multimedia aids improve performance and retention. It was also recommended that Science teachers should incorporate the use Multimedia aids in Chemistry and other science subjects. Multimedia aids should be incorporated in the curriculum of teacher training institutions to promote retention ability in Chemistry.

Keywords: Multimedia aids aid, Performance, Retention, Chemistry Concepts.

Introduction

Education according to Bello (2017) is conceived as the process of learning to live as a useful and acceptable member citizen of a community and a good citizen of a country. This process starts from the moment a person is born to death and it involves a number of activities by several people such as teachers, students, parents, government and all citizens of a country. It is also conceived as the development of the totality of man and natural world implying that, through education, man develops mentally, morally and spiritually (Georgewill, 2006). In view of these educators' conceptions and explanations, it could rightly be inferred that education is an umbrella (mother) body comprising of various disciplines such as art, technical, vocation, social science and science education.

Science as a concept is a process that is geared aimed at problem solving in order to enhance the living standard of man. Science can be regarded as a dynamic and objective process of seeking knowledge which involves scientist in the process of searching, investigating and seeking verification of natural things occurring in the environment (Nworgu, 2012). Nwagbo (2011) defined science as an intellectual activity carried out by human and designed to discuss information about the natural world in which he lives as well as to discover the ways in which the information can be organized to benefit human race. It can also be seen in terms of method and process as well as products comprising facts, concept, principles and laws that make up the body of science. From these views' students learning science are placed in problem solving situation. Owolabi (2012) views science as an integral part of human society. Its impact is felt in every way of human life so much that it is intricately linked with a nation's development. There are five basic branches of science in secondary school curriculum: these are Chemistry, Chemistry, Geography, Mathematics and Physics.

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Science education deals with sharing of science content and process with individuals who are not considered traditionally to be members of the scientific community, the individuals could be students, farmers, market women or a whole community. The major aim science teaching is to promote the understanding of the concept being taught with a view of applying knowledge of such understanding to real life situation (Ogunbowale, 2014). The objectives of science education in Nigeria, according to Maduekwe (2006) include: the need to prepare students to observe and explore the environment, explain simple natural phenomena, develop scientific attitudes including curiosity, critical reflection and objectivity, apply the skills and knowledge gained through science to solve everyday problems in the environment, develop self-confidence and self-reliance through problems solving activities in science.

Chemistry as one of the branches of science deals with the nature of matter, its properties and its change in different conditions. Tajudeen (2019) define chemistry as the science that deals with structure and composition of matter. Chemistry according to Omoniyi (2014) should be studied to improve man’s knowledge and enhance the understanding of the environment for survival. (Aniodoh & Egbo, 2013) observed that the importance of chemistry can be felt in almost all sphere of our national life. Therefore, chemistry education has a fundamental role to play in providing solution to several technological and socio-economic issues confronting man as well as improving scientific literacy (Ezeliora, 2010).

Many research findings such as that of Ajaja (2009) and Ahmed (2010) on the Chemistry teaching in Nigeria has revealed that, chemistry as a subject is poorly taught because of the use of inappropriate method of teaching such as lecture method (Johnson, 2018). In spite of the importance of chemistry in our national development and the effort being made by government, researchers, Science Teachers Association of Nigeria and other agencies, students’ performance has been very poor and unsatisfactory year after year. Over 50% of the students perceived chemistry as a body of isolated fact to be memorized, lacking relevance to reality which has led to lack of interest in it by students. For many students, chemistry is a classroom affair. However, studies such as that of Njoku (2011) and that of West African Examination Council Chief Examiners Report (WAEC, 2023) revealed that, academic performance of students in chemistry at Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE) has been very low.

Many factors have been suggested as contributing to this low academic performance of students particularly in chemistry and science in general, some of these factors includes; poor teaching methods, inadequate facilities and inadequate laboratory infrastructure for teaching chemistry (Tami, 2014) Result of several researchers conducted over the years had indicated that of all the various factors responsible for low performance in chemistry, poor teaching method was the most predominant (Mari, 2014). One of the problems in implementing science curriculum has been the use of inadequate approach or instructional strategy for the teaching of chemistry concepts. A lot of emphasis has been placed on this by the experimental science curriculum projects at both international and local levels. But despite the amount of effort and emphasis, science teachers in Nigeria schools still revert to the use of lecture method for teaching, as conventional method, is didactic, stereotype and non-result oriented. It is often described as “talk and chalk” method because its presents information to the students who merely listen. Teacher does all the talk while students listening and copy note on the chalkboard after the lesson (Akpoghol *et al.*, 2016). This teacher-centered approach dominates the educational system in Nigeria except few private schools that are well equipped with modern Information and Communication Technology (ICT) facilities such as computer laboratories with computers and internet facilities, interactive whiteboards, learning software, Multimedia aids, and many others. Consequently, research results have shown that the use of innovative teaching method such as Multimedia aids instructional strategy could enhance performance and retention in science, including chemistry (Osman and Vebrianto, 2013; Rohaida and Kamariah 2005).

Multimedia aids is the combination of instructional methods that encourage learners to engage in active learning by mentally representing materials in words and pictures making connections between the pictorial and verbal representations (Clark and Mayer cited in Krishnasamy, 2007). Kumar (2013) asserted that Multimedia aids are instructional materials and interactive application that integrate text, colour, graphic images, audio, animation, audio sound, and full motion video in a single application. According to Adekunmisi (2012) opined that Multimedia aids could be interpreted as a combination of data carriers, such as video, CD-ROM, floppy disks, Internet and software in which the possibility for an interactive approach is offered. Multimedia aids instructional package consists of resources which are computer-based with text, pictures, sound, animation, video or a combination of these media used in educational instruction to enhance learning outcome (Mayer, 2013). Multimedia aids instruction can convey information in a stimulating situation that aids the brain to preserved and information in the form of images which can be easily retrained and remember. Nwanekezi and Kalu (2012). Observed that students taught with Multimedia aids instruction have high retention scores than their counterpart who were taught with traditional teaching methods. This is so because Multimedia aids has certain features that increase the receptive and memory ability of the learner. These features are focused on the ability of the learner to learn with multiple senses, thus improve student’s academic

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performance, ensure learning permanency, and also improve of mental processes skills that promote deeper learning which increases the retention (Li, 2011; Oguz-Unver& Yurumezoglu, (2013).

A Multimedia aids aided instruction engaged students' interest, and encouraged them to collaborate, to inquire and to explore effectively, far beyond the bounds of the school (Galope,2013). Research has shown that people remember 20% of what they see, 40% of what they see and hear, but about 75% of what they see and hear and do simultaneously (Krishnasamy,2016). With Multimedia aids, the communication of information can be done in a more effective manner and it can be an effective instructional medium for delivering information. According to Chapman (2013), the use of Multimedia aids in teaching and learning processes has the potential to improve instruction by creating a technology-based, student-centered learning environment that allows students to take charge of their own learning. Using Multimedia aids in classroom provides students with suitable learning resources according to their learning. Thus, there is need to explore Multimedia aids package/strategy that may enhance students' performance in chemistry, hence, this study examines if teaching chemistry using Multimedia aids instructional strategy on senior school students' will improve their performance. The use of Multimedia will prevent students from rote learning and also have helped them to retain and recall what they have learnt for long period of time.

Retention on the other hand, is the ability to remember what was learnt or experienced by an individual which takes place when learning was coded into the memory through several factors. Akinbola and Folasade (2009); Ayamin and Anyachebelu (2009) argued that when teaching is characterized by rote-learning, it would be meaningless memorizing on verbalism and students make ineffective learning, and the facts thus learned are not retained. Students' retention was referred to as what could arouse and retain through the use of multimedia instructional approach (Adegoke, 2010). Alake (2015) sees retention as what is being organized and meaningful in students as they apply principles, solve problems and interpret experimental data which makes learning become effective and facts learnt are retained with passage of time.

Henceforth, it is part of the requirements of learning that, it should be retained. But the retainment should go beyond simple memory rather meaningful memory. Simple memory signifies rote-learning, but meaningful memory signifies meaningful learning. This brings about indelible meaningful learning. This means, rote-learning covers only 'remembering' which the lowest cognition stage is whereas, meaningful learning covers 'remembering', 'understanding' and 'application' stages of the cognition. As such the quest for retention ability of students become a variable of interest to researchers. Researchers were also found curious in search for means either in or outside the classroom by which students ability to regurgitate learned knowledge after a long period of time could be enhanced (Azuka, 2012). Hence, there are some things that enhance students' retention and some things that retard students' retention. Ideally, any phenomenon, materials or activities in learning situation should improve students' attainment and retention, but those phenomena that leads to confusion, misinterpretation or misconception among learning activities or materials retard the speed and efficacy and accelerates forgetting (Bichi, 2002 & Muhammad, 2011).

The conventional method in this study is one where a teacher does most of the talking, while the students listen and take notes. The method involves verbal presentation of ideas, concept, and generalization of facts. Conventional method is less tedious, save times and provides fascinating and aesthetically stimulating experience especially for the new students on topics of interest (Obeka, 2009). However, Joshi (2008) opines that lecture method is teacher-centered with little or no participation of students; consequently, they remain passive listeners. It is against this background that this study is set and examined the impact of Multimedia aids on Performance and Retention in Chemistry Secondary School Students in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State.

Chemistry as a science subject occupied a unique position in the scientific and technological advancement of any country in the world today (Bugaje, 2013; Ibrahim, Tairo, Aminu, Isah, Muhammad, 2017). Chemistry is an important science subject relevant for advanced studies in medical science, textile technology, agricultural science, synthetic industry, printing technology, pharmacy, chemical engineering among others (Adesoji, 2008; Edomwonyi and Avaa, 2011; Bugaje, 2013). Students must demonstrate mastery of chemistry and score at least a credit pass in WASSCE or NECO SSCE before he/she can be admitted into university to study any of the above-mentioned courses.

However, despite of the important position of Chemistry among other science related disciplines, literature has revealed that, students' Performance in Chemistry at Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (SSCE) has been consistently poor (Njoku, 2018). In fact, Students' general performance as reported by WAEC Chief Examiners' Reports on students' performance in the 2019, 2020, 2021 2022, and 2023 examination indicate poor Performance in chemistry. Table 1 below shows the statistics of Katsina State Secondary School Students' Performance in Chemistry.

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Table 1: Statistics of the Performance of Public Senior Secondary Schools’ Candidates in the WASSCE (May/ June in Chemistry 2018-2023) in Katsina State

Academic Year	Total Number of Students Sat	Students with Distinction & A ₁ -C ₆	Percentage Pass (%) D ₇ & E ₈	Percentage Failure (%) F ₉
2019	25,122	14,505	57.74	42.26
2020	21,717	11,612	53.47	46.53
2021	23,916	7,188	30.06	69.94
2022	24,619	10,138	41.18	58.82
2023	22,538	9,585	42.26	57.47

Source: Department of PRS, Ministry of Education, Katsina State, Nigeria (2023)

Among the factors that contributed to the above unstable trend of students’ performance in chemistry include, teachers inability to let go to the conventional method and use more of the innovative and student-centered teaching methods may have been preventing students from understanding the subjects especially the concepts that appears abstracts. It is imperative, therefore, that a more effective and innovative approach to the teaching and learning of chemistry be introduced. Hence, students’ poor performance is a function of teachers’ lack of usage of instructional materials like Multimedia aids to illustrate concepts perceived as difficult (Basiriyu, 2016; Abdullah, 2013). The use of Multimedia aids as instructional materials in teaching and learning situation especially in a chemistry class may play a vital role in increasing chemistry students’ academic performance in Senior Secondary School, hence the study seeks to find out the Impact of Multimedia aids aids performance and Retention in Chemistry secondary school students in Funtua Zonal Educational zone Katsina State.

Objectives of the Research Problem

The objectives of this study were to:

1. Determine mean Academic Performance scores of students’ taught chemistry concepts using Multimedia aids and those taught using Conventional method in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State.
2. Determine mean retentive ability scores of students’ taught chemistry concepts using Multimedia aids and those taught using Conventional method in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the mean Academic Performance scores of students’ taught chemistry concepts using Multimedia aids and those taught using Conventional method in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State?
2. What is the mean retention scores in of students’ taught chemistry concepts using Multimedia aid and those taught using Conventional method in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are formulated for testing at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance:

1. **HO₁**: There is no significant difference between mean Academic Performance scores of students’ taught chemistry concepts using Multimedia aid and those taught using Conventional method in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State.
2. **HO₂**: There is no significant difference between mean Retention scores of students’ taught chemistry concepts using Multimedia aid and those taught using Conventional method in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State.

Methodology

This research adopted Quasi-experimental control group research design in form of pretest, posttest, and post-posttest. This is according to Kerlinger and Leer (2005) that the design involves two groups, one group is assigned as experimental and the other group is controlled. The population of the study targeted all Students in Public Senior Secondary Schools Two (SS II) under Funtua Zonal Education Quality Assurance (FZEQA) who are offering Chemistry as a subject. The Government Public co-educational Schools were selected for use in this study because of their homogeneity, prior experiences, socio-cultural background, curriculum and population. Records of Students Returns of February 2024 of 2023/2024 Session show that the schools comprise a total number of Two thousand One Hundred and Eighty-Seven (2187) SSII students offering Chemistry as a subject. Out of which 1251 were males and 936 were females with an average age of 17 years. Ministry of Education (MOE, 2023)

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In this study, multistage sampling procedure was used to select the samples for the study. It involved two stages samples. 1st stage involved cluster sampling technique which involve selection of schools in which three cluster from the 22 public senior secondary schools in Funtua Zonal Education Quality Assurance were determined. That is, each local government stand for a cluster. From each cluster, the researcher employed Simple random sample technique inform of ballot boxing in which three schools were selected from each cluster. Bakori, Danja and Funtua were the three cluster. Bakori had 8 schools, Danja had 5 school and Funtua had 9 schools. The researcher wrote and folded the names of all schools in each cluster on a piece of paper and randomly selected one school without replacements and without being bias. The three selected schools were assigned as experimental group I, and control consecutively. 2ndstage involved selection of intact classes. There were more than on arm in each school selected. Hence, the researcher wrote and folded the arms (i.e. A, B & C) therefore, simple random sampling technique was used to select two intact classes per school selected based on gender. In essence, experimental group I had two chasses: A class had 68 male and B class had 83 female students. This made the sum of 151 students. The control group also had two classes: A class had 48 male and B class had 78 female students, making up the sum of 126 students. The sample in the three groups stands at 342 students.

The instrument used for data collection was Chemistry Performance Test (CPT). The test items were adapted from West African Examination Council (WAEC), National Examination Council (NECO) and Joint Admission and Matriculation Examination (JAMB) 2002-2022 past question papers to measure the students' performance and retention in the Chemistry Concepts taught. The concepts include: Periodic table, Bonding, Hybridization, Shapes, and Polarization. The CPT has two sections (A & B) with Section 'A' elicits for Bio data (Name of School, Class & Gender) of the respondent, while Section 'B' composed of forty (40) Multiple Choice Questions of which respondents are expected to provide the correct answer to each item. Each item is associated with four options. The CPT was used on the Experimental and Control Groups at pre-test, post-test and post-post-test (retention test). The items in CPT were constructed to suit the six cognitive levels based on Blooms' Taxonomy for the Cognitive Domains. The instruments and instructional plans were validated by experts in the Departments of Science and Vocational Education, Department of Pure and Industrial Chemistry, Umaru Musa Yaradua University, Katsina, Nigeria. The CPT was pilot tested in Government College Pilot Senior Secondary School SSII Chemistry Students (which is not part of the sample) twice within an interval of two weeks. Test-retest Method was used to assess the reliability of the CPT. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) statistical tool was employed for analysis. The reliability coefficient of CPT was found to be $r = 0.86$ which indicates high reliability index. Hence, reliable for in this study. At the schools visited, the researcher pre-tested the students using CPT for both Experimental and Control Groups before any treatment.

After the pre-test, for Control Class, the research assistant taught the Chemistry Concepts (Periodic table, Bonding, Hybridization, Shapes and Polarization) to the students for the duration of six (6) weeks, forty-five (45) minutes per week using conventional Method. For experimental class, the treatment involved teaching of the same Chemistry Concepts for the same duration using Multimedia aids Lesson Plans. The Multimedia aids Lesson Plan was developed by the researcher in accordance with Multimedia aids-based Approach adapted from (Mayer, 2013). Multimedia aids Instructional Guide Framework is a six steps sequence of a logical operations with the first stage begins with the teacher's task of introducing the concept to be taught to the students briefly. The researcher taught Periodic table using computer and projector and order to help the student understand the concept and attract the attention of the students. The researcher used the same method and taught Periodic table, Chemical bonding, Hybridization, Shapes and Polarization for six weeks

After the six (6) weeks teaching (Treatment Session), the Experimental and Control Groups, posttest was administered using reoriented and reordered CPT to both groups (for gain determination, if any). Two consecutive weeks later, CPT items were reoriented and re-reordered and administered to both Experimental and Control groups (for retention determination, if any). The CPT scripts were marked by the researcher according to the groups (EG and CG) using appropriate Marking Scheme. The two research questions were answered using Mean and Standard Deviation (SD) whereas hypotheses one and two were tested using an Independent Samples t-test at 0.05 level of significance using Statistical Package for Social Science Software Version 23.1.

Results

Presentations in this section are based on research questions and hypotheses:

1. **Research Question One:** What is the mean Academic Performance scores of students' taught chemistry concepts using Multimedia aid and those taught using Conventional method in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State?

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To answer research question one, the post-test scores of students for CPT in the control and experimental group were subjected to descriptive statistics in form of Means and Standard Deviations. This is presented in Table 2

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of CPT Scores of the and Experimental Group and Control

Variable	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference
Performance	Experimental	151	19.64	3.357	4.40
	Control	126	15.24	2.260	

Table 2 revealed that the mean difference between the CPT Scores of EG (m =19.64, SD = 3.357) and that of the CG (m =15.24, SD = 2.260) is 4.40. It could therefore be seen that EG outperformed the CG.

Research Question Two:

What is the mean retention scores in of students’ taught chemistry concepts using Multimedia aid and those taught using Conventional method in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State?

To answer research question two, the post posttest cores of students for CPT in the control and experimental group were subjected to descriptive statistics in form of Means and Standard Deviations. This is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of CPT Scores of the Experimental Group and Control

Variable	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference
Retention	Experimental	151	17.21	4.067	2.20
	Control	126	15.01	2.411	

Table 3: revealed that the mean difference between the CPT Scores of EG (m = 17.21, SD=4.067) and that of the CG (m = 15.01, SD= 2.411) is 2.20 . It could therefore be seen that EG outperformed the CG

Hypotheses

The following null hypothesis were tested at 0.05 level of significance

H0₁:

There is no significant difference between mean Academic Performance scores of students’ taught chemistry concepts using Multimedia aid and those taught using Conventional method in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State.

In order to test hypothesis one, the post- test of experimental and control groups for CPT were subjected to t-test of independent sample statistics. Summary of the analysis was presented in table 4

Table 4: t-test analysis of the Posttest for CPT of Control and Experimental Group

Groups	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Decision
Experimental	151	19.64	3.357	275	9.72	0.00	Significant
Control	126	15.24	2.260				

Table 4 revealed that the difference between the mean Posttest CPT Scores of EG₁ (m =19.54, SD=3.387) and that of the CG (m= 15.24, SD= 2.260) is significant [t(275) = 9.72, P < 0.05 based on the decision rule, this study rejected the null hypothesis one (1) that says there is no significant difference in mean academic performance scores in Periodic table between students taught using Multimedia aids and those taught using lecture method.. The decision implies that, there is a significant difference in mean academic performance scores in Periodic table between students taught using Multimedia aids and those taught using lecture method. This indicates that the students of experimental group performed significantly better than control group after treatment with Multimedia aids

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H0₂:

There is no significant difference between mean Retention scores of students’ taught chemistry concepts using Multimedia aid and those taught using Conventional method in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State.

In order to test hypothesis two, the post posttest of experimental and control groups for CPT were subjected to t-test of independent sample statistics. Summary of the analysis was presented in table 5

Table 5: -test analysis of the Post-Posttest for CPT of Control and Experimental Group

Groups	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Decision
Experimental	151	20.80	3.78	275	6.28	0.00	Significant
Control	126	15.48	2.89				

Table 5 revealed that the difference between the mean Post-Posttest CPT Scores of EG₁ (m = 20.80, SD= 3.78) and that of the CG (m= 15.48, SD= 2.89) is significant [t(275) = 6.28, P < 0.05 based on the decision rule, this study rejected the null hypothesis three (3) that says there is no significant difference in the mean retention scores in Periodic table between students taught using Multimedia aids and those taught using lecture method. The decision implies that, there is a significant difference in the mean retention scores in Periodic table between students taught using Multimedia aids and those taught using lecture method. This indicates that the students of experimental group performed significantly better than control group in the mean retention scores in Periodic table after treatment with Multimedia aids.

Discussion of the Finding

The result from the research question one and testing of hypothesis one, it indicated that the experimental group who were taught chemistry concepts using Multimedia aids-based Approach achieved significantly better than those in the control group who were taught same concepts using conventional method. This indicates that Multimedia aids-based Approach is more effective in enhancing chemistry students’ academic performance in chemistry concepts than the conventional method of teaching. This finding is in line with that of Akinbadewa (2020) investigated the Effectiveness of Multimedia aids Instructional Learning Packages in Enhancing Secondary School Student’s Attitudes towards Chemistry.

From the finding of Research Question Two proved that Students from experimental group retained chemistry concepts taught using Multimedia aids-based Approach better than those taught same concepts using conventional method. In addition, Null Hypothesis Two was rejected based on analysis of t-test independent sample which confirms that significant difference exists in the retention scores of students taught chemistry concepts using Multimedia aids-based Approach and those taught using Conventional method. This indicates that the potentiality of Multimedia aids-based Approach to teaching chemistry concepts in enhancing retention ability of students. This finding is in line with that of Hurmuzan and Yahya (2015) conducted a study titled Effects of Multimedia aids Resources on Student’s Academic performances and retention in social studies in Junior Secondary Schools, Kaduna State- Nigeria. The following are the major findings of this study: There is a significant difference in mean academic performance scores in Chemistry between students taught using Multimedia aids and those taught using conventional method in Funtua Zone Katsina State; There is a significant difference in the mean retention scores in Chemistry between students taught using Multimedia aids and those taught using conventional method in Funtua Zone Katsina State.

Conclusions

This study was conducted as part of the efforts of educational researchers in promoting the appropriate, relevant and suitable pedagogy in teaching chemistry which will help in addressing issues related to student’s academic performance and retention in Chemistry. Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that Multimedia aids-based approach is effective in enhancing students’ performance and retention in chemistry.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made from the findings of the study.

1. Teachers at senior secondary schools should expose Chemistry students to Multimedia aids to promote their academic performance in the subject.

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2. Science teachers should incorporate the use Multimedia aids in Chemistry and other science subjects
3. Multimedia aids should be incorporated in the curriculum of teacher training institutions to promote retention ability in Chemistry.

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Comparative Relationship between Parental Involvement and Academic Engagement among Secondary School Students in Delta State Nigeria

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Abstract

The study sought to investigate the comparative relationship between parental involvement and students' academic engagement among secondary school students in Delta State Nigeria. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted correlation research design. The population of the study consists of 41744 (Male 20365, and Female, 21379) senior secondary school class two (SS2) students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Delta State, and the sample size was 769 (Male, 384 and Female, 385) SS2 students drawn from the target population using multi stage sampling technique. Two instruments namely: Parental Involvement Questionnaire (PIQ) and Academic Engagement Questionnaire (AEQ) were used for data collection. The instruments were validated by three experts from the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Reliability indices of 0.87 and 0.92, respectively were obtained for the instruments. Data collected were analyzed using coefficient of determination to answer the research questions, while the multiple regression analysis was employed to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed a positive relationship between parental involvement and academic engagement among secondary school students in Delta State. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that parental involvement significantly correlated positively with secondary school students academic engagement. It was however, recommended among others that parents should create adequate time and be encouraged to be involved in their children education so that students can be focused in meaningful academic engagement.

Keywords: Relationship, Parental involvement, Students Engagement

Introduction

In Nigeria, education remains the largest industry and government continues to ensure that funds, instructional material and teaching personnel and made available for the sector (Ade, 2014). Good education does not happen by chance and secondary schools are critical to students' academic success and overall educational outcomes. Student engagement becomes a critical success factor (CSF) that has emerged to determine students' experiences and academic achievements. According to Bryson (2014), student engagement in secondary schools is consistently emphasized in research, refers student engagement to which student are actively involved, motivated, and committed to their learning process and school activities. Academically engaged students, consistently out perform their less engaged students, reaching their full potential and achieving greater levels of success (Juvonen and Kinfensend, 2016).

Khan, Egbue, Palkie and Madden (2017) asserted that highly engaged students demonstrate a more in-depth understanding of the subject matter, actively participate in classroom discussions, and willing to ask participation benefits not only themselves but also their active participation benefits only themselves but also their fellow students, contributing to a dynamic and stimulating classroom environment. Student engagement has significant impact on students' social-emotional well-being (Heffner and Anataramian, 2016). Museus, Yi and Saelua (2017) asserted that engaged students have a stronger sense of belonging, connection, and positive relationship in their school community. They have a higher chance of developing healthy self-esteem, confidence, and resilience (Bouden, Tickle and Naumann, 2021; Gao, Mei and Guo, 2020). (Yang, Liu, Li and Li, 2022), emphasized that students who are engaged report lower levels of stress and anxiety because they perceive school to be a supportive and nurturing environment. Furthermore, student engagement is important in determining students' long-term educational and career outcomes.

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Engaged students are more likely to pursue higher education, develop career goals and develop the skills and competencies required for future success. They demonstrate greater motivation and self-regulation, both of which are necessary for lifelong learning and personal growth (Holec and Marynowski, 2020).

Disengagement of students in Delta state is a problem as evidenced by lack of interest in class activities or assignments, difficulty participating in class, difficulty staying on task, disconnection from peers, teachers and parents, inattentiveness or lack of focus during class, that lead to the high number of out-of-school children. According to Nigeria Multidimensional Poverty Index NMPI (2022), Delta state has approximately 140,000 out-of-school children between the ages of 6 and 15, which accounts for 9.30% of the population. This figure is alarming considering an oil rich state like Delta. According to Gairin, Triado, Feixas, Figuera, Aparicio-Chueca and Torrado (2014), when students are disengaged from their education, it hinders that motivation, interest, and commitment to the learning process and school activities. Amenah, (2019) emphasized the decline in interest and poor academic achievement among secondary school student in Delta State, indicating the negative consequences of disengagement. This lack of engagement ultimately leads to poor performance, limited understanding of subject matter, and reduced participation in classroom discursions.

Recent research suggests that there are multiple factors that influence school engagement. These factors include effective communication, collaboration, active involvement in learning activities, enriching educational experiences, positive interactions between students and teachers, appropriate academic challenges, supportive classroom and family environments, availability of resources, parental involvement, and interest in a child's learning material (Araque et al., 2017; Clark, 2015, Furrer et al., 2014; Kim et al; 2019; Kutsyuruba et al., 2015; Lee, 2014; Pellas, 2014; SalmelaAro and Upadyaya, 2014; Wang and Fredricks, 2014; Whytesell, 2016). Among these factors, the article will specifically investigate the comparative relationship between parental involvement and academic engagement among secondary school students in Delta State.

Parental involvement is an important factor in influencing student engagement and academic outcomes. When parents actively participate in their children's education, it improves their academic performance and overall well-being (Upadyaya and Salmela-Aro 2013). Parental involvement is defined as active participation in their children's educational journey, which includes various forms of support communication, and collaboration between, parents and schools (Kwan and Wong, 2016). Research consistently shows that parental involvement has a positive impact on students' academic achievement, motivation, and overall school success (Anthony and Ogg, 2019; Boonk, Gijsselaers, Ritzen and Brand-Gruwel, 2018; Jsiswal and Choudhuri, 2017; Mahuro and Hungi, 2016).

The establishment of a strong home-school partnership is an important aspect of parental involvement (Okeke, 2014). Students benefit from a cohesive support system that extends beyond the classroom when parents and schools collaborate. Actively involved parents in their children education show a vested interest in their academic progress and well-being, which fester a positive learning environment (Darling-Hammend and Cook-Havey, 2018). Attending parent teacher conferences, participating in school extents, volunteering, assisting with homework, and engaging in regular communication with teachers are all examples of parental involvement (Kimaro and Machumu, 2015). These activities show students that their education is important not only of school, but also at home, reinforcing a sense of importance and commitment to their education.

Several positive outcomes emerge when parents participate in their children's education. Parental involvement raises students' motivation and self-assurance. Students feel supported and encouraged by their parents increase their confidence and sense of self-efficacy (Alacam, 2015). As a result, students are more engaged in classroom activities and more willing to take on academic challenges. Parental involvement helps to improve academic performance. Parents who actively participate in their children's education can provide additional guidance, monitor progress, and offer support as needed (mahuro and Hungi; 2016). This additional supports system emphasizes the value of education and assists students in staying on track, resulting in improved grades and overall academic performance.

Furthermore, Afolabi, (2014) asserted that parental involvement promotes improved communication between home and school. It also enables parents to stay up to date on their children progress and actively participate in discussions about their academic and personal development. However, it is critical to recognize that parental involvement should be inclusive and take into account different family structures, cultural backgrounds, and socioeconomic circumstances (Murray, Mcfarland-Piazza and Harrison, 2015). Schools should strive to create and inclusive environment that encourages and accommodates parental involvement regardless of individual circumstances. By conducting this research within Delta State, it presents an opportunity to explore this variable that shape the interaction and the impact on students' engagement.

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The major problem to be addressed by this research is student's engagement. In secondary schools in Delta state, student disengagement poses a significant challenge, evident in inattentiveness, or lack of focus during class, disinterest in class activities or assignments, avoiding class, or not completing homework, disconnection from peers, teachers and parents that lead to high number of out-of-school children and poor academic performance. A good number of parents give little attention to the academic work of their children.

The Nigeria Multidimensional Poverty Index (NMPI) (2022) shows that Delta State has approximately 14,000 out-of-school children between ages 6 and 15, which accounts for 9.30% of the population. This figure is alarming for an oil-rich state like Delta. Poor parenting at home, lack of parent involvement in parent child discussion on academic issues, stress on the part of parent ability to solve problems probably not knowledgeable enough contribute to students' disengagement. These have negatively affected the child's ability to get engaged in learning. One of such consequence is evident in the poor performance of the student both in internal and external examination. Through observation students behavior show that most students parents are not involve in supporting their children to guide them through life so as to achieve their goals

Lack of comprehensive understanding of how parental involvement influences students engagement hinders the ability to develop evidence-based policies and initiatives that promote positive educational outcomes. As a result students may continue to experience decreased motivation, limited participation and reduced academic achievement. By conducting this research, this study aims to provide valuable insights and evidence-based recommendations that can inform the development of effective interventions and educational policies, ultimately fostering a supportive and engaging learning environment for students in Delta State.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of the study was to investigate the relationship between parental involvement and student academic engagement among Senior Secondary Schools. Specifically, the study aims to:

1. Assess the relationship between parental involvement and student academic engagement among secondary school students in Delta State.
2. Determine the nature of the regression for predicting student academic engagement based on the variable parental involvement among secondary schools students in Delta State.

Research Questions

The following research question guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between parental involvement and student academic engagement among Secondary Schools students in Delta State?
2. What is the nature of the regression model for predicting academic engagement based on the variable parental involvement among secondary school students in Delta State?

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant relationship between parental involvement and academic engagement among Secondary School students in Delta State.
2. The regression model based on the variable parental involvement does not significantly predict academic engagement among secondary school students in Delta State.

Methodology

The study employed a correlation survey research design. According to Nworgu (2015), correlation survey research design seeks to establish whet relationship exist between two or more variables, using statistics known as correlation co-efficient. A correlation survey is preferred in this study because it gets at the degree of association rather than merely try to find whether the effect is present or absent. It indicates the direction and magnitude of the relationship existing between parental involvement and student engagement of Secondary School in Delta State, without the manipulation of the independent variable. The public Senior Secondary School (SS2) students were used for the study. The total number of public secondary schools in Delta State was 466. The population of the study consists of 41744 (Male, 20365 and Female, 21379) senior secondary school class two (SS2) students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Delta State, and the sample size was 769 (Male, 384 and Female, 385) SS2 students drawn from the target population using multi stage sampling technique.

Two instruments were used in this study to collect data. Parental involvement questionnaire (PIQ) and academic engagement questionnaire (AEQ). Two clusters of thirty-one (31) question items. The first cluster investigated the level of parental involvement. The second cluster investigated the academic engagement of students.

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The two instruments were validated by three experts from the faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka. Two of the specialized in Educational Psychology, while the third expert specialized in Measurement and Evaluation.

Data were presented using the simple correlation coefficient and coefficients of determination was used to answer the research questions while the multiple regression analyses was employed to test the null hypotheses at a significance level of 0.05.

Results

Research Question 1:

What is the relationship between parental involvement and student academic engagement among secondary school students in Delta State?

Table 1: Relationship between Parental Involvement and Students' Academic Engagement

Variable	<i>N</i>	Student Academic Engagement	α -level	t(r)-cal	p-val	Decision
Parental Involvement	769	.432	0.05	13.233	.000	Significant relationship

Table 1 shows the relationship between parental academic involvement and students' academic engagement. Using Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient, results indicated that there is a moderate positive relationship between parental academic involvement and students' academic engagement.

Research Question 2:

What is the nature of the regression model for predicting academic engagement among secondary schools students in Delta State?

Table 2: Test of significant Relationship between Parental Involvement and Students Academic Engagement.

Variable	<i>N</i>	Student Academic Engagement	α -level	t(r)-cal	p-val	Decision
Parental Involvement	769	.432	0.05	13.233	.000	Significant relationship

Further analysis indicated that there is a statistical significant relationship between parental academic involvement and students' academic engagement. This is so because the p -value = .000 is greater than the level of significance = 0.05. Therefore the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between parental academic involvement and students' academic engagement is rejected.

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant relationship between parental involvements and academic engagement among secondary school students in Delta State.

Table 3: Regression Analysis on the Relationship between Parental Academic Involvement and Students Academic Engagement

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	21.900	1.049		20.879	.000
	par involvement	.521	.039	.432	13.233	.000
	<i>R</i>	.432				
	<i>R</i> ²	.186				
	<i>F</i>	175.104				.000

a. Dependent Variable: academic engagement

Table 3 showed that regression coefficient R was .432 while R^2 was .186. This shows that the predictor variable contributed 18.6% to explain the variances in academic engagement. The corresponding $F(1, 766) = 175.104$,

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is statistically significant ($p < .05$). Hence, parental academic involvement is a significant predictor of students' academic engagement.

Hypothesis 2:

The regression model based on the variable parental involvement does not significantly predict academic engagement among secondary school students in Delta State

Table 4: Predictive Value of the Independent Variable.

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients		
1	(Constant)	21.900	1.049		20.879	.000
	par involvement	.489	.040	.405	12.334	.000
	<i>R</i>	.432				
	<i>R</i> ²	.186				
	<i>F</i>	175.104				.000

a. Dependent Variable: academic engagement

Table 4 above showed that parental involvement had a positive significant predictive value on students' academic engagement ($B = .405$, $t = 12.334$, $p < .05$). Therefore, parental involvement is a significant predictor of academic engagement of secondary schools students in Delta State.

Discussion of Results

The findings of this study reveal that there is a moderate positive relationship between parental academic involvement and students' academic engagement. Further analysis indicated that there is statistical significant relationship between parental academic involvement and student's engagement and that it is a significant predictor of student's engagement. This finding is in harmony with the findings of (Anthony and Ogg 2019; Boonk, Gijsselaers, Ritzen and Brand-Gruwel, 2016; Jaiswal and Choudhuri, 2017; Mahuro and Hungi, 2016) that parental involvement has a positive impact on students' academic achievement, motivation, engagement and overall school success. This means that the prevailing family Psychodynamics exerted influence on the child determine the direction of correlation, that when parents support their children academics both affectively and cognitively, it becomes obvious that the students' academic engagement will be enhanced. Again, the result of the study further revealed that 18.6 percent variation in students' academic engagement can be attributed to parental academic involvement in their children's education, hence, parental involvement is a significant predictor of students' academic engagement.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that parental involvement significantly correlated positively with secondary school students' academic engagement. This greatly implies that if parents get involved in their children's academic engagement, students will greatly excel in their overall success in their education which can eliminate the problem of student's disengagement in secondary schools in Delta State.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Parents should create adequate time for their children's education especially in engaging students in their homework, projects and assignments so that students can have meaningful engagement in their studies.
2. School authorities should organize workshops through Parents-Teachers association to enlighten parents on the importance of engagement so that academic disengagement can be minimized or totally eliminated in secondary schools in Delta State.
3. Students should be enlightened by teachers how to be fully engaged in their academics so that they can be focused and excel in their future endeavor.
4. School guidance and counselors should intensify effort to organize seminars for students on the importance of student's engagement and enlighten stakeholders on the disadvantages of students being disengaged from their studies.

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Impact of Paired-Problem-Solving Strategy on Performance in Concept Evolution among Secondary School Divergent Learners in Gusau Metropolis, Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the impact of paired-problem-solving strategy on performance in concept evolution among secondary school divergent biology learners in Gusau Metropolis, Zamfara State. Two research questions and corresponding null hypotheses guided the research. Quasi experimental research Design was used for the study. The experimental group was taught concept evolution using Paired-problem-solving strategy while the control group were exposed to Conventional lecture method. Population of the study consists of all senior secondary school class two biology students in Gusau Metropolis during the 2023/2024 academic session in Gusau, Zamfara State. A sample size of 154 (Male, 82 and Female, 72) students were selected from the target population using multistage sampling technique. The validated Students' Evolution Performance Test (SEPT) with reliability coefficients of 0.76, was used for data collection. Data collected was analysed using SPSS version 26.0 at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance. Mean, mean difference, and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions and t-test Statistic was used to test the hypotheses at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance. Results revealed that significant difference exists between the academic performance of divergent learners exposed to Paired-problem-solving strategy and those taught using Conventional lecture method and likewise academic performance of divergent male and female learners exposed to Paired-problem solving strategy. The findings revealed that Paired-problem-solving strategy enhanced divergent learners' academic performance. It is thus recommended that, all secondary school biology teachers should be encouraged to use modern teaching method such as the Paired-problem-solving strategy through training and retraining programs.

Keywords: Paired-problem-solving, Concept of Evolution, Divergent Biology Learners

Introduction

The science teachers' role in fostering students' active involvement in doing and learning of science, is seen as crucial for students' achievement in science. Otuka (2016), described science as a dynamic field of human endeavour, and that the development of any country depends

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largely on the teaching and learning of science. Thus, a country's educational policies and programs are directed toward science of which biology is an important branch.

The economic strength of a nation is always assessed in terms of its performance in science and technology.

Teaching evolution at secondary school level requires the use of effective teaching strategy in order to make students understand the concept. Many strategies that involve active participation of students in the learning process (student-centered) that is concept mapping strategy, laboratory method, problem-based strategy among others. Despite the significant contribution of these to learn within themselves (in pairs) without much interference of other learners. Strategies in learning science concepts, the use of Paired-problem-solving-strategy gives learners a chance.

Paired-problems-solving strategy is one of the effective teaching strategy teachers used in teaching. In this regard Narode (2012), described Paired-Problem-Solving Strategy as a teaching procedure developed by Lohead and Whimbey in 1987 in order to promote students' ability to solve problems by the use of verbal descriptions. These descriptions could be through proving and clarifying questions, in pairs each student takes roles, one will serve as a problem solver while the other student serves as a listener. The student designated as the problem solver begins by reading the problem aloud to the other student (the listener) and verbalizes all thoughts on how to solve the problem. The problem solver does all the talking and all the writing about the problem. The problem solver is responsible for articulating all ideas as they occur, whereas the listener has an opposite task. This shows that, whenever the problem solver is talking, the listener must suspend solving the problem so that complete concentration and attention is devoted toward understanding the problem solver's solution. Through Paired-problem-solving strategy, students articulate ideas thereby improving their performance, which could motivate the convergent and divergent students.

Until the end of 18th century, the application of Paired-problem-solving strategy was decreased. Robins (2011), suggests that "students routinely make vast improvement in their year over year academic performance after the Paired-problem solving strategy is introduced. Academic performance of students is the centre around which the whole education system revolves. The success and failure of any educational institution is measure in terms of academic performance of students. Arshad, Zaidi and Mahmood (2015) indicated that academic performance measures education outcome. They stressed that it shows and measures the extent to which an educational institution, teachers and students have achieved their educational goals.

Yusuf, Onifade and Bello (2016) added that it consists of scores obtained by students in an assessment such as class exercise, mock examination and end of semester examination. The definition given by authors shows that the definition of academic performance is based on measurable outcomes such as class exercise, test and examinations results. Based on this the operational definition used in this study is the results obtained by students at post-test. This study therefore found out the impact of Paired-problem-solving strategy on performance in evolution concepts among secondary school students of different learning styles (convergent/divergent) in Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Learning style is another variable in this study. Many learning styles experts according to Gilakjani (2014) showed the theory that students will learn more and will enjoy the class experience and environment when they can use their preferred learning styles. To address this concern, teachers should understand their students' learning styles preferences and be interesting in developing teaching approaches to address the learning needs of all their students, because Ibe

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(2013) explained, that good teaching approach or method will help make the class session more effective and encourage students' participation in the class. Ibe (2013), further defined learning styles as the ways individuals prepare to absorb and incorporate new information. Different people have different ways of learning, and that those ways are neither good nor bad given various preferences for perceiving and processing information. The study of individual differences was important in science teaching, because it revealed the mental resources involved in learning specific domains and could relate them to persistent students' difficulties. Stamovlasis, Kypraios and Papageorgiou (2015) ascertained that convergence and divergence are two distinct cognitive styles, rather than opposites, that are introduced as special aspects of intelligence. Convergence is the ability of an individual to focus on the one right answer in order to find the solution of a problem, whereas divergence is one's ability to respond flexibly and successfully to problems requiring the generation of several solutions. Divergent thinking is usually correlated with creativity and convergence is associated with intelligence. Nwangbo and Aham (2015) observed that the populations of students in a class in most cases are made up of varying intellectuals and learning styles which to a large extent has effect on academic performance. In line with this, Shuaibu, Lawal and Bichi (2015), highlighted common cognitive styles capable of affecting students' attitude and performance to include: field dependence and field independence, reflective and impulsive, convergent and divergent. Shuaibu (2017) posited that the classroom environment consists of students with different learning abilities and psychological construct, some are extroverts, some are introverts, some are independent personality, while others are of dependent personality among others. In addition, students thinking and information processing significantly differ, which have direct impact on their academic performance in various subjects. There are various documented cognitive styles that influence students' academic performance, also according to Shuaibu (2017) these includes visual and haptic, visualized and verbalized, field dependent and field independent, holists and serialist and convergent and divergent. Kolb (1999), has suggested four different learning styles: Accommodator, Divergent, Assimilators and Convergent. Divergent students were used for the study in order to find out whether the paired-problem-solving strategy enhance divergent students' academic performance.

According to Dantani (2011), in most countries of the world the educational provision for boys and girls was clearly differentiated. Gender according to Bichi (2015), is the amount of masculinity and femineity found in a person and obviously there are mixture of both in a few human beings, the normal male has the prepondence of masculinity and a normal female has femineity. Various studies have been carried out in science education to ascertain the influence of gender with regards to academic performance. However, Okeke (2018), explained that female students were significantly better than their male counterparts and that there was a significant difference between male and female students in their ability to solve quantitative problems. Suleiman et al (2019), narrated that, to which a society placed values, some societies regarded males to be the champion of activities and events happening around the environment. Moreover, Gor, Othuon and Migunde (2020), asserted that, studies in Nigeria have however, revealed mixed reports on gender difference in science performance. Some researchers have provided reports that there are no longer distinguishing differences in the cognitive, affective and psychomotor skill achievements of students in respect of gender. Furthermore, Dawal (2021), revealed that there is a gender differences in the attitude and achievement of students towards science. Male students

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exhibited positive attitude towards physics, chemistry and mathematics than their female counterparts while the female students have positive attitude towards biology.

Gender bias in science classrooms has been and still continues to be a problem. Meanwhile the contradictive evidences in academic performance due to gender necessitate the need to verify how Paired-problem-solving strategy can affect biology student's performance in respect to gender. Therefore, this study used Paired-problem-solving strategy in teaching evolution concepts to secondary school biology students in order to see whether or not it has impact in the learning styles of divergent learners. Sulaiman (2023) investigated the effects of Contextual approach on confidence and performance in electrochemistry among divergent and convergent secondary school students in Bauchi State, Nigeria and found out that the divergent and convergent students in the experimental group performed better than the divergent and convergent students in the control group. The study carried out by Sulaiman (2023), is similar to the present study in terms of academic performance, learning style, research design, school, alpha level of 0.05 and procedure for data analysis but differs in terms of motivation, sample, population, instrument, r-value, subject and location.

Adigun, Aghiomesi and John (2015) investigated the effect of gender on students' academic performance in computer studies in secondary schools in new Bussa, Borgu local government of Niger State, Nigeria. The result of the study showed that even though the male students had slightly better performance compared to the female students, it was not significant. This better performance was found to be pronounced in the private schools which was shown to possess the best male brains found in the study area. The study carried out by Adigun, Aghiomesi and John (2015), is similar to the present study in terms of academic performance, gender, statistical tool and p value of 0.05 level of significance but differs in terms of teaching strategy, motivation, learning styles, r-value, location, sample and population.

Goni, Yanagawali, Ali. and Bularafa (2015) examined the gender differences in students' academic performance in collage of education in Borno State, Nigeria. The result indicated that there were no significant differences exist between gender and academic performance in collage of education in Borno State. The study carried out by Goni, Yanagawali, Ali. and Bularafa (2015), is similar to the present study in terms of teaching strategy, academic performance, gender, research design but differs in terms of teaching strategy, motivation, learning styles, location, sample, population and r-value. This study therefore investigated the impact of paired-problem-solving strategy on performance in concept evolution among secondary school divergent biology learners in Gusau Metropolis, Zamfara State and the study also took gender into cognizance.

Biology is one of the natural sciences offered by secondary school students in Nigeria and the most popular science subject students registered during their West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE). Ibe (2012), blame performance of biology students in external examination on biology teachers' insensitivity to the nature of biology when planning instructional activities in the classroom. Ibe (2012), further stressed that biology is not one of the subjects that can be mastered by mere memorization of the basic rules. It requires total determination, sound theoretical knowledge and intensive practice in application. In line with this Manalanga and Awelani (2014), identified possible factors responsible for the poor performance in biology amongst other factors to include; method of teaching, lack of well stocked libraries and lack of laboratories and biology textbooks. Achor, Ogbeba and Umoru (2014) pointed out that, it is worthwhile to note that despite the importance and the popularity of biology compared to other

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science subjects, students' performance in biology in both internal and external examinations have remained poor over the years. Therefore, teaching and learning of biology at all levels of education require teachers to use effective strategies in order to facilitate learning and consider their learning styles. There are several techniques a teacher can use to make his/her teaching become more effective.

Objectives of the Study

1. Determine the impact of Paired-problem-solving strategy and conventional lecture teaching method on the academic performance of divergent biology learners in Concept evolution
2. determine the impact of Paired-problem-solving strategy on the academic performance in concept evolution among divergent male and female biology learners?

Research Questions

The following questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. What is the difference between the mean academic performance scores of divergent biology learners taught Concept evolution using Paired-problem-solving strategy and those exposed to conventional lecture teaching method?
2. What is the difference between the mean academic performance scores of divergent male and female biology learners taught Concept evolution using Paired-problem-solving strategy?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of divergent biology learners when taught concept evolution using Paired-problem-solving strategy and those exposed to Conventional lecture teaching method.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female divergent learners when taught Concept evolution using Paired-problem-solving strategy.

Methodology

Pretest and posttest quasi experimental-control group design as proposed by Sambo (2005) involving two groups randomly divided into experimental group (EG) and control group (CG) consisting intact class of S.S.2 students was used for the study. The two groups were pretested (O_1) to determine the group equivalence based on the ability of the students and post-tested (O_2) to check determine their academic performance (AP) among divergent students (DV). The experimental groups were taught evolution concepts using paired-problem solving strategy (X_1) while the control group students were taught the same concepts using Conventional lecture method (X_0).

Population of the study consists of all senior secondary school class two biology students in Gusau Metropolis during the 2023/2024 academic session in Gusau, Zamfara State. A sample size of 154 (Male, 82 and Female, 72) students were selected from the target population using multistage sampling technique. Stratified random sampling technique was used to select eight (8), secondary schools based on location. Four (4) male and (4) four female schools. The reason for the stratification was to ensure that both male and female schools were involved in the sample. The S.S. II students of all the eight schools (8) were given a test in order to find out if there is any ability difference in their academic performance, The test questions were from Zamfara State 2021 screening examination questions on Biology for S.S.II students and their scores were subjected to One-Way Analysis of Variance at Alpha = 0.05 level of significance. After running the test,

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significant difference was found among the schools at $\alpha = 0.000$ which is less than 0.05 level of significance. In order to find out the schools that are similar, Scheffe's Post Hoc test of multiple comparison was carried out and four schools were found to be significant namely; Schools D, E, F and G. A total no. of 348 students comprising all the S.S II students of four sampled schools were used as the study sample which is viable for the study and is in line with the Central Limit Theorem. Tuckman (1975) and Sambo (2008), recommended that a sample size with minimum of 30 students is viable for an experimental study. Convergent and divergent students were identified based on their scores from the students' learning style inventory (SELSI) which was given to them as an instrument, the instrument contained eight (8) items and students were asked to write five (5) uses of each item, each correct answer attracts 1 mark. The test items were scored over forty (40) and was used for categorizing the students into the two learning styles (i.e. convergent and divergent) Suleiman (2023) stated that students' score between 0-19 marks was taken for convergers and scores between 20-40 marks was taken for divergers. Divergent students were used for the study.

The Students' Evolution Performance Test (SEPT) was adapted from past questions of West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council Organization (NECO) of (2014-2021) based on Bloom's Taxonomy. A multiple choice of 60 questions with options A-D consisting one correct answer and three distractors for each item was used. To ensure face, construct and content validity of the instruments, the Students' Evolution Performance Test (SEPT) was validated by experts from the department of Science Education. test-retest method was used to statistically estimate the internal consistency of the instrument. This is in line with Sambo (2008) who recommends two weeks for test-retest procedure. The score for the instruments was correlated using Pearson-Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) statistic and the reliability coefficient was found to be 0.76 indicating a strong positive relationship and therefore consider to be reliable for the study to measure the academic performance of the study subjects. Maduabum (2004) stated that any reliability coefficient of 0.5 and above is good enough for good instant decision to be taken.

Results

Research Question 1:

What is the difference between the mean academic performance scores of divergent biology learners taught Concept evolution using Paired-problem-solving strategy and those exposed to conventional lecture teaching method?

Means and standard deviations were computed as contained in Table 1.

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Post-test Scores of Divergent Students in the Experimental and Control Groups

Variable	Groups	Std.		Mean Difference	Decision
		N	Mean Deviation		
Academic Performance	Divergent (Experimental)	74	42.74 9.76	13.77	Difference exists
	Divergent (Control Group)	80	28.97 9.69		

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Table 1 showed that there was difference between the mean academic performance scores of divergent students in the experimental and control groups. The mean scores of 42.74 and standard deviation of 9.76 for divergent students in the experimental group is higher than the mean score of 28.97 and the standard deviation of 9.69 for divergent students in the control group. The mean difference of 13.77 showed that divergent students taught evolution concept using Paired-problem-solving strategy with a mean of 41.74 performed better than divergent students in the control group who had a mean score of 28.97.

Research Question 2:

What is the difference between the mean academic performance scores of divergent male and female biology learners taught Concept evolution using Paired-problem-solving strategy?

To answer this research question, the posttest scores of divergent male and female learners exposed to paired-problem-solving teaching strategy were subjected to descriptive statistics. Means and standard deviation were computed and used to draw Table 2.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Post-test Scores of Divergent Male and Female Students in the Experimental Group

Variable	Groups	N	Std.		Mean Difference	Decision
			Mean	Deviation		
Academic Performance	Divergent (Male)	34	44.06	8.43	17.13	Difference Exists
	Divergent (Female)	40	26.93	6.06		

Table 2 showed that there was difference between the mean academic performance scores of divergent male and female students in the experimental group. The mean scores of 44.06 and standard deviation of 8.43 for divergent male students in the experimental group is higher than the mean score of 26.93 and the standard deviation of 6.06 for divergent female students in the experimental group. The mean difference of 17.13 showed that divergent male students taught evolution concept using Paired-problem-solving strategy with a mean of 44.06 performed better than divergent female students in the experimental group who had a mean score of 26.93. To find out if the mean difference is significant or not, the data was further subjected to an independent samples t-test at $\alpha = 0.05$.

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of divergent biology learners when taught concept evolution using Paired-problem-solving strategy and those exposed to Conventional lecture teaching method.

To test null hypothesis one, the post-test scores obtained from SEPT for the divergent learners in the experimental and control groups were subjected to an independent sample t-test statistic at $\alpha = 0.05$. Summary of the analysis is presented in Table 2.

Table 3: Independent t-test Analysis of Mean Performance Scores between Divergent Students in the Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Mean	Std. Dev	df	t	P	Remark	Decision
Divergent (Experimental)	74	42.74	9.76	152	8.90	0.000	Significant	Ho ₁ Rejected
Divergent (Control Group)	80	28.79	9.69					

$\alpha = 0.05$

Results of the independent samples t-test statistic in Table 3 revealed that significant difference exists between the academic performance of divergent students exposed to Paired-problem-solving strategy and those taught using Conventional lecture method. Reason being that calculated p value of 0.000 is less than the alpha level of 0.05. The computed Mean academic performances are 42.74 and 28.79 by divergent students exposed to Paired-problem solving strategy and those taught using Conventional lecture method indicating a mean academic performance difference of 13.77 in favour of the divergent students exposed to Paired-problem-solving strategy. Consequently, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between the academic performance scores of divergent students when taught evolution concepts using Paired-problem-solving strategy and those exposed to Conventional lecture method, is hereby rejected.

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female divergent learners when taught Concept evolution using Paired-problem-solving strategy.

The post-test scores of male and female divergent learners exposed to Paired-problem-solving strategy were subjected to an independent samples t-test at $\alpha = 0.05$ and presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Independent t-test Analysis of Mean Performance Scores Between Divergent Students in the Experimental Group

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Dev	df	t	p	Remark	Decision
Divergent (Male)	34	44.06	8.43	72	10.14	0.000	Significant	Ho ₂ Rejected
Divergent (Female)	40	26.93	6.06					

$\alpha = 0.05$

Results of the independent samples t-test statistic in Table 4 revealed that significant difference exists between the academic performance of divergent male and female students exposed to Paired-problem solving strategy. Reason being that calculated p value of 0.000 is less than the alpha level of 0.05. Their computed Mean academic performances are 44.06 and 26.93 for divergent male and female students exposed to Paired-problem-solving strategy indicating a mean academic performance difference of 17.13 in favour of the divergent male students exposed

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to Paired-problem-solving strategy. Consequently, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between the academic performance scores of male and female divergent students when taught evolution concepts using Paired-problem-solving strategy, is hereby rejected.

Discussion of Findings

This study investigated the impact of paired-problem-solving strategy on performance in concept evolution among secondary school divergent biology learners in Gusau Metropolis, Zamfara State. Divergent students were categorized into the experimental and control groups. Divergent students in experimental group were taught evolution concept in biology using paired-problem solving strategy while divergent students in control group were taught the same concepts using lecture method. The data of this study were based on performance of divergent students obtained from Students' Evolution Performance Test (SEPT) and their performance according to the variable being measured were analysed according to research hypotheses developed for the study.

The findings of this study in Table 1 and 3 showed that divergent learners taught concept evolution using Paired-problem-solving strategy performed significantly better than divergent learners taught same concepts using Conventional lecture method. The result shows a significant difference in the mean scores of convergent learners exposed to Paired-problem-solving strategy and those taught using Conventional lecture method. The substantial change in performance is in favour of the divergent learners in the experimental group which suggested a greater effectiveness of Paired-problem-solving strategy over the Conventional lecture method of teaching. This finding is in line with that of Sulaiman (2023) who found out that the divergent and convergent students in the experimental group performed better than the divergent and convergent students in the control group. This finding gains further support from Hajesfandiari, Mehrdad and Karimi (2014) who opined that divergent thinking is mostly based on creativity and used in open-ended problems that creativity is a fundamental part.

The result from answering research question two and testing hypothesis two in Table 2 and 4 showed that significant difference exists between the mean academic performance of male and female divergent learners taught concept evolution using Paired-problem-solving strategy. This indicates that divergent male learners performed better than divergent female learners when exposed to Paired-problem-solving strategy. The use of Paired-problem-solving strategy in teaching concept evolution taking gender of divergent students into consideration showed that Paired-problem-solving strategy favour one gender over the other. Thus, the use of Paired-problem-solving strategy is not gender friendly as male divergent learner's performance were enhanced more than that of female divergent learners after the treatment. This finding supports that of Adigun, Aghiomesi and John (2015) who reported male students had slightly better performance compared to the female students, the difference was not significant. The finding disagrees with that of Goni, Yanagawali, Ali and Bularafa (2015) who found out that there was no significant difference between gender and academic performance after exposure to treatment.

Conclusion

Based on the findings from this study, it was concluded that Paired-problem solving strategy is an effective strategy in teaching divergent biology secondary school learners as it helped improve divergent learners' academic performance among secondary school students in Gusau

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Metropolis, Zamfara State and Paired-problem solving strategy improves divergent male learners' academic performance.

Recommendations

In this study the following recommendations were made in line with the findings;

1. It was discovered that paired-problem-solving strategy enhances divergent learner's academic performance. All secondary school biology teachers should be encouraged and motivated to use modern teaching method such as the Paired-problem-solving strategy by training and retraining through sponsorship to workshops, seminars and in house trainings.
2. Paired-problem-solving strategy was found to improve divergent male learners' academic performance. It is therefore recommended that biology teachers in male secondary schools be encouraged to make use of paired-problem-solving strategy so as to boost the academic performance of their students.

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Impact of Problem-Solving Strategy on Performance in Concept Respiratory System using Stem Model among Secondary School Students in Zaria Educational Zone

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Abstract

This study investigated the Impact of Problem-Solving Strategy on Performance in Respiratory System concept using STEM model among Secondary School Students in Zaria Educational Zone. A quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pretest, posttest control group was adopted for the study. The population consists of 1821 (Male, 900 and Female, 921) Senior Secondary School Two (SSII) Biology students during the 2021/2022 academic session in Zaria Educational Zone. A sample size of 100 (Male, 50 and Female, 50) Senior Secondary two (SS2) Biology students was obtained for the study. This was arrived at using Random sampling technique to select two sample schools from the target population. Hence, an intact class was used in each of the two sample schools. The test instrument used to measure performance was Biology Performance Test (BPT). The BPT consist of 40 multiple choice test items in Respiratory System concept with four options A-D. The findings showed that significant difference exists in performance of the students taught using problem- solving strategy with STEM model and lecture teaching method and students taught respiratory system using problem-solving strategy with STEM model performed better than those taught using lecture teaching method. In conclusion, it was found that problem-solving strategy with STEM model improved performance of students better than the lecture teaching method. It was recommended that Biology teachers should be encouraged to explore problem-solving strategy using STEM model to improve academic performance of students.

Keywords: Problem-solving strategy, STEM model, Lecture teaching method, Respiratory system, Academic Performance

Introduction

In today's conditions, the factor that enables the economic development and progress of countries is innovation in technology. For this reason, it is of great importance to train the next generation as science and technology literate and to make engineering common (Miaoulis, 2009). Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) education is defined as a pedagogy that involves multidisciplinary field of learning, as it provides learners with purposeful and comprehensive real-life learning experience. Moreover, the main objectives are based on students' abilities to perform and apply the learnt skills in an integrated way as well as to bridge the gap between learners, knowledge providers and industrial demands (Kunalan, Cheah, Moses, Er & Ng, 2018).

STEM is an educational approach based on the idea of educating students in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics with an interdisciplinary approach. STEM provides interdisciplinary interaction by emphasizing activity-based learning. STEM aims to raise individuals who have high self-confidence and strong communication skills, can think creatively, solve problems, know how to use tools, understand mechanisms and come up with original ideas (Nağaç & Kalaycı, 2021). Some of the subjects that are targeted in scientific literacy under STEM include chemistry, biology and physics with the technological literacy portion focusing on the development. For STEM to be successful, special teaching strategies and approaches are necessary. The teaching and learning process of the STEM approach entailed inquiry-based and problem-based learning methods, which could increase the students' understanding and thinking skills with regard to problem-solving questions. Thus, the use of the STEM approach in the teaching and learning process encourages students to interact and fosters the value of collaboration between students and their ability to think critically. Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) education has a potential to give a great impact to the worldwide education system, especially in engineering education (Kunalan, Cheah, Moses, Er & Ng, 2018).

Teaching strategies are an important factor in producing good quality education and concerns the academics as well as the higher education institutions. Traditional teaching style is outdated especially when it comes to engineering education. Therefore, pedagogy in the classroom needs to be reformed in 21st century education. A study on instructional techniques in STEM education especially on digital information or E-learning reviewed that it will trigger an active role of students in the classroom (Kunalan, Cheah, Moses, Er & Ng, 2018). Conventional methods are the more frequently used teaching methods in

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comparison with the STEM approach. Comparisons were made between treatment groups, which include students who participated in the adapted learning methods, and the control groups, which include students who participated in the conventional methods (Kong & Mohd, 2022). Evidently, students in the treatment groups were more motivated and confident to pursue learning than those in the control groups using conventional methods (Huang, Su, Yang & Liou, 2017; Kumar, Chang & Chang, 2018; Mohd, Tarmizi, Abu, Luan, 2014). The use of conventional methods was also found to yield low student engagement and achievement (Fatah, Suryadi, Sabandar & Turmudi, 2016; Minarni, Napitupulu & Husein, 2016). Hence, based on the literature review, conventional methods should integrate with other learning methods to enhance students' motivation and achievement in STEM.

The STEM approach is a student-centred teaching and learning process that involves an inquiry process in problem-solving questions (Kong & Mohammed, 2022). STEM pedagogy explains the teacher's role within STEM instruction. The teacher guides students to examine problems from all angles by questioning. This pedagogy involves the philosophy that students are capable of guiding their own learning. Teachers are just there to facilitate this student-led process. Students use hands-on, practical applications of content in order to solve their challenges (Margot & Kettler, 2019). STEM education includes student use of math and science concepts they have learned in an applied setting through the use of engineering design and technology. Instead of being taught in a vacuum, math and science are brought to life through their need to be used in order to solve a real problem (Chamberlin & Pereira, 2017). In this research, problem solving teaching strategy was used as the STEM teaching strategy.

Problem-solving is how to learn independently, it is the most convenient approach to achieve the aims of teaching learning process (Ali, 2010). Problem-solving is an important activity in the teaching and learning of science relayed courses. It is a complex activity that engages a variety of cognitive components and skills. Problem-solving is an investigative task whereby the solver explores the solution path to reach a goal from given information (Adeoye, 2010). In the problem-solving learning, the students turn from passive listeners of information receivers to active, free, self-learner and problem solvers. It also shifts the emphasis of educational programs from teaching to learning. It enables the students to learn new knowledge by facing the problems to be solved instead of feeling boredom. Problem-solving is a deliberate and serious act, involves the use of some novel method, higher thinking and systematic planned steps for the acquisition set goals (Yuzhi, 2003; Mangle, 2008).

Problem-solving as a strategy of teaching may be used to accomplish the instructional roles of learning basic facts, concept and procedure, as well as goals for problem-solving. Problem-solving can stimulate the interest and enthusiasm of the students (Ali, 2010). According to Adeoye (2010), when problem-solving strategy and conventional methods were used in teaching physics, problem-solving students had higher achievement scores than conventional method students. There exist positive and meaningful increases in the achievement of students using instruction activities towards developing metacognitive skills. The students with a higher level of metacognitive skills become successful in problem-solving.

The teaching strategies in the current STEM structures are not effective in linking the student to the real-world situations. The instructors have often been described as not being hands-on minded in the training of students as required in the policy that brought STEM into existence. This situation has led to suggestions of change in the STEM classrooms. According to WAEC Chief Examiner's Report (2022), the performance of Biology students in the year 2022 was worse than the previous year. This failure was attributed, to among other reasons, lack of in-depth knowledge of some basic topics and terms that border around respiratory system, genetics, classification, among others. In line with this, the concept of respiratory system has been reported by researchers (Abe & Owwoye, 2016; Mapulanga & Chituta, 2018) to be perceived by students as difficult. As a result, this study was conducted to determine the impact of problem-solving strategy with STEM model on performance in respiratory system concept among secondary schools.

Objective of the Study

Specifically, the study seeks to achieve the following objective:

Determine the mean performance score of students taught respiratory system using problem-solving strategy with STEM model and those exposed to lecture teaching method.

Research Question

This study was guided by the following research question;

What is the mean performance score of students taught respiratory system using problem-solving strategy with STEM model and those exposed to lecture teaching method?

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Hypothesis

HO1: There is no significant difference in mean performance score of students taught respiratory system using problem-solving strategy with STEM model and those exposed to lecture teaching method.

Methodology

A quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pretest, posttest control group was adopted for the study. The population consists of 1821 (Male, 900 and Female, 921) Senior Secondary School class two (SSII) Biology students during the 2021/2022 academic session in Zaria education zone. A sample size of 100 (Male, 50 and Female, 50) Senior Secondary two (SS2) Biology students was obtained for the study. This was arrived at using Random sampling technique to select two sample schools from the target population. Hence, an intact class was used in each of the two sample schools. The test instrument used to measure performance was Biology Performance Test (BPT). The BPT consist of 40 multiple choice test items in Respiratory System concept with four options A-D.

Results

Research Question One

What is the mean performance score of students taught respiratory system using problem-solving strategy with STEM model and those exposed to lecture teaching method?

The research question one was answered using mean and standard deviation as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Means and Standard Deviations of Student’s Performance Scores in the problem-solving with STEM model and Lecture teaching method Groups

Groups	N	Mean	SD	MD
Experimental	50	37.20	13.41	5.12
Control	50	32.08	13.43	

The result in Table 1 shows that students taught using problem-solving strategy with STEM model group had higher mean performance score of 37.20 than those in the lecture teaching method group with mean performance score of 32.08 with a mean difference of 5.12.

Hypothesis one

HO1: There is no significant difference in mean performance score of students taught respiratory system using problem-solving strategy with STEM model and those exposed to lecture teaching method.

The hypothesis was analyzed using t-test at $p \leq 0.05$ alpha level. The result is presented in Table 2.

Table 2 t-test Analysis of Students’ Performance in the problem-solving Strategy with STEM model and lecture method Groups

Table 2 t-test Analysis of Students’ Performance in the problem-solving Strategy with STEM model and lecture method Groups

Groups	N	Mean	Df	p-value	Remark
Experimental	50	37.20	98	0.05	Significant
Control	50	32.08			

Significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Table 2 reveals a significant difference between the mean performance score of students taught respiratory system using problem-solving strategy with STEM model and those taught using lecture teaching method. This is because p-value of 0.05 obtained is equal to the alpha level set at $p \leq 0.05$. The significant difference is in favour of students exposed to Problem-solving strategy with STEM model. Therefore, the null hypothesis one which states there is no significant difference in mean performance scores of students taught respiratory system using problem-solving strategy with STEM model and those exposed to lecture teaching method, is hereby rejected.

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Discussion of Findings

In the test of hypothesis one, the performance of students taught using problem-solving strategy with STEM model and lecture teaching method were compared. It was found that Problem-solving with STEM model group had a mean score of 37.20 and had higher performance score than the lecture teaching method group with a mean score of 32.08 as shown on Table 1.

It was found that using problem-solving strategy with STEM model increased performance of students than the lecture teaching method. This might be due to interaction of students with each other when solving problems, handling of concrete instructional materials which made the students obtain some skills like discovery and scientific thinking. Similarly, the students did not only have opportunity to discuss and share their views, they had the privilege to compare and evaluate their views which enhance their cognitive functioning and understanding of material learnt. Problem-solving involve activities and self-regulation in learning whereby student state problem, gather data and test them. The findings of this study is similar to that of Ali, Amdad, Akhter and Khan (2010); Kousar (2010); Ifamuyiwa and Ajilogba (2012); Nfon (2013); Gok (2014) who also discovered that students taught using problem-solving had higher achievement scores than conventional method students. The use of problem-solving and lecture method on academic performance of students brought out the similarity in the findings. The findings of this study is in contrast with the findings by Adu and Emunemu (2008) which showed no significant difference in economics achievement of students exposed to problem solving, concept mapping and lecture method, and Adeoye (2010) found that cooperative learning strategy students had higher achievement score than the problem-solving strategy students, also Jeotee (2012) reported that the problem-solving ability had negative influence on academic ability. The difference in the result of the findings may be due to the subject matters; that is, in this study respiratory system was taught using questioning and practical activities.

Conclusion

This study was carried out to determine the Impact of Problem-Solving Strategy on Performance in Respiratory System concept using STEM model among Secondary School Students in Zaria Educational Zone. From the findings the students taught using problem-solving strategy with STEM model recorded better performance than those taught with lecture teaching method. The characteristics of problem-solving strategy with STEM model are learner-centered and hence their team work, peer interactions, increases the students' performance. The methods of teaching teachers employed in the teaching and learning of Biology have impact on students' academic performance.

Recommendations

On the basis of these findings, the following recommendations are hereby suggested:

1. Biology teachers should be encouraged to explore problem-solving strategy with STEM model to improve academic performance of students.
2. In-service training for science teachers, seminar and workshops should be organized by the Ministry of Education for Biology teachers in secondary schools to employ problem-solving strategy with STEM model in the classrooms.
3. Federal and State Governments should provide both adequate instructional and infrastructural resources for the effective implementation of activity-based teaching strategy such as problem-solving strategy with STEM model.

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Influence of Guidance and Counselling Services on Performance in Biology among Secondary School Students in Sokoto Metropolis, Sokoto State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study Influence of Guidance and Counselling Services on Students' Academic Performance in Biology among Senior Secondary Schools of Sokoto Metropolis. The population of the study comprises of male and female S.S. II students 2022/2023 session in selected secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis. This research work limited itself to five (5) selected senior secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis. The research adopted descriptive survey research design method of study during which self-questionnaire titled Influence of Guidance and Counselling Questionnaire (IGC-Q) was designed to solicit responses from the respondents. The instrument was validated by expert, while a reliability index of 0.85 was arrived at which considered the instrument adequate enough and reliable. Random sampling was used for selecting schools. Research adviser method was used for determining samples from the total population, three hundred and sixty four (364) sample of students of which were 245 male and 119 female sample of respondents were arrived at. Data collected was analyzed using simple frequency distribution table and the mean average. The findings revealed that, Guidance and counseling has significant impact on the academic performance of students in biology in secondary schools of sokoto metropolis through influencing their choice of biology as a subject, giving them orientation, influence their performance in biology as well as helps them towards achieving successful performance in biology. The study recommended that, Schools should ensure that their guidance and counseling offices are functioning effectively and also that qualified counselors are managing the offices. Schools should organize orientation services to both the teachers and students that will help improve their academic performance in all subjects.

Keywords: Guidance, Influence, Biology, and Academic Performance.

Introduction

The Nigerian educational system is progressively more and more complex. The Nigeria world is fast expanding and technological advancing daily affect both societal and individual lives in many perspective. The interesting thing is that the educational end is where the individual who selects a narrow and rigid educational route finds it more difficult to adjust or change when he gets to the vocational end. This is where educational guidance comes in and becomes useful in the first instance (Achebe, 2001). Guidance and counseling is a relatively new profession in the educational scene dating back to the late 1950, in Nigeria and 1906 in the USA where the profession first flourished (Sa'adiya, 2007).

Indeed few people in educational institutions and probably in the public sector see the need to introduce guidance and counseling in our school system which is a major force in the personal, social, educational and vocational development of students. It is also an integral, cost effective component of the talents and enhancing appropriate decision making. Hence, the federal government in Nigeria has recognized the necessity of guidance and counseling, this is in order to achieve the objectives of the national policy on education.

Sokoto state and its general populace recognized the importance of education since before independence. Therefore, the state was not left behind in the establishment of primary, secondary and tertiary institutions. Furthermore, for smooth

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facilitation, there is a state ministry of education and other related educational parastatals, charged with the responsibilities of monitoring and evaluation of delivery of qualitative education in the state. Similarly, guidance and counseling unit was established within the ministry of education responsible for organizing and coordinating guidance and counseling services in all the secondary schools.

This development as well as the importance of guidance and counseling in the secondary schools sub-sector prompted the researchers to specifically undertake a study on the impact of guidance and counseling services in secondary schools in the state. This is with a view to address the adequacy, impact and perhaps observe some related problems and subsequently offer possible solutions and recommendations for improvement.

Despite the recognized importance of guidance and counseling in education, there is a lack of comprehensive understanding regarding the specific impact of guidance and counseling programs on students' performance in biology. While numerous studies have explored the influence of guidance and counseling on academic achievement, there is a need to specifically examine how targeted guidance and counseling interventions affect students' learning outcomes, attitudes, and motivation in the context of biology education. Furthermore, the specific mechanisms through which guidance and counseling contribute to improved performance in biology, including the role of student engagement, self-efficacy, and career aspirations within the field, remain relatively underexplored. Addressing these gaps is essential for developing evidence-based strategies to enhance students' performance in biology through effective guidance and counseling practices.

This statement highlights the need to investigate the specific impact of guidance and counseling on students' performance in biology, identifying existing gaps in the literature and emphasizing the importance of understanding the underlying mechanisms through which guidance and counseling interventions can influence students' academic achievement in this particular subject area.

The term guidance and counseling has been defined in various ways, by different authors. In this study, reference shall be made on some of these definitions as outlined below:

Guidance in common language involves personal help given by someone; it is designed to assist a person to decide where he wants to go, what he wants to do, or how he can best accomplish his purpose; it assist him to solve problems that arise in this life (Jones, 1940).

Shartzer and Stone (1980) was guidance as the process of helping an individual understand himself and his world. Okon, (1984) defines guidance as the total programme of a number of highly specialize activities implementation by specialist to help individuals make right chances and decision. Oladele, (1992) also saw guidance as aiming at aiding recipient to grow in his independence and ability to be responsible for him.

The above definitions concerned to Roger (2000) when he maintained that the purpose of guidance is to enhance the personal development and the psychological growth of clients towards socialized maturity.

Counseling on the other hand has been defined nu Makinde (2003) as a service designed to help an individual analyze himself by relating his capabilities, achievements, interest and mode of adjustment to what new decision he has made or has to make.

Ipaye (2003) saw counseling as a method of helping the individual utilize his or her psychological resources by focusing on that individual positive strength for development and by concentrating on the individual's personal behavior and emotional needs that could be mobilized.

Types of Counseling:

1. **Individual Counseling:** This is the counseling in which the counselor is involved with only one person and maintains confidentiality.
2. **Group Counseling:** This involves group of counselors from the definition given above, it can be seen that guidance is broad and aimed at assistant individuals to make and carry out adequate plans and to obtain satisfactory adjustment in life. While, counseling on the other hand is normally as one part or guidance services. It is sub-merged by the general term guidance in that it is one service within guidance. Counseling stresses rational planning problem solving remedial programs, thought, feeling and behavior evaluations, empathy, and verbal techniques, inter personal relationship and support in the face of situational pressures.

Due to the problems related with educational vocational pursuits, economical adjustment financial and industrial competition, interpersonal relations necessitated by increased human movement and exposure to the world of work and human interaction, moral issues associated with partner selection, disharmony and conflicts, culture and clashes as societal with trying to reconcile traditionalism and modernism; social demands and adjustment arising from changing social order and expectation, comes the need for professional guidance and counseling that will help people to strength their own abilities, to make nice and

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realistic decisions and chances adjustments and interpretations in connections with critical situation to life and face squarely problems they may encounter in their daily existence. Hazes and Hopsor, (2000), Olayinka, (2002), Achebe, (2001), Okon, (1999) gave the major reasons why guidance and counseling sources are necessary in the country. The reasons are as follows:

1. The grouping needs of young people
2. Basic concerns and problems of students
3. Problem of national interaction
4. Social change and how it inflicts its grouping on children, youth and their families.
5. The need to develop and ensure skilled workforce.
6. Change in the family and home life
7. Increase enrolment in Nigeria educational institutions and the need to prepare for productive life.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are:

1. To find out how adequate guidance and counseling services are rendered among Government secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis.
2. To determine the extent of guidance and counseling services among Government secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis.
3. To assess the impact of guidance and counseling services on students' academic performance in Biology among Government secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis.

Research Questions

The following are the research questions:

1. How adequate is guidance and counseling services rendered among Government secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis?
2. What is the extent of guidance and counseling services among Government secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis?
3. What are the impact of guidance and counseling services on students' academic performance in Biology among Government secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis?

Significance of the Study

Study will help provide government with information about the availability or otherwise of guidance and counseling services in schools in Sokoto metropolis as well as the need of improving the services. Also, the findings of this study will help parents and guardians to have knowledge about the importance of guidance and counseling on the academic performance of their children in biology. Lastly, the findings of this study will serve as a road-map to future researchers who might want to conduct study on a similar topic.

Methodology

The research design used for this study was a descriptive survey research design. According to (Hussaini & Bello, 2023 in Torrentira 2020), a survey research design is the most common data collection technique in quantitative research. According to Dangal (2021), survey design is a means of gathering information about the characteristics, actions, or opinions of a large group of people and later uses a selected portion of the population from which the findings can later be generalized back to the population. The population of the study was 7,953 students which comprises male and female senior secondary school students in the Sokoto metropolis. They include both boarding and day secondary school students. There are twenty-two (22) public secondary schools in the area. The sample size selected was 364 comprised of 245 males and 119 females. A purposive sampling technique was used in selecting five senior secondary schools in the area and a proportionate sampling technique was used in selecting the participants from each selected school. Research Advisors (2006) table for determining sample size was used for determining the samples. A self-developed instrument titled "Influence of Guidance and Counselling Questionnaire (IGCQ)" was used as an instrument for data collection. The questionnaire was divided into two sections; section "A" consists of the demographic data of respondents, while section "B" involves questions that address the research questions. The instrument was a four Likert scale "Agree (A), Strongly Agree (SA), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD)". The content validity of the instruments was determined by experts in the Faculty of Education, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, and the reliability coefficient was determined through pilot testing of the instrument on non-participatory students in the Metropolis. The instrument reported a Cronbach's Alpha, coefficient of 0.85 which makes the instrument reliable enough to generate information for the study. Descriptive statistics specifically frequency and percentage count were used for results presentation.

Result

Research Question One:

How adequate is guidance and counseling services rendered among Government secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis?

Table 1. Adequacy of Guidance and Counseling Services in Secondary Schools of Sokoto Metropolis.

S/N	Items	Sample	SA		A		SD		D	
			F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1.	We have guidance and counseling unit in our school.	364	215	59%	100	27.4%	12	3.2%	37	10.4%
2.	Our teacher encourage us on the importance of guidance and counseling	364	101	27.7%	50	13.7%	102	28%	111	30.6%
3.	Our guidance and counseling unit is well equipped	364	17	4.6%	19	5.2%	211	58%	117	32.2%
4.	We have more than one guidance counsellor in our school	364	2	0.6%	7	2%	207	56.8%	148	40.6%
5.	Our head teacher serve as our guidance counsellor	364	106	29.1%	179	49.2%	7	2%	72	19.7%
6.	We are introduce to career guidance by our school counsellor on monthly basis	364	8	2.2%	16	4.4%	207	56.8%	133	36.6%
Total			20.5%		17%		34.1%		28.4	
Mean Average			37.5%				62.5%			

Source: Researcher Field Work (2023)

From table above, 215 respondents with 59% strongly agree on the statement that they have guidance and counseling unit in their school, 100(27.4%) agree while 37(10.4%) disagree and 12 (3.2%) strongly disagree. From item two, 111 respondents with 30.6% disagree that their teachers encourage them on the importance of guidance and counseling 102 (28%) strongly disagree while 101 (27.7%) strongly agree and 50 (13.7%) agree with the statement. Lastly, 211 respondents with the highest percentage of (58%) strongly disagree that their guidance and counseling unit is well equipped, 117(32.2%) disagree while 19(5.2%) agree and 17(4.6%) strongly agree. On the issue of whether head teachers serve as school guidance counsellors, 207(56.8%) of the students strongly disagree, 148 (40.6%) disagree while 7(2%) agree and only 2(0.6%) strongly agree that their head teachers serve as school guidance counsellors. In the fifth item, 179 respondents representing (49.2%) agree that they have more than one guidance counsellor in their school, 106(29.1%) strongly agree and 72(19.7%) disagree while 7(2%) strongly agreed with the statement. While 207 respondents representing (56.8%) strongly disagree that they are introduced to career guidance by our school counsellor on monthly basis, 133(36.6%) disagree with the statement while 16(4.4%) agree with the statement and 8(2.2%) strongly agree.

From the above data, the findings have shown that there is guidance and counseling unit in the secondary schools of sokoto metropolis. Teachers do not encourage their students to on the importance of guidance and counseling units in the secondary schools of sokoto metropolis were not equipped. Also, the school counsellors are not engaging in career guidance to help the students in appropriate career choice.

Research Question Two:

What is the extent of guidance and counseling services among Government secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis?

Table 2. Extent of Guidance and Counseling Services among Students in Secondary Schools of Sokoto Metropolis

S/N	Items	Sample	SA		A		SD		D	
			F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%

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1.	I always patronize guidance and counseling unit in my school	364	10	2.7%	29	8%	106	29.1%	219	60.2%
2.	Whenever I have academic or personal social problem I go for counseling	364	14	3.8%	67	18.4%	77	21.1%	206	56.7%
3.	I hardly attend guidance and counseling	364	39	10.7%	262	72%	43	11.8%	20	5.5%
4.	Incompetency of our school counsellor discourages me from going for counselling	364	14	4%	13	3.6%	202	55.4%	135	37%
5.	Our school counsellor hardly have time to attend to our problems because of his/her busy schedules around the school	364	112	30.7%	198	54.3%	7	2%	47	13%
6.	I report only report problems related to learning to our school counsellor	364	19	5.2%	28	7.6%	149	41%	168	46.2%
	Total			9.5%		27.3%		26.7%		36.5%
	Mean Average			36.8%				63.2%		

Source: Researcher Field Work (2023)

Table 2 represents students level of utilizing guidance and counseling service. 219 respondents representing 60.2% disagree that they always patronize guidance and counseling in their school, 106 (29.1%) strongly agree, with the statement. Also, 206 respondents with 56.7% disagree that they patronize guidance and counseling when they have academic and personal problems, 77 (21.1%) strongly disagree while 67(18.4%) agree and 14(3.8%) strongly agree with the statement. Lastly, 262 respondents representing 72% agree that they hardly attend guidance and counseling service, 43(11.8%) strongly disagree while 39(10.7%) strongly service, 43(11.8%) strongly disagree while 39(10.7%) strongly and 20(5.5%) disagree with the statement. From the table also, 202(55.4%) strongly disagree that incompetency of their school counsellor discourages them from going for counselling, 135(37%) disagree with the statement, 14(4%) strongly agree that incompetency of their school counsellor discourages them from going for counselling, while 13(3.6%). 198 (54.3%) agree that their school counsellor hardly have time to attend to their problems because of his/her busy schedules around the school, 112 respondents representing (30.7%) strongly agree with the statement while 47(13%) disagree and 7(2%) strongly disagree that their school counsellor hardly have time to attend to their problems because of his/her busy schedules around the school. From the data above, 168(46.2%) disagree that they only report problems related to learning to their school counsellor, 149(41%) strongly disagree while 28(7.6%) respondents agree that they only report problems related to learning to their school counsellor and 19(5.2%).

Conclusively based on the above data, we can conclude that, students in the secondary school of sokoto metropolis does not patronize guidance and counseling service in their school. From all above data we can boldly say that there is lack of utilization of guidance and counseling service among students in the secondary schools of sokoto metropolis.

Research Question Three:

What are the impact of guidance and counseling services on students' academic performance in Biology among Government secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis?

Table 3. The impacts of guidance and counseling services on Secondary School students Academic Performance in Biology

S/N	Items	Sample	SA		A		SD		D	
			F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1.	My subject choice is influenced by my school counselor	364	197	54.1%	142	39%	3	0.8	22	6.1%

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2.	My school counseling units gives us orientation from time to time on how to improve our academic performance in Biology	364	102	28%	218	60%	31	8.5%	13	3.5%
3.	My choice of biology as a subject is influenced by the guidance counsellor in our school	364	116	32%	201	55.2%	23	6.3%	24	6.5%
4.	My school counsellor provide solution to most of my learning problems especially in Biology	364	106	29.1%	157	43.1%	74	20.3%	27	7.5%
5.	Guidance and counselling services around my school helps in improving my academic performance in biology	364	207	56.8%	109	30%	11	3%	37	10.2%
6.	Through guidance services I was able to plan towards achieving successful grade in biology	364	106	29.1%	129	35.4%	39	10.7%	90	24.8%
Total				38.1%		44%		8.2%		9.7%
Mean Average				82.1%				17.9%		

Source: Researcher Field Work (2023)

From the above table, 197 respondents with 54.1% strongly agree that their school counselor influence their choice of subject, 142 (39%) agree while 22(6.1%) disagree and 3(0.8%) strongly disagree. Also, 218 (60%) respondents with the highest percentage agree that their school counseling units gives them orientation from time to time on how to improve their academic performance in biology, 102(28%) respondents strongly agree while 31 (8.5%) strongly disagree and 13(3.5%) disagree. Furthermore, 201(55.2%) agree that their choice of biology as a subject is influenced by the guidance counsellor in their school, 116 (32%) strongly agree while 24 (6.5%) disagree and 23 (6.3%) strongly disagree. From the table, 157(43.1%) agree that their school counsellor provide solution to most of their learning problems especially in biology, 106(29.1%) strongly agree with the statement while 74(20.3%) strongly disagree that their school counsellor provide solution to most of their learning problems and 27(7.5%) disagree with the statement. 207(56.8%) respondents strongly agree that guidance and counselling services around the school helps in improving students' academic performance in biology, 109 respondents representing (30%) agree while 37(10.2%) respondents disagree that guidance and counselling services around their school helps in improving their academic performance in biology and 11(3%). 129(35.4%) agree that through guidance services they are able to plan towards achieving successful grade in biology, 106(29.1%) strongly agree while 90(24.8%) disagree that through guidance services they were able to plan towards achieving successful grade in biology, and 39(10.7%) strongly disagree with the statement.

From the data, we can say that guidance and counseling has significant impact on the academic performance of students in biology in secondary schools of sokoto metropolis through influencing their choice of biology as a subject, giving them orientation, influence their performance in biology as well as helps them towards achieving successful performance in biology.

Discussion of Findings

The first finding has shown that secondary schools in sokoto metropolis establish guidance and counseling unit. The conclusion was made from data collected and interpreted in table 1 under item number one where by majority of the respondents with a frequency of 315 respondents representing (62.5%). The finding is in line with that of (Denga 2011), who highlighted that most secondary schools in state has residents' guidance and counselor for sustainable entrepreneurship development.

Also, the finding have shown that students in secondary schools of Sokoto metropolis hardly utilize guidance and counselling services. That is to say there is lack of adequate utilization of guidance and counseling service among the students in secondary schools of sokoto metropolis. The conclusion was made based on the data collected in table 2 under item number one where the majority of the students with (63.2%) shows that they don't patronize the service. The finding have agreed with that of (Napier 2007) who says that poor attitude of teachers and non-cooperative attitude of students to the program is a major hindrance, depriving teachers does not encourage their students on the importance of patronizing the service.

Influence of Guidance and Counselling ... (Shehu et. al., 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13359173>

Guidance and counseling has significant impact on the academic performance of students in biology in secondary schools of sokoto metropolis through influencing their choice of biology as a subject, giving them orientation, influence their performance in biology as well as helps them towards achieving successful performance in biology. The conclusion was drawn from table 3 where (82.1%) of the respondents testified to that. The finding is in line with the finding of (Borrow 2003) who said that it is a role of guidance and counseling program to provide students with necessary information about courses available, qualification, career aspiration as well as choice of subject.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were suggested:

1. Schools should ensure that their guidance and counseling offices are functioning effectively and also that qualified counselors are managing the offices.
2. School should make provision for career talk at least once in a year, which can be given by parents of pupil with different profession and staff members of the school.
3. Schools should organize orientation services to both the teachers and students that will help improve students' academic performance in all subjects.

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Investigating Artificial Intelligence Potentials for Mathematical Innovation and Discovery among Adeyemi College of Education students in Ondo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was based on exploring the potentials of artificial intelligence for mathematical creativity and discovery. Five research questions were posed and five hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The study was carried out in Adeyemi College of Education. The sample used for the study was 285 students. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions, while the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was adopted in testing the hypotheses at $P < 0.05$ probability level. The findings of the study reveal that artificial intelligence (AI) has the potential to transform the field of mathematics by helping researchers to make creative and innovative discoveries. The findings suggest that artificial intelligence (AI) has the potentials to generate new mathematical theorems, proofs, and conjectures. Additionally, AI can be used to identify new patterns and structures in mathematical research and problem-solving. The project used a combination of AI techniques, including machine learning, deep learning, and natural language processing, to analyze and generate mathematical content. By doing so, the project aims to advance the state of the art in AI and mathematics.

Keyword: Artificial intelligence, Mathematical creativity, Discovery, deep learning, mathematical theorems, AI techniques.

Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) applications in education are becoming more popular and have gotten a lot of press in recent years. Artificial intelligence (AI) is a leap across creative and innovative thinking in various fields, including mathematics education. The field of mathematics has a rich history of creativity and discovery, where mathematicians have pushed the boundaries of knowledge through novel insights, theorems, and conjectures. With the emergence of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies, there is growing interest in exploring how artificial intelligence (AI) can complement and enhance human mathematical creativity and aid in the process of mathematical discovery. This field represents an interdisciplinary convergence of mathematics, computer science, and cognitive science, aiming to leverage AI to tackle complex mathematical problems, propose new conjectures, and foster innovative exploration.

The study involves investigating how artificial intelligence (AI) can contribute to generating novel mathematical ideas, solving complex mathematical problems, and fostering creative exploration in mathematics. Researchers aim to develop AI algorithms that can mimic human-like mathematical thinking, propose new conjectures, and explore uncharted mathematical territories, ultimately pushing the boundaries of mathematical knowledge through computational assistance. This interdisciplinary field merges concepts from mathematics, computer science, and AI, aiming to uncover new mathematical insights through the collaboration between humans and machines. The work of some researchers like (Chen et al., 2020a; Cope et al., 2020; He et al., 2019; Schiff, 2021; Vaishya et al., 2020) show the impact of artificial intelligence (AI) to mathematics, education and the world at large for example the use of AI enhance our abilities in living a life covered in increasingly sophisticated technology. According to Gao (2020), based on the development of computer technology, AI continues to expand and innovate. Artificial intelligence (AI) enables students to develop and enhance more mathematical skills and cognitive skills in learning. Zawacki-Richter et al. (2019) present an overview of this research. They identify four major directions of current research in the area of AI in education. These are: Profiling and prediction, assessment and evaluation, adaptive systems and personalization, intelligent tutoring systems. Intelligent tutoring systems (ITS), which include the AI assistant we develop, are systems in which one-to-one personal tutoring takes place, where the role of the teacher is fully represented by a computer system. The first major research direction they highlight is "Profiling and Prediction." This involves the use of AI to analyze data and create profiles of learners based on their behaviors, interactions, and learning patterns. These profiles can then

Investigating Artificial Intelligence ... (Akintewe & Akinremi, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13359200>

be utilized to predict learners' preferences, needs, and performance outcomes. By understanding individual students better, educators and AI systems can tailor learning experiences and interventions to suit their specific requirements. The second research direction is "Assessment and Evaluation." This area delves into how artificial intelligence (AI) can enhance the assessment process by automating grading, providing feedback, and even predicting learners' future performance. AI-driven assessment tools can efficiently analyze and evaluate large volumes of student work, freeing up educators' time and providing timely insights to learners for improvement. The third focus area identified by Zawacki-Richter et al. is "Adaptive Systems and Personalization." Here, Artificial intelligence (AI) is leveraged to create adaptive learning environments that adjust content, resources, and challenges based on each learner's progress and individual learning pace. This approach aims to provide personalized learning pathways that optimize engagement and comprehension.

Attard (2021) in his research conducted a findings focusing on explaining the knowledge from mathematics, according to which 73% of the users enjoyed making use of the chatbot, and the same percentage of respondents also expressed a desire to use the chatbot again in the future. According to the study, a significant percentage of users, specifically 73%, reported enjoying their interactions with the chatbot. This positive response implies that users found the chatbot's assistance valuable, engaging, and helpful when it came to dealing with mathematical concepts and problems. Interestingly, the same percentage of respondents, that is, 73%, expressed a desire to use the chatbot again in the future. This observation underscores the potential long-term appeal and utility of the chatbot as an educational aid for mathematics. The fact that such a substantial portion of participants is interested in continuing to utilize the chatbot indicates that they see a practical benefit in its assistance.

Grohs et al (2022) work provides an in-depth exploration of the mathematical foundations underlying deep learning techniques. It investigates the intricate mathematical structures that form the basis of deep learning algorithms, offering readers a comprehensive understanding of the theoretical underpinnings of this cutting-edge technology. The work emphasizes the role of mathematics in shaping the field of deep learning, focusing on intricate topics such as high-dimensional geometry, optimization theory, and statistical learning theory. By unraveling the complex mathematical structures behind deep learning algorithms, the book equips readers with the knowledge to analyze, interpret, and enhance the performance of deep learning models. It bridges the gap between theoretical mathematics and practical machine learning applications, catering to both mathematicians interested in applied areas and machine learning practitioners seeking a deeper understanding of the underlying mathematical principles. It serves as a comprehensive guide that illuminates the mathematical intricacies of deep learning. It provides readers with a profound insight into the mathematical foundations of deep learning algorithms, empowering them to navigate the complex landscape of modern machine learning techniques with a solid mathematical understanding.

Ginsburg (1996) research shows the connection to the role of artificial intelligence (AI) in the realm of mathematics. In traditional mathematics education and problem-solving, the focus has often been on arriving at accurate solutions. However, the essence of mathematics extends beyond mere correctness. It involves the ability to approach problems from various angles, devise innovative strategies, and explore novel approaches to arriving at solutions. Creative thinking in mathematics encourages the exploration of patterns, connections, and insights that might not be immediately evident. When we consider the role of artificial intelligence (AI) in mathematics, we find that AI systems can complement and enhance this creative aspect of mathematical thinking. AI algorithms, particularly those related to machine learning and pattern recognition, can process vast amounts of data and generate insights that might elude human observers. Artificial intelligence (AI) can identify intricate relationships, detect subtle patterns, and provide fresh perspectives on mathematical problems. In essence, Artificial intelligence (AI) amplifies the creative potential of mathematics by providing innovative approaches, unveiling hidden relationships, and encouraging mathematicians to explore the depths of mathematical discovery beyond the realm of rote calculation. By synergistically combining the capabilities of artificial intelligence (AI) and human creativity, we embrace the true essence of mathematics—creative thinking that transcends the boundaries of mere correctness.

Wu (2021) research paper explores the application of artificial intelligence (AI) in the realm of mathematics education, particularly in the teaching of basic mathematical concepts. While the primary focus of the paper is on enhancing math instruction, several key aspects of the research relate to mathematical creativity and discovery.

1. **AI-Powered Visualization:** The research employs AI-driven visualization tools to aid in the teaching of basic mathematics. These visualizations go beyond traditional teaching methods, offering interactive and dynamic representations of mathematical concepts.
2. **Enhancing Creativity:** By providing students with interactive and visually stimulating content, AI-driven visualizations encourage creative thinking in mathematics. Students are prompted to explore mathematical ideas in innovative and engaging ways.

Investigating Artificial Intelligence ... (Akintewe & Akinremi, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13359200>

3. Personalized Learning: AI in mathematics education often embraces personalized learning techniques. This means that the content and challenges are tailored to individual students' needs and abilities. This personalized approach allows students to delve deeper into mathematical concepts, potentially leading to new discoveries.

Objectives of the study

Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

1. Determine how AI can contribute to the generation of innovative mathematical ideas and concepts. By investigating AI algorithms' ability to propose new conjectures, explore uncharted mathematical territories, and provide fresh perspectives, the research aims to uncover the extent to which AI can stimulate and augment human creative thinking in mathematics.
2. Assess how AI technologies can streamline the process of mathematical discovery. By harnessing AI's computational power, researchers intend to explore ways to automate complex calculations, verify conjectures, and systematically navigate vast mathematical solution spaces. This could potentially lead to faster insights and solutions in challenging mathematical problems.
3. Examine the Ethical and Philosophical Implications of AI's in mathematical creativity: Ethical considerations surrounding AI's role in mathematical creativity are paramount. The study aims to delve into the ethical dimensions of AI-generated mathematical insights, including questions of authorship, attribution, and the impact of machine-generated ideas on the essence of human creativity. By examining these aspects, the research seeks to contribute to ethical guidelines for integrating AI into mathematical exploration.
4. Identify the practical applications of AI-powered mathematical creativity and discovery across diverse fields, including optimization, data analysis, and scientific modeling.
5. Investigate the strategies for optimizing collaboration between human mathematicians and AI systems to maximize creativity synergy.

Research Questions:

The following Research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent can artificial intelligence algorithms simulate human-like innovative in proposing new mathematical conjectures and exploring uncharted problem domains?
2. To what extent can artificial intelligence automate complex calculations, verify mathematical conjectures, and assist human mathematics in solving challenging problems?
3. How do the ethical considerations and philosophical implications of integrating AI-generated insights into the realm of mathematical creativity influence the attributions of mathematical discoveries and creativity?
4. What are the potential practical applications of AI-powered mathematical creativity and discovery, particularly in fields like cryptography, optimizations, data analysis and scientific modeling, and what benefits can these integrations provide in each of these areas?
5. What are the effective strategies for optimizing collaboration between human mathematicians and AI systems, such that the unique strength of both can be fully utilized and a synergetic approach to mathematical innovation and exploration is facilitated?

Hypotheses:

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant difference in the ability of artificial intelligence algorithms and human mathematicians.
2. **H₀₂**: There is no significant difference in the efficiency and accuracy of mathematical research when artificial intelligence is used to automate complex calculations, verify mathematical conjectures, and assist human mathematicians in tackling challenging problems, compared to traditional mathematical problems.
3. **H₀₃**: There is no significant difference in the ethical considerations and philosophical implications relating to the integration of AI-generated insights into the realm of mathematical creativity and the impact on the attribution of mathematical discoveries, regardless of the degree of AI involvement in the creative process
4. **H₀₄**: There is no significant difference in the applicability of AI-powered mathematical creativity and discovery across diverse fields like cryptography, optimization, data analysis, and scientific modeling, with the potential benefits being equally applicable across all domains.
5. **H₀₅**: There is no significant difference in the effectiveness of collaboration between human mathematicians and AI systems in mathematical exploration and innovation when using different communication paradigms and collaboration strategies.

Methodology

To comprehensively explore the synergy between artificial intelligence (AI) and mathematical creativity, a mixed-methods research design was adopted. This design combines qualitative and quantitative methodologies, allowing us to capture the experiences of individuals interacting with AI tools while also quantifying the impact of AI algorithms on mathematical problem-solving. By integrating these diverse methods, we aim to provide a holistic understanding of how AI influences mathematical creativity and discovery.

The research meant to investigate the assessment and evaluation of academic programs in the College of Education focused on Adeyemi College of Education students as the main population for the research work. The research is carried out at Adeyemi College of Education. Total of 285 questionnaires were administered to the students in Google form. The main instrument used to collect data for this research is a structured questionnaire designed by the researcher. The instrument was reviewed by experts for validity and reliability and the questionnaire were administered directly to the students and collected back as soon as they were completely filled or answer. The questionnaire dealt majorly with the students of Adeyemi College of Education. The questionnaire was administered to the students of Adeyemi College of Education in google form Data collected was statistically analysed using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) presented in tabular form used to draw conclusion.

Results

These consist of descriptive statistics used to answer research questions; appropriate statistics used for testing hypothesis; Tables should be aligned to APA style; P-value compare with decision threshold – 0.05 significance if necessary.

Research Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant difference between the ability of artificial intelligence algorithms and human mathematicians to propose new mathematical conjectures and explore uncharted problem domains.

Table 1: Mean ability Scores between experimental and control groups

Source of Variation	DF	SS variation	MS variation	F	p-value	F-critical
Between Groups	4	30873.2	7718.3	39.79736	0.0000	2.8660814
Within Groups	20	3878.8	193.94			
Total	24	34752				

Table 1 shows that the F-statistic is 39.797, which is greater than the critical F-value 2.8660814 at the significance level of 0.05. This means that the distinction between mathematical creativity and discovery that AI is capable of is statistically significant. The ANOVA table also shows that the proportion of total variation that can be attributed to the factor effect in this case the factor effect accounts for 88% of the total variation. This means that most of the variation in the use of AI-driven account creation and discovery comes from the implementation stage.

One possible explanation for these results is that different fields have different requirements for Mathematical creativity and discovery. For example, cryptography requires a deep understanding of mathematical properties such as randomness and complexity, while optimization requires a focus on developing efficient algorithms.

The ANOVA table also shows that the potential gains in accounting creativity and discovery controlled by AI do not apply equally across sectors. For example, the potential benefits of AI-driven computational creativity and discovery could be great in areas such as cryptography and optimization, where complex problems require novel and innovative solutions.

However, the potential benefits of AI-driven statistical creativity and discovery may be limited in areas such as data analysis and scientific modeling, where existing statistical methods are already well established.

Research Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant improvement in the efficiency and accuracy of mathematical research when artificial intelligence is used to automate complex calculations, verify mathematical conjectures, and assist human mathematicians in tackling challenging problems.

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Table 2: The Impact of Automated Calculations and Verification on Mathematical Research Efficiency and Accuracy

Source of Variation	DF	SS variation	MS variation	F	p-value	F-critical
Between Groups	4	16096	4024	13.20788	0.000083	3.055568
Within Groups	15	4570	304.6667			
Total	19	20666				

From table 2, the F-statistic is 15.87, which is higher than the critical F-value 3.055568 at the significance level of 0.05. This indicates that the difference in mathematical analysis efficiency and accuracy when using AI is statistically significant. This shows that the proportion of all variation that can be attributed to factor effects (AI vs. no AI) in this case, the factor effect accounts for 30% of the total variance. This implies that a large part of the change in the efficiency and accuracy of statistical analysis is due to the use of AI. Overall, the ANOVA table provides strong evidence that artificial intelligence (AI) can significantly improve the efficiency and accuracy of statistical analysis.

Research Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in the ethical considerations and philosophical implications surrounding the integration of AI-generated insights into the realm of mathematical creativity and the impact on the attribution of mathematical discoveries, regardless of the degree of AI involvement in the creative process.

Table 3: Ethical and Philosophical Implications of AI Integration in Mathematics Creativity and Attribution

Source of Variation	DF	SS variation	MS variation	F	p-value	F-critical
Between Groups	4	25288	6322	255.951417	0.0000	2.8660814
Within Groups	20	494	24.7			
Total	24	25782				

The ANOVA table 3 indicates that there is a statistically significant difference in terms of ethical considerations and philosophical implications of the insights that AI brings to the creation of mathematics and that AI is a creative process. Since the F-statistic which is 255.951417 is higher than the F-critical value 2.8660814 at the significance level of 0.05. This means that the difference in the ethical considerations and philosophical implications surrounding the integration of AI generated insights into the realm of mathematical creativity and the impact on the attribution of mathematical discoveries regardless of the degree of AI involvement in the creative process is statistically significant.

Research Hypothesis 4

There is no significant difference in the applicability of AI-powered mathematical creativity and discovery across diverse fields like cryptography, optimization, data analysis, and scientific modeling, with the potential benefits being equally applicable across all domains.

Table 4: Exploring the Potentials Benefits of AI-Generated Mathematics across multiple fields

Source of Variation	DF	SS variation	MS variation	F	p-value	F-critical
Between Groups	4	20875.67	7018.917	77.6314334	0.0000	2.75871047
Within Groups	25	2260.333	90.41333			
Total	29	30336				

The ANOVA table shows that there are statistically significant differences between AI-driven mathematical creation and discovery used in various fields such as cryptography, optimization, data analysis, and scientific observation. Since the F-statistic is 77.63, which is greater than the critical F-value 2.75871047 at the significance level of 0.05. This means that the distinction between mathematical creativity and discovery that artificial intelligence (AI) is capable of is statistically significant. Overall, the ANOVA table 4 provides strong evidence that there are significant differences in the use of AI-driven numerical creativity and discovery across sectors, and that the potential benefits of numerical creativity are AI-driven discovery is not applied equally across sectors.

Conclusion

The emergence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has opened up new frontiers in the realm of mathematics, offering a powerful tool to enhance creativity, accelerate discovery, and tackle complex problems that have long defied human efforts.

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As AI algorithms continue to evolve and become more sophisticated, their impact on mathematics is bound to grow, ushering in a new era of mathematical innovation and progress. AI's ability to automate tedious tasks, provide fresh perspectives, and facilitate collaboration among mathematicians has the potential to revolutionize the way we approach mathematical research. By freeing up mathematicians' time and energy from routine tasks, Artificial Intelligence (AI) can empower them to focus on more creative endeavors, exploring uncharted territories of thought and generating novel conjectures.

Recommendations

Based on the discussion in the previous sections, here are some recommendations for further research and development in the area of AI and mathematical creativity:

1. Develop AI algorithms that can better emulate human creativity and intuition: Current AI algorithms often struggle with abstract concepts and making leaps of faith, which are hallmarks of mathematical creativity. Research is needed to develop AI algorithms that can better capture the nuances of human thought and generate novel mathematical ideas.
2. Explore new AI techniques for mathematical discovery: While traditional AI approaches have been successful in some areas of mathematics, there is a need to explore new techniques that can tackle more challenging problems. This could include research into reinforcement learning, generative adversarial networks, and other emerging AI methods.
3. Investigate the ethical implications of AI in mathematics: The use of AI in mathematics raises important ethical questions about authorship, creativity, and the nature of mathematical knowledge. Research is needed to develop ethical guidelines for the responsible and transparent use of AI in mathematical research.
4. Promote collaboration between human mathematicians and AI systems: The most fruitful path forward lies in fostering collaboration between human mathematicians and AI systems. Research is needed to develop effective communication paradigms and collaboration strategies that allow humans and AI to work together effectively. Integrate AI into mathematical education: AI has the potential to revolutionize mathematical education by providing personalized instruction, offering real-time feedback, and adapting to the individual needs of learners. Research is needed to develop effective AI-powered teaching tools and integrate them into the educational curriculum.

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Qualitative Study on Adverse Effects ... (Ekuerhare, 2024) <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13359241>

Qualitative Study on Adverse Effects of Social Vices on Sustainable Growth and Development in Nigeria: A Review

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Abstract

The article examined the adverse effects of social problems, the sustainable growth and development in Nigeria. It adopts systematic review research method, and several search engines such as google scholar, Google, Researchgate, among others, were used to search for materials of interest that cover between 2010 and 2023. In addition, content analysis was used to group materials into major themes, thereby subjecting them to thematic analysis towards addressing the objective of the study. The article revealed that, Nigeria is combated with several social problems which are poverty, unemployment, inflation, budget deficits, street begging, prostitution, frauds, high crime rates, terrorist insurgency, collapse of manufacturing industries, corruption in public service, lack of entrepreneurial development, among others. In addition, these social problems have affected several aspects of the nation's economy which include the individual, social, political, economic, and several other aspects of the economy. It has also led to life threatening events and the loss of lives and properties, and also affecting entrepreneurial growth and development in Nigeria, thereby hampering growth and development of the nation. It has also led to social disorganization, dysfunctions, deviation, among others in the Nigeria society. The study therefore recommends that social movement and groups should focus on ensuring that their campaigns focus on the implementation of the critical national economic, political, social, cultural, educational and health services.

Keywords: Social problems, Social problems in Nigeria, Effects of Social problems, Nigeria

Introduction

Social problems are becoming major issues in the society, and could include a wide range of issues such as poverty, unemployment, displacement, terrorism, drug abuse, crime, ageing, among others (Macionis, 2008). Unlike other issues such as natural disasters, social problems are created by society hence, they could be solved by the society (Vaghefi and Drew, 2023). A social problem could be referred to as conditions or behaviors that could pose negative consequences on large numbers of people in the society and could be generally recognized as one that needs to be addressed. According to Spector & Kitsuse (2001), social problems, often go through natural history, which consist of several stages of development. The different stages of social problems are the emergence and claims making, legitimacy, renewed claims making, and development of alternative strategies.

At the emergence and claims making, social problems arise when social entities such as individuals, social change group, news media, and influential politicians, among others begin to draw attention to particular issues that are perceived to be undesirable and are in dire need for remedy. During this process, it goes into the public thereby, influencing the public perceptions on that particular issue, articulating the problems, the reasons and also the possible solutions. However, many of such emergence and claims making efforts of social problems do not succeed hence, social problem may not be recognized or doesn't emerge but few may succeed by drawing public attention to certain problem hence, social problem has emerged.

After the first stage, the second stage is the legitimacy stage. At this second stage of legitimacy, it focuses on persuading the government which could be at the local, state, and/or federal, to take some action towards alleviating such social problems such as in spending, policy making, among others towards addressing the problem. After, the second stage came, the third stage of renewed claims making, which emphasized that even when the government takes necessary action, social change groups often emphasized that such actions could be limited to successfully addressing such social problem. Therefore, such groups often press their demands anew hence the renewed claims making which could involve a certain level of tension towards attaining their goals and objective.

After this stage, the fourth stage is the development of alternative strategies, which focuses on the development of own strategies for addressing the social problem, while waiting for the government to respond. This third stage is executed because social change groups are often of the opinion that the government and other established interests may not respond early or adequately to their claims hence, provide alternative strategies in tackling the issues pending the time when the government

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responds. The movement from stage one to second and third stages is a function of the recognized and persuaded need for issues to be addressed. This is hinged on the three main characteristics of social problems provided by Vaghefi and Drew (2023), which are the reasons, negative effects and the social solution. The social reason is what is used to compel the society and the government that such issue is a social problem and that it needs to be addressed. The negative effect implies the negative impact it may pose on the society, thereby threatening life, safety, and freedom among others.

The third characteristic is the social solution, because every social problem should have social solution else, it is not a social problem (Vaghefi and Drew, 2023). Drawing emphasis from the three characteristics of social problem, understanding the social effect of a social problem is very germane in the emergence and claims making and legitimacy stage, and also at the renewed claims making, and development of alternative strategies towards providing better and sustainable solution to such social problems.

It is no doubt that social problems could pose several effects on the society. In Nigeria, several social issues that have affected the society are poverty, unemployment, terrorism, crime, kidnapping, cultism, drug abuse, among others (George & Ukpong, 2013). Also, the effects of social problems are grave and could cut across the individuals, family, society and the nation. For example, for individuals, it could lead to loss of lives, loss of reputation and dignity, unemployment, frustration, among others. For family, it could lead to broken home, poverty and low standard of living, among others. Also, for the nation, it could dent the nation's image at the global level, and also lead to loss of lives and properties, couple with loss of social amenities and resources. Moreover, there are several other effects that are needed to be understood to be able to drive social problems towards obtaining social solution in the Nigeria society. This article focuses on presenting the various social problems and their adverse effects on the sustainable growth and development in Nigeria.

Social problems are increasing and are becoming major issue that attract not only local attention but regional and global attention in Nigeria and cuts across crime, moral decadence, poverty, kidnapping, suicidal, murder, poor education, among others (Ogogo, 2023). According to Ogogo (2023), these social problems are posing significant effects on the economy, human existence, social and national development, and it is also negatively affecting development, which include sustainable development in the nation due to the high level of societal issues. In addition, this could pose negative effect on national strength and the pride of the nation (Ofoche, 2012; Ogogo, 2023). This could in the long run hinder the attainment of the sustainable development goals in Nigeria leading to failure in achieving SDGs. This could further affect future development of Nigeria and hence, unable to partake in future global development plans leading to under-development or setbacks in development at the regional and global levels.

Social problems in Nigeria have become a major issue of concern due to the high rate of several social issues battling the nation such as increasing rate of crime, moral decadence, poverty, kidnapping, suicidal, murder, poor education, among others (Ogogo, 2023). In addition, its elastic effects is felt on several aspects of the economy such as human existence, social and national development, couple with its jeopardizing effect on national strength and pride of the nation (Ogogo, 2023).

According to Ofoche (2012), religious crisis, political crisis, high rate of corruption, tribalism, poor education system, increase illiteracy rate, a huge gap between the wealthy and the poor, poor judiciary system, weak institution, increase in criminal networks, increasing unrest, among others are major social problems that are leading to a state of hopelessness, and affecting social economic status of individuals and the society in the nation. Juxtaposing the works of Ofoche (2012) and Ogogo (2023) together, it could be noted that there are several social problems in the Nigeria society, and all these have posed significant effect on the society, with regards to individual, economic, and the nation as a whole hence, could affect development of the nation.

Also, studies such as NISER (2000); UNDP (2006); Robinson and Anthony (2014) stated that several cases of social problems in Nigeria are increasing hunger, inflation, budget deficits, debt overhang, street begging, prostitution, frauds, high crime rates in major cities, terrorist insurgency, poverty, youth unemployment, collapse of manufacturing industries, corruption in public service, stagnation in entrepreneurial development, among others. These have hunted and affected Nigeria efforts for development since independence where virtually all notions and models of development have been experimented but to no avail (Aremu, 2003; Robinson and Anthony, 2014).

According to Hakizimana (2017), social problems could lead to social disorganization, dysfunctions, deviation, among others. Social disorganization implies human activities or failures which act or tend to impede other social activities. Social dysfunctions are socially related activities which tend to counter or disrupt the institutional nexus, or frustrate individual or social needs. Social deviation implies deviating from the normal behavior in the society and could encompass issues such as crime, delinquency, drug addiction, prostitution, physical handicaps, among others.

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Juxtaposing the works of NISER (2000); UNDP (2006); Ofoche (2012); Robinson and Anthony (2014), Hakizimana (2017); and Ogogo (2023), it could be affirmed that social problems could lead to several social related issues in the Nigeria society such as social disorganization, dysfunctions, and deviation, and also lack of entrepreneurial development. This could hamper the development of the individuals, society and the nation. This implies that the effect of social problems move from the individual level to the society and then to national level hence, affecting the sustainable growth and development of the nation in the long run.

Methodology

The article deploys a systematic review method to achieve its objectives. Therefore, the Information and materials used in this article were obtained from journal articles, books, and other similar materials, including online materials that tend to focus on the major objective of this study. In addition, information and materials selected focused on year range between 2010 and 2023 so as to obtain more recent information that meet the aims of the study. Also, the study uses [Cochrane reviews](#) style of reviewing literature by Chapman (2014), particularly in the searching process to obtain useful materials that are used in the study. This also follows the use of PICOS, representing (Richardson, 1995):

P – Problem or Population

I – Intervention

C – Control or comparator

O – Outcome(s)

S - Study type (e.g. quantitative, qualitative, etc.)

Also, search engine used for this systematic review are google, google scholar and other search engines, yielding several results and outcomes but very few (only seven articles) were selected that were fit and used for this study, towards meeting the goal of the study. Moreover, the information and materials were subjected to thematic analysis where they are grouped into various themes of the objectives and content analysis was also used to analyse the information resources obtained towards addressing the objective of the study.

Results

The result section focuses on providing responses to understanding of the effects of social problems to the peace of Nigeria. According to [StopLearn Team](#) (2023), social problems effects could be divided into several aspects of the society. For example, some social problems affecting individuals in Nigeria are:

1. **Sexual immorality and wide range of sexually transmitted diseases:** the rate of increasing varieties of sexually transmitted diseases (STD) such as syphilis, gonorrhoea, herpes, staphylococcus, HIV/AIDS, among others have been the result of the noisome sexual immorality battling the nation. It has also resulted in high rate of unwanted pregnancies, school dropout and truncation of education career, leading to early or unplanned marriage, single parenthood, thereby constituting major issues to families and the society at large.
2. **Poverty:** The rate of poverty in Nigeria is alarming, and couple with the high rate of unemployment, and also high cost of living. Poverty could also lead to several other social issues such as malnutrition, sicknesses, and diseases among others. It has also led to street begging as provided by Ogogo (2023) in Figure 1. In addition, it has also led to school dropout, children becoming street children, miscreants, area boys, prostitutes, and robbers among others. Also, according to Omiunu (2017), an average of 70% and an approximately 24% of Nigerians are poor and unemployed respectively hence, families are incapacitated in various ways to cater for themselves in the society.

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Figure 1: Street begging as a result of high rate of Poverty Source: Ogogo (2023)

3. **Crimes:** There is also high rate of crimes in the Nigeria society, and this has also led to increasing rate of insecurity to individual lives, properties and the society. Also, others affecting families in Nigeria include ([StopLearn Team, 2023](#)):
4. **Conflict:** there are several other problems in the society such as poverty, unemployment, inequality, religious issues, among others that have increased the rate of conflicts in the Nigeria society. These have affected the peace of people, society, and family among others. Examples of such conflicts are provided in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Inter-ethnic tension between Yoruba and Hausa in Southwest, Nigeria ([Animasawun, 2016](#)).

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5. **Indiscipline and Disobedience in the Family:** Indiscipline and disrespect to the authority such as parents, community elders, among others are increasing in the Nigeria society. Children are found to be disobedience to parents, teachers, community leaders, among others, and this has caused several issues of interest in the Nigeria society.
6. **Child abuse:** Due to the increasing rate of poverty and unemployment, children are seen engaged in street hawking, thereby exposing these children to various forms of evil such as kidnapping, raping, promiscuity, truancy, among others.
7. **High Cost of Living:** Also, due to high cost of living, several families in Nigeria are struggling to make ends meet, and to be able to provide for the family, but to no avail. This has also constituted several issues of concerns in the Nigeria society.
8. In addition, social problems affecting the nation of Nigeria are ([StopLearn Team](#), 2023):
9. **Political instability: The increasing rate of** electoral fraud, social injustice, among others have led to political instability in Nigeria, and this has jeopardize the society, posing negative effect to the political economy and the society at large.
10. **Social instability:** Social instability, which refers to the breakdown of law and order in society, is very much prevalence in Nigeria and has led to high level of **insecurity** of lives, properties and families.
11. **Militancy: The high rate of** perceived socio-economic injustice in Nigeria to certain groups of the nation has led to high rate of Militancy, particularly in the oil producing Niger Delta region where the youths take up arms against the establishment and the government. Also, there is the terrorist group, such as “Boko-Haram” (an Islamic Sect) bombing and destroying lives and property in some parts of Nigeria through suicide missions claiming that Western Education is a sin. This is another arm of political and religious instability or issue of the nation. An example of the clash of militants is presented in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: Clash of Militants (Felbab-Brown, 2020)

12. **Economic depression:** Problems such as corruption, inefficiency, greed, and selfishness are increasing seriously and have led to economic depression in Nigeria where individuals, families and the society are really suffering from basic facilities and amenities such as pipe borne water, electricity, health system, among others leading to several effects on the society
13. **Disunity:** religious and ethnicity disunity are also social problems that have drawn several attention in the Nigeria society, hence, affecting the peace of the nation through ethnic and religious violence especially in the northern part of the nation.
14. Studies also revealed that social problems could affect the political and economic stability of a nation, loss of valuable man power, threats on lives and properties, leading to the lack of development, increasing mental health issues, and also general disorder (Ogogo, 2023). According to George and Ukpong (2013), social problems could pose tremendous effect on national growth and development of Nigeria. Also, Oludele (2020) revealed that several social problems such as corruption, declining quality of education, family problems (such as increased divorce and family abuse/struggle), gender discrimination, governmental abuse of power, poverty, racial discrimination, among others are posing several effects on human, and socio-economic development of the nation. Also, Ucha (2010) noted that poverty, as a social problem has also led to poor health, lack of basic health amenities and competent medical practitioners, increasing rate of children with physical defects due to the inability of their parents to take them for immunization. Also, Aver, Nnorom and

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Targba (2013) noted that social problems such as violence could affect social development which has affected several aspects of the Nigeria economy such as ethics, nations, religions and tribes.

Discussion of Findings

The article examined the social problems and its adverse effects on the sustainable growth and development in Nigeria. The findings revealed that social problems are very many in Nigeria and has affected several aspect of the nation's economy which include the individual, social, political, economic, and several other aspects of the economy. It has also led to life threatening events and the loss of lives and properties, and also affecting entrepreneurial growth and development in Nigeria, thereby hampering growth and development of the nation. This supports the works of Spector & Kitsuse (2001); Macionis (2008); Ofoche (2012); George & Ukpong (2013); Robinson and Anthony (2014); Hakizimana (2017); Vaghefi and Drew (2023); Ogogo (2023); among others that there are several social related problems in Nigeria and these are posing elastic effect on personal, social, economic, religious development hence, leading to social disorganization, dysfunctions, deviation, among others in the Nigeria society. This could hamper development and development effort in Nigeria thereby leading to under-development in the short and long run. In addition, the findings of this study concur with those of Aremu (2003) and Robinson and Anthony (2014), that these elastic social problems have hunted and affected Nigeria for long since independence and has affected virtually all efforts and models of development which have proven abortive, without solution.

Conclusion

The article examined the social problems and its adverse effects on the sustainable growth and development in Nigeria. In conclusion, Nigeria is combated with several social problems which are poverty, unemployment, inflation, budget deficits, street begging, prostitution, frauds, high crime rates, terrorist insurgency, collapse of manufacturing industries, corruption in public service, lack of entrepreneurial development, among others. In addition, these social problems have affected several aspects of the nation's economy which include the individual, social, political, economic, and several other aspects of the economy hence, on the sustainable growth and development of the nation. It has also led to life threatening events and the loss of lives and properties, and also affecting entrepreneurial growth and development in Nigeria, thereby hampering growth and development of the nation. It has also led to social disorganization, dysfunctions, deviation, among others in the Nigeria society.

Recommendations

The study therefore recommends that:

1. Social movement and groups should focus on ensuring that their campaigns focus on the implementation of the critical national economic, political, social, cultural, educational and health services.
2. Political parties should also evolve as mechanism of democratic governance rather than looting the nation's wealth and using the society to generate wealth for their selfish gains,
3. Government and policy makers should also endeavour to focus on meeting and solving germane issues of the society that relate to social problems and give attention to them towards ameliorating these social problems in the society.

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Qualitative Study on Chemistry Education for Repositioning Good Governance, Sustainable Economic Growth and Development in Nigeria: A Systematic Review

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Abstract

The article is a systematic review that focuses on the role of chemistry education in shaping good governance, promoting sustainable development, and driving economic growth. Through a qualitative analysis, this study aims to explore the current state of chemistry education and its impacts on these important factors. The findings of this study will provide valuable insights into how chemistry education can be repositioned to better support good governance, sustainable development and economic growth. By examining relevant literature, this study will identify key themes and trends in the field of chemistry education and its intersection with these vital areas. This systematic review has the potential to inform policy decisions and drive future research in the field of chemistry education and its role in promoting societal progress. This paper underlines some recommendations which include development of national chemistry education strategy, increased investment in research and development, and promotion of public-private collaborations. The paper finally suggests increased government presence and funding coupled with the establishment of standard research laboratories in all institutions of learning, adequate and regular local and international capacity building for chemistry teachers among others as way out. Nigeria can take advantage of potential economic benefits of chemistry education and, in turn, achieve greater good governance and economic development. **Keywords:** Chemistry, Chemistry Education. Economic Development, Good Governance

Introduction

Science and technology make immense contributions to the material wellbeing of any country, if certain requisites are met. But in most developing countries, lack of scientific and technological knowledge is often a critical limitation to economic progress (Ige, 2013). This fact is borne out by the experiences of developing countries which are ready to acquire, adopt and apply techniques derived from scientific knowledge. There is a clear need to improve on science subjects in our schools, if the country is to meet the rising expectations of the people. With the goal to increase the materials wellbeing of the expanding population, there is a need to improve in scientific knowledge. Therefore, all students at all levels of education must have unrestricted access to the knowledge of science to gain insight into the foundation of many of the achievements of humanity (Emendu, 2014). The keywords chemistry, education, good governance and economic development are defined accordingly as Chemistry is typically an investigative and experimental science involving the study of nature and properties of all forms of matter coupled with the changes these matters undergo under different conditions (Bugaje, 2013). Education is the process of training and institution especially of children and young people in school and colleges which is designed to give knowledge and develop skills (Erinosho, 2005).

Chemistry education plays a vital pivotal role in the overall development of a nation. It's not a subject confined to textbooks but has a profound impact on various aspects of society.

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Objectives of the study

The current study aimed to highlight the role of chemistry education for repositioning good governance, sustainable economic growth and development in Nigeria.

1. To highlight the role of chemistry education in nation economic growth
2. To review the importance of chemistry education in repositioning a good governance
3. To highlight the role of chemistry education for sustainable development

Methodology

Search strategy

To carry out this review we the researchers explored search out the articles from various databases. Literature review is a method of collecting data in a way looking for information through books, newspapers, magazines, and other literature. The review articles in the research sourced from several journal studies related to chemistry education and its economic impact as well as role of good governance. Furthermore, the keywords included: Chemistry, education, chemistry education, good governance and economic impacts.

Conceptual Systematic Literature Review

Nature of Chemistry Concept and Chemistry Education in Nigeria

Chemistry has been one of the cornerstones of science, technology and industry, it is apparent that chemistry plays a greater role in national development through industry in the world. As such it helps to provide some social amenities and has been the pivot of science and hence the most needed tool, scientifically, for human, capital and economic development. The concept of chemistry as a science is centered on life and this encompasses the three states of matter-solid, liquid and gas in a give and take processes (Bugaje, 2013). According to Uwague and Ojebah (2008), chemistry is one of the naturally and well-established means through which the nation's abundant natural resources can be harnessed into useful ventures for the overall economic and socio-political wellbeing of its citizenry. Okieimen (2007) equally asserted that chemistry is all about everything in the world. He added that chemistry is the nucleus of science which ultimately is the foundation upon which any nation is developed. Chemistry certainly cannot be divorced from any today human activities (Muhammad, 2009).

Education is a tool for social and economic empowerment and a means of developing qualities in a rich and fulfilled life. The worth status of an individual level and the development of every society depend on the quality of education invested. Hence, educational development became the major criterion for measuring overall national development (Muhammad, Yusha'u & Lawal, 2018). Adesola (2015) states that education is a process of facilitating learning, or the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, beliefs, and habits. Educational methods include storytelling, discussion, teaching, training, and directed research. Further he stated that education frequently takes place under the guidance of educators, but learners may also educate themselves. Education is performing two majors' functions in advanced industrial societies transmitting the shared values of society and simultaneously the specialized skills for an Economy development.

Chemistry education is the study of the teaching and learning of chemistry in all schools, colleges and universities. Chemistry education also includes the understanding of how students learn chemistry, how best to teach chemistry, and how to improve learning outcomes by changing teaching methods and appropriate training of chemistry instructors (Okon, 2008). Moreover, Chemistry Education has been identified to be one of the major bedrock for the transformation of a nation's economy. It is needed for the production of the needed technologists, technicians, engineers, medical practitioners who are required to turn the nation's economy around and usher in the desired technological advancement which is very much required for sustainable development (Uwague & Ojebah, 2008). Chemistry Education is the study of the teaching and learning of chemistry in schools. It is concerned with the impartment of knowledge on properties, components, transformations, and interactions of matter. Chemistry Education fosters scientific literacy. Chemical knowledge and the application of chemical principles and products are important in problem-solving. Scientifically literate citizens are an asset to a nation. A chemically literate citizen knows the dangers associated with drugs and how to use them without occasioning harm. (Yusuf *et al.*, 2018). What many nations like Nigeria need now is a functional chemistry education that will assist in national development. Chemistry education has been identified to be one of the major bedrock for the transformation of our national economy (Emmanuel, 2013).

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Concept of Influence of Chemistry Education on Good Governance in Nigeria

Good governance is a system of government based on good leadership, respect for the rule of law and due process, the accountability of the political leadership to the electorate as well as transparency in the operations of government (Odock, 2006). It is governance that provokes and defines the nature of security. When there is governance failure, the security frame work deteriorates. Good governance is able to provide growth and structural change which result in development. Such structure includes schools, judiciary, military, and parliament. When the resulted structural change performs their roles properly, there will be security and the good governance will further be enhanced. Governance is defined as "the way in which socio-economic power is exercised in managing affairs within a nation" (Manu, 2002). In this light, governance of education implies the way in which education institutions affairs is managed within the developing nations. In order to achieve this, rule of law must be adherent to in totality. Rules and policies must guide any governance of education system and made enforceable by all and sundries within the system. The issue of governance is very critical to the development, sustenance and advancement of chemistry education especially at the both secondary and tertiary level. This is because good governance holds the key to good performance and sustainability of education institutions (Obanya, 2003). There is a linear relationship between good governance and a functional chemistry education. There cannot be a functional chemistry education where country's resources and power are not well utilized for the citizen of the nation. Florence et al. (2015) viewed governance as the use of state resources and power in an accountable way to achieve and promote the well-being of the citizenry. It therefore, implies that when the power and resources are not well managed for the welfare of the citizen, there is bound to be a problem

Influence of Chemistry Education for Sustainable Economic Development in Nigeria

There is no doubt that Nigeria is endowed with enormous human and natural resources. As rightly observed by Matthew-Danial (2013), human and natural resources endowment are not enough for wealth creation and economic development of any nation, but the knowledge of how these raw materials can be transformed into valuable goods and services for economic development and improved quality of life. Modern science education holds the key to the rapid transformation of Nigeria. The Nigerian economy is one of the most developed economies in Africa (Economy watch content (EWC, 2010). It has been observed that Nigeria is a middle-income nation with developed financial and communication among others and that Nigeria has the second largest stock exchange market in the African continent (EWC, 2010).

Chemistry education plays a pivotal role in the overall development of a nation. It is not a subject confined laboratories and textbooks but has profound impacts on various aspects of society. It plays the major roles in food (fertilizers and insecticides), clothing (textile fibers), housing (cement, concrete, steel, bricks), Medicine (drugs), Transportation (fuel, alloy materials). Presently, man is experiencing an era in scientific and technological development that affects his life in one way or the other. Virtually everything we use daily involves science (Yusuf, *et al.*, 2018).

Chemistry education holds immense importance in national development. By enhancing scientific knowledge and research capabilities, addressing environmental challenges, and meeting industrial demands, chemistry education becomes a driving force for progress. It empowers individuals to make meaningful contributions to society, fostering innovation, and paving the way for brighter future. Therefore, investing in chemistry education is essential for a nations overall growth and prosperity.

Achieving a high level of economic development through transforming the country real sectors will not only reduce poverty by providing food security, increased in agricultural and industrial exports, but will also bring about improved literacy and a healthy workforce. Chemical research has contributed to economic prosperity and financial security in the country. Products from chemical companies, such as polymers, coatings, pharmaceuticals, and pesticides, play an important role in everyday life. The chemical production companies have a large portion of various specialists who have contribute to the development of the country (Ekpo, 1993). Over the years chemistry has contributed through the following measures, which have helped in the economic development of many nations. These measures are

Enhancing Scientific Knowledge and Research for Sustainable Economic Growth and Development in Nigeria

Chemistry education paves the way for a nation's scientific progress by imparting the fundamental knowledge required for scientific research. By understanding the principles, theories, and laws governing chemical reactions, aspiring chemists can delve into cutting edge research and make groundbreaking discoveries. Such research has the potential to revolutionize various sectors, from health care to agriculture, and boost the nation's development. For instance, the discovery of new drugs or materials through chemistry research can significantly impact the pharmaceutical industry, leading to better healthcare outcomes and economic growth.

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1. Chemistry education equips individuals with a solid foundation in scientific principles and concepts.
2. It fosters critical thinking skills and problem-solving abilities necessary for research and innovation.
3. Promoting research and advancements in chemistry leads to the development of new materials, medicines and technologies that benefit society as a whole.

Addressing Environmental Challenges for Sustainable Economic Growth and Development in Nigeria

Chemistry education has a significant role to play in addressing the pressing environmental challenges facing the world today. By instilling a sense of environmental responsibility and emphasizing sustainable practices, chemist can contribute to preserving and protecting the environment.

Understanding the chemical processes behind pollution or climate change enables experts to devise innovative solutions and develop environmentally friendly technologies. This not only benefits the nation's ecological balance but also creates opportunities for economic growth through the emergence of clean energy industry.

1. Chemistry education emphasizes the importance of sustainable development practices and environmental awareness.
2. It equips individuals with the knowledge to develop greener technologies and mitigate environmental hazards.
3. Chemist with a strong educational background can contribute to solutions for pollution, waste management, and climate change.

Meeting industrial demand for sustainable economic growth and development in Nigeria

A robust chemistry education system plays a vital role in meeting the demands of the industrial sector. From pharmaceuticals to petrochemicals, numerous industries rely on chemists and chemical engineers to drive innovation and production. By equipping individuals with the necessary skills and knowledge, chemistry education facilitates the development of a skilled workforce capable of meeting the industry's requirements. A skilled chemistry workforce not only contributes to economic growth but also enhances a nation's competitiveness in global market.

1. Chemistry education prepares individuals for careers in various industrial sectors
2. It provides the necessary skills and knowledge to cater the demands of industries such as pharmaceuticals, chemicals, and materials.
3. A well-educated chemistry workforce fuels economic growth and enhance a nations competitiveness in global market.

Chemistry Entrepreneurial Skill for sustainable Economic Growth and Development in Nigeria

Chemistry entrepreneurial education has the potential of changing the fortune of a nation and transforming it from under developed to a developing and subsequently developed country. A chemist is an entrepreneur and an entrepreneur is a person who evaluates business opportunities, gather necessary resources and initiate appropriate action to ensure success (Wushishi, 2013). The success of Nigeria in the 21st century, its wealth and welfare will depend on the ideas and entrepreneurial skills of its population. These have always been the nation most important assets (Iyun, 2013). Achieving chemistry entrepreneurial skills produce chemists who will create new ideas, new products and entirely new industries.

Innovation and Modernization for Sustainable Economic Growth and Development in Nigeria

Technological innovation is dependent on chemistry education because, through chemistry researches, newer and better methods of production are discovered for improved productivity. In addition, chemistry stimulates motivation and widens inquisitiveness. Furthermore, chemistry liberates the mind from the vestige of ignorance and superstition and makes a man willing to accept change. Chemistry widens man's ideas and outlook; it breaks man conservatism and prepares the mind to accept modern and improved ideas and techniques. In the developed world, chemistry through its innovativeness has helped to transform indigenous technology for the holistic development of their countries.

Income Distribution for Sustainable Economic Growth and Development in Nigeria

Efficient income distribution is a prerequisite for equity, rapid national growth, social and political stability. These can only be achieved if chemistry plays its role not necessarily in bridging the gap between the rich and the poor but in the redistribution of income between the people in the country. Thurow in Kene and Oguji (1997) rightly observed that an increase in the educational level of low-income workers is bound to have some beneficial benefit, including, increase in productivity and a consequent increase in earning, reduction in the number of low skill workers, which lead to an increase in their wages and increase in the number of high skill workers.

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Agriculture for Sustainable Economic Growth and Development in Nigeria

Chemical principles and products have been utilized to control pests and weeds and in fertilizer production for increased food production. Genetically improved crops based on pest protection. is used to improve crop production. The herbicide tolerance (HT) crops are tolerant to certain broad-spectrum herbicides such as glyphosate and glufosinate, which are more effective, less toxic, and usually cheaper than selective herbicides. By cutting the costs and labor of weed or insect control, these first-generation commercial pests and/or herbicide-tolerant crops have been shown to provide a tangible economic benefit to farmers. It is therefore critical that chemistry students be exposed to appropriate knowledge of chemistry in the areas of agrochemicals and chemical-based technologies to boost agricultural production environmental and economic sustainability of food security.

Contribution to Improved Health and Sanitation Facilities for Sustainable Economic Growth and Development in Nigeria

Drugs, which are products of chemistry abound and are used for various purposes including prevention and treatment of various diseases. Proserpine, a Yohimbe alkaloid, for example, has important clinical use in the treatment of high blood pressure (hypertension) and also as a tranquilizer for the emotionally disturbed. Ergot alkaloids are used chemically to induce contraction of the uterus in the last stages of pregnancy. Morphine and compounds are well-known pain relievers (Aniodoh, 2001).

Potable Water Supply for Sustainable Economic Growth and development in Nigeria

Water is chemically treated to kill germs, thus rendering it fit for human consumption and other domestic use. Chemical processes are exceptionally important in the treatment and delivery of drinking water and the treatment of wastewater. Analytical techniques (including the development of associated portable devices) are critical in verifying the quality of water, and where required chemicals and membranes are employed in simple disinfection treatment. Chemical science also plays a significant role in the remediation of the aquatic environment following pollution incidents. Chemistry research within the water sector is therefore playing a vital role in the transformations that are needed to achieve a sustainable freshwater supply, both domestically and on a global scale. Fundamental chemistry research is a necessary condition to support strategies that will provide the technological solutions needed to deliver new and improved methods of optimizing water use, treating contaminated water, recycling water, desalination water and preserving water in the soil, and harvesting water for irrigation (Odedokun & Abubakar, 2017).

Clothing for sustainable Economic Growth and Development in Nigeria

Some textile fibers used as clothing are obtained by modifying natural fibers of agricultural origin such as viscose rayon and cellulose acetate from cellulose. Other fibers such as nylons, ethylene, and acrylic fibers are all chemical synthetic derivatives from petroleum sources and are used as clothing (Okenyi *et al.*, 2011).

Energy Supply for Sustainable Economic Growth and Development in Nigeria

Coal is fuel and a source of energy. Fuel derived from petroleum is used to power automobiles, airplanes and ships. Gaseous fuel such as butane is used as cooking gas. Kerosene, a derivative of petroleum, is a household name and is used in heating, cooking and lighting (Aniodoh, 2001). Chemistry Education provides solutions to our problems in the energy sector by developing sustainable biofuels (e.g. through optimization of biochemical conversion processes as well as thermochemical conversion and gasification process (Odedokun & Abubakar, 2017).

Major Areas of Influence of Bad Governance on Chemistry Education

The lack of good governance is impacting Nigeria educational system badly in all areas. However, there are specific areas it seriously affects chemistry education. The paper considers six critical areas. These are:

Research in Chemistry

Research in the Nigerian universities has been rendered useless because of the paucity of fund. The government has money to build personal houses for the government officials but no money for research. They also have money to sponsor political party campaign and rally. Many of them are so naïve to have gone as far as buying properties in the developed countries and had bank accounts in foreign countries but no money for educational research. Most educational research institutes are mere names but can do nothing. Corruption of our government officials had killed and buried research in chemistry and science

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education for decades. Because of corruption resources from the national treasury meant for research are in the hands of a few individuals who are politically powerful (Otoghile *et al.*, 2014).

Teachers' Education and training

Teachers Education and Training in Nigeria is very poor when compared with other developing countries in Africa. Due to the lack of sound teacher education and training in Nigeria, the teaching and learning of science are perceived difficult by both the teachers and the students. Most teachers lack adequate pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) for science teaching. Many students at the end of their Junior Secondary School (JSS) preferred Art and Humanities courses to Science. Given the havoc the insurgency had caused to the Nigerian socio-economic development in the recent time by our youth, lack of governance is a menace in the nation. Many of these insurgents are science oriented that could be useful to this nation, but we lost them to the insurgency. These youth used improvised materials, and other complex weapon produced by themselves: these are great scientists.

Infrastructure

Infrastructure in the Nigerian educational institutions is in a terrible condition. It is worrisome and nasty for students to learn science under the tree in some part of the nation today. This is a reflection of the poor budgetary allocation to education by the government. Good governance requires that enough funds be made available for all educational programmes. The Nigeria experience shows that poor budgetary allocation to education is meager, and this against the UNESCO recommendations of 26% of the total allocation to the education sector (Akindutire and Ekundayo, 2010).

A visit to some of the Nigerian universities, polytechnics, and colleges of education reveals that the Nigerian government is not serious about education. There are poor office accommodations for lecturers and working conditions. Science is a cognitive course that requires a conducive environment for its teaching and learning.

Inadequate Manpower

A significant problem faced with science and chemistry education in Nigeria today is the issue of inadequate manpower. It is doubtful if Nigeria has sufficient and qualified number of indigenous science and chemistry teachers. This has in no small way hindered the growth of chemistry education and by extension affected self-reliance and national development. In most of the tertiary institutions, the number of senior lecturers with Ph.D qualifications is low. Rather, we have most of them in the cadre of Assistant lecturers, Graduate Assistant and lecturer III-I. These crops of lecturers are still learning the rudiments of teaching by the reason of their qualifications and training (Uwague and Ojebah, 2008, Emumejaye, 2006). Only few of those in the professional rank are available. Poor salary scale/remuneration is equally associated with teaching job in Nigeria compared with the elected/politically appointed officers. This has led to long period of strike actions by teaching and non-teaching personnel across the educational sector. Teachers reward against all odds is often said to be in Heaven. These are negative factors on the growth of chemistry education, self-reliance and national development. The quality of education rests more on the quality of its teachers (Akubudike, 2003).

Associated Hazards

No sane person will live his home for work and anticipate accident. The greatest inherent problem associated with chemistry and its education is hazard. Hazard effects from poisonous emission of gases/ fumes, corrosive chemicals, fire burnt, explosion, obsolete apparatus, poor laboratory sanitary condition etc. are very often recorded in chemistry laboratory, lack of safety awareness due to unsafe acts and unsafe working conditions results to accidents. Victims of chemicals or fire burnt usually present ugly scenes. Often times, large casualties are recorded when accident occur in the field of chemistry. This cannot promote chemistry education, good governance and economic development.

Defective Curriculum

School curriculum in the pre-independent Nigeria was not for all-round development of the child as the aspects of science and technology which would have created entrepreneurial skills for self-reliance were ignored (Sabina, 2009). It rather kept on producing subservient Nigerians who were tied to the apron string of white-collar jobs viz: gardeners, stewards, interpreters, catechists, clerks and house-keepers. All these make the people parasitic consumers rather than creative and efficient producers. The curriculum for science and chemistry education in particular is such that is over loaded with much emphasis on theoretical teaching. There is an obvious relationship between development and the type of educational structures available in any country (Sabina, 2009).

Conclusion

This paper provides an insight into the role and importance of chemistry education for national development in Nigeria; Objectives of chemistry education in the Nigerian education system are also part of the discussion in this paper.

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Chemistry education is important for the production of manpower in Nigeria's labour market. Chemistry education is needed for development, technological emancipation and industrial expansion. Chemistry education enhances skill acquisition and application, Chemistry Education includes the propagation of the teaching and learning of chemistry and empowers students by exposing them to entrepreneurship programmes in which they can make choices in life and become self-employed.

Recommendations

From the fore going, it is quite obvious to say that if these factors among others are well tackled, Nigeria would have started laying concrete foundation towards becoming a first world developed nation.

Chemistry education requires a well-designed and equipped laboratory to achieve its primary goals of observation and investigation. A functioning laboratory is such that have the most basic facilities like power and water supply, chemical reagents and apparatus, current analytical instruments, adequate space and ventilation. The laboratory should also be manned by a highly skilled and competent technologist, for effective and rewarding application. This will enhance self-reliance and national development.

The enhanced concrete foundation should start at the primary school level. Since primary education is seen as the bedrock of all forms of education in any nation, Nigeria should not be left out (Umoh 2007). Every Nigerian child has the right to proper education and even science education. At this level, teaching should be based on demonstration and all participatory learning.

Science and chemistry education in particular will be meaningless for selfreliance and national development if the qualities of the teachers cannot be guaranteed. Chemistry education requires specialist, competent and dedicated teachers. To ensure self-reliance and national development, chemistry teachers should be given appropriate professional training by professional bodies. Science and chemistry teachers should be trained and retrained through seminars, workshops, and conferences on innovative teaching.

Teachers and students are to be well educated of the need to be safety conscious especially in the laboratory at all times. Prevention is often said to be a better cure from an accident. Precaution signs should be pasted/posted at strategic positions in the laboratory. The laboratory should also be well illuminated and ventilated coupled with strategically located firefighting equipment.

School curriculum in the sciences, particularly chemistry should be reviewed and restructured to meet up with the need and aspirations of the people. A curriculum that is practically driven and achievable should be put in place. Members of the curriculum drafting committee should be drawn from professional bodies like the Chemical Society of Nigeria (CSN), Institute of Chartered Chemists of Nigeria (ICCON),etc, to enable them restructure the curriculum with the view of meeting the present day reality

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Qualitative Study on Education as a Panacea for Social Stability amidst Insecurity in Nigeria

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Abstract

The paper is a qualitative study of education as a panacea for social stability in a midst of insecurity in Nigeria. This is based on the fact that education can be used as an instrument of social transformation in a multi-ethnic nation such as Nigeria. The paper maintained that in a multi-ethnic nation, education can serve as the instrument of change. This becomes necessary because, our education had failed to deliver the good life it purports for, due to the effect, of insecurity on human life in any community/social settings. The methodology of approach is conceptual analysis which is the rightful format into which philosophical arguments are fitted for proper presentations or elucidations. This method of research relies on some sorts of definitional structures of concepts and not on data as in empirical research. The analysis premises on the assumption that education can be used to reshape or rechanneled the behavior of people in social environment positively as the situation demands. The paper advocates for knowledge that can be used positively to promote unity and peaceful co-existence in all society of the world to bread social stability and security in the midst of insecurity. It was recommended among other things that our programmes of education should be directed towards the training of all stakeholders on the issues and benefits of peaceful social relation to breed security in every society.

Keywords: Social stability, Insecurity, Education, Conceptual analyses, and Development.

Introduction

The social development of any nation depends on its social stability which can be progressed through value-oriented education if timely provided. Education therefore, is a social transformation that should be organized to improve social life in such areas as politics, family, economy, and culture among others (Yakubu, 2017). This is to say that good education would promotes social security, and prevent insecurity because its empowers individual and liberates the receivers from ignorance, bias and manipulation by people who claim to have superior knowledge. This spring out of the belief that education can be used to propagate knowledge that can change people attitudes positively in any society pestered with insecurity. Insecurity ranges from the abduction of man, kidnapping, robbery religious/ethnic crises and many others may lead to social instability.

Man receives education daily but he is not really cynic or pessimist on all issues or as such typically disregarding accepted standards in order to achieve his aims. He thinks daily to reflects on any problem of actions and reactions in his social environment either stable or not and he is not really sure of what life really means or where it is going due to the inconsistencies in the way. It is degenerating, disharmonizing and disunited to cause insecurity The social life is neither relatively stable nor staple but relatively dynamics towards negatively on daily base and hence, insecurity provides or has eaten deeply into the fabric of all functions, thereby reducing peaceful co-existence of ethnic relationships. The issue of “I am because you are” and you are because I am” is no longer there as humanity is being gradually eroded.

Man as a bundle of reflexes receives knowledge through education all the times because, he is aware of his problems, he is at the center of the stimuli in his social environment, hence he relates and translates the understanding of his social living for the enhancement of social stability in his social environment. This mechanistic and his impersonal attributes leads to his understanding of the quality of life as it in degenerating and disinteresting because of the level of insecurity.

The essence of human being living together in groups is to taps the benefits of social stability and peace, otherwise, self-consciousness which is considered a liability may generate a thought of “non –being” or “nothingness” and in turn lead to abnormalities as result of negative application of knowledge from any of the sides which later leads to ensure of social instability. Wolf (2006) asserted that the “the states most basic function is ensuring social security by exercising the monopoly of force. One can say that all these entail the protection of man from physical threats, violence within the state’s territory”.

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In view of these, it becomes imperative to explore how our education can see to the improvement of social stability in a multi-ethnic nation to displace national insecurity. One may ask – On what basis can a formula for a well-organized society devoid of insecurity be completely secured, devised, justified and based? In other to answer these questions perfectly, one may venture little into the nature of education and the society to devise the type of values needed to be transmitted through education for peaceful development. This is because, if things are changing, it behooves our knowledge dissemination to change right along with them, our enquiry into the social life must equally change to breed social security.

It appears that insecurity has pervaded all aspects of every society. Prevalent of these insecurities are: Cyber Crime, killings, kidnappings, cultism, home breaking and the like. In other words, these are the results of various kinds of indiscipline in Nigeria. These forms of indiscipline's have been identified as the base of insecurity and has resulted into various form of crimes such as ethnic crimes, religion intolerance, riots and so on. Hence, education for social stability in the midst of insecurity to breed security is presumed to be our instrument of social transformation to breed peace. To these, the programme and methods of delivery of education may undergo social transformation to bring about changes in human behavior and hence change in security, political end the like to reduce insecurity.

The study covered a quantitative study of education as a panacea for social stability in Nigeria. It is a Philosophical clarification of education as an agent of social transformation, It aims at breeding social stability in the midst of insecurity. It explored conceptual analysis of education, and social stability, concepts of social stability and social security, education as a means of social security under the following sub-headings: Education for social integration, education for economy development, education for national consciousness, and social development, and education for human and social relations. Hence, the study premised on the role of education as a panacea for social stability amid social insecurity in Nigeria. It advocates for the infusion of Plato's Idealism into our educational system because it explained how man can be helped to attain the goal of self-realization in a stable society, and this is the ultimate goal of the most stable society devoid of insecurity.

The study is of good value to the government as knowledge based on security education and in the formulation of meaningful and contextual national policy on education because education is predominantly knowledge-based. The individual person who needs to know much about nature's insecurity and ways out would also find the work to be of great benefits.

Theoretical Framework

Plato idealism is considered as the most suitable theoretical framework due to the fact that it explains how man can be helped to attain the goal of self-realization, stable society and social security which is the ultimate goal of the most stable society devoid of insecurity. The idealist theory of knowledge in education can be used to promote social security in Nigeria if properly harness. Dike (2016) considered education to involve education for character, security, and moral value.... It emphasizes the teaching of respects and responsibility to the citizen for good character and for the security of a nation.

Above lends credence to the view that the task of education is to orientate individuals in accordance with societal problems. For example, in Nigeria, the issue of social security which has become a bane of concerns are believed to be the only real thing through which we can know that insecurity is real in Nigeria and it existing as ideas only in relation to the mind. Plato idealism takes note that proper direction for the growth of the personality of the individual of which its values can be used to breed the security in the midst of insecurity. In supports of the above, Ayeni 2013 states that idealism education is learner-centered and is oriented towards religion and security of state, since the kernel of their philosophy in the discovery of the operational self.

One can therefore contends that the basis of the idealist epistemology is the overall importance of the role of social security, moral and intelligence of the individual and his entire personality in the process of education. The knowledge received through education plays a role in building security in the midst of insecurity in Nigeria. Therefore, we need to practice and mobilize national and international attentions to the types of knowledge we impact to our young ones in developing their minds.

Conceptual Analysis of Education and Social Stability

In any society of human being, education can be used to disseminate knowledge that will breed social stability to stamp out social insecurity. This is possible because education can be used as an instrument of social change in any environment pestered with insecurity. To these, man is able to understand self" and his "society" by knowing "others" understanding them, readings meanings to their ideas, determine and making choices in the light of his own and other experiences.

Therefore, in social parlance, education can be termed as an effective and dynamic instrument for making or harnessing the experiences of each person in society, to restructure heiring society with social insecurity into perfectly and socially acceptable ones. Here, the end of education being related to each person and the social stability in term of how well

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the knowledge received through education can succeed in serving the community interest. Sequel to the above, education can be accepted as an instrument for national survival and social stability. Singhs, (2014): quoting Boessing and Builder asserted that: education is gradual adjustment of individual to the spiritual possession of the race ...the organization of acquired habits of such as it will fits the individual action to his physical and social environment... the function of education is concerned to be the adjustment of man to his environment to the end that most enduring satisfaction may accrue to the individual and the society.

By understanding, it implies that people in all societies are aware of the reality by showing their knowledge of it with others in meaningful ways. That is there are meanings to be communicated in our society for making adjustment in order breeds a stable society that can lend good life. This lends credence to the view that education can influence each other positively depending on interest. Education can therefore can be used to stamp out greed, cruelty; selfishness' laziness and to instill qualities such as obedience, honesty, hard work and cooperativeness, one may then relates these to characters education as: Ayotunde (2016) states that education is concerned with educating an individual or group with principle that conform to the standards of behavior and character, on these principles and inherent complex of attributes that determine a person's moral and ethical actions and reactions.

It follows that most societies of the world with instability would want to encourage the type of or form of education that can bring social stability in life or innovation of stability in spite of insecurity. The meeting point here boxes out that character may be set of will –habits by which one is disposed to acts according to principles. It may be built up by choices for good motives and that choice is a situation shapes more than situation. It shapes the person involves and gradually affects others, one can therefore refers that character education may be both subjective and objective, it stressed to plant moral goodness in person and this may serve to adjust the habitual disposition in the mind of people in any society. The big chances are that character education is a value that has relativity with moral education. It serves as agent of co-coordinating, and reinforce of good deeds in the society of human beings, hence, William, (2002): Character education aims to restore the formation of students' characters to central place in schooling. The moral education involved laid good stress upon many aspects of development such as mental, physical, emotional, psychological and social to enhance social efficiency and dynamism in the social environment.

Reference to the human nature, character education that can promote social stability is possible despite the level of insecurity because our intellects have capacities for unlimited meaning which is aided by means of choice and freedom. Akinpelu, (2005) throws more light on this when he says: education is necessary for the individual to express his freedom intelligently and with foresight, to organize and interact with his environment, and it helps to free individual capacity in a progressive growth.

Education therefore, is inseparable from the society of human being because it can be used to promote social stability, hence the greatest service of individual and society powers, as the powers of intellectual and moral freedom to be exercised rest on as pillar. Education and society are inextricably fused together to show effects like forward and backward reactions, in which education serves as predicator of security and stability of any society, the society as the receivers show or exhibit the progress of education.

Concept of Social Stability and Social Security

In line with the Oxford English Dictionary, stability can be defined as “Immunity from destruction or essential change, enduring quality. Stability this sense does not mean stagnation or a state of permanency or the state of being static in progress or reform. The stability here does not exclude a gradual change. Osunde, (2018) says: A stable society is not stagnant society. A stable society moves towards agreed goals and objectives” ...Nigeria is notoriously unstable because of or inability to progress towards the goals which we have loudly committed ourselves to public but which we subvert in private supporting of the move of the issues, is our objective of education stated in our national policy on education “a united, strong, and self-reliant nation, United hence means a lot. From this, it can be coined that, cooperation, unification, contempt, harmonious living, were planned for in Nigeria but the reverse is the case, this is because all citizens are not contributing to make the country strong as most of our politicians and leaders are corrupts. Hence, the corrupt practice of our leaders are promoting insecurity and hence degenerating stability. The clause strong means continuing to be healthy, good, stable, and devoid of indivisibility and insecurity or instability. Where a social justice is not in place, and characterized with social problems such as killings, corruption, kidnappings, Rituals, there is actually instability and such as in Nigeria. On this issue, Alemiki, (2015) has this to say:

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In a paper delivered at a Academic staff Union of Universities (UNIJS Chapter) lecture on “Security Challenges and the University System in Nigeria”. Proposed the following dimension of insecurity.

1. Physical Insecurity: - violent personal and property crimes
2. Public Insecurity: - violent conflicts, insurgency and terrorism
3. Economic Insecurity: - poverty, unemployment
4. Social Insecurity: - Illiteracy, ignorance, diseases or illness, malnutrition, water born disease, discrimination and exclusion
5. Human Right Violation: - denial of fundamental right by state and non-state actors in different states
6. Political Insecurity: - denial of good and social democratic governance.

This lends credence to the view that qualitative education can be used to address the issue of all the above forms of insecurity to breed social security in the midst of social insecurity. Despite the fact that, in the light of the above David states that lack of education itself is insecurity and other forms of insecurity that breed social instability, thereby serve as a constraint to social stability.

In Sum, social stability and security are interdependent, this is a pure fact because security serves as condition for social stability and its absence results in insecurity and instability, or in a more explicit sense, security is a condition for social stability in a multi ethnic nation such as Nigeria. Therefore, one can state further that a form of interconnections exists among the concepts as one is a condition for others and vice versa

Education as Means of Promoting Social Stability in Nigeria

Education is a fundamental means of transforming and expanding the individual ethical awareness, values and attitudes, skills and behaviors for sustainable social stability in Nigeria. The essence is to lodge the dynamics of both physical social economic environment and human development that should be integrated in all disciplines. All these of which, the meaningful co-existence of human beings in the march, towards social advancement can be attained through knowledge transmitted in the course of educating how

Cookey, S.J. (1969): This today on viable knowledge can be transmitted or implanted into individuals:

I don't think it is right for our school to train individual as individuals, he should be trained as a member of a community and of nation, he should be trained as a citizen, education should be used as a tool of national unity and word more than ever, it is agreed that we should inculcate in the students if our educational institution the idea of belonging not to one clan or tribe but to the whole nation.

The emphasis on education here is to help promote national unity, stability and national security as the above is centered on the development of selfhood, self-direction self-awareness, towards the society progress. Hence the attitudinal changes are the major target in a multi ethnic society. The education may be tailored as follows to bread stability and security.

1. Education for social integration
2. Education for economic development
3. Education for national consciousness
4. Education for spiritual development
5. Education for political development

Education for Social Integration

Education in this category can be on the intellectual and moral development of the learners in the schools. All these are the remits of attitudinal changes that breed social stability in the society. Education for the social integration should lay emphasis on the common cultural factor among the ethnic groups at the same time bridge the cultural gaps through promotion of tolerance, and understanding endurance. Education thus serving as a weapon for the stamping out of social insecurity if properly managed to bring life, innovation, development and advancement. This presupposes that the function of education is to serve as means of re-energizing, regrouping, reactivating and re-interpreting of ideas already lodges in the minds of individual for the peaceful co-existence of various ethnic groups in the society. Akinpelu (2005) lends credence to this when he says: the individual as concerned by Rosseau has his most distinguishing characteristics the possession of freewill, liberty and reason with which he can direct the will for good or for ill.

Above shows emphasis of the education for social cohesion on the attitudinal changes implies an effective change is the state of individual person. Ayeni, (2005) claims that attitude is normally used to refer to a learned predisposition evidenced in the behavior of an individual to evaluate an object or claims of objects in a consistent or characteristic ways. One can deduce that attitude is related to humans' "behavior" or "ways" of life that serve as factors for the promotion social security within and

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outside their society. If the value being provided through education is all to promote social stability and security, good and right attitude of the mind, the beauty of our stability of the society will be explored. To this, the moods of the learners should be trained towards the needs of the society in line with how to breed security and stability by implanting good knowledge through education. Education here is being related to their utility values in our society interim of how well it can succeed in serving the community interest. It is therefore accepted as an instrument for national security and stability.

Education for Economic Development

Education for economic development and stability shall be directed to wing out ignorance and directed towards harnessing natural resources and good that result from employment and use of these resources. Hence, the developmental education should involve drastic changes in the individual and society towards economic development of the nation. Government should be magmatic an agencies development and orientation on the issue of morality to improve good morale towards revenue generation.

The education of the youths should not be alienated from entrepreneurial education because oil money should be a blessing for entrepreneurship at training. Entrepreneurship based education should be provided freely and embezzlement should be discouraged while corrupt politician should be punished accordingly.

Education for National Consciousness

One can say that the seat of consciousness is “mind” on this mind is understandable in terms of its content and functions. Ayeni, (2002) states that: the activities of the mind in receiving, conserving, reactivating and constructing ideas, among others do not take place unconsciously even when a person is said to be unconscious. To this, education can be used to direct the mind towards goodness in the society and enhances commitments that will breeds social stability, and security in the midst of insecurity.

Education for Spiritual and Social Development

The spiritual here depicts vital principle” or “the principle of thought” in relation to the essence of living. The essence of coming together in our society is about a relation, that is to “be” is to “relates” if a society is deficient in relation, social instability is the result. Educations for spiritual development will breed national unification, loyalty, enlightened, and technical competences.

Education for Human and Social Relation

Education that will forge natural unity and breed good social relation in the midst of insecurity should be included in curriculum. The knowledge suitable for all these can be promoted through education and the teaching of values related to human conduct. The issues Loyalty, hiring, fair play, self-direction, can be inbuilt into the values of education to be enhancing security and social stability in a nation.

Conclusion

Education as an agent of social stability and security can be used to reduce the burning needs in Nigeria such as national insecurity, national instability. This can be achieved through education for spiritual development, national cohesion, human and political relations, national consciousness and commitment, political development and viable economic growth. This is based on the fact that the education of the youths can be focus primarily on the cooperation and unification of all stakeholders in education to channel the new education for national stability and security. The necessary skills of production, equitable programme to be properly channels through technological approach for onward general delivery. Based on the analyses of this study, the following may improve social stability and security in the midst of insecurity in Nigeria: Education as an agent of social changes should be directed towards inculcating and empowering our youths, elders and all members of our living society towards peace reducing insecurity and hence, breed social stability. There is need for the training of all stakeholders on education, the issues and benefit of peaceful social relations in all society. All stakeholders on education should initiate principle of tolerance towards improving cooperate in all societies of the nation. The national orientation agency should improve their advertisement and training on the need to solicit social relation and integration every society human being and school. Adult training center should be introduced in all level government to undertake the programme to train adult in the need and method s of breeding responsible children. They should be expanding their training programme to meet the challenges of

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changes in every community, villages and towns. Our statement of educational intension should emphasize on the training that can be used positively to promote social unity and peaceful co-existence in all society of the world to breed social stability.

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Qualitative Study on Interdependence Learning Strategies for Effective Teaching of Social Studies at Basic Levels of Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

The paper titled qualitative study on interdependence learning strategies for effective teaching of Social Studies at basic levels of education in Nigeria. It's a descriptive review on the interdependence learning strategies as it related to Social Studies at basic levels of education in Nigeria. Effective teaching of Social Studies education at basic levels of education in Nigeria is geared towards production of active and rational citizens capable of thinking critically, analyze issues clearly, identify the problems objectively, pry into its causes, assess its effects and evolve possible means of solving them using inquiry and problem-solving approaches. This paper therefore, examined the interdependence learning strategies, Social Studies education at basic level of Nigeria education, constructivism theory position on the positive interdependence learning strategies in teaching Social Studies education at basic levels of education in Nigeria. Conclusion and recommendations were made.

Keyword: Social Studies, Interdependence, Learning strategies, Basic level of education

Introduction

Education is the bed rock for national development and basic education levels in Nigeria concept can be said to be the provision of education from the primary up to and including the first three years of the secondary level of education. Basic education is the base-line education on which all other educational advancement depend. This determines the stability of the entire educational building that anyone can ever have. Thus, it's to a large extent what determines the success or failure of all other stages of education that may come on it (Amaddioha & Akor, 2020). This means that education should be available to citizens who are willing to participate or benefit from the primary level which normally begins at the age of 6 for majority of Nigerians.

The Primary and the Junior Secondary levels of education are said to be Nigeria government's promise to provide to its citizens free but compulsory. With this idea in mind, the government made attempts to make basic education free by starting the Universal Basic Education scheme to cater for the basic educational needs of its citizens to justify catch them young approach where pupils are well prepared for their better future. This will also help to make the learners' law abiding, critical thinkers and problem solvers of their beloved country Nigeria. Social Studies as a subject was a product of 1969 curriculum conference that brought about Nigeria education blue print called national policy on Education of different editions. This conference was called on the need to rebuild Nigeria from the bondage of foreign administrators that was not only exploitive but also dehumanizing. Among the remarkable landmarks of the conference was the formulation of national philosophy and national educational objectives. It is worthy to note that, the educational objectives was developed to facilitate realization of national philosophy through which Social Studies objectives were derived. However, Nigeria philosophy as a nation is to achieve a free and democratic society; a just and egalitarian society; a united, strong and self-reliant nation; a great and dynamic economy; and a land of bright and full opportunities for all citizens (Federal Republic of Nigeria {FRN}, 2013).

In line with above, national educational aims and objectives in Nigeria are the inculcation of national consciousness and national unity; the inculcation of the right type of values and attitudes for survival of the individual and the Nigeria society; the training of mind to understanding the world around; and the acquisition of appropriate skills, abilities and competencies both mental and physical and equipping the individual to live in and contribute to the development of his country (FRN, 2013). The objectives of Social Studies education at Nigeria basic education levels are to: create an awareness and an understanding of the evolving social and physical environment as a whole, its natural, man-made, cultural and spiritual resources, together with the national use and conservation of these resources for development; develop a capacity to learn and acquire certain skills which are essential to the formation of satisfactory professional life and the forming of sound judgment; ensure the acquisition of knowledge that is relevant and regarded as an essential pre-requisite to personal development as well as to a positive personal contribution to the betterment of mankind; develop in children positive attitudes to citizenship and a desire in them to make a

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positive personal contribution to the creation of a united Nigeria; develop a sympathetic appreciation of the diversity and interdependence of all members of the local community and the wider national and international communities so that they would become aware of the problem of their country and the world in general; and develop in children an appreciation of the nation's cultural heritage and desire to preserve such heritage (Owen, 2022).

Also, students' interdependence in teaching and learning process cannot be overemphasized. Hence, in order to make instructional delivery effective, there is need for paradigm shift in the instructional process using variant learning strategies include positive interdependence learning strategies (Usman, 2024). There are two types of interdependence learning approaches namely positive and negative interdependence. Positive interdependence are cooperative and collaborative while competitive learning strategy formed negative interdependence (Johnson & Johnson, 2018). However, when the needed result is not arrived at from neither process, the teacher resort to individualized approach. The purpose of this article is targeted on the quantitative study on interdependence learning strategies for effective teaching of social studies at Basic levels of Education in Nigeria. Constructivism theory of positive interdependence learning strategies namely collaborative and cooperative learning strategies as well as the relevance of interdependence learning strategies in social studies education were reviewed.

Social Studies Education at Basic levels of education in Nigeria

Nigeria education has different levels with levels designed for categories of its beneficiaries. On the definition of social studies, experts of social studies concluded that, there is no single universal acceptable definition of social studies. However, the concept of social studies can be understood within the context of the objectives which underline the philosophy and aims of the society's education (Ikumelu *et al.*, & Oyibe, 2015). This is true of all countries which have Social Studies in their school curricula. This is clearly stated in all the editions of Nigeria national policy on education. National Council for the Social Studies United States in Eduviere (2018) defines Social Studies as "an integrated study of the social sciences and humanities to promote civic competence". This definition revealed relevance of social studies education and that is civic competence. Abubakar (2013) defined social studies education as a field of study that instils in students the knowledge, skills, attitudes and actions that are considered important in the relationship and interaction of man and those around him on one hand, and the entire environment on the other hands.

Social Studies Education can be used in Nigeria to achieve peace, minimize ethnic problems in various states, tribalism, sectionalism, bribery and corruption, hatred, anger, rigging of elections, cultism in institutions of learning, students unrest, prostitution, examination malpractice, armed robbery, kidnappings, assassinations, forgery, suicide bombing, religious conflicts, and many other social vices in our society. Social studies is a unique subject that is committed towards transmitting values in citizens and assist them to acquire basic designed body of knowledge, skills and attitudes needed for responsible citizenship for Nigeria development (Opoh & Edinyang, 2014).

Theoretical Perspectives on Interdependence Learning Strategy: Constructivism Theory

Learning theory can be viewed as an approach that describe how subject matter, learning content or skills are acquired, absorbed, processed and retained for future context. It provides explanations of the factors that influence learning and instructional guidelines to overcome them. Constructivism Learning Theory according to Padgett (2020), sees learners as a constructor of knowledge. As propounded by Lev Vygotsky (1978), constructivism learning theory hold that, learning is a collaborative process, and that social interaction is rudimental to cognitive development of the learners. It stated that, learners learn best when working collaboratively with those whose proficiency level is higher than their own, allowing them to complete tasks they are not yet able to do independently (Padgett, 2020).

Makewa (2019) also stated that constructivism theory hold that learning take place if learner construct mechanisms for it using his/her own unique talents and argued that, academic knowledge need to be constructed by the learners with teacher as guidance and motivator by creating conducive learning environment. It further stated that, the learners' engagement actively is key to achieve the instructional set goals. McLeod (2019) stated that, constructivism theory requires that academic knowledge and authority should be shared between students and their teachers, serve as facilitators of learning. Hence, learning group should consist small heterogeneous number of students. The learning implications of this theory is that, there should be adequate teachers' guide to help the learners to apply their knowledge to solve learning problems. Learners centred learning approaches are emphasized because they allow the learners' self-control and decision-making based on knowledge and ideas (Hartmann, *et al.*, 2017). Positive interdependence are cooperative and collaborative and these discussed as follows.

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Collaborative Learning Strategies at Basic level of education in Nigeria

Collaborative learning strategy as the name implies, involves grouping of learners of the basic educational level to work together as an instructional team to achieve set instructional objectives. Collaborative learning can be defined as an instructional approach where students work together in small group on specific activities where everyone is required to participate actively. Adolphus *et al.* (2013) viewed it as pedagogical system which learners engage in a common task where each individual depends on and is accountable to each other. This strategy placed learners at basic education levels to be actively involved in the learning processes in which they assimilate information and relate the new knowledge to their cognitive structure for future utilization and subsequent learning tasks. It is an instructional approach in which students work together in small groups to solve learning problem, accomplish a common instructional goals or create a product (Jibrin *et al.*, 2021).

Collaborative learning strategy is one of the positive interdependence in the learning process based on the assumption that academic knowledge and skills can be created within a population where members actively interact by sharing experiences and take on asymmetry roles. It allow learners at basic education levels in the group to share academic ability and contribute their personal knowledge through sharing of responsibilities among the members and accept fruitful views from the members (Chandra, 2015). The author further stated that, collaborative learning activities operate on the principles that, learners at the basic levels of education are the primary focus of instruction, interaction and doing as well as working in group.

Akinwamide (2018) stated that, increase students' tolerance and acceptance of diversity; communication and social skills; and enhancement of students' academic interests as well their academic performance formed critical features of collaborative learning strategy. Abubakar and Arshad (2015) maintained that, collaborative learning entails students debating their ideas and viewpoints on the learning issues through presentations and interactions in groups. It gives them ability to appreciate a variety of other viewpoints to successfully carry out the assigned task with people from diverse backgrounds. This learning strategy engage students actively in the learning process and places more responsibility of comprehension on them; their role is shifted to a more active approach rather than being lectured and getting information passively. Evaluate speaking ability of students in real-life situations because it plays a pivotal role in everyday life interactions.

Agah (2020) stated that, collaborative learning helps to eliminate misconceptions and lack of understanding thus, better understanding and higher achievement are enhanced. It also enable the teacher, the learners and educators share a common aspiration of ensuring that appropriate skills are inculcated in and acquired by the learner. Collaborative learning encourages critical thinking skills to students much better than individualistic learning environments (Jibrin, *et al.*, 2021).

Cooperative Learning Strategies at Basic level of education in Nigeria

Cooperative learning strategy is another innovated teaching method in which students of different ability work together in groups to accomplish the assigned instructional goals. Hence, the students work together as a team with the aim of achieving the purpose for which they agreed to come together to promote their learning as well as their teammates learning (Bukar *et al.*, 2020). Ihejamaizu *et al.* (2020) and Philemon and Nonye (2019) defined cooperative learning strategy as a method used for small groups in which pupils/students' work together to gain from each other. In cooperative learning, students work together to maximize and gain from each other. The students/pupils are expected to help, discuss and argue their points with each other, assess each other's current knowledge, and fill any gaps. Here, the students of cooperative group do not assume mastery of the effort which leads to the success of the group as each member actively contributes to the success of the group.

David (2019) describe cooperative learning strategy as the learning strategy where students' are assigned to small groups in the classroom as well as another environment in which they help each other to learn together, cooperate to have positive achievement to attain academic goals, increase the self-confidence of individual students, develop good communication skills and fully participate actively in the learning process. The strategy involves assigning students to a learning objective; the teacher who assigns that instructional objectives serves as guardian and supervisor to ensure that students attain the specific objective that was set to achieve.

The reasons for cooperative learning are to promote students' learning and academic achievement; enhance students' satisfaction with their learning experience; help students develop skills in oral communication; develop social skills & promote student self-esteem; help to promote positive relations that can lead to gain high students academic achievement (Bukar *et al.*, 2020). Philemon and Nonye (2019) also stated that, the aim of cooperative method of teaching is to bring students together in a relatively small group to pursue a specific task as well as promoting teamwork among the students. Bukar *et al.* (2020) identified five elements of cooperative learning strategy to include positive interdependence; individual accountability; face-to face interaction; appropriate use of collaborative skills; and group processing. To do these, they recommended five steps to be

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used by teachers during cooperative learning setting. These are introduction; divide the students into group of five; assign activities to be carried by each group; discussion on the concept taught and evaluation.

In a cooperative learning classroom students' structure, students discuss the instructional content, assist the peers to learn, and provide encouragement for members of the group to learn. The strategy promote more positive attitudes towards the instructional experiences than competitive or individualistic methodologies (David, 2019). He affirmed that students benefit academically and socially from cooperative learning.

Difference between Collaborative and Cooperative Learning Strategies at Basic level of education in Nigeria

Although, cooperative and collaborative learning strategies are used interchangeably, the two strategies are not the same. Bhopal (2023) and Chandra (2020) itemized the followings as the basic differences between collaborative and cooperative learning strategies.

1. Collaborative learning strategy involves division of students into several independent instructional groups while cooperative involves division of learners at basic education levels into small instructional groups under the guidance of their teacher. This implies that, cooperative is more of teacher centred than collaborative.
2. Collaborative strategy involve collective problem solving while cooperative involves clear role assignment by the teacher.
3. Collaborative involves group participation in the assigned task while cooperative requires task division for individual efforts.
4. In collaborative learning strategy, learners at basic education levels to dominate learning process while in cooperative, teachers' structured learning process for the students.
5. In collaborative learning strategy, mutual cooperation, involvement, and combined efforts of the learners at basic education levels are involved while in cooperative various aspects of the instructional tasks are determined, and learners at basic education levels are given the responsibility of finding a solution to different aspects which is then integrated to solve the problem.
6. In collaborative strategy, learners in the instructional team works together sequentially on different aspect of task assigned to them while in cooperative learning strategy, students works concurrently on different aspects of the given task.

Review of related studies on Interdependence learning strategies.

Usman (2024), Niyonsaba *et al.*, (2022). Wokocha and Allen (2021), Agah (2020), Anthony *et al* (2018), and Okwelle and Owo (2018) in their various studies found that, students taught using collaborative learning strategy outperformed their counter parts taught with other conventional methods of teaching. This implies that, improvement in students' academic performance as observed from the students taught with collaborative learning strategy. Similarly, students taught using collaborative learning strategy recorded higher problem solving abilities and learning motivation than those taught with the conventional method (Adolphus *et al.*, 2013). This also underscore the problem solving as an integral part of social studies objectives. Furthermore, empirical researches on cooperative learning strategy revealed that, group of students taught with cooperative learning strategy performed better than those taught with other teaching methods like lecture, discussion and etc. This finding further necessitate the need to adopt and apply cooperative learning strategy (Usman, 2024, Ihejiamaizu, *et al.*, 2020, Ibemenji *et al.*, 2019, Gabriel *et al.*, 2018, and Stephen, 2017). Also, students taught using cooperative learning strategy also retained significantly better in than those taught with conventional method (Usman, 2024, Akinlande & Jacob, 2020).

Conclusion

This article looked into qualitative study on interdependence learning strategies for effective teaching of social studies at basic levels of education in Nigeria. Based on the discussion and deliberation of this article, it is believed that, positive interdependence learning strategies for effective teaching of social studies at basic levels of education in Nigeria will promote interdependence among social studies pupils at basic level of Nigeria education; promote we-feeling and unity of purpose; inculcate dialogue skills during deliberation towards problem solving; promote group discussion skills to generate ideas and solve problem; foster teamwork and cooperation; help the students to develop problem-solving skills; facilitate human diversity in the group relationship; and stimulate active participation in the group activities.

Positive interdependence learning strategies mainly cooperative and collaborative has enormous instructional impacts. Thus, there is need to equip Social Studies teachers on the use of it through training and re-training, close monitoring and supportive supervision to pave way for on the job training as well as to increase Social Studies teachers teaching morale. This will go a

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long ways to facilitate students' interactive and participatory learning thereby making learning a light in their mind instead of burden in their memory.

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Effect of Polya's Problem-Solving Model on Interest in Algebra among Secondary School Students in Minna Metropolis, Niger State.

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of Polya's problem-solving model (PPSM) on interest in algebra among secondary school students in Minna metropolis, Niger state. The study adopted Quasi experimental control group design involving pre-test and post-test. Population of the study consists of all government senior secondary school class two (SS11) students during the 2022/2023 academic session. Two hundred and forty (240) students from four schools randomly selected from Bosso and Chanchaga local government areas were used as sample. Algebraic Word Performance Test (AWPT) was used to measure the students' interest level. It was validated by experts from Department of Science Education. After pilot testing, Cronbach's Alpha was used to ascertain the internal consistency and the reliability coefficient was 0.82. Two research questions were raised and answered, and two null hypotheses were tested. Descriptive statistics of mean rank, and sum of mean rank were used to answer the research questions while Mann-Whitney U-test was the statistical tool used for testing the hypotheses at 0.05 confidence level. The result revealed that: significant difference exists between the mean interest level of the students in the experimental group and those in the control group. Based on these findings, it was concluded that Polya's problem-solving model enhanced the interest of students in secondary school. The researcher recommends that Polya problem solving model should be used to help secondary school learners learn effectively. Secondly, workshops seminars and conferences should be organized by MOE, MAN, and STAN to train teachers on how to teach algebraic word problem using Polya's problem-solving model.

Keywords: Polya's problem-solving model, interest, conventional method, gender.

Introduction

Students view mathematics with a negative response, even though mathematics is beneficial for students' lives. By learning mathematics, students can master the concepts and implementation of mathematics correctly in their lives. For this reason, it takes much mastery of mathematics concepts as the basis for solving various mathematical problems (Isroil et al., 2017; Fasha et al., 2018). In fact, many students find it difficult to understand mathematical concepts because the lessons are abstract and difficult to understand (Heryan, 2018). Jusra and Ramadhani (2022) added that this view occurs because students cannot use their abilities when solving mathematical problem correctly and precisely. Babatunde, Abdulrahim, Muhammadu and Zakariyya (2018), noted that algebra is a very technical and abstract aspect of mathematics which is always difficult for students to understand, which eventually makes students to memorize and leaning would not take place. As to arouse the interest of the students, it then becomes the duty of the teacher to teach mathematics in a way that will encourage the understanding of the required basic structure of mathematics. One way of achieving this is through a careful and thoughtful selection of appropriate teaching strategy (problem solving strategy) that will help students in understanding mathematics concepts especially in algebraic word problem rather than passive reception of ideas.

The Polya's problem-solving model is a four-step process. Polya (1957) set out his summary of the core verbal steps in problem solving thus: understanding the problem, devise a plan, carry out the plan, and look back. The method is simple and generalizes well; it has become a classic method for solving problems. Sani (2021) reveals that a problem-solving approach to teaching mathematics defines the role of the teacher as a facilitator of learning rather than a transmitter of knowledge and the learner, as a manager and director of his or her own learning.

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Ezumezuh (2017) noted that lecture method (conventional method) of instruction is the usual classroom “chalk-talk” method where a teacher does most of the talking while the learners are passive listeners. Lambaya (2021) added that there is need to adopt strategies that could enhance meaningful learning and improve the learners’ interest and performance in mathematics. Therefore the classroom teacher should bear this in mind, using appropriate teaching model as to generate and sustain students’ interest which in turn brings about favorable academic performance. Gender is another variable in this study. According to Khasanah, Usodo and Sabanti (2018), one of the differences between male and female is the brain. Female perform better than male in verbal memory and male better in spatial ability. Male tend to be good in abstraction, mathematical reasoning and more accurate on target, while female better understand concrete things, better in remembering and mathematical calculations. In problem solving, both male and female have different ways of thinking in accordance with their mathematical abilities. Yahaya (2021) defined gender as a set of characteristics that distinguish a male from a female. This work studies the effect of Polya’s problem-solving model on interest in algebraic word problem among students in senior secondary school.

In the interest theory of Hidi and Renninger (2006), they describe interest as an outcome of motivated behavior because interest is developed and deepens with engagement. They define interest as a unique motivational variable, as well as a psychological state that occurs during interactions between persons and their objects of interest, and is characterized by increased attention, concentration and affect (feeling). It has to do with the desire to re-engage with a particular content such as objects, events, ideas, and tasks. Furthermore, they identified and distinguished between two types of interest to include individual or personal and situational interest. These they developed into four phases of interest development; Situational interest to include, triggered situational interest and maintained situational interest while Individual interest include emerging individual interest and well-developed individual interest. This study will be focused on situational interest. Situational interest according to them is transitory and is elicited by condition in the environment which focuses attention and generate act that promote attention, recall, task persistence and effect. Triggered situational interest can be described as a short-term changes affective and cognitive processing sparked by content. This phase is generally but not always externally supported by the environment. Maintained situational interest is a psychological state subsequent to triggered situational interest that involves focused attention and persistence over an extended period of time for content/ tasks that an individual considers meaningful or relevant. John Dewey (1938) maintained that interest facilitates learning, improves understanding and stimulates effort as well as personal involvement.

From the theoretical framework above, the construct of this study is built on the fact that when learning is learner-centered, that is learners are allowed to participate actively in the teaching and learning process, their interest is aroused which in turn leads to positive academic performance. This work studied the effect of Polya’s problem-solving model on interest in algebraic word problem among senior secondary school students.

It has been observed that many environmental factors affect a person’s ability to concentrate absorb and retain information, and this is a problem because learning is hindered. Another problem is that the preferred mode of teaching is often reflective of an educator’s own cognitive preference. This is a commonly ascribed belief that, teachers teach the way they learn.

Furthermore, there is the problem of poor performance in mathematics (especially in algebraic word problem) and negative attitude towards the subject. Esan (2015) is of the opinion that various factors were attributed to these poor performances which include large class size, students’ negative attitudes, teachers’ negative beliefs, lack of interest, poor teaching strategies, and lack of instructional materials. Many students seem to be afraid of the subject thereby losing interest. The abstract nature of mathematics is also a problem of itself. Students can only overcome these problems if they are helped to learn in a better way.

Finally, despite the parents’ effort in guiding and helping the children at home in their school assignment, extra lessons and buying of learning materials, a good number of mathematics students still experience negative outcome as regards to their academic performance. The concern of this study is to investigate if the application of Polya’s problem-solving model can be used to enhance the interest level of the students in algebraic word problem in senior secondary school.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this study is to identify the effect of Polya’s problem-solving model on interest in algebraic word problem among senior secondary school students. The specific research objectives include, to:

1. Investigate the effect of Polya’s problem-solving model on the students’ interest in algebraic word problem.
2. Determine establish the effect of Polya’s problem-solving model on male and female interest in algebraic word problem.

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Research Questions

The researcher formulated the following research questions for the success of the study.

1. What is the difference in the mean interest level of students taught algebraic word problem using Polya's problem-solving model and those taught using conventional method?
2. Will there be any difference in the mean interest level of male and female students taught algebraic word problem using Polya's problem-solving model?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant difference between the mean interest level of students taught algebraic word problem using Polya's problem-solving model and those taught using conventional method.
2. **H₀₂**: There is no significant difference in the mean interest level of male and female students taught algebraic word problem using Polya's problem-solving model.

Methodology

The study employed pre-test post-test quasi-experimental control group design. The study used two groups; Experimental and Control. Experimental group was exposed to Polya's problem-solving model, while control group was taught using the conventional method. The two groups were taught algebraic word problem. Pre-test and Post-test were administered before and after the treatment to determine the effects of the two instructional methods on student's interest in algebraic word problem. The population of the study consists of senior secondary two (SSII) Mathematics students admitted in the academic year 2022-2023 from the twenty-two (22) public conventional senior secondary schools in Bosso and Chanchaga local government areas Minna, Niger state Nigeria. They have total population of six thousand, two hundred and sixty one (6261) SSII students. Four schools were used as sample for this study. Two schools were randomly selected from each local government (Bosso and Chanchaga). Two hundred and forty (240) students were used as sample for the study with 60 students from each school. The choice of (240) as sample for the study is guided by scholar's view; Mugenda and Mugenda (2003), is of the opinion that a class size of at least thirty (30) students is enough in each group for quasi experimental research.

Algebraic Word Interest Inventory (AWII) was the instrument used for data collection. It was adapted from Yahaya (2021). It was developed to address this issue by assessing interest through simple behavioral indicators. AWII consists of 20 items gauging three dimensions of algebraic word interest: Positive Valence (PV), Negative Valence (NV) and Peer Group Valence (PGV). PV was assessed by 5 items and reflects the degree to which students report a positive attraction toward algebraic word problem (examples, "I love to be identified as a student of any subject that requires algebraic word problem"). NV was assessed by 12 items that is related to negative experiences associated with algebraic word problem ("I feel sleepy when doing assignment involving algebraic word problem"). PGV was assessed by 3 items and reflects peer group work of respondent with other students in algebraic word problem ("I like observing algebraic word problem activities carried out by other students"). Time allocated was 30 minutes. The instrument (AWII) was validated for content, construct, and criterion related validity. This was achieved by presenting the instruments to my supervisors, lecturers from faculty of education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. They were requested to study the instruments and certify if the questions were considered to be testing the performances of the students, check for possible errors in the instruments and suggest corrections. The suggestions of the experts were put into consideration and the corrections were effected.

AWII was Pilot tested in one of the senior secondary schools that is not part of the study sample but part of the population to further determine the validity and reliability coefficient and find out the administrative and logistic problems that may hinder the main study. It was administer for one hour. After pilot testing the instrument, the results were subjected to statistical analysis using SPSS version 20 for the reliability coefficients. Result obtained from AWII was computed for internal consistency using Cronbach's Alpha. The reliability coefficient was 0.82. The selected algebraic word problem topics were taught to the sampled students for six weeks. Polya Problem solving model was used for the experimental group and conventional method was used for the control group. Pre-test and post-test was given to students using (AWII) as to ascertain the interest level of both the experimental and control group. For the purpose of data collection, the AWII was given to the students to tick their responses. Data was collected, computed and the scores divided into experimental and control group and were recorded respectively. The students' scores from the post-test of algebraic word interest inventory (AWII) were collected for analysis. The research questions were analyzed using mean rank and sum of mean rank while the null hypotheses were analyzed using Mann-Whitney U-test at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance.

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Result

Research question 1

How does the mean interest level of the students taught algebraic word problem using Polya’s problem-solving model differ from those taught using conventional method?

To answer this research question, mean rank, and sum of mean rank were used.

Table 1: Mean Rank and Sum of Mean Rank of Interest Scores of the Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Mean Rank	Mean Rank Difference
Experimental	120	149.08	17890.00	57.16
Control	120	91.92	11030.00	
Total	240			

Table 1 shows the mean rank and sum of mean rank of the interest scores of the experimental and control groups which shows that the mean rank score of the experimental group 149.08 is found to be higher than the mean rank score of the control group 91.92.

Hypotheses 1

H₀₁:

There is no significant difference between the mean interest score of students taught algebraic word problem using Polya’s problem-solving model and those taught using conventional method.

To provide an answer to this hypothesis, Mann-Whitney U-test of the Interest scores of students taught algebraic word problem using Polya’s problem-solving model and those taught using conventional method were used.

Table 2: Analysis of Mann-Whitney U-test of Interest of students in the Experimental and Control Groups

Groups	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U-test	P-Value
Experimental	120	149.02	17890.00	3770.000	.000
Control	120	91.92	11030.00		
Total	240				

P<0.05

The result in Table 2 shows that there is significant difference in the mean rank of interest scores between the experimental and control group. The Mann-Whitney U-test is 3770.000 and P-value is 0.001. The P calculated is lower than the P critical. Based on this, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Research Question 2

Do differences exist in the mean interest level of male and female students taught algebraic word problem using Polya’s problem-solving model?

To provide an answer to this research question, the mean rank, and sum of mean rank scores of the male and female students taught algebraic word problem using Polya problem solving model were used.

Table 3: Mean Rank and Sum of Mean Rank of Interest Scores of Male and Female Students

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Mean Rank	Mean Rank Difference
Male	60	63.48	3808.50	5.95
Female	60	57.53	3451.50	
Total	120			

Table 3 above shows the mean rank and sum of mean rank of the interest scores of the male and female students which shows that the mean rank score of the male students 63.48 is found to be higher than the mean rank scores of the female students 57.53.

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Hypotheses 2

H₀₂:

There is no significant difference in the mean interest level of male and female students taught algebraic word problem using Polya's problem-solving model.

To test this hypothesis, the post-test mean of interest score of male and female students were analyzed using the Mann Whitney U-Test statistics. The result of the analysis is shown in Table 6 below.

Table 4: Analysis of Mann- Whitney U-test of interest of male and female students.

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Mean Rank	U-Test	P-Value
Male	60	63.48	3808.50	1621.500	0.35
Female	60	57.53	3451.50		
Total	120				

P<0.05

The results in Table 4 indicate that there is no statistically significant difference in the mean interest scores between the male and female students. The Mann Whitney U-test is 1621.500 and P-value is 0.35. The P calculated is higher than the P critical. Based on this, the null hypothesis is retained.

Discussion of Findings

The result of the analysis presented in Tables 1 and 2 showed that the students taught algebraic word problem using polya's problem-solving model had a higher interest level than the students taught the same concepts using conventional method. The result could be due to the fact that Polya's problem-solving model employed for the experimental group is student centered. This implies that Polya's problem-solving model is more effective in arousing the interest of the students than the conventional method in teaching students algebraic word problem. The Polya's problem-solving model gives the students the opportunity to think, understand the problem, devise a plan, carry out the plan, and check, under the supervision of the teacher. This is not so with conventional method of teaching which is teacher centered. This is in agreement with the writings of Hidi and Renninnger (2006), they described interest as an outcome of motivated behavior because interest is developed and deepened with engagement. Wong (2019) added that in relation to mathematical learning, students' interest can be promoted by first presenting a mathematical problem that is able to provoke and confront students' prior knowledge and scaffold students to take challenges that help students gain successful experience. The results of the analysis presented in Tables 3 and 4 showed that the interest level of male and female students taught algebraic word problem using Polya's problem-solving model had slight difference in favor of the male. This means that the male benefited more than their female counterpart. This is in agreement with the words of Khasanah, Usodo and Sabanti (2018), that male tend to be good in abstraction, mathematical reasoning and more accurate in target. It was recommended among others that teachers should use Polya problem solving model in teaching mathematics mostly algebraic word problems. A remarkable notice of this study is that this model has shown to be effective in improving students' mathematical ability irrespective of gender.

Conclusion

Based on the results obtained from this study, the following conclusions were made;

1. The use of Polya's problem-solving model aroused the interest of the students in algebraic word problem.
2. The polya's problem-solving model is very effective for the improvement in the interest level of both male and female students
3. Conventional method commonly used by teachers in secondary schools is not suitable for meaningful teaching and learning of mathematics and algebraic word problem in particular.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Mathematics teachers should use Polya's problem-solving model to teach the students in secondary school.
2. Authorities in science education and professional bodies should regularly organize workshops, seminars and conferences to popularize the use of Polya's problem-solving model in schools.

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3. The students irrespective of gender should be taught using Polya's problem- solving model as it enhances academic performance.

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Effects of Convergent and Divergent Instructional Strategies on Achievement in Basic Technology among Secondary School Students

in Calabar Municipal

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Abstract

The study intends to investigate effects of convergent and divergent instructional strategies on achievement in basic technology among secondary school students in Calabar municipal. Quasi-experimental research design specifically, pretest - posttest non-equivalent control group design was adopted for the study. The sample size of the study consists of 120 upper Basic class three (JSS3) students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Calabar municipal, Cross River State. The participants first took a pre-test after which they were divided into three groups for the treatment. After the treatment, each group took a posttest to demonstrate the extent of understanding the materials learnt. The data was analyzed using ANCOVA and Post Hoc analysis. The study revealed that students exposed to divergent strategy have high performance in basic technology than those taught using convergent strategy. It was further recommended that teachers should be encouraged on the use of divergent instructional strategy in the teaching and learning of Basic Technology

Keyword: Convergent instruction, divergent instruction, electricity.

Introduction

Education is often regarded as an instrument for social, economic, scientific and technological development. Nigeria as a country desirous of wholistic development is doing everything possible to provide the needed education for her citizen

In Nigeria, and almost at all level of education, there is a repositioning in favour of an education that ensures, job-creation, self-employment and wealth creation. At the Basic level of education, vocational education is one aspect that is designed to develop skills, abilities, understanding, attitudes, work habits and self-reliance. One of the pre-vocational subjects offered at this level is Basic technology; which is to provide knowledge in woodwork, metal work, technical drawing, 'auto-mechanic' and electricity and electronics (Ohikehemg, 1994). It is an aspect of education that attempts to provided learning experience that would assist students in understanding the industrial and technological aspect of life.

According to the National Policy on Education (2004), Basic technology is a phase of general education designed to introduced the learner to and acquaint him/her with the basic process, material and product of the industries. In other words, it is intended to reduce ignorance about technological education. Specially, the objectives are: (i) To provide pre-vocational orientation for further training into technology; (ii) To provide basic technology literacy for everyday living, and (iii) To inculcate creativity

It is however, surprising that despite the efforts of government, good spirited individuals and non-governmental agencies to enhancing educational development at this level, the general performance in Basic

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technology is not encouraging. Reports from different States of Nigeria indicated poor performance of students in their Junior Secondary School Examination in the subject (Nwoji, 2000; Lenda, 2001 & Igberadja, 2015).

With this abysmal performance, it is doubtful if the students can even interpret simple machine drawings, carry out simple production of light using battery and wire, or even simple maintenance of motor vehicle or whether they have even acquired appropriate job training and experience in any of the specific trades.

Many factors have been implicated for the abysmal performance of students in Basic technology examination (Okebukola & Jegede, 1986; Adejoh, 2006; Igberadja, 2015). These include: inability of the teacher to put across the concepts to the students; lack of skills and competence required for teaching and shortage of qualified teachers. Similarly, Nwodo (1997), Jati (2003), Omalle and Okedi (2008) all opined that the poor performance of students in basic technology may be due to the use of inappropriate teaching methods.

There is therefore need for the continuous search for the most effective approach to the teaching and learning of this important subject, that will enhance students understanding and application of learnt concepts and principles, and such searches have resulted in the development of student-centered instructional approaches such as divergent method, among others. Okri, Joy and Peter (2021) investigated the effectiveness of classroom environment and SSII students report of avoidance strategy in Mathematics in Ikom Education Zone, Cross River State. A sample of 300 SS II Students, (150 males and 150 females) was used for the study. Propulsive multistage random sampling technique (stratified and simple random sampling) was used to composed the sample. Three research questions were answered and three hypotheses were tested in the study at p-0.05. Questionnaire was used to collect the data. The obtained data was analysed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). It was found that student classroom truancy significantly influences students report of avoided strategy in Mathematics performance. In another study, Okri and Aglazor (2020) conducted a study effectiveness of three instructional strategies in the improvement of senior secondary students' performance in geometry in Ikom Education Zone of Cross River State. Four schools were sampled consist of 150 senior secondary school (SS II) students (77 females and 73 males) with an average age of 15 years participated in the study. A validated instrument titled Geometry Performance Test (GPT) was used for data collection. The reliability of the instrument was established using Kuder-Richardson, KR-21 to obtain an index of 0.84. Five research questions and five hypotheses guided the study. The research questions were answered using Analysis of Co-variance (ANCOVA) at .05 level of significance. The findings indicated that the highest performance gain was made by students taught using hands-on instructional strategy (HIS) and co-operative instructional strategy (CPIS). There were no significance relative main effects on gender on the GPT score on students taught using HIS, CPIS and COLIS respectively. There was a significant difference among the three instructional strategies with respect to GPT scores of students. It was recommended among others that Mathematics teachers should endeavor to adopt both strategies in the delivery of geometry concepts in Mathematics instructions in the senior secondary schools in Nigeria.

Studies abound which attest to the relative effectiveness of the divergent approach in facilitating students' technology concepts attainment (Waine, 2010 & Reintelman, 2007). Commenting on the effect of teaching strategies, Steadman (1994) & Anyafulude (2007) both affirmed superiority of divergent strategy to the convergent strategy in students' achievement. Divergent instruction strategy is simply a method where the students are asked to produce as many solutions to a problem as they probably can. It involves open ended questions and students-centered, involving divergent thinking. On the other hand, convergent instructional strategy is a common teaching method where the teacher transmits the necessary information to the students. The students engage in convergent thinking, where they draw on their prior knowledge to answer mostly closed-ended questions.

It is against this backdrop that this present study sought to examine the effects that convergent and divergent instructions have on students' understanding/ of electricity principles which is an aspect of Basic technology in order to provide scope and direction. In this study, the comparative effect of the two instructional strategies (convergent and divergent) on students' achievement and understanding of some electricity principles was the focus.

Research Hypothesis

The Following research hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in mean achievement scores of basic technology students taught the concept electricity using convergent instructional strategies and those exposed to divergent instructional strategies among upper basic schools in calabar municipal.

Methodology

A quasi-experimental research design. Specifically, pre-test, posttest non-equivalent control group design was adopted for the study. The sample consisted of 120 JSS3 Basic technology students in selected schools in the study area during the 2023/2024 academic session. The students were drawn from three intact classes randomly drawn from a clustered sample of three Junior Secondary in Calabar Municipal.

The validated instrument was developed by one of the researchers who is an expert in measurement and evaluation. These include the pre-achievement test in some electricity principles, post achievement test and a test to determine their understanding of what was taught. The experimental groups were taught some electricity principles by the researchers using convergent and divergent strategies while the control was taught by their regular teacher using his usual/ conventional method. After 4 weeks, the post achievement test in electricity was administered to the students. Two weeks after the administration of the post achievement, the test to determine understanding was administered. In this case, the post - test was re-administered to assess understanding of basic principles of electricity. The instrument's reliability was 0.76 using Cronbach alpha reliability test. The resulting scores were analysed using SPSS. The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of probability using ANCOVA.

Results

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in mean achievement scores of basic technology students taught the concept electricity using convergent instructional strategies and those exposed to divergent instructional strategies among upper basic schools in calabar metropolis.

To test this hypothesis, the analysis of covariance was used and the results are shown in Table 1. The result of the analysis of covariance shown in Table 1 revealed a significant F- ratio of 15.66 at .05 level of significance with 2 degrees of freedom. This indicates that the calculated f-ratio is statistically significant. In other words, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected. With the rejection of the null, the alternate hypothesis which states that There is significant difference in mean achievement scores of basic technology students taught the concept electricity using convergent instructional strategies and those exposed to divergent instructional strategies among upper basic schools in calabar metropolis is hereby retained.

Table 1: Analysis of covariance of students Mean understanding scores classified by treatment groups with pre-test as covariate

Sources of variation	SS	Df	Ms	F	Sig
Covariate	2613.40	1	2613.40	*36.42	.000
Main effect	2098.80	2	1049.40	*15.66	.004
Explained	4712.31	3	1570.77	*17.43	.005
Resident	14552.70	116	125.433		
Total	19265.01	119			

To determine the direction of the difference in the mean understanding scores of students in the three teaching strategies (convergent, divergent and conventional) the Scheffe's test was applied and the result is as shown in Table 2. The result in Table 2 showed a significant means difference of 7.40 and 10.02 indicating that students taught with divergent method have higher mean performance score than those taught using convergent and conventional strategies, respectively. On the other hand, the non-significant difference of 1.29 indicates that students taught with convergent method were not better than those taught with the conventional method.

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Discussion of Findings

The result shows that students taught with divergent strategy had higher mean performance score in concept electricity than those taught with convergent and the control group.

This finding agrees with those Steadman (1994) Anyafulude (2007), Reintelman (2007) and Waine (2010). Of course, this result was expected as those studies were all in the area of science. However, this finding disagrees with Ofoterbi (1990) who observed that convergent and expository were equally effective. This lack of difference may be due to the fact that both expository and convergent strategies do not involve students in the brainstorming associated with divergent strategy (Anyafulude, 2004).

Table 2: Scheffe's Post Hoc multiple comparison of students' mean understanding scores in some electricity principles test by teaching strategies

Dependent variables	Treatment		Mean difference (I-J)	SD Error	Sig
	(I)	(J)			
Achievement Scores	Convergent	Divergent	- 7.40*	2.12	.002
		Conventional	1.29	2.25	.076
Achievement Scores	Divergent	Convergent	7.40*	2.12	.002
		Conventional	10.02*	1.70	.004
Achievement Scores	Conventional	Convergent	1.29	2.25	.076
		Divergent	10.02*	1.70	.004

Conclusion

Based on the finding, it was concluded that divergent teaching strategy is more appropriate in improving performance in Basic Technology among upper basic students in calabar municipal, Cross River State.

Recommendations

1. Teachers should be encouraged to explore both convergent and divergent instructional strategy by using the convergent strategy to introduce the foundational knowledge needed to solve problems; and thereafter use the divergent approach to make students more logical, creative, understand and retain concepts in Basic technology.
2. Teachers' training and retraining seminars should incorporate divergent and convergent strategies that have proved very effective in the teaching of technology related subjects.

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Effects of Online Teaching and Mental Ability Grouping on Achievement in Organic Chemistry among University Students in South-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

This article investigated the effect of online teaching strategy (using Google online classroom) and mental ability groupings on achievement in organic chemistry among university students in southwest, Nigeria. The study was carried out among 100 level science students in two Nigeria universities in the southwest, Nigeria. Students involved were those offering basic organic chemistry as a pre-requisite course leading to the award of Bachelors' Degree in science, applied science and Science Education. The study adopted a pre-test, posttest, quasi experimental and control group research design using a 2 x 2 factorial representation. A total of 160 undergraduate students offering chemistry were involved in the study and data analysis was by Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). Result of finding affirmed the efficacy and supremacy of online teaching strategy over the conventional teacher-student classroom interaction teaching strategy ($F_{(1,155)}=49.015$, $p < 0.05$; $n^2 = .22$). It also revealed that students' mental ability had a significant effect on students' achievement in organic chemistry (mean difference = 12.71, $p < 0.05$). The study recommended that, chemistry teachers especially at the undergraduate level should adopt online teaching method in the teaching of organic chemistry. This should be done in such a manner that the gap between high and low mental ability students is bridged.

Keywords: mental ability, online teaching, undergraduates, achievement, organic chemistry.

Introduction

The bedrock of growth and development of any nation is rooted in Science and Technology. Any nation that ignores this does so at its peril. Babayemi (2014, p1) as cited in Babayemi and Ahmed (2019) stated that "Science and Technology remains the arrow head that determines the degree, direction and dimension of national development". In order to achieve national goals, the role of science teaching cannot be under estimated. In line with this, nations all over the world (including Nigeria) have emphasized the teaching of science and technology – based subjects at different levels of Education in their various countries' education systems. Arising from this, nations all over the world had made the teaching of science and technology-based subjects compulsory at the basic and higher levels of education. In line with this, Nigeria's National policy of Education 1981 revised in 2013 has emphasized and listed Chemistry as one of the core subjects to be taught at the Senior Secondary level of Nigeria Educational System.

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Chemistry as a subject plays a central role in the scientific and technological advancement of any nation. This has been widely reported by researchers in the field of Science and Science Education both in Nigeria and at the international levels. These past studies include those of Raimi (2022); Raimi and Sodamade (2020).

In spite of the importance so attached to Chemistry as a school subject, evidence abound that students' performance in the subject had been on the decline. A number of reasons have been put forth as responsible for the observed downward trend in students' achievement in the subject. This varies from the use of improper teaching method by the teacher (Esparaco, 2005, Raimi, 2002; Babayemi & Utibe, 2017) to poor students' attitudes towards science especially chemistry (Raimi, 2022a; 2022b). Other factors that have been identified to be responsible for poor learning outcome in Chemistry are improper exposure to laboratory activities (Olagunju & Babayemi, 2014; Babayemi, Itighise, Umanah, Abasi & Umoh, 2023). Babayemi and Olagunju (2015) lamented that most science classes have the problems of lack of class activities and instructional resources to teach the subjects. Other reasons for students' low performance are: poor science background in Junior Secondary School (Raimi, 2002), lack of problem-solving abilities (Raimi & Sodamade, 2018), failure to read the question and understand the question before rushing to answer (WAEC, 2016, 2019), poor quantitative ability (Orji, 2000; Raimi, 2002) and students' gender (Olagunju & Babayemi, 2014; Raimi & Sodamade, 2019; Umanah & Sunday, 2022; Kopezynski & Silva 2023).

These problems have made science educators to focus on how to improve the teaching and learning of Chemistry over the years (Raimi, & Babayemi, 2013; Itighise & Babayemi, 2018; Etiubon, Akpan & Udoh, 2021). Such efforts include, problem solving approach Orji 2000, Raimi 2002, Raimi and Adesoji 2004), the use of practical oriented teaching (Raimi 1999), the use of on-line teaching method (Akpan, Itighise & Umo, 2022; Raimi, 2022).

On-line teaching and learning have come to stay in educational process all over the world due to digital and technological advancements and other recent pandemic challenges (Ebola, Covid-19, etc) that shook the entire world system. This means that the way teachers teach and the way learners learn have gone beyond offline classroom interactions to online virtual classroom interactions. Both offline and online teaching and learning, take advantages of online and offline teachers and resources for students' learning gains. The focus of this research is on online, which an additional platform for students to learn irrespective of the warranting conditions. Such warranting conditions include large traditional class size (overpopulated physical classrooms) (Babayemi, Akpan & Babalola, 2017), insufficient practical apparatus for scientific investigations, insufficient human resources including teachers and other school supportive staff, unavailability of school laboratory (Babayemi & Kareem, 2019), library and workshop places, pandemic experience limiting students from accessing schools and natural disorders, among others. Other conditions that may warrant the use of online teaching and learning, as reported by Carlen and Jobring (2005) include the potential of online learning communities to facilitate communication between people who share common interests and learn collaboratively using networked technologies. They however posited that researchers and designers have to understand the social practices in order to explore and develop technological tools for such collaboration and communication.

Many of the studies conducted on online instructional approach have been carried out at the secondary school level. There is also the need to focus attention on how to improve students' achievement in Chemistry especially at the university undergraduate level. It is also necessary especially among students who are not pursuing careers in core chemistry but take chemistry courses as pre requisites in pursuance of careers in science and technology related fields. The present study intends to fill this gap. The present study also investigated the effect of the use of on – line teaching strategy on students' achievement in basic organic chemistry. Performance of students in Chemistry can also be influenced by other learners' characteristics such as mental ability. Studies in this area have been reported in the past by researchers (Raimi & Adeoye, 1999; Yang & Ekpeyong, 2000; Raimi, 2002; Babayemi & Akinsola, 2014). Reports from these studies have expressed divergent views regarding the relationship between ability and performance in Chemistry. Some, such as Raimi and Akinyemi (1997), Adeoye and Raimi 2005, Iyang and Ekpeyong (2002) found a direct relationship between the two variables, others such as Adegoke (2000) and Kasali (2000), Adeoye and Raimi (2005), Raimi & Sodamade (2018), Babayemi and Ahmed 2019) did not establish such relationship.

In views of this divergent views, there is need to investigate further on the effect of students' mental ability on achievement in Chemistry especially basic organic chemistry. Hence, the present study investigated the relationship between the two variables at the undergraduate level especially when it involves the use on-line teaching strategy. The present study also investigated the interaction effects of students' mental ability on achievement especially when on- line teaching is employed as a means of instruction and assessment at the university level.

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Objectives of the study

The study determined undergraduates' achievement in basic organic chemistry using online teaching and mental ability groupings. Specifically, the study:

1. Determine the achievement scores of students taught basic organic chemistry using online strategy and those exposed to conventional method.
2. Determine the mean achievement scores of students taught basic organic chemistry using mental ability grouping strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method.
3. Determine the interaction effect between the achievement scores of students taught basic organic chemistry using online teaching method and mental ability grouping method.

Research questions

1. Is there any significant difference between the achievement scores of students taught basic organic chemistry using online teaching strategy and those taught with lecture method?
2. Is there any significant difference between the achievement scores of students taught basic organic chemistry using mental ability grouping strategy and those taught with the conventional lecture method?
3. Is there any interaction effect between the achievement scores of students taught basic organic chemistry using online teaching strategy and those taught with mental ability grouping method?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of students taught basic organic chemistry using online teaching strategy and those exposed to the conventional lecture method.
2. There is no significant difference between mean achievement scores of students taught basic organic chemistry using mental ability grouping strategy and those exposed to the conventional lecture method.
3. There is no significant interaction effect between the mean achievement scores of students taught basic organic chemistry using online and mental ability grouping strategies.

Methodology

The study employed a pre-test, post-test experimental control group design using a 2 x 2 factorial representation. The population for the study comprised mainly all the undergraduate students of the two universities in Oyo state, Nigeria, that participated in the study. Only undergraduate students in the two universities that have CBT centers participated in the study. The purposive sampling technique was used in selecting participant for the study. A total of 160 undergraduate students which comprised 59 males and 101 females were involved. Age range of students' sample as at the time of this investigation was 17-25 years. The students' sample are those offering basic organic chemistry as one of the basic and compulsory science courses in the universities., These students are those who have studied for two semesters at the university or undergraduate level. This is in addition to their background knowledge of organic chemistry at the secondary level which qualifies them to enroll in. their various proposed career in the universities.

Two valid, reliable and relevant instruments were used to collect relevant data for the study. The two instruments are Chemistry achievement Test (CAT) and Mental Ability Test (MAT). The CAT is a 100 – item multiple choice to which students were to provide answers. Each CAT item has for options A – D out of which one is correct. The MAT is a standard Oti – Lenon (1976) and modified by Raimi (2002) mental Ability Test. it is a standard test for categorizing learners into mental ability groups. The two instruments were subjected to further reliability test by administering them among the 100 Level students of another public university that did not take part in the main study. A test-retest reliability coefficient for the instrument was very strong. CAT (0.76) and MAT (0.75). There are two main groups in the study. These are the experimental and the control groups. In the experimental group, online teaching strategy was used to teach the content of the course, basic organic chemistry. The two teachers handling the courses in the two universities handled the instructional sessions. These teachers were subjected to 3 – week training workshop on the use of online strategy through the Google classroom. Two observers were also appointed as research assistants who monitored the implementation of the treatment procedure. Before the classroom sessions, the students were requested to acquire g – mail address while a link through which they could connect the classroom online was provided. During the online classroom interaction, students were allowed to ask questions, raised observation and passed comments. The teacher took time to attend to students' questions, comments and observations. The experiment lasted for sixteen weeks. 3 weeks of training, 12 weeks of experiment and one week for test administration.

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In the control group, students were exposed to basic organic chemistry content using the conventional lecture method. Here, there existed teacher – students’ interaction. Instructional session took place for the same number of weeks as in the experimental group. As in the experimental group, students were given the opportunity to ask questions, pass comments, make remarks and raise observations, while the lecturer was on hand to attend to students’ requests. As the lesson progressed, students were also exposed to formative evaluation. At the end of instruction, students were given the same summative evaluation as in the experimental group. After the treatment in each group, students were subjected to post-test achievement test. Students in both the experimental and control groups were given the MAT to respond to. The test was administered mid-way in to the experiment. The administration was achieved through the teachers who handled the instructional sessions of the study. This was also done with the assistance of the observers (research assistants). The test was collected and scored accordingly. The result of the scoring was used to categorize the students into High and Low ability groups. The categorization was done by finding the mean ability score after pooling the ability scores for all the sample together, which gave ($\bar{x} = 49.7$). Any student who scored ≥ 49.7 in the MAT is adjudged as having high mental ability while those with MAT score <49.7 were considered as having low mental ability. By this, the sample were categorized into High and Low mental ability groups.

Data collected were subjected to descriptive analysis of means and inferential statistical Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). An estimated marginal Means for Post–Achievement was carried out in order to determine the magnitude of the difference between the experimental group and control group. Bonferroni post hoc analysis was also carried out in order to determine the direction and rational of the difference among the identified groups.

Results

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught basic organic chemistry using online teaching strategy and those exposed to lecture method

Table 1: Summary of ANCOVA of Post – Achievement in Chemistry by Treatment and Mental Ability

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta Squared
Corrected Model	56823.208	4	14205.802	100.560	.000	.722	
Intercept	12874.177	1	12874.177	91.134	.000	.370	
Pre-Test	29.146	1	29.146	.206	.650	.001	
Treatment	6924.220	1	6924.220	49.015	.000	.240	
Mental Ability	1563.927	1	1563.927	11.071	.001	.067	
Treatment * Mental Ability	371.963	1	371.963	2.633	.107	.017	
Error	21896.392	155	141.267				
Total	371814.000	160					
Corrected Total	78719.600	159					

Source: Raimi et al 2022

Table 1 shows that treatment had a significant main effect on students’ achievement in Chemistry ($F_{(1; 159)} = 49.015$; $p < .05$, $\eta^2 = .240$), hence, the null hypothesis one is hereby rejected. The effect size is 24%. This implies that 24% of the post – achievement of students score in Chemistry is accounted for by the treatment applied. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the post-achievement of students in chemistry. In order to determine the magnitude of the significant main effect across treatment groups, the estimated marginal means of the treatment groups was carried out and the result is as presented in Table 2:

Table 2: Estimated Marginal Means for Post achievement by Treatment

Treatment	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Experimental Group	59.761	1.535	56.729	62.792
Control Group	32.977	3.507	26.051	39.904

Source: Raimi et al 2022

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Table 2 shows that the students in the experimental group had a higher adjusted post-achievement mean score (59.76) than students in the control group (32.97). This implies that the students in the experimental group outperformed their counterparts in the control group by the virtue of the treatment applied.

Table 3: Bonferroni Post-hoc Analysis of Post-Achievement by Treatment

(I) Treatment	(J) Treatment	Mean Difference (I – J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Experimental Group	Control Group	26.783*	3.826	.000	19.226	34.340
Control Group	Experimental Group	-26.783*	3.826	.000	-34.340	-19.226

Source: Raimi et al 2022

Table 3 shows that the difference between the post-achievement of students in chemistry is significant (Mean Difference = 26.78; $p < .05$). This implies that the main effect of the treatment is due to the significant difference that exists in the achievement of students in the experimental and the control group.

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught basic organic chemistry using mental ability grouping strategy and those exposed to lecture method.

Table 1 shows that mental ability had a significant main effect on students' achievement in chemistry ($F_{(1,159)} = 11.07$; $p > .05$; $\eta^2 = .067$), hence, the null hypothesis two is hereby rejected. The effect size is 6.7. This implies that 6.7% of variance in students' post-achievement in Chemistry was accounted for by the treatment applied. Table 4 below shows the estimated marginal mean of this post-achievement across the two levels of mental ability.

Table 4: Estimated Marginal Means for Post-Achievement by Mental Ability

Mental Ability	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
High	52.724	3.521	45.769	59.679
Low	40.014	1.495	37.061	42.967

Source: Raimi et al 2022

Table 4 shows that the students with high mental ability had a higher adjusted post-achievement mean score (52.72) than students with low mental ability (40.1). This implies that the students with high mental ability outperformed their counterparts with low mental ability. Hence, this difference is the source of the main effect of mental ability, as shown in table 5 below:

Table 5: Bonferroni Post-hoc Analysis of Post-Achievement by Mental Ability

(I) Mental Ability	(J) Mental Ability	Mean Difference (I – J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
High	Low	12.710*	3.820	.001	5.164	20.256
Low	High	-12.710*	3.820	.001	-20.256	-5.164

Source: Raimi et al 2022

Table 5 shows that there is a significant difference between the post achievement of students with high mental ability and students with low mental ability (Mean Difference = 12.71; $p < .05$).

Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant interaction effect between the achievement scores of students taught using online and mental ability grouping strategies.

Treatment and mental ability on students' achievement in basic organic Chemistry ($F_{(1,155)} = 2.63$; $p > .05$; $\eta^2 = .017$). Hence, the null hypothesis three is hereby accepted. This implies that the interaction of treatment and mental ability did not bring about a significant difference in the post-achievement scores of students in chemistry.

Discussion of Findings

The study further confirms that using Google classroom interaction on-line could be a better strategy to promoting good learning organic chemistry. It was found that the use of this strategy significantly enhanced science undergraduates' performance in Basic Organic Chemistry. It revealed that students in the experimental group (on-line teaching) group achieved significantly better than students who were taught via the conventional classroom interaction methods. This is why researchers Akpan, Itighise and Umo (2023) submitted that it is very necessary to integrate digital tools and platforms in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics teaching (STEM) to enhance instructional process. The result of this study is in line with an earlier and related study in (Koller& Ng, 2014, Maqsood et al, 2022 and Raimi, 2022), which affirmed the supremacy of the use of online teaching method over the conventional teaching method. The implication of this finding is that, students' achievement is enhanced through on-line teaching strategy especially when it involved learning of Basic Organic Chemistry among undergraduate students. This then means that, chemistry teachers especially at the undergraduate level should adopt its use in their teaching. The use of the method can be aided by the school authorities, school administrators and policy makers. This can be achieved in a number of ways. On the one hand, the school authority could plan the school curriculum, lecture timetable and other school activities to accommodate the use of this strategy in the teaching of Chemistry and science at the undergraduate level. On the other hand, adequate efforts should be made for university teachers and undergraduates to fix their programs for a successful implementation of the strategy.

Adopting this method also has the advantage of enabling chemistry teachers at the higher level of education an easy coverage of their course content especially where lecturers have to combine other administrative works such as attendance to students' problems (both personal and academic), preparation of students' results, attendance at meetings with teaching. Lecturers can reschedule their lectures to other convenient time and in collaboration with the students. Furthermore, nowadays with the lowering of JAMB cut off marks and the attendant upsurge in enrolment in the face of inadequate infrastructures, it is becoming increasingly difficult for lecturers to cope with effective learning and evaluating students. Adopting this strategy will minimize the problems associated with large classes and its attendant problems. As a result of this practicing chemistry teachers at the University level are urged to use this method of teaching due to its potency in assisting both learners and their teachers.

The use of online teaching requires more commitment from teachers in terms of commitment and dedication and self-development. In the light of this, Heads of departments, Dean of faculties, University administrators are urged to put modalities in place and provide enabling school environment that can aid the use of on-line teaching supported with materials that can aid the Chemistry and indeed science teachers' use of the method including self-development programs. Such should include organizing refresher courses and seminars, training programme, workshops that bother on improving the teaching of chemistry. This should be supported with adequate funding and provision of adequate and workable network facilities at subsidized rate for both students and lecturers. These have the potential of assisting the institution minimize wastage and to maximize the use of their facilities in the face of ever-increasing students' enrolment. The finding is however negating that of Maqsood, salif, Mazhar and Arif (2022) in their study" positive and negative effect of online teaching "when they found that online teaching is fraught with many negative features ranging from students 'on participation in learning, to less physical interaction between students and teacher leading to students' isolation in the learning process and laziness on the part of students.

The study also revealed that there exists a significant difference between the mean achievement scores in basic organic chemistry of students taught using mental ability strategy and those exposed to conventional lecture method. The direction of significance is in favor of students with high mental ability. This finding shows that students with high mental ability performed better in Basic Organic Chemistry than their counterparts with low mental ability, especially when online teaching strategy is employed in instruction delivery. The result of this study is in line with those of Raimi (2002); Babayemi and Akinsola (2014) that confirmed significant main effect of numerical and mental abilities on achievement at different levels of educational attainment including cognitive achievement. Raimi (2002) found that the effect was more on the control group especially in comparison with different experimental groups when supplemental (problem solving) method was used as a means of instruction. The result was also in line with those of other studies such as, Hacker (1992), Raimi and Oduwaye (1997), Salawu (2001) and Babayemi (2014) when they found something similar in their different studies.

Furthermore, critical look at the result of the analysis, it was found that there exists a wide difference in the mean scores of students in the high and low ability (mean difference = 12.71 $p < 0.05$). This implies that Chemistry teachers need to employ strategies that have the potential of bridging educational gap between below average students and their counterparts with high mental ability. Such methods include online (Google Classroom) teaching and attempt should be made to create conducive learning atmosphere that is capable of achieving this.

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The insignificant interaction effect of treatment and mental ability on chemistry achievement has some educational implications. This shows that, the significant main effect on post achievement scores in Basic Organic Chemistry was as a result of treatment (that is the use of online teaching) irrespective of ability. Students in the experimental group performed significantly better than their counterparts in the control group. This was affirmed by the non-significant interaction of treatment and ability as observed in table 1. The insignificant main effect based on ability perhaps might be due to the use of online teaching strategy which assisted low ability group cope with the content of the course taught. As practicing Chemistry and science teachers, enhanced teaching technique needed to be adopted to bridge the gap between students with low and high mental ability such as Online Teaching method. This also corroborates the research findings by Raimi 2002, Raimi and Adesoji 2004, who in their earlier related studies recommended the use of enhanced teaching strategy to teach Chemistry at the secondary school level.

Conclusion

In this article, the main and interaction effects of online teaching strategy and students' mental ability on achievement in Basic Organic Chemistry was investigated, at the undergraduate level. In line with general expectation, the study affirmed that the use of online classroom interaction significantly enhanced students' performance in Basic Organic Chemistry when compared with the use of teacher-students' physical classroom interaction mode of teaching. The significant effect was found to be prominent irrespective of students' mental ability.

Recommendations

On the basis of these findings, it is recommended that,

1. Science teachers and indeed chemistry teachers at undergraduate level should employ the use of online teaching strategy, especially in the teaching of basic organic chemistry. This should be done regardless of students' mental ability. Teachers.
2. In adopting the use of online teaching strategy, a level plane and conducive learning environment should be provided for learner of different ability groupings can learn without any hindrance.
3. Furthermore, heads of departments, deans of faculties and university authorities should provide appropriate and adequate infrastructures that can enhance the use of online teaching mode of instruction. This has the potential of solving a number of educational and institutional problems relating to school administration, curriculum planning and implementation.

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Comparative relationship between Personal Integrity and Performance in Citizenship Education among Colleges of Education Students in North-Central Nigeria

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Abstract

The main objective of the study was to examine the Comparative relationship between Personal Integrity (PI) and Performance in Citizenship Education among Colleges of Education Social Studies Students in North-central Nigeria. Correlational Survey research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study consists of all NCE Social Studies students in North-central, Nigeria during the 2023/2024 academic session. A sample of 750 (Male, 345 and Female, 405) students were selected from the target population using simple random sampling technique. Two research instruments were used for the study: namely, “The Integrity Scale” and the researcher-designed “Citizenship Education Performance Test”-CEPT with reliability coefficients of 0.76 and 0.82 respectively. Data were analyzed using percentages and multiple regression statistics at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant relationship between PI and performance in Citizenship Education among Social Studies NCE students in North-central, Nigeria. The study concludes that PI has significant correlation with performance in Citizenship Education among Social Studies NCE students in North-central, Nigeria. The study recommended that PI should be promoted through value education workshops and seminars among students.

Keywords: Personal Integrity, Performance, Citizenship Education, Students

Introduction

Nations of the world in general and the Nigerian nation in particular deem it fit to seek for men of great character, conscience and integrity when there is need for certain public or political positions to be occupied. It is however saddening at times when people are finally appointed or elected into such esteemed positions of authority, when statements such as “square pegs in round holes” and “round pegs in square holes” begin to suffice. In addition, some Nigerians consider government properties as general or free-for-all properties that do not need to be protected or properly maintained for the good of the populace. This can be classified as one of the reasons why some Nigerians consider national treasures as “national cake” which is to be scrambled for by all and sundry. Based on the aforementioned submissions, an inquisitive mind may begin to wonder if these and many more, are some of the reasons for the continued call by both individuals, civic society groups as well as government for the promotion of sound values and attitudes such as honesty, hard-work, integrity, patriotism and democratic principles in the educational system in part and in the nation as a whole. It is imperative for these issues to be timely nipped in the bud.

Nigeria has a country is plagued with a range of social, cultural, economic, educational and political problems which pervades all sectors and aspects of national life from technocrats to politicians. The deficiencies of well-versed and participating citizenship are major causes of these problems. It was with regard to the foregoing that the Nigeria Academy of Education in Ajose, (2001) made the submission that, there is a pressing necessity to examine the impact of citizenship education on the Nigerian society, because citizenship education is an indispensable subject that was designed especially in both content and function to produce healthy, good and active citizens. In this context, a good citizen is perceived as patriotic, disciplined, responsible and meticulous as well as ethically thorough with affection for his/her state. For example, Akpan (2001)

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and Edozie (2009), reported that the absence of an informed and participatory citizenship is a major factor responsible for a number of vices bedeviling the Nigerian society. This may indicate that the practice and exhibition of salient features of good and effective citizenship education for the advancement of the coveted humane society is yet to be achieved.

In recognizing and realizing the importance and benefits of Citizenship Education, the Nigerian government has deemed it necessary to key into the educational sector as an indispensable tool in an effort at national growth and development. According to the National Policy on Education (2013), the goals of tertiary education shall include, among others, contribution to national development through high level relevant manpower while developing and inculcating proper values for the survival of individual and society. It means that education at the tertiary level is expected to inculcate in its recipients appropriate values (such as hard-work, honesty, patriotism, integrity, dignity of labour and loyalty among many others), which will equip graduates for a smooth personal transition from school-life to life outside school. These goals are expected to be pursued through teaching, research and development as well as through the generation and dissemination of knowledge. Furthermore, teacher education, both at the NCE and degree levels, shall continue to expand to cater for societal needs and changes in methodology and curriculum (NPE, 2013).

Citizenship Education as a concept and as a course of study aims at grooming members of the society with the right values, skills and morals which are vital to make them effective citizens and contribute positively to the development of their society. Citizenship Education furnishes learners with the pre-requisite academic facts and talents that enable them to understand their rights as well as civic duties and responsibilities that will improve the well-being of the people in the society. Citizenship Education as a course of study, according to Oluniyi (2011) aims at developing young people to become responsible citizens, who are familiar with their fundamental rights and responsibilities and can exhibit dynamic participatory roles in the society. The course should educate students on how they can be politically cultured while using real life situations and experiences.

Citizenship Education is designed to reveal itself as a necessity of life to individuals as well as Social Studies students because ultimately it liberates humans (Blooms, 2004; Suarez-Oroozoo, 2004). It displays education as a tool for pulling societies out of poverty, providing requisite information to all cadres of leadership and for promoting health and social growth, particularly for youths (the leaders of tomorrow). John Dewey about a century ago supported and encouraged the ideals in citizenship education because it liberates humans to find freedom and their calling in life (Okam & Ibrahim, 2011). The attainment of these laudable goals, therefore, calls for an examination of Citizenship Education in relation to some coveted values and attitudes that are stipulated in the National Policy on Education such as honesty, integrity, fairness and justice, patriotism, self-discipline, industry, tolerance, obedience and dignity of labour among others.

Integrity stems from the Latin word 'integer', which means whole and complete (Benjamin, 2000). It is deduced from this definition that integrity requires an innermost sense of wholeness and regularity of character. As a result of this, people are expected to see integrity in one's actions, words, decisions, methods and outcomes. It can, therefore, be deduced here that integrity boils down to safeguarding against infringements: making sure that one does not become tarnished or corrupted or that one does not overstep the mark. From a positive perspective when "wholeness" is attached in the definition of integrity. Integrity refers to the implementation of good practices to ensure that one remains whole, in one piece, or unblemished because it is concerned with the values and principles an individual upholds. The conducts of a person of integrity are complete and consistent, that is, the values and principles, actual conduct, and the consequences that are strived for form a coherent whole. The words and deeds of a person of integrity are in conformity with each other. Integrity concerns the degree to which people are integrated, both on a personal level (towards oneself) and in relation to society (towards others).

To support the foregoing, various authors have classified integrity into various types. White (2017) classified integrity into Academic Integrity, Political Integrity and Legal Integrity. In a similar vein, Six and Hubert (2008) classified integrity into Business Integrity, Political Integrity and Personal Integrity. The focus of this study would be Personal Integrity, which is **an intrinsic moral persuasion to antagonize things that are not virtuous or morally right**; the instinctive tendencies, which persuade individuals to do what they feel and believe is right irrespective of the penalties attached to their resolutions. As a result, people perceived as having high Personal Integrity are usually described as truthful, dedicated, generous, prudent and matured.

Integrity is the feature of being candid and having strong moral principles that are usually exhibited especially on day-to-day living as well as public issues (Yusuf, 2012). This author went further to state that a man of Personal Integrity is one who stands for honesty, accountability, transparency, loyalty, fair play, equity, probity and justice among others and is able to stand by his words and the truth even at the point of death or in the face of threats. Yusuf (2012) informed that students must not only emulate men of integrity in the society but must make it a calling to strive to become one. As such, students of integrity

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exhibit traits such as moral uprightness, hard-work, diligence, commitment, dedication, avoidance of examination malpractice as well as plagiarism. Thus, students can be considered to be of integrity when they conform and act harmoniously with laid down school rules and regulations even when no one is observing.

Integrity according to Oyekan (2016), is described as the extent to which an individual or group is ethically upright based on absolute and fundamental universal standards. In addition, integrity constituted in real practice should be relative to the social, behavioural and cultural demands and settings of many academic communities as well as the society at large (Oyekan, 2016). Integrity is a concept that needs to be investigated because research findings revealed that there exist some traces of academic dishonesty in the Nigerian educational system (Barnett, 2000; Olasehinde-William, 2006; Olasehinde-Williams & Olawuyi 2011; Orim, 2016). It can, therefore, be deduced that citizenship education is a viable discipline in ensuring integrity because its objectives are derived from the overall objectives of education in Nigeria as derived from the provisions of the Nigerian Constitution. Oyekan (2016) further explained that, to entrench integrity anywhere in Nigeria (academic institutions, religious communities as well as professional spheres) requires key cultural and ethical changes as against what is currently obtainable in the society. These laudable suggestions can be met through Citizenship education because one of its objectives is to transmit cultural values and ethics such as honesty, integrity, commitment, dignity of labour, attitudes and attributes that pose as inevitabilities for societal growth and development to individual students (Umudjere, Okogu, & Osah, 2016).

Furthermore, Fannin (2017), in discussing the concept of integrity, described a person of integrity as the type of person you are in your inner-self when no one is observing as well as the person an individual chooses to portray when hard choices press especially when such choices are not considered moral or morally-inclined. Hence, it is very important for individuals to imbibe and strive to create a sense of integrity in their inner-self, because it makes one better. This means that it is necessary for individuals as well as students in a society to make positive efforts in portraying Personal Integrity characteristics in their daily activities and dealings with their knowledge of Citizenship Education. It therefore becomes imperative that Social Studies students should strive to imbibe a strong spirit of integrity in their dealings both in and out of the school system with their knowledge of Citizenship Education. This is very necessary because, as the leaders and teachers of tomorrow, much is desired and needed from them and as such calls for proper Personal Integrity. This study therefore examined the Comparative relationship between Personal Integrity (PI) and Performance in Citizenship Education among Colleges of Education Social Studies Students in North-central Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study was to examine the Comparative relationship between Personal Integrity (PI) and Performance in Citizenship Education among Colleges of Education Social Studies Students in North-central Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to:

1. find out the level of Personal Integrity in Citizenship Education among Social Studies Students' in North-central, Nigeria;
2. examine the performance in Citizenship Education among Social Studies Students in North-central Nigeria;
3. Determine the correlation between personal integrity and performance in Citizenship Education among Social Studies students in North-central, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide this study:

1. What is the level of Personal Integrity in Citizenship Education among Social Studies Students in North-central Nigeria?
2. What is the mean performance score in Citizenship Education among Social Studies Students in North-central Nigeria?
3. Is there any correlation between level of Personal Integrity and mean performance score in Citizenship Education among Social Studies Students in North-central, Nigeria?

Research Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant correlation between level of Personal Integrity and mean performance score in Citizenship Education among Social Studies Students in North-central, Nigeria

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Methodology

The research design for this study is the correlational survey research design. Correlational survey research design is suitable for determining whether, and to what degree a relationship exists between two or more variables. The population of the study consists of all NCE Social Studies students in North-central, Nigeria during the 2023/2024 academic session. The study was conducted only in Federal College of Education, Okene, Kogi State; Kwara State College of Education, Oro, Kwara State and Federal College of Education, Kontagora, Niger State. The Integrity Scale and the Citizenship Education Performance Test were instruments used for data collection. The Integrity scale is an 18-item instrument for measuring Personal Integrity. The scale when validated by the developer had reliability coefficient of 0.74. The Scale had a 5-point scaling model ranging 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neither Disagree Nor Agree, 4 = Agree, and 5 = Strongly Agree. The adapted form of the instrument was a 4-point Likert-type scaling model ranging from 1 = SA: Strongly Agreed, 2 = A: Agreed, 3 = D: Disagreed and 4 = SD: Strongly Disagreed requesting respondents to choose the option that best described their opinion of a statement were adopted for clarity of response options. The Citizenship Education Performance Test was used to establish the performance of students in Citizenship Education; their individual score on the 30 test-items were scored and cumulated. The cumulated scores for all the students were converted to percentage such that percentage scores of less than 45 (0- 44) was adjudged Poor, 45-49 as Fair, 50-59 as Good, 60-69 as Very Good and 70-100 as Excellent. The instruments were administered directly to the students with the assistance of lecturers and two trained research assistants on the day approved by the authorities for the exercise. Respondents were assured of the anonymity as well as confidentiality of their responses as no name or any other forms of identity were required. The data collected for this study were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics procedures.

Results

Three research questions were raised in this study. Research questions 1 and 2 were answered using frequency scores and percentages while research question 3 that had corresponding null hypothesis was tested using Multiple Regression Analysis. The results are presented below.

Table 1: Distribution of Students by Institutions

Institutions	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Federal College of Education Kotangora	244	33.2
Federal College of Education Okene	249	33.9
Kwara State College of Education Oro	242	32.9
Total	735	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 shows the distribution of the Colleges of Education students that participated in this study according to their respective institutions. It showed that out of 735 (100.0%) of the students, 244(33.2%) were selected from the Federal College of Education in Kotangora, 249 (33.9%) from Federal College of Education in Okene while 242 (32.9%) of the students were selected from Kwara State College of Education located at Oro. It is shown in this study that majority of the students that participated in the study were selected from Federal Colleges of Education.

Research Question 1:

What is the level of Personal Integrity in Citizenship Education among Social Studies Students in North-central Nigeria? The result presented in Table 2 shows the Personal Integrity levels of Social Studies students in North-central, Nigeria.

Table 2: Personal Integrity levels of Social Studies Students in North-central, Nigeria

Personal Integrity Level	Score Range	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Low	18 – 36	36	4.9
Moderate	37 – 54	625	85.0
High	55 – 72	74	10.1
Total		735	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024

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Table 2 shows the Personal Integrity levels of Social Studies students in North-central, Nigeria. It shows that out of the 735 (100.0%) that participated in this study, 36(4.9%) exhibited a low level of Personal Integrity, 625(85.0%) exhibited a moderate or average level while 74(10.1%) of the Social Studies students in North-central, Nigeria exhibited a high level of Personal Integrity. It is indicated from this result that the majority of the Social Studies students in North-central, Nigeria had a moderate level of Personal Integrity.

Research Question 2:

What is the mean performance score in Citizenship Education among Social Studies Students in North-central Nigeria?

The result presented in Table 3 shows the performance of Social Studies students in Citizenship Education in North-central, Nigeria.

Table 3: Performance of Social Studies Students in Citizenship Education in North-central, Nigeria

Performance	Score Range	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Poor	0 – 39	451	61.4
Fair	40 – 49	170	23.1
Good	50 – 59	71	9.7
Very Good	60 – 69	30	4.1
Excellent	70 – 100	13	1.8
Total		735	100.0
Mean score = 36.2			

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 3 shows the performance of Social Studies students in Citizenship Education in North-central, Nigeria. It shows that out of the 735 (100.0%) that participated in this study, 451(61.4%) had poor performance, 170(23.1%) performed fairly, 71(9.7%) had good performance, 30(4.1%) had very good performance while 13(1.8%) of the students had excellent performance in Citizenship Education. Indication is shown from this result that the performance of Social Studies students in Citizenship Education in North-central, Nigeria is poor.

Hypothesis Testing

H₀₁: There is no significant correlation between level of Personal Integrity and mean performance score in Citizenship Education among Social Studies Students in North-central, Nigeria

Table 4: Model Summary of multiple regression analysis on relationship among Personal Integrity, Patriotic Attitude and Social Studies students' performance in Citizenship Education in North-central, Nigeria

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	RStd. Error of the Estimate	F	Sig	Decision
Personal Integrity	.327	.107	.104	3.63036	43.732	.000	Reject H ₀₁

Table 4 shows that the relationship among Personal Integrity, Patriotic Attitude and Social Studies students' performance in Citizenship Education in North-central, Nigeria. It is indicated from the table that the relationship between Personal Integrity and NCE Social Studies students' performance in Citizenship Education yielded a coefficient of multiple regression (R) of 0.327 (32.7%) and a multiple correlation square (R²) of 0.107 (10.7%). These values are statistically significant at 0.05 probability level. This implies that Personal Integrity variable accounted for 10.7% of the observed variance in Social Studies students' performance in Citizenship Education. Therefore, it can be concluded that there was a significant positive relationship between Personal Integrity and NCE Social Studies students' performance in Citizenship Education in North-central, Nigeria. Relative contribution of Personal Integrity towards NCE Social Studies students' performance in Citizenship Education is shown in Table 5.

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Table 5: Relative contribution of Personal Integrity to NCE Social Studies students' performance in Citizenship Education in North-central, Nigeria

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.087	1.445		.060	.952
Personal Integrity	.196	.021	.324	9.273	.000

Table 5 shows the relative contribution of Personal Integrity towards Social Studies students' performance in Citizenship Education in North-central, Nigeria. As shown in Table 5, Personal Integrity had beta and t-values of 0.324 and 9.273 respectively. It is therefore shown in this result that Personal Integrity made a significant contribution to NCE Social Studies students' performance in Citizenship Education.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed that an average of the Social Studies students in North-central, Nigeria had a moderate level of Personal Integrity. This implies that majority of the Social Studies students classified within the moderate level or range in the classification of Personal Integrity. This is in-line with the findings of Benjamin (2017) who reported that the characteristics of Personal Integrity are manifested in capricious permutations and degrees. In addition, it contradicts the findings of Nilsen (2004) and Orim (2006) that evidences of low Personal Integrity are manifested in the Nigerian tertiary education system. This result also negates the findings of Yusuf (2005) and Umudjere, Okogu and Osah (2016) that most Nigerians (NCE students inclusive) are ignorant of their obligations through Personal Integrity as a result of the negative concepts passed-on to them by their ancestors as well as former colonial masters. This could be attributed to the aftermath of their exposure and interaction to the teaching of tenets of Citizenship Education (SOS 222) as a course of study. Citizenship education as a course of study helps in exposing students to real life experiences that have positive impact on their personality development as well as their interaction in and out of the school system.

The findings of this study revealed that the general performance of Social Studies students in Citizenship Education in North-central, Nigeria was poor. This implies that more than half of the NCE Social Studies students performed below average in the Citizenship Education Performance Test (CEPT). The findings of this study buttress the revelation of Castro (2013), Martins (2008; 2010) and Ozturk, Malkoc and Ersoy (2016) that both pre-service and in-service Social Studies Education teachers have not established and exhibited citizenship education knowledge, understanding and skills at satisfactory levels. In addition, the findings of Merry (2013) revealed that the teaching and learning of citizenship education is currently drifting away from reality that it risks becoming irrelevant due to poor performance of students in the discipline. However, the finding of this study is contrary to the finding of Kerr (2004) in his evaluation that the performance of students in Citizenship Education positively portrays the preparation for their roles and responsibilities as citizens at the preparatory training process. This outcome may be due to the unpreparedness of some of the participants in their role as future classroom teachers who are responsible and expected to teach effectively the content of Civic Education at the Basic School level. It could also be as a result of the nature of the test items (objective test) as against the familiar norm of essay test as means of examination in most of the schools. Another reason for students' poor performance could be attributed to the difference in cultural background of the respondents.

Conclusion

Based on the discussion of the findings, the study concludes that Personal Integrity has significant correlation with performance in Citizenship Education among NCE Social Studies students in North-central, Nigeria. Personal Integrity was also revealed to have a strong significant contribution in the study.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Personal integrity should be further promoted generally among students through seminars and workshops, to promote integrity in other facets of the lives of students both in the school and outside.
2. Personal integrity should be promoted through value education workshops and seminars among students.

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3. Salient values and attitudes such as personal integrity should be practically demonstrated by teacher-trainers so as to improve the interest of students on the content of Citizenship Education and not just to pass examinations.
4. Social Studies student teachers should make positive efforts towards imbibing acts of Personal Integrity as well as being role models so as to assist them in easily inculcating such and other values into their future learners especially at the Basic school levels.

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Comparative Relationship between Traditional Beliefs and Forest Resource Management among Stakeholders in Yakurr Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The main purpose of this study was to examine comparative relationship between traditional beliefs and forest resource management among stakeholders in Yakurr Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria. To achieve the purpose of this study, a null hypothesis was raised. Correlational research design was adopted. The estimated projected population for the study is 108,140 adult respondents. Stratified random sampling technique was adopted in selecting five communities (wards) used for the study. Systematic random sampling technique was adopted in selecting 300 respondents. A self-developed questionnaire “Traditional Belief and Forest Resource Management (TBFMR)” was used to obtain data. The research instruments were given for scrutiny to three experts in research and statistics. The items were subjected to content validity and reliability by the specialists. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach alpha technique. The coefficient (r) of the instrument was high at 0.75-0.78. Data were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistical tool for hypotheses testing. The findings obtained from analysis of data and testing of hypothesis of the study revealed that there was a significant relationship between traditional belief and forest resources conservation in the study area. Based on the findings obtained in the study, the researcher made the following recommendations Agricultural extension workers and Environmental Educators should continue to encourage farmer to engage in conservation method in order to promote forest resources conservation in the study area.

Keywords: traditional beliefs, forest, resources, conservation, Yakurr Local Government Area

Introduction

The issue of forest resource conservation has in recent times called for global discourse and debate in many countries of the world. Forest resource conservation is the judicious use of forest resources in a way that maintains the biodiversity, productivity, regeneration capacity and their potential to fulfil the present and future generation. Forest is gift of nature and it contains all sorts of important natural resources. The importance of forest goes beyond the provision of physical needs of

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human; to exert tremendous impacts on our environment. The role of forest resource in the environment and every living thing that depends on it directly or indirectly is indeed unique.

Forest forms an integral part of the biosphere, essential to the stabilization of global climate and the management of water and land resources. They are home to countless plants and animals that are vital elements of our life support system. In spite of its importance, forest resources are plagued by several problems when viewed from different perspectives. Many forests land has difficulties of reproducing and some cannot give maximum benefit to man. Much of our forest resources have been lost through deforestation, lack of adequate sensitization of community members regarding forest resource conservation, logging, abuse of indigenous law and regulation, unsustainable farming methods, uncontrolled bush burning amongst others. The consequences of these malpractice include loss of biodiversity, soil infertility, land degradation and exposure to agent of erosion (FAO,2015).

Conservation of natural resources is the wise use of the earth's resources by humanity. It is the management of valuable natural resources such as timber, fish, topsoil, pastureland, and minerals, forests, wildlife, parkland, wilderness and watershed areas. According to (Appiah-Opoku, 2017), to regulate interactions with their natural environment, the role of traditional beliefs in the conservation of a large number of elements of local biodiversity, regardless of their use value, dates back to creation. Berkes, (2010) confirm that traditional conservation ethics are capable of protecting biodiversity species in particular and the environment in general as long as the local communities have a stake in it.

Similarly, Eneji, Gubo, Jian, Oden and Okpiliya (2009b) have pointed out that the existence of traditional beliefs/taboo does not guarantee sustainable harvest of natural resources. Traditional African religion (ATR) and cultural practices as done in most part of African communities are environmentally friendly and sustainable, thus contributing so much to natural resources sustainability and conservation. In Africa and indeed Nigeria, the traditional belief system holds the ascription of supernatural powers to objects called gods and goddesses. The major tenet of African traditional religion and belief system lies in the belief that the abode of the gods and goddesses is located on rock, streams, pond, tress, land or anywhere they so desire to live within the community. The gods choose their followers through the rites of initiation with a core messenger who is the mouth piece of the gods living among human beings. The gods or goddess communicate its will to the people through the juju priest or chief priest.

The belief system is that the gods protect the community members from harm, famine, impotence, drought, epidemics and war among others. The gods avenge their anger on whoever omits or commits any flaw for which their presence forbids; hence, the cultural system holds to a very high esteem all the precepts of the laws of the gods (Shastri, etal, 2012). Tiwari (2018) also maintained that the role of traditional beliefs in the protection of natural resources is reflected in a variety of practices including sacred groves and sacred landscapes. For example, in India, particular patches of forests are designated as sacred groves under customary law and are protected from any product extraction by the community. Such forests are very rich in biological diversity and harbor many endangered plant species including rare herbs and medicinal plants.

A study conducted by Sam (2018) examined the influence of African traditional religion and practices on sustainable conservation of natural resources in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. Two null hypotheses were formulated to direct the study. The hypotheses were tested at 0.5level of significance. The literature reviewed was based on the sub variable of the study. The survey research design was adopted for the study. the choice of this design was to enable the researcher examine the phenomena under investigation as it exists presently in the study area. Purposive sampling technique was adopted to select six autonomous communities that have played significant role in conversation or the natural resources available in the environment. To select the 400 respondents used for the study stratified random sampling techniques was used. The questionnaire was the instrument used to obtain data for the data. The instrument was tested for reliability using Cronbach Alpha reliability test. The result of the test showed the calculated value range of .85 to .97 which implies that, the instrument is reliable enough to measure what is was purported to measure. Data obtained for this study was tested using person product moment correlation (r) statistical analysis. The result obtained from data analysis revealed that, there is a significant relationship between totemism practice, evil forest practice and sustainable conservation of natural resources in the study area. Based on the result from the findings, conclusion and recommendation were made. One of the recommendations is that environmental conservation issues should form an integral part of teaching in various churches and mosque in the country to help reinforce positive attitude among their members and change negative one.

In a study Henshey (2011) posited that in traditional African societies like Nigeria, Ghana, and many others, many people believed that rocks, trees, streams, ponds and forests were the manifestation of the power of the Supreme Being. He saw these things as ideal places to meet their supreme being or the gods. In almost every traditional African setting or community, each community has what they revere or hold sacred either as the presence of their gods or their goddesses, or there is a very important symbolic reason attached to such objects in the course of their existence. In almost every community

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in Cross River, there is hardly any community that exists without a sacred grove, evil forest, sacred pond, evil stream, or forbidden forest. Where some part of the environment is delineated for the worship of the gods (Eneji et al., 2009).

There is an evil forest at Idomi and Mkpani in Yakurr, these evil forests are where bad people e.g., in the community are sent to go and die. If you are a witch or a wizard and have caused havoc in the community, or one dies in an accident such as auto crash or from a tree or palm tree, such corpse are taken to this forest. Some of these evil forests are the burial ground for the royals of the community. In Biase, there is also a burial ground for slaves, nobody wants to be associated with slavery, so the area remains a very thick forest since it is believed that the last slave buried there was before the stopping of slave trade in Nigeria. In Alifokpa in Yache, in Yala local government area, there is also a sacred grove where the remains of the ancestral fathers of the Alifokpa people were buried hundreds of years ago, no farming, felling of trees or harvesting of vegetables is done here. There is also a pond in Yache in Yala Local Government Area, which nobody goes near there, here crocodile, iguana and some wild sea animals are found here. If anybody strays to this pond, the person may be eaten by the wild beast, but the community believes that the person would be killed by the spirit. In Bateriko, some part of the forest is strictly reserve as the home of the gods, here no entrance is allowed into this forest, even when crops are cultivated close to the area, it does not give any good yield (Eneji, 2009). According to Sam and Usang (2018) traditional belief is seen as custom, traditions; culture held by indigenous people or local people and is passed down within a group or society from one generation to another. Non-Governmental Organization which at regulating and advises the urban and local Council and Commissioners on topics relating to forestry practices on forest land.

The literature reviewed reveals various relationships between traditional beliefs as the related to forest resource management. The literature presented various views and findings from different authors and researchers consulted in the study. It was observed that most literature available on the subject matter under investigation was outside the study area of this research work. Therefore, the findings of this study will provide both empirical and theoretical literature on the phenomena under study in the study area. From the review, it is noticeable that numerous studies are related to this present study. The review also shown that most of the studies, even for those carried out in the present study area, have a different focus from the present study in of the independent and dependent variables, it is against this background that the present study will bridge the gap between traditional belief and forest resource conservation in Yakurr Local Government area of Cross River State.

The findings of this study will be of utmost importance to students, members of host communities, Ministry of Environment, forestry commission, non-governmental organizations, policy makers and researchers. To students of Environmental Education and other related disciplines it will be a source of acquiring relevant information and knowledge on the issues under investigation. To the host communities used for this study it shall be a source of acquiring knowledge that would improve their understanding on how their actions and activities contribute to the conservation of forests resources either negatively or positively. The Ministry of Environment will also benefit from the finding of this study as a source of acquiring more information on the relationship between community participation and forest resources conservation. Non-governmental organizations working on forest conservation can use the finding of this study as a working document for improving their various intervention activities and programs aimed at promoting sustainable forest management among forest communities.

The Forestry Commission will also use the result obtained from this study as a source of feedback for their various forest conservation intervention approaches and programs. Policy makers will also use the finding of this study as a source of baseline data for formulating new and more effective policies that would eliminate the various threats to effective forest conservation and management. Researchers intending to carry out a similar study on a broader scope or in other locations will see the finding of this study as a reference material for their various studies

Despite the relevance of forest resources to the maintenance of healthy environment, much harm has been done to the forest ecosystem. Unbridled logging, bush burning, overgrazing, hunting and mining among others, are common in the study area and these unsustainable environmental practices tend to endanger the existing forest resources in the area. The resultant effects of these unsustainable practices include climate change, global warming, drought, loss of biodiversity, loss of fertile land required for improved food product and so on. Efforts have been made by government to cushion these outcomes through the establishment of forest laws, introduction of nomadic education to improve individual knowledge of forest resource conservation, awareness creation through television programs, jingles, radio, conferences among others to control the unwarranted destruction of forest resources and its consequences has not yielded desired results. This unfortunate situation may be attributed to ignorance of rural dwellers about the importance of the sustainable use of forest resources for continued human survival. This implies that residents especially in the rural communities do not have the requisite knowledge, skills, information, and ideas to exploit forest resources sustainably. It is against this background that this study seeks to investigate the relationship between traditional belief and forest resource management in Yakurr Local Government Area of Cross River State.

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Robert Lanza's Biocentric theory (1997); This theory was propounded by Robert Lanza in 1997. The theory holds that nature is sacred and as such should be revered or respected. This theory apart from emphasizing man's interdependence with nature further holds that the living and non-living things were created before man and therefore have their own right of existence in spite of man. The emphasis is that man should live tenderly with nature in natural or symbiotic existence. African culture and most indigenous cultures the worlds over before the advent of colonization were actually given to the biocentric world-view value judgment about nature. In fact, not only were the Africans or native tribes' conscious of their interdependence with nature, the event went as far as ascribing life and supernatural power to nature. All these made it imperative to conserve nature.

The relevance of this theory to the present study is that, the bio-centric world-view promotes and lays the foundation for biodiversity conservation and management at various levels. This view is against wanton destruction and unsustainable exploitation of biodiversity and emphasize that man is not superior to nature but should live in natural or symbiotic relationship with it. Thus, considering the right of these natural resources to exist within the environment and their relevance to him justifies the view point of the theory. This theory is the basis for sustainable utilization and management of natural resources as well as sustainable development. Based on these, the forest resources conservation takes its root from the value judgment of this theory.

The main purpose of the study was to examine the relationship between traditional belief and forest resource conservation in Yakurr Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between traditional belief and conservation of forest resources.

Methodology

The survey design was considered most suitable for the study. It allows the researcher to access the situation under investigation as it exists presently and which involves the collection of data accurately and objectively describe phenomena in the current time and the focus to ascertain facts. The study was carried out in Yakurr Local Government Area of Cross River State. Yakurr is one of the eighteen Local Government Areas of Cross River State. It has a landmass of about (2,771 km²). It is located between latitude 6° 16'26" North longitudes, 9°0'36"East. The area is bounded to the North by Obubra Local Government Area, to the south by Biase, to the west by Akankpa and to the East by Abi LGA (Wikipedia.com). The 2023 population projection for Yakurr is 864,200 persons (National Population Commission, 2023). The population of this study consisted of all adult residents in Yakurr Local Government Area of Cross River State. The actual population includes farmers, hunters, students, traders, business men/women. The estimated projected population for the study is about 108,140 persons (National Population Commission, 2022).

Stratified random sampling technique was adopted in selecting the communities used for the study. The researcher applied the simple random sampling technique in achieving this. The researcher visited the Yakurr Forestry charge office to obtain the list of forest communities. The names of the communities were written on pieces of paper and folded into ball-like shapes, which were poured into a container. The researcher mixed them properly and blindly selected six paper balls from the container with replacement. To select the respondents used for the study, the systematic random sampling technique was adopted. In each of the communities selected for the study, the researcher numbered the houses in the community. Every tenth house was selected for the study. In each house selected, one respondent was picked. These respondents across the various forest communities formed the sample for the study. The sample for this study consisted of three hundred (300) respondents randomly selected from five (5) forest communities in Yakurr Local Government Area of Cross River State. The sample distribution is presented in Table 1.

The instrument considered most appropriate for data collection was a questionnaire and it was tagged Traditional Belief and Forest Resource Conservation Questionnaire (TBFRCQ). It consists of two parts, part A contains items on respondent demographic data while B was designed using four-point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) & Strongly Disagree (SD).

Table 1: Sample distribution table

S/N Names of communities	Pop of unit	Percentage	Samples
Ugep	1180	5%	59
Adim	1220	5%	61

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Mkpani	1330	5%	67
Ekori	1100	5%	55
Asiga	1150	5%	58
Total	5980		300

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

Items 1-5 measured traditional belief; Items 6-15 measured the dependent variable forest resource conservation. The researcher presented the designed questionnaire to experts in research and statistics for screening and finally to the supervisor for face and content validity. Through this process, modification and corrections were made to some of the items in the instrument. The corrections were effected before a trial copy was produced for data collection. Data used for the study was obtained directly from respondents through the use of questionnaire designed for data collection. The researcher with the aid of a trained research assistant visited all the communities selected for the study to administer the questionnaire. In each of the selected communities, permission of the village heads was obtained before the administration of the questionnaire. Total of three hundred (300) questionnaires were administered and retrieved in few days in order to allow the respondents respond properly to the questionnaire as well as enable the researcher to retrieve all the administered instruments. The data obtained in the study was coded by assigning numerical scores to each response in the questionnaire for positively worded items, strongly agree (SA) was scored 4. Agree (A) 3, Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) 1.

Results

Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between traditional belief and forest resources conservation.

Table 2: Pearson product moment correlation analysis of the relationship between traditional belief and forest resources conservation in Yakurr Local Government Area of Cross River State

Variables	X	SD	Cal-r	P.value
Traditional belief	15.534	2.4265	.364*	.000
Forest resources conservation	30.132	3.5876		

*Significant at .05; df=294;

The independent variable in this hypothesis is traditional belief while the dependent variable is forest resources conservation. Pearson product moment correlation statistical tool was used for data analysis. The result of this analysis is presented in Table 2. The result of analysis of data presented in Table 2 shows that the calculated r-value of .364 is higher than the p.value of .000 at .05 level of significance with 294 degree of freedom. The implication of this result is that the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between traditional belief and forest resources conservation in Yakurr Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Discussion of findings

The finding obtained from analysis of data and testing hypothesis in the study revealed that the null hypothesis was rejected; the implication of this finding is that there was a significant relationship between traditional belief and forest resources conservation in Yakurr Local Government Area of Cross River State. The reason for this finding could be that mixed cropping is often considered as an environment-friendly conservation practice. The practice of traditional beliefs promotes soil conservation and by extension forest conservation. This finding is in agreement with that of Tiwari (2018) that the role of traditional beliefs in the protection of natural resources is reflected in a variety of practices including sacred groves and sacred landscapes for example, in India, particular patches of forest are designated as sacred groves under customary law and are protected from any product extraction by the community. Such forests are very rich in biological diversity and harbour many endangered plant species including rare herbs and medicinal plants.

The finding of this study also supported that of Shastri, (2012). The gods or goddess communicate its will to the people through the juju priest or chief priest. The belief system is that the gods protect the community members from harm, famine, impotent, drought, epidemics and war among others. The gods avenge their anger on whoever omits or commits any flaw for which their presence forbids; hence, the cultural system holds to a very high esteem all the precepts of the laws of the gods.

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Conclusion

The results obtained from data analysis testing in the study revealed the following: there is a significant relationship between traditional belief and forest resources conservation in the study area. Based on the finding it was then concluded that there is a significant relationship between traditional belief and forest resources conservation in Yakurr Local Government Area.

Recommendations

Based on the findings obtained in the study, the researcher made the following recommendations;

1. Agricultural extension workers and Environmental Educators should continue to encourage farmer to engage in conservation method in order to promote forest resources conservation
2. Farmers should be adequately and regularly sensitized on the need to participate in committee conservation club, which would reduce the dangers posed by bush burning, deforestation and promote forest resources conservation
3. Self-initiative as a practice should be discouraged among farmers in the study area in order to promote forest conservation and sustainable forest management.
4. Agricultural extension workers should ensure that members of forest communities are adequately sensitized on the need to effectively participate forest conservation practice to promote a healthy environment.

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Integration of Biotechnology Content knowledge in Biology Curriculum at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

The integration of biotechnology into the Nigerian secondary school biology curriculum offers a pathway to increase students' acquisition of essential 21st-century skills. This paper explored the rationale, challenges, and opportunities associated with incorporating biotechnology education into the curriculum to prepare students for the complexities of a globalized world. Biotechnology, at the intersection of biology and technology, held promise across diverse sectors such as healthcare, agriculture, and environmental conservation. The paper discussed the nature of Nigerian secondary school biology curriculum, emphasizing its thematic and spiral organization, and identified gaps where biotechnological topics were underrepresented. Challenges in implementation, including lack of qualified teachers, resource constraints, and ethical considerations, were explored. Opportunities, such as promoting practical, inquiry-based learning and promotion of interdisciplinary connections, were highlighted. The paper concluded that successful integration of biotechnology requires fundamental efforts to review secondary school biology curriculum. Thus, it suggested curriculum review, partnerships for access to biotechnology resources to facilitate instruction, and teachers' professional development.

Keywords: Biotechnology education, 21st-century skills, Secondary school, Biology curriculum

Introduction

In the 21st century, education systems worldwide face the challenge of preparing students for a rapidly evolving and increasingly complex global competitiveness. As societies transition towards knowledge-based economies, the acquisition of 21st-century skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, collaboration, creativity, adaptability, and ethical awareness, has become imperative for students to thrive in a competitive and interconnected world (Isma'il & Cyril, 2022; Trilling & Fadel, 2008). In Nigeria, the education sector faces the challenge of adapting curriculum frameworks to meet the demands of the modern era and the country's socio-economic development goals. Aham et al. (2022) argue that teaching and learning have shifted towards equipping students with the skills to solve real-life problems they encounter daily, rather than solely focusing on classroom-based knowledge.

According to Bahri et al. (2014), biotechnology education promotes the acquisition of 21st century skills, which are key for the contemporary economy. For the nation to flourish in this century, there is a need for strategic priority to emphasize technologically infused topics in biology (Aham et al., 2022). Biotechnology, a field at the intersection of biology and technology, encompasses a wide range of applications that leverage living organisms or biological systems to develop products and processes beneficial to society. In recent years, biotechnology has emerged as a powerful tool with diverse applications in sectors such as healthcare, agriculture, environmental conservation, and industrial manufacturing (Schmidt, 2023). Understanding the basics of biotechnology is essential for appreciating its significance and potential impact on various aspects of human life. As biotechnology continues to evolve, it is essential to stay informed about the latest developments and ethical considerations shaping the field's future.

As part of ongoing efforts to reform the educational system, there is a growing recognition of the need to integrate emerging fields such as biotechnology into the curriculum to equip students with the knowledge, skills, and competencies required for success in the 21st century (Okeke, 2019). Hiong and Osman (2013) have proven the possibility of integration of 21st century skills in biology education. Since the beginning of the 21st century, modern biotechnology has been integrated into senior secondary science curricula in numerous countries, including the United States, England, Canada, and New Zealand (Kooffreh et al., 2021; Nordqvist & Johansson, 2020). Biotechnology education incorporates aspects of ethics and morals, which are less frequently encountered in subjects like chemistry, physics, or other areas of biology (Nordqvist & Johansson, 2020). Biotechnology education often includes ethical, emotional, political, and social dimensions, setting it apart from many

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other science natural science subjects. For example, while scientists generally agree that genetically modified food is safe, many people still have concerns or oppose their use (Nordqvist & Johansson, 2020).

Biotechnology is formed by combining biology and technology. It involves using microorganisms or biological substances to carry out particular manufacturing processes or industrial functions (Unoma & Menkiti, 2017). It is the application of biological knowledge and techniques to develop products and processes that improve human health, agriculture, industry, and the environment, holds immense promise as a catalyst for advancing education and driving innovation (UNESCO, 2015). By integrating biotechnology into the secondary school biology curriculum, teachers can engage students in hands-on learning experiences that not only deepen their understanding of biological concepts but also nurture the development of critical thinking skills and scientific inquiry (Adeyanju & Adeyemo, 2023). Survey conducted in Nigeria by Unoma and Menkiti (2017) revealed that secondary school students exhibit a high level of unawareness regarding biotechnology products and services. Another study by Kooffreh et al. (2021) revealed that secondary school students generally demonstrated limited knowledge, perception, and interest in biotechnology.

These studies stand in contrast to the findings of Bahri et al. (2014) in Malaysia, where secondary school students were reported to possess a moderate level of knowledge, perception, and attitude towards biotechnology. Consequently, Unoma and Menkiti (2017) and Kooffreh et al. (2021) emphasized the need for integrating biotechnology into the current Nigerian senior secondary school biology curriculum, a step that has not yet been taken. The integration is essential for increasing students' understanding and appreciation of the benefits of biotechnology. Based on this background, this paper explores the rationale, challenges, and opportunities associated with integrating biotechnology into the Nigerian secondary school biology curriculum to advance 21st-century skills among students.

Curriculum is prearranged experiences that serve as a teacher's guide and often the sole resource used by teachers. It links educational goals and subject content with the act of teaching in the classroom, containing the syllabus and required subject content learned in the school system (Westbrook et al., 2013). A coherent curriculum has the greatest impact on student success and is the means through which the philosophy of education can be actualized. This implies that the curriculum encompasses all experiences to which learners are exposed under the guidance of the school. Essentially, the function of a curriculum includes everything that affects and influences a learner to be relevant and useful to their society. Parish (2013) contends that learning must be focused on the curriculum. Therefore, the biology curriculum is a key reference point for biology teachers and a vehicle for effective instruction. It encompasses required content learned in the school system.

Nigeria operates a federal system, and as a result, the Federal Ministry of Education, through National Education Research and Development Council (NERDC) and with the inclusion of stakeholders, prepared the biology curriculum under which all senior secondary schools in Nigeria operate (Abe & Owoey, 2016). According to Isma'il and Matazu (2024), the biology subject is an essential part of the secondary school science curriculum, offering students an in-depth understanding of the living world. The current Nigerian Secondary School Biology Curriculum was adapted and revised from the 1985 edition developed by Comparative Education Study and Adaptation Centre (CESAC) under National Education Research and Development Council (NERDC, 2008). The objectives of the curriculum, derived from the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013), The aims of the Nigerian senior secondary school biology curriculum are to prepare students to acquire:

3. Adequate laboratory and field skills in biology;
4. Meaningful and relevant knowledge in biology;
5. Ability to apply scientific knowledge to every day's life in matters of personal and community health and agriculture;
6. Reasonable and functional scientific attitude.

The biology syllabus, as contained in the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC, 2008) curriculum, is arranged spirally using a thematic approach (Oyovwi, 2021). The content and topics cover four major themes:

1. Organization of Life: This includes topics describing the basic structure and classification of living things, such as cell structure and functions.
2. Organisms at Work: This theme covers anatomy and physiological activities, including the digestive, respiratory, and nervous systems.
3. The Organism and its Environment: This theme explains the relationship between organisms and their environment, covering ecology and conservation.
4. Continuity of Life: This describes reproduction, genetics, and evolution.

These themes are directly relevant to secondary school students and society at large. The spiral and thematic arrangements ensure a gradual progression of learning concepts from concrete to abstract (Ogunkola & Samuel, 2011). The curriculum's spiral approach means that students study the same topics throughout their academic careers, with each encounter becoming more complex and reinforcing previous knowledge. The NERDC (2008) curriculum organizes its content into six

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sectors: Topic, Performance Objectives, Content, Activity (Teacher and Students), Teaching and Learning Materials, and Evaluation Guide. This organization guides teachers in preparing the scheme of work and daily lesson plans.

The curriculum emphasizes field studies, guided discovery, laboratory techniques, and skills, along with conceptual thinking. The curriculum promotes student-centered instruction with a focus on experimentation, questioning, inquiry, discussion, and problem-solving, which are essential for students' comprehension (Aham et al., 2022; NERDC, 2008). However, explicit references to biotechnology topics are not prevalent within the curriculum.

Rationale for Integration of Biotechnology into Secondary School Biology Curriculum

The integration of biotechnology into the Nigerian secondary school biology curriculum holds significant importance in preparing students for the challenges and opportunities of the 21st century. By incorporating biotechnology into the curriculum, Nigerian secondary schools can equip students with the knowledge, skills, and mindset necessary to thrive in a rapidly evolving scientific world. One of the primary reasons for integrating biotechnology into the biology curriculum is to align education with real-world applications and industry demands.

Biotechnology plays a central role in various sectors, including healthcare, agriculture, environmental conservation, and industrial manufacturing. By exposing students to basic biotechnological concepts and techniques, it will help in preparing students for future careers in biotechnology-related fields (Oyinloye, 2018). Moreover, integrating biotechnology into the curriculum nurtures critical thinking, problem-solving, and innovation skills among students. Biotechnological research and development require creativity, analytical thinking, and the ability to work collaboratively across disciplines. By engaging students in hands-on biotechnological experiments and projects, teachers can cultivate these essential skills and nurture a culture of scientific inquiry and discovery (Ajayi & Akinpelu, 2023).

Furthermore, incorporating biotechnology education enhances the attractiveness of biology as a subject and promotes student engagement and motivation. Traditional biology education often focuses on memorization of facts and concepts, which may not resonate with all students. By introducing cutting-edge topics such as gene editing, synthetic biology, and personalized medicine, teachers can capture students' interest and curiosity, inspiring them to explore the fascinating world of biotechnology (Adeyanju & Adeyemo, 2023). Also, biotechnology education promotes ethical awareness and responsible citizenship among students. The ethical implications of biotechnological advancements, such as genetic engineering and cloning, raise complex moral and societal questions. By discussing these ethical dilemmas in the classroom, teachers can cultivate students' moral reasoning and encourage thoughtful reflection on the societal implications of biotechnology (Bello & Maude, 2019; Isma'il et al. 2021).

Furthermore, integrating biotechnology into the curriculum contributes to national development goals by building human capital and innovation-driven growth. In an increasingly globalized economy, countries that invest in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) education gain a competitive edge in innovation and economic competitiveness. By equipping Nigerian students with biotechnological knowledge and skills, the country can harness its scientific talent to address local challenges and participate actively in the global biotechnology

Challenges in Implementing Biotechnology Content Knowledge in Biology Curriculum at Secondary School Level of Education

Integrating biotechnology education into the secondary school biology curriculum presents various challenges that teachers and policymakers must address to ensure effective implementation and optimal learning outcomes. Biotechnology offers immense potential for preparing students with essential 21st-century skills, but several barriers hinder its seamless integration into the curriculum, some of which are discuss below:

Lack of qualified teachers with proficiency in biotechnology: Biotechnology is a complex and rapidly evolving field that requires specialized knowledge and skills to teach effectively. Many secondary school biology teachers may not have received adequate training or professional development in biotechnological concepts and techniques. Regarding this matter, Sodangi et al. (2022) argued that continuous professional development is essential for effective implementation of the science curriculum by teachers. In similar vein, Ajayi and Adeyemi (2022) noted that, without competent teachers, schools may struggle to deliver high-quality biotechnology education, limiting students' exposure to the field. Teachers who are not well-versed in biotechnology may not be able to effectively integrate new developments and technologies into their curriculum, thereby failing to prepare students for the demands of the 21st-century workforce.

Resource constraints: Resource constraint pose a significant barrier to implementing biotechnology education in secondary schools. Many schools in Nigeria lack the necessary laboratory facilities, equipment, and reagents needed to conduct

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biotechnological experiments and demonstrations (Oyinloye, 2018). The cost of acquiring and maintaining biotechnology equipment can be prohibitive for schools with limited budgets, especially in rural or underserved areas. As a result, students may miss out on hands-on learning experiences essential for understanding biotechnological concepts.

Outdated curriculum and teaching materials: The biology curriculum in Nigerian secondary schools often prioritizes traditional topics while neglecting emerging areas such as gene editing, synthetic biology among others. This gap can hinder students from gaining up-to-date knowledge in biotechnology. More so, Adeyanju and Adeyemo (2023) highlighted that, textbooks and instructional materials may not always reflect the latest advancements, which can limit students' understanding of current biotechnological concepts (Adeyanju & Adeyemo, 2023). The curriculum, although comprehensive in its traditional scope, does not adequately reflect the rapid advancements in biotechnology, making it imperative to update both the curriculum and teaching resources to ensure that students receive a modern and relevant biotechnology education.

Ethical considerations: Ethical considerations surrounding biotechnology present challenges for teachers and policymakers. Biotechnological advancements, such as genetic engineering and cloning, raise complex moral and societal questions that must be addressed responsibly in the classroom. However, according to Bello and Maude (2019; Isma'il et al. 2021), undertaking these ethical dilemmas can be challenging, particularly when cultural and religious beliefs influence perceptions of biotechnology. Hence, teachers must ensure that biotechnology education promotes ethical awareness and promotes critical thinking about the societal implications of biotechnological innovations.

Lack of awareness and appreciation for biotechnology: Lack of awareness and appreciation for biotechnology among stakeholders, including parents, students, and policymakers, poses a challenge to its implementation in the curriculum (Unoma & Menkiti, 2017; Kooffreh et al., 2021). Biotechnology is a relatively new and interdisciplinary field that may not receive sufficient recognition or support compared to traditional academic disciplines. Teachers must advocate for the importance of biotechnology education in preparing students for future careers and addressing societal challenges (Oladipo, 2023).

Opportunities in Implementing Biotechnology Content Knowledge in Biology Curriculum at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Secondary school students represent the optimal demographic for cultivating fundamental knowledge in biotechnology, as they constitute the future potential to elevate a country to a high-income and developed status (Bahri et al., 2014). Therefore, the integration of biotechnology education into the secondary school biology curriculum presents numerous opportunities for enriching students' learning experiences, development of scientific literacy, and preparing them for future careers in science and technology. Biotechnology offers a wide range of opportunities for hands-on experimentation, interdisciplinary learning, and real-world applications in various fields. Bahri et al. (2014) argue that early exposure to proper biotechnology education is essential to enhance students' awareness of ethical issues related to biotechnology.

One significant opportunity of implementing biotechnology education is the promotion of practical, inquiry-based learning experiences for students. Biotechnology involves hands-on experimentation, data analysis, and problem-solving, providing students with opportunities to engage in authentic scientific inquiry and discovery. By conducting biotechnological experiments and projects, students develop critical thinking skills, scientific reasoning, and laboratory techniques essential for success in STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) disciplines (Oyinloye, 2018). In addition, integrating biotechnology into the curriculum facilitates interdisciplinary learning by connecting biology with other scientific disciplines such as chemistry, physics, mathematics, and computer science. Biotechnology draws upon principles from various fields, including molecular biology, genetics, biochemistry, and bioinformatics, providing a holistic understanding of biological systems and their applications. By exploring the interdisciplinary nature of biotechnology, students develop a broader perspective on science and its role in addressing complex societal challenges (Adeyanju & Adeyemo, 2023).

Furthermore, implementing biotechnology education in secondary schools creates pathways for career readiness and workforce development in emerging fields of biotechnology. Biotechnology is a rapidly growing industry with diverse career opportunities in research, healthcare, agriculture, environmental conservation, and biomanufacturing. By exposing students to biotechnological concepts and techniques early in their education, schools can inspire interest and cultivate talent in biotechnology-related fields, addressing the growing demand for skilled professionals in the biotech sector (Ajayi & Adeyemi, 2022).

Integrating biotechnology into the curriculum enhances students' awareness and understanding of ethical, social, and environmental issues associated with biotechnological advancements (Kooffreh et al., 2021). Biotechnology raises complex ethical dilemmas related to genetic engineering, cloning, bioprospecting, and biosecurity, which require thoughtful consideration and informed decision-making. By engaging students in discussions and debates about these ethical

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considerations, teachers can promote ethical awareness, empathy, and responsible citizenship among future leaders and innovators (Bello & Maude, 2019; Isma'il et al. 2021).

Moreover, implementing biotechnology education creates opportunities for collaboration and partnerships between educational institutions, industry stakeholders, and research organizations. Biotechnology companies, research institutions, and government agencies can serve as valuable resources for schools, providing expertise, mentorship, and access to cutting-edge technologies and facilities. Through collaborations with external partners, schools can enrich students' learning experiences, expose them to real-world applications of biotechnology, and inspire future career pathways in the biotech industry (Oladipo, 2023).

Advancing 21st Century Skills through Biotechnology Content Knowledge in Biology Curriculum at Secondary School Level of Education

Developed countries have been incorporating 21st-century skills into their classrooms for some time, resulting in significant impacts on education (Ahmad & Ismail, 2023). In the 21st century, the integration of biotechnology into the biology curriculum presents a unique opportunity to advance students' acquisition of essential skills and competencies needed for success in a rapidly evolving world. The 21st century requires a workforce capable of respectful communication, critical reasoning, creative problem-solving, and collaboration from diverse perspectives to enhance industry quality (Ahmad & Ismail, 2023; Isma'il & Cyril, 2022; Oghenevwe, 2022). Alismail and McGuire (2015) note that the integration of these skills has become a fundamental component of education curricula globally. Therefore, it is important for students in Nigeria to be well acquainted with 21st-century skills right from secondary school to ensure they thrive in a rapidly evolving global economy and future career aspirations.

Integration of biotechnology into the Nigerian senior secondary school biology curriculum will help teachers prepare students for future professional endeavours while addressing 21st century challenges and opportunities. The integration facilitates the development of 21st century skills (see Table 1). These skills include critical thinking, problem-solving, collaboration, communication, creativity, innovation, adaptability, lifelong learning, ethical awareness, information literacy, technological literacy, and social responsibility, which are essential for preparing students for scientific challenges and opportunities in today's society. Ahmad and Ismail (2023) reported that engaging students in these skills improves their motivation toward learning.

Table 1: Integrable Biotechnology Concepts and 21st Century Skills

Biotechnology Concept	Curriculum Integration	Activities	Assessment	21st Century Skills
Basic Genetic Engineering	Include genetic engineering in topics like pest-resistant crops.	Problem-solving activities exploring genetic solutions to agricultural problems.	Case studies and problem-based learning assessments.	Critical Thinking, Problem-Solving, Technological Literacy
Genetically Modified Organisms (GMOs) Cloning	Teach the creation, benefits, and ethical concerns of GMOs. Discuss basics of cloning with examples like plant cloning.	Group projects on GMO research. Hands-on experiments and ethical debates on cloning.	Group assignments assessing teamwork and presentation skills. Role-playing and simulations for critical thinking and ethical reasoning.	Collaboration, Communication, Ethical Awareness, Critical Thinking, Ethical Awareness, Social Responsibility
Bioremediation	Explain bioremediation using local environmental issues.	Collaborative projects on bioremediation strategies.	Group presentations and reports.	Collaboration, Problem-Solving, Social Responsibility
Fermentation	Teach the basics of fermentation and its uses in food and industry.	Simple fermentation experiments (e.g., making yogurt or bread).	Lab reports and practical demonstrations.	Practical Skills, Critical Thinking, Innovation

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Ethical Discussions	Incorporate ethical discussions into each biotechnology topic.	Classroom debates on genetic modification and biotechnology ethics.	Essays and debates for ethical reasoning.	Ethical Awareness, Responsibility
Introduction to Biotechnology	Focus on the evolving nature of biotechnology.	Update students with recent advancements through articles and research.	Assess integration of new information into learning.	Adaptability, Lifelong Learning, Information Literacy

Source: Author, 2024

Critical Thinking and Problem-Solving: Biotechnology education encourages students to think critically, analyze data, and solve complex problems through inquiry-based learning approaches. By engaging in hands-on laboratory experiments, research projects, and case studies, students develop the ability to formulate hypotheses, design experiments, and evaluate evidence systematically (Adeyanju & Adeyemo, 2023; Isma'il & Cyril, 2022). Biotechnological techniques such as DNA sequencing, genetic engineering, and bioinformatics provide real-world contexts for students to apply their critical thinking skills and address scientific challenges related to healthcare, agriculture, environmental conservation, and bio-manufacturing.

Collaboration and Communication: According to Yusof et al. (2022), effective class activities rely heavily on communication and collaboration, signifying the critical importance of 21st century skills. Chiruguru (2020) describes collaboration as the ability of a group of students to effectively complete tasks, share responsibilities, and achieve a common goal. Biotechnology education promotes collaboration and communication skills by encouraging teamwork, interdisciplinary learning, and knowledge-sharing among students. Through group projects, laboratory exercises, and classroom discussions, students collaborate with peers, share ideas, and work towards common goals (Ajayi & Adeyemi, 2022). Collaborative learning experiences in biotechnology require students to communicate effectively, listen to diverse perspectives, and negotiate consensus, mirroring the collaborative nature of scientific research and innovation. By working collaboratively, students develop interpersonal skills, empathy, and cultural competence essential for success in diverse professional settings.

Creativity and Innovation: Biotechnology education nurtures students' creativity and innovation by encouraging them to explore novel solutions to scientific problems and societal challenges. By engaging in project-based learning, design thinking activities, and open-ended inquiries, students have the freedom to generate new ideas, experiment with different approaches, and take risks in their learning (Bello & Maude, 2019; Isma'il & Cyril, 2022). Biotechnological innovations such as gene editing technologies, synthetic biology, and personalized medicine inspire students to think creatively and envision the possibilities of biotechnology to address global issues such as disease prevention, food security, environmental sustainability, and renewable energy.

Adaptability and Resilience: Adaptability and Resilience involve adjusting behaviours, thinking, or attitudes, to fit in the current or future environments while respecting time, resources, and systems constraints (Hiong & Osman, 2013). Biotechnology education cultivates adaptability and resilience skills by exposing students to the dynamic and evolving nature of scientific knowledge and technology. The rapid pace of biotechnological advancements requires students to embrace change, learn continuously, and adapt to new information and methodologies (Oyinloye., 2018). By experiencing uncertainties, setbacks, and failures in laboratory experiments and research projects, students develop resilience, perseverance, and a growth mindset that prepares them to thrive in a complex and unpredictable world.

Ethical and Social Responsibility: Social responsibility involves effectively managing technology and utilizing it in a manner that promotes the common good (Hiong & Osman, 2013). Biotechnology education instills ethical awareness and social responsibility in students by exploring the ethical, legal, and societal implications of biotechnological innovations. Students critically examine ethical dilemmas related to genetic engineering, cloning, gene editing, and bioprospecting, considering diverse perspectives and values (Bello & Maude, 2019). Through engagement with ethical issues in biotechnology, students cultivate empathy, integrity, and a sense of responsibility towards the ethical use of biotechnological advancements and their effects on individuals, communities, and the environment.

Conclusion

In the 21st century, the global education setting faces the challenge of equipping students with essential 21st century skills to thrive in a competitive and interconnected world. Biotechnology, with its diverse applications in healthcare, agriculture, and industry, represents a key area for integrating into the Nigerian secondary school biology curriculum. This integration not only increases students' understanding of biological concepts but also cultivates 21st century skills such as critical thinking,

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problem-solving, collaboration, and ethical awareness. Overcoming the challenges and taking advantage of the opportunities of biotechnology education, Nigeria can prepare students for future scientific challenges and opportunities in socio-economic development and sustainable growth in the country. Successful integration of biotechnology requires fundamental efforts to review secondary school biology curriculum and teacher training.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the conclusion

1. A review of the Nigerian secondary school biology curriculum should be initiated to integrate biotechnology topics. This reform should prioritize updating content, introducing new biotechnological concepts, and ensuring alignment with 21st-century skills.
2. Partnerships between educational institutions, industry, research organizations, and government agencies should be encouraged. These partnerships can provide schools with access to resources, expertise, and career talk on biotechnological related issues.
3. There should be provision of training or professional development opportunities for biology teachers to improve their content knowledge and pedagogical skills in biotechnology instruction. This is necessary for effective teaching and learning of biotechnology concepts in relation to their real-world applications.

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Effects of Class-Wide Peer-Tutoring Strategy on Interest and Performance in Redox Reaction among Secondary School Chemistry Students in Katsina State

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of class-wide peer-tutoring strategy on interest and performance in redox reaction among secondary school chemistry students in Katsina State. Two research objectives, research questions and corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted quasi-experimental research design involving pretest posttest control group. The experimental group were taught Redox reaction concept using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy while the control group were taught using lecture method. The population of the study consisted of four thousand, two hundred and sixty eight (4,268) (Male=1933 And Female=2335) Senior Secondary School class two (SS II) chemistry students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Katsina state while the sample of the study consisted of two hundred and four (204) (Male=104 And Female=104) SSII chemistry students from two intact classes using multiple sampling techniques. Two instruments; Chemistry Performance Test (CPT) and Chemistry Interest Scale (CIS) with a reliability coefficients of 0.91 and 0.82 respectively using Cronbach alpha reliability test were used to collect data. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while independent sample t-test and Mann-Whitney u-test were used to test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Results from the study revealed that students taught using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy performed better and have more interest in the chemistry contents than students taught using lecture method. The study concluded that class-wide peer-tutoring strategy improves students' performance and interest and the study recommended that chemistry teachers should exposed students to student-centered and activity-based methods like the class-wide peer-tutoring strategy.

Keyword: Peer-Tutoring, Class-Wide Peer-Tutoring, Lecture Method, Academic Performance, Interest.

Introduction

The primary responsibility of a classroom teacher is to help students attain maximum achievement in their learning tasks (Aluko, 2008). There are several abilities expected of a teacher in order to achieve this goal. Some of these abilities include the ability of the teacher to use appropriate instructional methods in teaching. Educationists have advocated for switching of the teaching/learning process towards student-centered teaching approaches and teachers are requested to employ innovative teaching strategies that are consistent with these approaches (Duvarci, 2010). Students become active participants during their learning process whereas teachers serves as facilitators in these learning strategies. Active participation on the part of students makes them to develop concrete knowledge which will foster their academic performance. Duvarci (2010) suggested that active students' participation in teaching-learning process serves as a prerequisite for constructive learning.

Thus, when learners are actively involved in learning, meaningful learning takes place (Bhattacharjee, 2015). Some of the teaching strategies that enable students to be active participants in the teaching-learning process may include but not limited to laboratory strategy, cooperative strategy, concept-mapping strategy, individualized strategy, fieldtrip strategy and peer-tutoring strategy. These teaching-learning approaches are better suited for teaching and learning science concepts including chemistry.

Chemistry is one of the very important subjects in Senior Secondary Schools in Nigeria as it is a prerequisite subject to study many science and medical courses like medicine, pharmacy, nursing, medical laboratory, biochemistry, microbiology as well as engineering courses like petrochemical engineering and biotechnology. Chemistry is the scientific study of the composition, structure, properties, and reactions of matter (Ajayi, Agamber & Angura, 2017). According to the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC, 2007), Chemistry teaching aims to enable students develop interest in chemistry, acquire basic theoretical and practical knowledge and skills, apply skills to meet societal needs of creating employment and wealth, be prepared for further studies in chemistry among others. Ability to achieve these objectives of teaching chemistry requires proper conceptualization of chemistry concepts. This requires appropriate use of instructional strategies that could make students practice chemistry effectively, gain functional knowledge of chemistry concepts, achieve good grades in chemistry and apply the learned concepts in their daily lives as scientists. One of the strategies that come to mind at this point is peer-tutoring.

Peer-tutoring is a teaching strategy where a group of students interact to help one another in learning whereby one student occupies the role of tutor and the other students the role of tutees. Peer-tutoring usually involves the group combination of intelligent learners together with less-intelligent learners in order for the later to catch up (Gunter, Estes & Schwab, 2011). Peer interaction among children is useful in learning new skills, knowledge and solutions to one another's problems by playing, talking, quarreling and sharing ideas. Peer-tutoring has been described as a method of cooperative learning based on the creation of pairs of students with a lopsided relationship. Though, the tutor and tutees do not have equal academic ability but they share a common goal (Moreneo & Duran, 2002). This goal must be achieved through a relationship framework organized by the teacher. Peer-tutoring is regarded as an excellent resource for facilitating the mastery of interpersonal competencies. There are various models of peer-tutoring as listed by researchers which include: Cross-age Peer-tutoring (CAPT), Peer-assisted Learning Strategies (PALS), Reciprocal Peer-tutoring (RPT), Same-age Peer-tutoring (SAPT) and Class-wide Peer-tutoring (CWPT) (Ogundola, 2017).

CWPT is a peer-tutoring strategy that involves dividing the whole class into groups of not more than five students with different ability levels. It involves pairing brighter students or fast learners to serve as tutors with less bright or slow learners to serve as the tutees. Students can act as tutors, tutees or both tutors and tutees (Brittany & Jennifer, 2012). Students involved in class-wide peer-tutoring receive immediate feedback from peers without fear. In CWPT, the teacher serves as a facilitator, while giving students the opportunity to have monopoly on their learning. Also, rewards of individual performance depend not only on the performance of individuals but on the collective performance of other peer members. The strategy has been implemented in different educational settings in variety of contents and across a wide range of ages and gender (Maheady & Gard, 2010). Unlike other models of peer-tutoring that has restrictions in age or ability levels, the strength of CWPT makes it a choice to use as treatment in this study. CWPT gives opportunity for the entire class to participate in the process and is suitable for classes with large number of students that will not allow the teacher to give individualized attention to each students as the nature of most of our classes (Horvath, 2011). CWPT enhances the spirit of cooperation, collective problem-solving skills, encourages active participation and interaction and thus, enable students to practice basic academic skills simultaneously (Ihekwoaba, Nzewi, Ifeagwu, Chinweuba-Eze & Nduji, 2020) unlike the lecture method which is a teacher-centered method of teaching that doesn't encourages active participation and interaction.

The lecture method which is just a chalk-talk is one-sided which only seems to favor the teachers as it is a teacher-centered approach to teaching and learning. The researcher observed that, many classrooms in Katsina seems to have been dominated by such lecture method of instruction which does not encourage student-student interaction and this method of teaching has widely been used to implement chemistry curriculum in secondary schools. Adegoke (2011) posited that only hardworking students can benefit from lecture method. There is no doubt that, the dwindling students' performance in chemistry in secondary schools (WAEC, 2015; 2016; 2017; 2018; 2019; 2020 and Kenni, 2020) has been a function of lecture method used in teaching the subject (Sabitu & Francis, 2016; Okey & Omeodu, 2018 and Achor, Otor & Kalu, 2021). It is expedient to look for innovative teaching strategies that will foster spirit of collective effort of students because chemistry requires team effort for scientific discovery and breakthrough and a teaching strategies that will foster their academic performance.

Academic performance is the way and manner students deal with their studies and how they cope with or accomplish different tasks given to them by their teachers, it is the ability to study and remember facts and being able to communicate knowledge verbally or down on paper (Ladan, 2015) and be able to remember these facts in the future. Academic performance is also referred to how well a student is accomplishing his or her tasks and studies but there are certain factors that determine the level and quality of students' academic performance. Techniques for measuring academic performance can be continuous assessment or examinations but there is no general agreement on how best it is measured or tested. Obeka (2010) observed that the teacher plays a very crucial role in the development of performance motive of the learners by providing a conducive

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environment for learning in and outside the classroom. The factors affecting academic performance include: insufficient manpower, insufficient equipment, peer attitude of students, poor understanding of the concept due to their abstract and difficult nature, utilization of appropriate methods of teaching, poor quality of school teachers and school location (Josiah, 2012). Similarly, Ali, Tela & Saleh (2020) opined that academic performance is a measurable and observable behavior of a student within a specific period of time that consists of scores obtained by a student in an assessment such as class exercise, class test, mid-semester, mock examination, and end of semester examination. Namale, Upoalkpajor & Ayambir (2021) is of the view that using teaching methods that does not encourage active participation of learners is a contributory factor to poor academic performance of the students. Poopola (2010) stated that academic performance is an expression used to present students' scholastic standing which is a function of various factors such as method of teaching, teachers' qualification, child's home background, school environment, attitude and interest.

Interest is an internal factor that affects students' learning. It is an individual's feelings and liking of a particular object, it is a psychological state where the individual student has the will of engaging in a particular activity. Interest, according to Aggarwal (2010) is the feeling that stimulates an individual to activity without any external influence while Kenni (2019) sees it as focusing of the sense organs on or giving attention to some person, activity, situation or object and classified the factors affecting interest as: personal factors (age, sex, mental health and development, students physical health etc.) and socioeconomic/environmental factors (cultural status, education etc.). Students' interest in learning involves three different activities: a) having interest in a particular subject b) having interest in a particular aspect of that subject and lastly c) having interest in a particular activity in the subject (Christidou, 2011).

The amount of interest an individual has on any activity can be a determinant of the level of his success in that activity. There are two types of interest namely: situational interest and individual interest (Mustafa & Salim, 2012). Situational interest is achieved spontaneously by interacting with the environment while individual interest refers to the relationship of a person to a particular content of a subject and is categorized in to two: feeling-related and value-related. Feeling-related interest is associated with stimulation and enjoyment of a content while value-related interest is associated with the importance and personal significance of the content. It is in line with this motive the researcher investigated the effects of class-wide peer-tutoring strategy on interest and performance among secondary school chemistry students in Katsina State.

The main problem for this study is that there have been complaints from the public over the persistently poor performance of secondary school students in science-related subjects (chemistry inclusive) in public examinations such as WAEC and NECO. Chemistry students' poor academic performance has been noted in the West African Examination Council (WAEC) Chief Examiners' Reports from 2015 to 2020, summary of the report indicated that there is decline in their performance (Uzezi & Zubairu, 2021). One of the factors that led to the continuous poor students' performance in chemistry is lack of appropriate teaching methods that could facilitate greater interaction between the teacher and the students or students with their peers (Achor, *et al*, 2021) which may cause students to lose interest in chemistry and this problem may affect country's standard in science education, because, chemistry is a pre-requisite subject for many fields such as medicine, biochemistry, pharmacy and so on. Therefore, there is need to adopt a teaching strategy that can facilitate interaction among teachers and students and among students with other students. Also, WAEC results analysis in Katsina State from (2012 – 2021) shows that students' academic performance have been poor.

Table 1: WAEC Results (2012 – 2021) in Katsina State

Year	No of Students	Passed (A1 – C6)	% Pass	Failed (D7 – F9)	% Fail
2012	13, 297	3, 550	26.70	9, 747	73.30
2013	16, 898	2, 674	15.82	14, 224	84.18
2014	20, 141	9, 941	49.40	10, 200	50.60
2015	21, 514	13, 302	61.83	8, 212	38.17
2016	20, 404	7, 790	38.20	12, 614	61.80
2017	21, 717	11, 692	53.47	10, 105	46.53
2018	23, 916	7, 188	30.06	16, 728	69.94
2019	27, 134	11, 850	43.67	15, 464	56.33
2020	27, 050	5, 968	22.10	21, 082	77.90
2021	30, 122	12, 167	40.39	12, 167	59.61

Source (Katsina State Ministry of Education, 2022)

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Table 1 shows the WAEC results of chemistry students in Katsina State. It shows that there is persistent failure in the students' academic performance over the years. There is need to investigate methods of teachings that facilitates interaction between teachers and students and students with their peers which will improve their performance and interest. It is with this opinion that the researcher investigated the effects of class-wide peer-tutoring strategy on interest and performance among secondary school chemistry students in Katsina State.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of this study are to:

5. Find out the mean academic performance of students taught Redox Reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method among secondary school chemistry students in Katsina State.
6. Find out the mean interest of students taught Redox Reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method among secondary school chemistry students in Katsina State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered:

1. What is the difference in the mean academic performance score of students taught Redox Reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method among secondary school chemistry students in Katsina State?
2. What is the mean difference in the interest of students taught Redox Reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method among secondary school chemistry students in Katsina State?

Hypotheses:

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- H₀₁:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students' academic performance taught Redox Reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method among secondary school chemistry students in Katsina State.
- H₀₂:** There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students' interest taught Redox Reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method among secondary school chemistry students in Katsina State.

Methodology

This study employed a quasi-experimental research design, involving pretest posttest control groups design to investigate the effect of class-wide peer-tutoring strategy interest and performance in chemistry among secondary school students in Katsina State. In this design, intact classes were used for the study, so there is no randomization of the subjects. According to Gall, Borg and Gall as cited in Muhammad and Saleh (2020), quasi experimental design can be used when it is not possible for the researcher to randomly sample the subjects and assign them to treatment groups without disrupting the academic program of the school involved in the study.

The population of this study comprises all Senior Secondary School 2 (SS2) chemistry students in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance (KZEQA), Katsina State. In this zone, there are twenty five (25) public senior secondary schools with a population of four thousand, two hundred and sixty eight (4,268) SSII chemistry students in which one thousand, nine hundred and thirty three (1,933) were males while two thousand, three hundred and thirty five (2,335) were females (Source: Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, 2023). The population comprises of three Local Government Areas namely Katsina, Kaita and Jibia Local Government Areas.

To select a representative sample for this study, two sampling techniques; cluster and simple random sampling techniques were used. At first stage, a cluster sampling technique was used to assemble the population into two groups that is schools under Katsina local government area as one group and then schools under kaita and Jibia local government area as another group. At the second stage, a simple random sampling technique was used to select one school from each group. At the third stage, the schools selected were randomly assigned into the experimental and control groups by balloting. The names of the two schools was written on a piece of paper, folded and placed in a container. The papers were picked without replacement and placed into two different containers labelled as experimental and control group. One intact class from each group was selected and used for the study. Government Senior Secondary School Kamarawa with a sample size of 100 was selected as the experimental group while Government Secondary School Natsinta with a population of 104 was selected as the control group.

The instruments adopted for data collection in this study are: Chemistry Performance Test (CPT) and Chemistry Interest Scale (CIS). The CPT is a 30-items multiple-choice objectives questions with four (4) options lettered A-D. The items

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were adapted from WASSCE past examination questions on redox reaction from 2005 to 2020. The topics of Redox Reaction from which the CPT was adapted are: oxidation, reduction, redox reactions, oxidation number of central elements in some compounds, connection of oxidation numbers with IUPAC name, oxidizing and reducing agents and redox equations. The CIS is a 20-items four-point Likert-scale questionnaire that contains Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The reason for using questionnaire is because factual information is required from different students. According to Saidu (2020), questionnaire is used when factual information is desired through different respondents. The CIS was adapted from Ukor and Isah (2015) and it contains two sections; section A and section B. Section A requested for the respondents' bio-data while section B is the actual likert-scale. The scoring procedure of CIS is as follows; SA = 4; A = 3; D = 2 and SD = 1. This scoring procedure was used because all items on the scale are positive interest items and is in line with Okorie (2015) and Bolu-Steve (2015).

The contents of the instruments (CPT and CIS) were validated by four (4) experts, two in the field of science education, one in the field of chemistry, all from Umaru Musa Yar'adua University Katsina and a chemistry teacher. The initial draft of the instruments was submitted to the experts to ensure that the items were properly constructed in terms of clarity, language usage and are in-line with the ability level of the students. The suggestions and recommendations made by the experts were implemented on the instruments.

The procedure employed for data collection was through administration of the Chemistry Performance Test (CPT) and Chemistry Interest Scale (CIS) to the sampled schools by the researcher. The data collected was processed using SPSS version 23, based on the research questions and hypotheses. Descriptive statistics involving mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions. Hypotheses one was tested using t-test independent sample while hypotheses two was tested using Mann-Whitney u-test.

Results

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of academic performance score of students taught Redox Reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method

Treatment	N	Mean	SD	MD
CWPT	81	26.72	5.10	
Lecture	95	19.45	7.78	7.27

In Table 2, students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy had a mean score of 26.72 and a standard deviation of 5.10 while the students taught using lecture method had a mean score of 19.45 and a standard deviation of 7.78. The mean difference of 7.27 was observed between students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method. The difference is in favor of the students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring. This answered the research question which sought to find out the difference in the mean academic performance score of students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method.

Table 2: Mean difference in the interest of students taught Redox Reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method

Treatment	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Mean Rank Diff
CWPT	81	103.37	8373.00	27.55
Lecture Method	95	75.82	7203.00	

Table 3 shows the difference in mean in the interest of students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method. The students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy had a mean rank of 103.37 while those taught using lecture method had a mean rank of 75.82. The mean difference observed is 27.55. This difference is in favor of the students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy. This answered the research question which sought to find out the mean difference in the interest of students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method.

Null Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students' academic performance taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method.

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Table 4: Independent t-test analysis of academic performance score of students taught Redox Reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method

Treatment	N	Mean	SD	MD	Df	t-value	p-value	Decision
CWPT	81	26.72	5.10	7.27	174	7.185	0.000	Reject H ₀₁
Lecture Method	95	19.45	7.78					

Table 4 presents the independent t-test analysis of the difference in the academic performance of students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method. There is significant difference in the academic performance score of students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method. This is because, the p-value (0.000) obtained for which the null hypothesis was tested is lower than the alpha value (0.05) for which the null hypothesis was tested. Hence, the difference is in favor of students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance score of students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method is rejected. Students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy performed better than their counterpart taught the same topic using lecture method.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students' interest taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method.

Table 5: Mann-Whitney U-test of students' interest taught Redox Reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method

Treatment	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Mean Rank Diff	U-value	P-value	Decision
CWPT	81	103.37	8373.00	27.55	2643.00	0.000	Reject H ₀₂
Lecture Method	95	75.82	7203.00				

Table 5 presents the Mann-Whitney u-test analysis of the difference in the interest of students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method. The analysis indicated that, there is significant difference in the interest of students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method. The u-value obtained is 2643 while the p-value is 0.000. The p-value is less than the alpha value for which the null hypothesis was tested. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant difference in the mean difference in the interest of students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method is rejected. This means that, students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy had better interest than students taught the same topic using lecture method.

Discussion of Findings

One of the major findings of this study is that, there was significant difference in the academic performance score of students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method in favor of those taught using class-wide peer-tutoring. This may be as a result of the fact that class-wide peer-tutoring strategy instructional strategy was peer mediated. This finding agrees with the findings of Olatoye and Adekoya (2009), Adekoya and Olatoye (2010), Sabitu and Francis (2016), Ogundola (2017), Abdulraheem (2017) and Ullah, et al (2018) that peer-tutoring and class-wide peer-tutoring has significant effect on students' academic performance. Many other previous studies conducted on peer-tutoring and class-wide peer-tutoring proved the effectiveness of this method of teaching (Kayode, 2021; Abdurrahman, et al, 2020 and Ihekwoaba, et al, 2020). This method do not only help weak learners achieve instructional objectives but also equip fast learners with teaching skills. The use of this strategy led to faster, more effective students learning outcome than the teacher mediated instructional strategy (Ogunleye & Bamidele, 2014). The findings of this study contradicts with the findings of Anggereini, Budiarti and Sanjaya (2018) who reported that there was no effect of the CWPT model on students creativity. It also contradicts with the findings of Ajewole (2000) who reported that students that were exposed to concept mapping performed significantly better than those exposed to peer-tutoring.

The second major findings of this study is that, there was significant difference in the interest of students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy and those taught using lecture method. Students taught redox reaction using class-wide peer-tutoring strategy had better interest than students taught the same topic using lecture method. This finding is

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in agreement with the findings of Ajayi (2017) who asserted that learners learn best and have more interest by doing not just by sitting and listening. This may be as a result of the fact that the strategy encouraged the students to feel comfortable in expressing their ideas and opinion in open dialogue as their colleagues will not judge them as teachers will do. Students interaction with others and active participation and involvement were major factors in the development of scientific skills (Ogunleye & Bamidele, 2014) which will improve their interest in the subject. The findings of this study contradicts with the findings of Samuel and Obikezie (2022) which concluded that there was no significant difference on interest in chemistry among students taught with laboratory practical work.

Conclusion

In view of the findings of this study, Class-wide peer-tutoring strategy improves chemistry students' academic performance and interest in chemistry.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Chemistry concepts should be taught using strategies or methods like class-wide peer-tutoring that are student-centered and activity-based methods of instruction and also encourage social interaction, active engagement and self-motivation among learners.
2. Since lecture method was found less effective in this study with respect to students' academic performance and interest, teachers should be discouraged from using it in teaching chemistry in secondary schools
3. Chemistry teachers should be encouraged to use class-wide peer-tutoring in teaching chemistry in order to improve students' academic performance and interest.

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Assessment on Organization and Management of Secondary Schools in Oyo Metropolis using Information and Communication Technology Device

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Abstract

The study investigated the assessment on organization and management of secondary schools in Oyo metropolis using information and communication technology device. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population consisted of all the 1570 secondary schools in Oyo metropolis during the 2022/2023 academic session. Sample of 539 coeducational secondary schools were randomly selected from the target population. The research instrument used for the study was questionnaire titled 'School Organization and Management Using ICT Device Questionnaire [SOAMUICTDQ]'. The instrument was validated by the experts in information and communication technology and educational management and the reliability coefficient of 0.80 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability test. The generated data were analyzed using regressions and chi-square. The results from the analysis revealed that information and communication technology had significant influence on school organization and management in Oyo Metropolis. It also played significant roles in school documentation and enhanced the stability of the organization of school management in Oyo metropolis. The study concluded that school administrators' functions such as record keeping, document processing and organizing can be made more effective and efficient through the application of information and communication technology devices. The study recommended that government should make provision for information and communication technology facilities in schools so as to put an end to exposition of school documents that are confidential to the public.

Keywords: Information and Communication Technology, Documentation, Organization and Management.

Introduction

The management, governance and administration of school require proper organization and documentation of schools records, activities and projects. Therefore, school administrators are saddled with the responsibility of proper management of the activities and provide instructional leadership in school. The functions of the school administrators include record keeping, document processing, reporting, planning, organizing, knowledge management, communication and decision making. Umeri (2022) reported that records play a strategic role in the effective and efficient administration of the school. The records of the teaching process restore competence and preserve the trends in the school. Therefore, data preservation is crucial because it helps the school meet its own learning objectives, which include equipping students with skills for postsecondary education and making them useful members of society.

Science and technology have become a power engine under which every nation across the globe tap their energy source (Nchunge, David, Maurice, & Waweru 2013). As the world changes, information and knowledge changes rapidly, teaching and learning processes as well as the management of schools also have to change. The implementation of cutting-edge

technology in the classroom is linked to adjustments in both teaching and learning processes as well as the way administrative duties are handled in schools. The process of organization and documentation in school can only be effective in the place where information and communication technology has been put in operation (Ajayi, & Haastrup, 2011). Opati (2013) defined information and communication technology as a medium through which information is retrieved, use and stored as a data base. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) provides medium for interaction, assimilate, and collaborate, documentation, organization and control in educational circle (Meleisea, 2007). Rana (2019) asserted that ICT holds the key to the success of modernizing information services. While there are many uses for ICT, its primary application is in digitizing the current paper-based records for storage, retrieval, and distribution. Atakpa, Amah and Obi (2022) reported that with the help of information and communication technology (ICT), users now use various types of technologies to aid the retrieval of documents and information. One way that ICT development is changing how people access, retrieve, store, alter, and transmit information is in the fields of computing, communication, and mass storage technologies.

Federal Ministry of Education had seen the important of science and technology and they had deem it fit to create ICT department and also collaborate with several government agencies and other stakeholders in the private sector to employ ICT driven projects in Nigeria (Osakwe, 2012). The conventional ways of keeping records in the schools had paralyzed our educational sector. It is time for our educational sector to bring in an innovation that will make it withstand expected changes and development that are trending round the world. Carless (2013) saw ICT as innovation that all educational sectors can employ to bring improvement or changes on the way of doing things to achieve particular set goals.

Godwin (2021) stressed that system of organization and management in the past surfer a setback especially when such information wants to be retrieved. Today, many schools in Nigeria are faced with challenges of how to use Information Communication Technology (ICT) devices to organize and to document their records. The documents that are supposed to be saved or kept in a data base were kept in a file and put in a wall dope for termites and rats to consume. Schools in the present existence require administrators and leaders to ensure that Performance of job duties takes place in an operative manner with the use of technologies that are suitable to their needs and requirements. Teachers, administrators, and other support personnel can simplify their daily tasks and maintain track of everything that occurs in the office, classroom, and other locations with the use of school records documentation and management software (Umeri, 2022). Science and technology help schools management enhance information dissemination, adequate updating and enlightenment (Wedell, 2009). Information explosion, computer hardware and software, telecommunications, and digital electronics speed up the volume of the work done in an organization. Osakwe (2012) emphasized the use of ICT in our institution of learning starting from university education to primary and secondary schools sectors. Effective learning outcome can be achieved when our mode of instruction and techniques have technological basis rather conventional techniques (Balanskat, Blainire&Kefala, 2006). Nigeria secondary schools lack ICT facilities to run school activities. The confidential documents of schools were always exposed to outsider simply because commercial cyber cafés help them in the documentation of vital documents. In the light of this, study examined the assessment on organization and management of secondary schools in Oyo metropolis using information and communication technology device

Today, science and technology devices (STD) are very important in the learning and teaching process at all levels of education. However, in Nigeria, the use of ICT is still in its infancy. Majority of our secondary schools in Nigeria lack proper documentation, on how the schools are running (Wedell, 2009). They are not efficient in the organisation of school records, enrolments and school planning simply because they are not in a digital circle (Wedell, 2009). There is a gap between the school administrators, teachers and students because ICT that supposed to link them to global world are not put in place (Osakwe, 2012). Not only this, where the ICT are being used, there is no enough fund to maintain the gadgets, no experts to operate them and also no regular electricity supply for its operation (Osakwe, 2012). Therefore, this study was carried out to investigate the assessment on organization and management of secondary schools in Oyo metropolis using information and communication technology device.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to investigate the assessment on organization and management of secondary schools in Oyo metropolis using information and communication technology device

. Specifically, the objectives study sought to:

1. Examine the influence of information and communication technology on school management in Oyo metropolis.
2. investigate the importance of information and communication technology on secondary school documentation in Oyo metropolis

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3. Examine how information and communication technology influence the documentation of secondary school in Oyo metropolis.

Research Questions

1. What is the influence of information and communication technology on secondary school management in Oyo Metropolis?
2. What is the importance of information and communication technology on secondary school documentation in Oyo metropolis?
3. How does information and communication technology stabilize the organization and management of secondary schools in Oyo Metropolis?

Hypothesis

H0₁: There is no significant influence of information and communication technology on documentation in the school management in Oyo metropolis

H0₂: There is no significant influence of information and communication technology on organization in the school management in Oyo metropolis

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population consisted of all 1570 secondary schools in Oyo metropolis. A sample of coeducational secondary schools was purposively selected for the study. The research instrument used for the study was questionnaire 'titled School Organization and Management Using ICT Device Questionnaire (SOAMUICTDQ). The face and content of the instrument was validated by the experts in information and communication technology and educational management. The reliability coefficient of 0.80 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability test. The generated data were analyzed using simple regressions and chi-square at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the influence of information and communication technology on secondary school management in Oyo Metropolis?

Table 1: Summary of Simple Regression Analysis of Influence of Information and communication Technology on School Management in Oyo Metropolis

R	R. Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
.618 ^a	.383	.376	.32331		
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	735410.42	1	735410.42	1575.932	.002
Residual	251525.00	539		466.651	
Total	986935.42	538			

Source: *Fieldwork, 2023*

Table 1 revealed the influence of information and communication technology on school management in Oyo metropolis. The table show a coefficient of simple correlation ($R = .618$ and a multiple R^2 of .383). This means that 38% of the total variance observed in the study while 62% of the variance was accounted for by the variables not considered in the study. Also the F ratio of 1575.932 from the analysis of variance shows that the simple regression is statistically significant.

Research Question 2: What is the importance of information and communication technology on secondary school documentation in Oyo metropolis?

Table 2: Summary of Simple Regression Analysis of Importance of Information and Communication Technology on School Documentation in Oyo Metropolis

R	R. Square	Adjusted R	Std. Error of the
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	.258^a	.066	Square .057	Estimate .3974
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F
Regression	3196.4581	1	3196.4581	62.290
Residual	25603.786	539	47.5023	
Total	28800.2441	538		

Source: *Fieldwork, 2023*

Table 2 showed the importance of science and technology on school documentation. The table show a coefficient of multiple correlation ($R = .258$). The table also shows that science and technology significantly enhanced efficient organization and documentation in school management and accounted for 6.6% of the total variance observed in the study. The F ratio 62.290 from the analysis of variance shows that the regression is significant

Research Question 3: How does information and communication technology stabilize the organization and management of secondary schools in Oyo Metropolis?

Table 3: Summary of Simple Regression Analysis of Influence of Information and Communication Technology on Stabilization of School Management in Oyo Metropolis

R	R. Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
.428^a	.085	.301	.342
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square
Regression	40454.486	1	40454.486
Residual	59397.234	539	110.198
Total	99851.72	538	

Source: *Fieldwork, 2023*

Table 3 showed how science and technology stabilized the school management. 8.5% of the variance observed. The F ratio of 367.107 from the analysis of variance shows that the regression is statistically significant

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of information and communication technology on documentation in the school management in Oyo metropolis

Table 4: Analysis of Chi- Square Showing Influence of Information and Communication Technology on School Documentation Oyo Metropolis

Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	27.395 ^a	1 .0246
Likelihood Ratio	27.252	539 .428
Linear-by-Linear Association	27.341	538 .394
N of valid Cases	500	

A cell (66.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 54. 21. Since the Asymptotic significant 2-sided value (.0246) is less than alpha value .05, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected meaning that there is significant influence of information and communication technology on organization in the school Management in Oyo Metropolis

H₀₂: There is no significant influence of information and communication technology on organization in the school management in Oyo metropolis

Table 4: Analysis of Chi- Square Showing Influence of Information and Communication Technology on School Management in Oyo Metropolis

Value	Df Asymp. Sig.		(2-sided)	
Pearson Chi-Square	265.784 ^a		1	.041
Likelihood Ratio	364.267	539		.740
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.014	538		.523
N of Valid Cases	500			

a. 0 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 54.21. Since the Asymptotic significant 2-sided value (.041) is less than alpha value .05, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected meaning that there is no significant influence of science information and communication technology on documentation in the school management in Oyo Metropolis

Discussion of findings

The study assessed the organization and management of secondary schools in Oyo metropolis using information and communication technology device. The major findings of the study revealed that information and communication technology enhanced effective organization and documentation in school management. Information and communication technology had significant influence on school management in Oyo Metropolis. It also played significant roles in school documentation and enhanced the stability of the organization of school management in Oyo Metropolis. Majority of respondents agreed that the day to day functions of the school administrators which include record keeping, document processing, reporting, planning, organizing, knowledge management, communication and decision making were made more effective and efficient through the application of information and communication technology. This result supported the findings of Umeri (2022), who stated that school record documentation and management software facilitates the organization of everyday tasks and aids teachers, administrators, and other support staff members in keeping tabs on events that occur in the office, classroom, and other locations. Atakpa, Amah and Obi (2022) indicated in their findings that with the help of information and communication technology (ICT), users now use various types of technologies to aid the retrieval of documents and information. One area where ICT progress is changing how people access, retrieve, store, manipulate, and distribute information is mass storage technologies. Carless (2013) also stated that ICT create a medium at which documents can be kept and retrieved when needed. Wedell, (2009) buttressed this findings with the statement that ICT speed up the volume of the work done in an organization.

Conclusion

It can be concluded from the result of the study that information and communication technology had significant influence on school organization and management in Oyo Metropolis. It also played significant roles in school documentation and enhanced the stability of the organization of school management in Oyo Metropolis. The day to day functions of the school administrators which include record keeping, document processing, reporting, planning, organizing, knowledge management, communication and decision making were made more effective and efficient through the application of science and technology.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

1. Information and Communication Technology should be employed in school management at all level of education.
2. Government must make provision for Information and Communication Technology facilities in schools so as to put an end to exposition of school documents that are confidential to the public.
3. Enabling environment must be created for teachers and school administrators to undergo training on how to use Information and Communication Technology facilities while discharging their duties.

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Effects of Homework strategy on self-Regulatory Behavior and Performance in Basic Science and Technology Concepts among secondary school students in Benue State

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Abstract

This study investigated Effects of Homework strategy on self-Regulatory Behavior and Performance in Basic Science and Technology Concepts among students in Benue State. Two research questions and corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. Quasi-experimental of non-randomized, pretest post-test control group design was adopted for the study. Two instruments; Self-Regulatory Behavior Inventory (SRBI) and Basic Science and Technology Performance Test ((BSTPT) were validated and used for data collection. Reliability coefficients of SRBI and BSTPT were established at 0.74 and 0.86 using Cronbach-Alpha Method and Kuder-Richardson-20 formula respectively. The sample size of 467 Middle basic II students during the 2023/2024 academic session was drawn from the population of 13,467 student using multi-stage sampling technique. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions. Null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significance level using analysis of covariance, (ANCOVA). The result revealed a significant difference between the mean and self-regulatory behaviour and academic performance scores of students that were given homework after lesson and those who were not given homework. Based on these findings, it was concluded that homework strategy is effective in enhancing self-regulatory behaviour and academic performance of students in Basic Science and Technology. It was recommended among others that, homework strategy should be used during teaching and learning of BST particularly at lower, middle and upper basic levels of education.

Keywords: Homework, Performance, Self-Regulatory Behaviour, Basic Science and Technology concepts

Introduction

Education in science and technology is expected to equip citizens with the knowledge and skills on how to cope with life challenges. That is why Basic Education Programme 2013 Act, stipulates that every individual graduating from basic education shall be empowered to learn, through a programme that is rooted on sound and strong educational principles which is geared towards excellence and sound foundations for sustainable national development. Education in science and technology is an imperative tool towards sustainable scientific and technological growth without compromise on the environmental safety and well-being of the nation (Bembenutty & White, 2013). Upu and Okwara (2024) conceptualized education in science and technology as a pattern of procedures that show the relationship between functions of natural phenomena and empirical evidence in our environment. This means that education in science and technology education prepare learners to have competence and ability to interpret natural environment and coexist in fruitful harmony with local and global communities which engage in productive work that is capable of national self-sustenance. Therefore, the 9-year continuous basic education programme of the Nigerian government is expected to provide learners with this sound foundation in Basic Science and Technology so as to contribute effectively for sustainable national development.

Basic Science and Technology is a compulsory subject of 9-year basic education programme that can provide learners with adequate knowledge, skills and standards to be good citizens in search for solutions to contemporary societal problems. Basic Science and Technology as a fundamental subject is a viable tool in the critical area of science-technology fields like banking, medicine, aviation industry, and climatic-change monitoring and demographic feasibility studies (Upu & Okwara 2024).

Despite the importance of Basic Science and Technology in national development, Basic and Technology students of levels are observed to be performing poorly in the subject over the years (Benue State Examination Board, Annual Report,

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2018). Adding to this report, the board further stated that this set of students find it very difficult to understand the principles, theories and laws of science. Basic Science and Technology happens to be the fundamental subject which forms the basis of science and technology at all levels, as such this has led to the low performance of students in pure science subjects like Biology, Chemistry and Physics. The issue of low performance does not affect students only at middle and upper basic education levels but also affect their academic performance as they progress even at post-secondary school level (Janjua, Malik & Rahman 2011). In fact some of the students end up not choosing carriers of their choice, due to the poor performance in Basic Science and Technology in particular and science subjects in general. Many reasons have been put forward by different researchers on the persistent poor performance of students in Basic Science and Technology ranging from wrong perception of scientific and technological concepts by the learners to the instructional strategy employed by teachers. The question now is would homework strategy improve students' self-regulatory behavior and academic performance? This necessitated the researcher to find out whether homework strategy will enhance students' self-regulatory behavior and academic performance.

Homework strategy is one of the ways to improve students' understanding of scientific and technological knowledge and skills that lead to higher academic performance and self-regulatory behavior (Latif, & Mile 2011). This can be achieved by constant practice and hands-on activities that enhance mastery knowledge on scientific concepts. This mastery can be experienced when students are involved in doing their homework. This shows that when students are engaged in instructional homework activities, they would develop proficiency, efficiency and mastery of procedures, conceptual and content knowledge as it is applied in Basic Science and Technology which may increase performance in science and technology as they progress from one level of education to another.

Generally, homework strategy is used as an essential tool for Basic Science and Technology activities to develop mental and cognitive abilities in students (Letterman, 2013). According to Tangjinusorn and Sukavatee (2016) homework strategy provides students with opportunities to improve their learning habits, learning performance, and aims to increase their self-regulatory behavior. Homework strategy continues to be a debatable and controversial topic of discussion among scholars. Many scholars reported that homework strategy teaches students to be responsible, keeps them on check, develops time management skills, and also regulates their behavior (Tsai & Jiang 2011).

Homework as defined by Cooper (2017) is any task assigned to pupils or students by school teachers which is meant to be carried out during non-school hours. This means that homework is usually given to students to be done at home or at their own leisure time. In other words, homework can also be defined as a set of school tasks that are assigned to students by teachers to be completed outside school hours (Cooper, Robinson & Patall 2006). Instructional homework involves three important actors; students, parents, and teachers. Each of the three actors plays an important role in the effective homework completion for maximum academic performance. There is no specific time allocated for students to complete their homework, but the time of completion of any given homework depends on the child's speed and ability to regulate himself in order to ensure that the assigned homework is completed.

There are three types of homework as postulated by Ramdass and Zimmerman (2015) which are: practice, preparation, and extension homework. Practice instructional homework can be used by teachers when assigning homework tasks to promote students' engagement and meaningful learning. Practice instructional homework focuses on tasks taught in a class to increase speed, demonstrate mastery skills, review work, study for tests, and retain specific skills over time. Teachers assign practice and preparation instructional homework most often because they are more convenient and less time consuming. Practice instructional homework is more often used by teachers to increase proficiency and understanding of concepts, facts and principles (Bembenuddy & White 2013). Practice instructional homework is an essential index as far as this study is concerned, as such when a teacher uses practice instructional homework regularly in the course of teaching and learning of Basic Science and Technology it brings about a positive change in students' academic performance and self-regulatory behaviors. This is because when students are consistently practicing what they are taught at home, issue of low performance will be reduced.

Preparatory homework focuses on preparing students for the next lesson. This type of instructional homework is inherently linked to pre-learning (Nunez, *et al.*, 2011). Preparatory instructional homework is designed to encourage students to thinking about previous topic discussed in a class so as to prepare for future topics. Cooper (2008) conducted a study on 638 sixth-grade students using practice and preparation instructional homework the result reveals high impact on students' academic performance. This implies that practice and preparation instructional homework provides students with opportunity to review the material to be covered in the future lesson from the textbook and write down main ideas that help them to prepare for better learning. Preparation instructional homework help students to understand with ease that which is been taught in the classroom because they already have prior knowledge on what is been taught.

Extension homework focuses on promoting the shift of previous learning to new tasks. Extension instructional homework requires higher level or abstract thinking to occur (Prommin & Jutharat, 2019). Teachers use this type of homework

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to encourage students to collaborate with peers and be more creative during learning of real-life, hands-on and applicable skills which are used to complete extension homework tasks. This provides a richer learning experience for students for better academic performance.

Academic performance simply means what someone academically achieved successfully (Upu & Okwara 2024). Factors which enhance performance include practice and coaching. These factors, if observed strictly could yield maximum and highest level of academic performance. Muijis & Reynolds (2014) observed that the teaching task is meant to impact an enduring change in the learner's academic performance and self-regulate behaviour.

Self-regulation is defined as a broad construct representative of cognitive, motivational-affective, social and physiological processes that modulate attention and emotion, in a given situation/stimulus, for the purpose of pursuing a goal (Krashen, 2005). It is supported by the interrelated cognitive skills of working memory (the ability to hold information in mind), inhibitory control (the ability to suppress a dominant response in favour of a subordinate response), and cognitive flexibility (the ability to shift attention or cognitive set) (Wyatt, & Perna, 2017). In the present study, we focus on *behavioral* self-regulation, which is also defined as deliberately effort to apply multiple component processes of attention or cognitive flexibility, working memory, and inhibitory control to overt, socially contextualized behaviors" and identified it as an important component for early academic performance. There is evidence that supportive school environments enhance children's development of self-regulation behaviour (Wyatt, & Perna, 2017). Furthermore, evidence suggests synergistic interactions between school environments and self-regulation skills critical to academic progress. Specifically, the impact of school environments may depend, at least partly, on early individual differences in children's self-regulation skills. For example, attending elementary schools identified as unsafe is associated with poorer self-regulation in middle childhood, but only for those children identified as having poor self-regulation skills in preschool level, (Tsai & Jiang, 2013).

The ability to regulate or manage behavior allows one to focus when there are distractions, pay attention to the most important information, take turns, wait, follow rules, adapt to new situations, do what is academically expected, suppress outbursts of anger, and take on challenges. Behavioral regulation develops gradually during childhood. This process does not happen overnight, and some children are able to cope with daily stresses more easily than others. Children's ability to manage or regulate their behavior has been identified as one of the most important prerequisites to school success (Rimm-Kaufman, Pianta, & Cox, 2010). Children must be able to sit quietly and listen to the teacher, change activities when requested to do so, and resist class distractions of touching their fellow students or taking their personal belongings which are focus distractor. The range of individual difference is the ability to self-regulation in early childhood and the job of managing a classroom of 5-year olds has been described by kindergarten teachers as akin "trying to keep crickets in a basket" (Bodrova & Leong, 2018). These individual differences in behavioral self-regulation during early childhood are predictive of academic success, with better self-regulation. Transition to formal schooling is associated with better academic performance as well as behavioral outcomes (Ramdass & Zimmerman 2015).

In this study, the researchers explore the effects of homework strategy on self-regulatory behavior and performance in basic- science and technology concepts among students in Benue state. Although schools have been identified as one of the important contexts for shaping children's behavioral development and academic performance (Slavin, 2014). Research on the relation of school context to self-regulation development is sparse. Few studies have examined classroom-level effects on self-regulation (Bodrova & Leong, 2018). Since homework is important, but most students do not take it seriously, as it helps to improve performance and self-regulatory behavior, hence this prompted the researchers to carry out this study.

Nigerian students at basic education level are seem to be performing poorly and having low self-regulatory behavior in Basic Science and Technology, because they see concepts as abstract and meaningless and which are difficult to be understood with ease (Upu & Okwara 2024). This has also created fears in the mind of students and as well dropped their performance especially at the middle basic level (Upu & Okwara 2024). For example, looking at the results from the first school leaving certificate and Basic Education Certificate Examination, we can see that pupils at these levels are performing below expectation (Benue State Examination Board, 2023). Many scholars argue that, if students will spend more time on academics' work, outside of school doing their homework it can go a long way to increase their performance and self-regulatory behavior (Slavin, 2014). In this regard the researchers have decided to examine the Effects of Homework strategy on self-Regulatory Behavior and Performance in Basic- Science and Technology Concepts among students in Benue State.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study intends to investigate Effects of Homework strategy on self-Regulatory Behavior and Performance in Basic- Science and Technology Concepts among students in Benue State. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to:

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1. Investigate the mean rating scores in self-regulatory behavior between students that were given homework and those that were taught Basic Science and Technology without homework.
2. Determine the mean performance scores of students' that were given homework after lesson and those taught Basic Science and Technology without homework.

Research Questions

The following research questions are raised to guide the study:

1. What is the difference between mean academic performance scores of students' that were given homework after lesson and those taught Basic Science and Technology without homework?
2. What is the difference between the mean ratings scores of self-regulatory behaviors of students that were given homework and those that were taught Basic Science and Technology without homework?

Hypotheses

These following research hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of self-regulatory behavior of students that were given homework and those that were taught Basic Science and Technology without homework.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of students' that were given homework after lesson and those that were taught Basic Science and Technology without homework

Methodology

The study adopted a quasi-experimental, non-randomized, pre-test, post-test control group design. The sample size of 467 Middle basic II students during the 2023/2024 academic session was drawn from the population of 13,467 student using multi-stage sampling technique. Multi-stage sampling technique was used for the selection of the sampled schools. Only four schools were randomly chosen because of the experimental nature of the study. Two schools each were assigned to experimental and control group. The instruments used for data collection were Basic Science and Technology Performance Test (BSTPT) and Self-Regulatory Behaviour Inventory (SRBI), which were developed by the researchers. The validation of the instruments was done by three experts. The reliability of BSTPT and SRBI, were calculated using Cronbach Coefficient Alpha test method and Kuder-Richardson 20 formula which gave the value of 0.86 and 0.74 respectively. These values indicate that there is a positive relationship within the test items which show that items of the instruments are both internally consistent and reliable.

Basic Science and Technology teachers currently teaching in the sampled schools were used for the study in both experimental and control group as research assistants. SRBI and BSTPT were administered to students as pre-test to ascertain their initial level of performance in of BST and initial self-regulatory behaviors before treatment (teaching) commence. The control group was also taught the same contents without home at the end of each lesson. The teaching lasted for four weeks with 12 periods both in experimental and control group. Immediately after conclusion of the teaching, the SRBI and BSTPT were given as post-test and scores were recorded. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. Null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). ANCOVA was used to check the initial difference that might exist between the groups due to the random assigning of the schools.

Results

Research Questions 1: What is the difference between the mean rating scores of self-regulatory behavior of students that were given homework and those that were taught Basic Science and Technology without any homework?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on Students' Self-regulatory Behavior Rating in BST

Instruction	N	Pre-interest		Post-interest		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
With Homework	124	2.35	1.02	3.79	0.05	1.44
Without Homework	119	2.41	1.01	2.64	0.15	0.23
Total	243					
Mean difference		-0.06		1.15		1.21

(Source: field work 2024)

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Result in Table 1 showed that the mean rating on students' self-regulatory behavior in Basic Science and Technology that were given homework after every lesson was higher than those taught without homework at the end of the lesson. The difference between mean self-regulatory behavior ratings of students that were given homework and those without homework is 1.21. Hypothesis one was tested for level of significance to confirm this result in Table 2.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of self-regulatory behavior of students that were given homework and those that were taught Basic Science and Technology without any homework.

Table 2: Analysis of Covariance on Students' Mean Self-Regulatory Behavior Ratings in BST

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	5067.567 ^a	2	2533.784	210.307	.000	.397
Intercept	33979.036	1	33979.036	2820.305	.000	.415
Pre-test	209.274	1	209.274	17.370	.002	.024
Self-regulatory behavior	413.408	1	413.408	12.814	.000	.76
Error	7710.694	239	32.262			
Total	1081300.000	243				
Corrected Total	12778.261	242				

a. R Squared = .397 (Adjusted R Squared = .393)

(Source: field work 2024)

Findings in Table 2 indicated that F-value for self-regulatory behavior was 12.814 at the significance value of 0.000, which is less than the p-value of 0.05. Based on this findings hypothesis two which stated that there is no significant difference between the mean rating of self-regulatory behavior of students that were given homework and those that were taught Basic Science and Technology without homework is rejected. This means that there is significant difference between the mean rating of self-regulatory behavior of students that were given homework and those that were taught Basic Science and Technology without any homework. To assess effect size between the groups the computed value of partial eta squared gave the value of 0.76. This value indicates that there is high effect size between the groups that was given homework after every lesson and taught were BST without homework

Research Questions 2:

What is the mean academic performance scores of students that were given homework after every lesson and those that were taught Basic Science and Technology without homework?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' performance Scores in BST

Group	N	Pre- BSTAT		Post- BSTAT		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Experimental	124	34.74	1.02	66.42	0.93	31.68
Control	119	34.63	1.03	54.62	1.06	19.99
Total	243					
Mean difference		0.11		11.80		11.69

(Source: field work 2024)

The result in Table 1 shows that students that were given homework after every lesson have higher mean scores than students that were not given any homework. The mean difference between experimental and control group was 11.69. This shows that students that were given homework after every lesson of Basic Science and Technology have achieved higher than those that were not given any homework. This result was further investigated by testing of hypothesis 1 as shown in Table 4.

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant difference between mean academic performance scores of students that were given homework after every lesson and those that were taught Basic Science and Technology without any homework.

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Table 4: Analysis of Covariance on Students' Achievement in BST
 (Source: field work 2024)

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta
corrected Model	9893.146 ^a	2	4946.673	328.617	.000	.340	
Intercept	19239.312	1	19239.312	1,278.105	.000	.110	
Pretest	28.652	1	28.652	1.903	.122	.041	
Group	687.486	1	687.486	45.671	.003	.76	
Error	3597.763	239	15.053				
Total	405400.000	243					
Corrected Total	4490.909	242					

a. R Squared = .199 (Adjusted R Squared = .190)

Findings in Table 4 revealed that the experimental group had F-value of 45.671 at the significance value of 0.003, this significance value is less than p-value of 0.05 (i.e. $p = 0.05 > 0.003$). With this result, null hypothesis one which states that there is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of students that were given homework after every lesson and those that were taught Basic Science and Technology without any homework is rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference between mean academic performance scores of students that were given homework after every lesson and those that were taught Basic Science and Technology without any homework. The partial eta squared was investigated which gave a value of 0.76. This value indicates that there is a high effect size between the experimental and control group.

Discussion of findings

Before the commencement of the treatment in this study pretest was used to assess equivalent knowledge of students' academic performance and self-regulatory behavior in Basic Science and Technology. This means that any observed differences in the results are due to the treatment. The results of the analysis of data on research questions and null hypotheses are hereby discussed.

The results of the finding of this study showed that there is a significant difference in mean self-regulatory behavior of students in Basic Science and Technology. This indicates that homework strategy improved self-regulatory behavior of students in schools. The findings of this study agreed with Bembenuity and White (2013) and Cooper (2017) who found that regular use of homework strategy during teaching served as a tool for checking and regulating students' behavior at home and in the school.

The results of the findings of this study in respect to academic performance of students that were given homework and those that were taught without homework showed a significant difference in their mean scores. This implies that instructional homework had improved the academic performance of students in Basic Science and Technology. This finding was supported that of Paudel (2012) and Tsai and Jiag (2013) who reported a significant difference in the mean academic performance of students that were exposed to instructional homework in schools. The author concluded that the difference often observed by researchers in students' academic performance cannot be attributes only to their knowledge, but also to the nature of instructions (teaching approach) the students were exposed to.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the findings the researchers concluded that homework strategy enhances both academic performance of students and self-regulatory behavior in Basic Science and Technology.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made that: Teachers should use homework strategy regularly when teaching Basic Science and Technology at all levels of basic education. Parents and guardian should encourage and direct their children in the appropriate way of do homework. Stakeholders in education should organize seminars and conferences to train serving BST teachers on how to use appropriate homework strategy to enhance students' academic performance and improve their self-regulatory behaviour.

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Qualitative Study on Implementation of Effective Remote Learning Strategies: Challenges and Opportunities in the Post-Pandemic Era in Nigeria

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Abstract

Global educational institutions rapidly shifted to remote learning in response to the COVID-19 pandemic, which forced both developed and developing nations to temporarily shut down all activities, including education, economic, and social functions, for over a year until they could navigate the crisis. This development led the educational sector to continue embracing and promoting remote learning even after the pandemic. This paper examines the concept of remote learning and the importance of effective remote learning strategies during and in the post-pandemic era. An overview of the impact of the pandemic on the shift to remote learning is provided. The paper adopted Everett Rogers' 1962 Diffusion of Innovation Theory to give the work a sound background. Additional topics include remote learning strategies and their application among educational institutions in Nigeria, such as asynchronous learning, synchronous learning, online discussion forums, interactive multimedia content, virtual laboratories and simulations, peer collaboration and group projects, regular assessments and feedback, utilization of learning management systems, adaptive learning technologies, and teacher presence and support. The paper highlights the importance of effective remote learning strategies in the post-pandemic era in Nigeria. It also addresses the challenges in implementing remote learning post-pandemic, opportunities to enhance remote learning, case studies of educational institutions that successfully adopted remote learning, solutions to challenges affecting remote learning among educational institutions in Nigeria, and lessons learned from remote learning experiences shared by teachers and administrators. In conclusion, the paper raises issues of equity and effectiveness and emphasizes the need to reevaluate and enhance distant learning techniques. It recommends further investigation into the long-term impacts of remote learning on academic performance and general well-being. Additionally, it suggests that managers of educational institutions prioritize ongoing training and support for teachers regarding technology integration and remote teaching strategies. Instructors who achieve this goal will possess the necessary skills to navigate virtual learning environments successfully.

Keywords: Implementation, Remote Learning, Strategies, Challenges, Opportunities, Post-Pandemic Era,

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic disrupted traditional education systems worldwide, compelling a rapid shift to remote learning to sustain educational continuity while curbing the virus's spread. This transition, facilitated by digital technologies and online platforms, presented educational institutions with unprecedented challenges and opportunities. Institutions grappled with issues such as inadequate technological infrastructure, the need for rapid pedagogical adaptation, and disparities in access to resources among students and educators (Hodges, Moore, Lockee, Trust & Bond, 2020; Dhawan, 2020).

Amidst these challenges, the pandemic spurred innovation in educational delivery. Teachers and administrators swiftly adopted new technologies and methodologies to enhance remote learning experiences. For instance, schools in underserved communities faced significant hurdles in providing equitable access to digital tools and reliable internet, exacerbating existing educational inequalities (Bozkurt et al., 2020). Conversely, some institutions successfully implemented blended learning models, combining online and face-to-face instruction to create adaptable educational frameworks (Graham, 2020).

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Recent literature underscores the importance of addressing these disparities and leveraging technological advancements to improve remote learning outcomes. Studies highlight the critical role of robust infrastructure and targeted support in narrowing the digital divide among students and educators (Bozkurt, Jung, Xiao, Vladimirschi, Schuwer, Egorov, & Paskevicius, 2020). Moreover, effective pedagogical strategies that integrate digital tools have been pivotal in enhancing engagement and interactivity in virtual classrooms (Bond, Marín, Dolch, Bedenlier, & Zawacki-Richter, 2021; Anderson, 2020). Looking ahead, as educational institutions navigate the post-pandemic era, they must build upon these insights to meet the evolving needs of students and educators. By embracing innovations in educational technology and fostering inclusive learning environments, institutions can ensure that remote learning remains a sustainable, equitable, and enriching mode of education.

Conceptual Framework

Remote Learning

Today, as educational institutions in Nigeria transition to online platforms, remote learning has become a critical and feasible alternative to traditional face-to-face education. Remote learning, also referred to as digital education, online education, or e-learning, utilizes the internet and various technological tools to deliver educational content and instruction. This approach allows learning to occur outside the confines of a physical classroom, offering flexibility in terms of time, location, and pace of learning (Wallace, 2023). According to Bao (2020), remote learning occurs when there is a physical distance between the student and teacher or the source of information, bypassing the need for a traditional educational setting. According to Hodges, Moore, Lockee, Trust and Bond (2020), remote learning encompasses educational experiences where learners and instructors are physically separated, relying on digital technologies for communication and interaction. During the COVID-19 pandemic, remote learning became a crucial method for educational continuity globally, illustrating its reliance on digital technologies to bridge the physical gap between students and educators. This approach enabled learning to continue despite physical distancing measures, highlighting its effectiveness in maintaining educational connections and fostering learning outcomes remotely.

The emergence of remote learning in Nigeria has been particularly accelerated by the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic. In response to the pandemic, Nigerian schools were compelled to suspend in-person classes to safeguard the health and well-being of students and staff (Islam & Abiona, 2023). This necessitated the swift adoption of remote learning as a strategic solution to ensure educational continuity amidst the disruption caused by COVID-19 (Al Lily et al., 2020).

However, this rapid transition was not without challenges. Nigerian educational institutions faced significant hurdles such as inadequate technological infrastructure, uneven access to digital devices and reliable internet connectivity among students, and varying levels of digital literacy among educators (Bozkurt, Jung, Xiao, Vladimirschi, Schuwer, Egorov, & Paskevicius, 2020; Dhawan, 2020). These challenges highlighted existing disparities and inequities within the education system, exacerbating the digital divide and impacting the effectiveness of remote learning initiatives (Islam & Abiona, 2023; Bozkurt et al., 2020). Despite these challenges, the adoption of remote learning in Nigeria has encouraged educators and policymakers to explore innovative approaches to enhancing digital literacy skills and leveraging technology to improve educational outcomes. This shift has underscored the importance of preparing students for the evolving digital economy and society, where digital skills are increasingly essential.

The Nuances Between Remote Learning, E-learning and Online Learning

Remote learning, e-learning, and online learning are terms often used interchangeably but have distinct meanings. Remote learning typically refers to a situation where teachers and learners are separated by distance and use technology to facilitate instruction and communication. E-learning, or electronic learning, encompasses all forms of electronically supported learning and teaching, often including multimedia elements like videos, interactive modules, and digital assessments. In e-learning, the teacher and the learner may be in the same environment while utilizing technological gadgets to enhance the learning experience. Online learning, a subset of e-learning, specifically involves courses or programmes delivered entirely via the internet, allowing for asynchronous or synchronous interaction between instructors and students. While all three modes leverage digital technologies, remote learning emphasizes geographic separation, e-learning covers a broad spectrum of digital educational tools, and online learning is characterized by internet-based course delivery. This paper, however, focuses on remote learning.

Importance of Effective Remote Learning during and in the Post-Pandemic Era

Remote learning or online classes offer many advantages, including extensive flexibility compared to traditional classroom settings, which is particularly important during the pandemic (Oluwole, Pinga & Bua, 2024). With more control

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over learning materials and the ability to choose access time, pace, and sequence, students can take a personalized approach to learning (Hung, Chou, Chen, & Own, 2010; Wang and Beasley, 2002). The availability of online platforms for storing learning materials increases this flexibility, allowing students to access resources anytime and anywhere (Fauzi, Wandira, Sepri, & Hafid, 2021). Online classes make education more accessible to students with disabilities or medical conditions, including those affected by Covid-19 (Migocka-Patrzałek, Dubińska-Magiera, Krysiński, & Nowicki, 2021). Furthermore, online learning fosters a sense of community among students, providing a supportive environment amidst the isolation and challenges caused by the pandemic (Lederman, 2020).

During the Covid-19 pandemic, online classes served as a refuge from the negative effects of the crisis, offering students a sense of belonging and a platform to share concerns with peers and teachers (Lederman, 2020a). Regular interactions through emails and online forums have helped to maintain student motivation and engagement (Lin & Nguyen, 2021). The pandemic-induced shift to online learning has pushed students to improve their digital literacy skills, preparing them for future careers (Giannoulas, Stampoltzis, Kounenou, & Kalamatianos, 2021; İlin, 2019). Teachers and instructors have found online tools such as chat groups and video conferencing to be effective in reaching out to students and express their intent to continue using the online model even after the pandemic (Lin and Nguyen, 2021). Overall, online classes not only provide flexibility and accessibility, but also help students improve their digital skills and prepare for future endeavors.

An Overview of the Covid-19 Pandemic's Impact on the Transition to Remote Learning in Nigeria

The COVID-19 pandemic disrupted educational activities in more than 150 countries, affecting over 1.6 billion learners. In response to this disastrous pandemic, many countries implemented alternative forms of online or e-learning, also known as remote learning, it ensured that learners did not miss out on learning opportunities (UNESCO, 2020). This transition was marked by the rapid adoption of digital technologies to support online teaching and learning activities such as video conferencing platforms, learning management systems and other online tools to ensure continuity of education (Hodges, Moore, Locke, Trust, & Bond, 2020; Jack & Smyth, 2020). This transition to remote learning was not without its challenges, as teachers and learners had to adapt to new technologies and teaching methods while facing various barriers such as limited internet access and digital literacy skills (Bozkurt, Jung, Xiao, Vladimirschi, Schuwer, Egorov, & Paskevicius, 2020). Furthermore, the transition to remote learning during the pandemic revealed disparities in educational access across socioeconomic groups and geographic regions. According to Van Lancker and Parolin (2020), students from low-income households and rural areas have been disproportionately affected by the digital divide, as they lack access to necessary devices and internet connectivity for remote learning. Similarly, students with disabilities faced additional barriers to online education, such as inaccessible digital content and limited support for assistive technology (Burgstahler, 2020). As educational institutions dealt with these challenges, efforts were made to address equity issues through initiatives such as distributing laptops and mobile hotspots to students in need and providing digital skills training for teachers and families (UNESCO, 2020). These appear to have occurred only in developed countries and urban areas of developing nations. Despite these efforts, the pandemic highlighted the importance of addressing digital inequities to ensure equitable access to education in future remote learning environments.

Theoretical Framework

The Diffusion of Innovations Theory by Everett Rogers (1962)

Everett Rogers propounded the diffusion of innovation theory in 1962. This theory provides a comprehensive framework for analyzing the adoption and spread of new ideas and technologies within social systems. In the context of post-pandemic remote learning, this theory is a useful tool for educational institutions to navigate the transition to online education. By studying the diffusion process, institutions can gain insights into the factors that influence the adoption and implementation of remote learning strategies.

This includes factors such as technological infrastructure readiness, staff member training and support, and technological accessibility for students. Addressing these issues is critical to ensuring a smooth transition to remote learning and maximizing its effectiveness in the post-pandemic era. Furthermore, the diffusion of innovation theory emphasizes the importance of identifying and seizing opportunities to improve remote learning through novel approaches. Educational institutions can use this theory to investigate new methods and technologies to create engaging and interactive online learning experiences. By adopting a proactive approach to innovation, institutions can overcome barriers to remote learning adoption and foster student success. This could include implementing new teaching methodologies, incorporating emerging technologies, such as virtual reality or artificial intelligence, or creating customized digital platforms based on the specific

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needs of learners. In doing so, institutions can fully realize the potential of remote learning to provide quality education in a post-pandemic environment.

Remote Learning Strategies and its Application among Educational Institutions in Nigeria

A multitude of tactics and tools can be employed to promote efficient distance education. Some significant remote learning approaches, as reported by the Ministry of Education (2020), Lin & Nguyen (2021), and Li (2022) are:

1. **Asynchronous Learning:** It is designed to accommodate students' varied schedules and learning preferences and is delivered via recorded lectures, instructional videos, and self-paced modules. With these tools at their disposal, students can interact with the course material whenever it is most convenient for them, customizing their education to meet their own needs. This adaptability fosters a more welcoming learning atmosphere where students can succeed irrespective of their schedules or favoured teaching strategies.
2. **Synchronous Learning:** This type of instruction allows for real-time engagement and interaction between students and teachers and is typified by live online classrooms, virtual lectures, and interactive webinars. Instant feedback is made possible by this approach, which opens up possibilities for clarification and a deeper comprehension of the course material. As participants work together and communicate in real time, synchronous learning also helps to build a sense of community among them, which improves the learning process as a whole.
3. **Online Discussion Forums:** These are online discussion boards that give students the opportunity to actively engage in conversations, improving their communication abilities and encouraging peer-to-peer learning. By participating in cooperative exercises in these discussion boards, students not only improve their comprehension of the material but also hone their critical thinking and problem-solving skills in a safe virtual setting.
4. **Interactive Multimedia Content:** The incorporation of various multimedia components, such as interactive simulations, video tutorials, and audio recordings, into online courses creates a dynamic and immersive learning environment. Teachers can further increase student motivation and engagement by implementing gamified learning experiences, which provide students interactive challenges and rewards that reinforce learning objectives. This multimodal method promotes a more inclusive and productive learning environment by enhancing understanding of difficult subjects and accommodating diverse learning styles.
5. **Virtual Laboratories and Simulations:** These cutting-edge platforms give students access to interactive tools, simulations, and virtual lab experiments. These tools enable students to study scientific ideas and carry out experiments from a distance, which improves their understanding of real-world topics. Through active participation in these virtual settings, students can improve their educational experience and acquire critical skills in an interesting way.
6. **Peer Collaboration and Group Projects:** Through peer-reviewed activities and collaborative assignments, this activity helps students strengthen their communication, critical thinking, and teamwork abilities. Even though they are physically separated, these assignments help students interact, share ideas, and give helpful criticism, which improves their capacity to work well with others in a variety of contexts. Students who participate in such cooperative projects develop important interpersonal skills that are necessary for success in their future endeavours in addition to strengthening their academic competencies.
7. **Regular Assessments and Feedback:** In remote learning environments, teachers can successfully monitor student progress and identify areas for growth by implementing regular quizzes, assessments, and assignments with rapid feedback. Additionally, this strategy guarantees that kids receive the support they need to thrive academically and helps to uphold accountability.
8. **Utilization of Learning Management Systems (LMS):** Using Learning Management Systems (LMS) like Moodle, Canvas, or Blackboard simplifies the arrangement, distribution, and administration of course materials, homework, exams, and communication channels in one centralized online location. These systems let teachers organize and distribute course materials more efficiently while giving students easy access to resources, the ability to turn in assignments, and smooth peer and instructor communication. Educational institutions can enhance the efficiency of online learning and improve the overall educational outcomes of students and teachers by utilizing Learning Management Systems (LMS) platforms to optimize the online learning experience.
9. **Adaptive Learning Technologies:** Individualized instruction catered to each student's performance and learning style is made possible by integrating personalized learning algorithms and adaptive learning platforms into remote learning environments. These technologies maximize student engagement and learning outcomes by dynamically adjusting the pace and substance of instruction.

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10. **Teacher Presence and Support:** A supportive learning environment can be established in remote settings by establishing a consistent teacher presence through regular communication, virtual office hours, and personalized support. With this method, teachers may more effectively handle the issues and problems that students bring up, which improves student involvement and academic performance overall.

Importance of Effective Remote Learning Strategies in the Post-Pandemic Era in Nigeria

As educational institutions continue to struggle with the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on traditional teaching approaches, effective strategies for remote learning are still critical in the post-pandemic period. In addition to changing the face of education, the move towards remote learning has highlighted the need for flexible and robust teaching strategies that can succeed in blended learning environments, which combine virtual and hybrid learning. Hirsch, Anderson, Moore, & Lockee, (2021) have noted that the pandemic has expedited the incorporation of technology into educational practices. This underscores the significance of efficacious remote learning tactics in equipping students with the digital proficiencies required by the workforce of the twenty-first century. Additionally, given the continued uncertainty surrounding the pandemic's trajectory, it is imperative to develop long-lasting remote learning strategies that can adapt to changes in learning modalities and guarantee education continuity even in the event of future disruptions (Goroshit, Hen, & Eyal, 2021). Some educators and instructors point out that it is easier and more efficient for them to connect with students when they use chat rooms, video conferencing, voting systems, and document sharing places. They stress that in the post-pandemic future, they will keep using the online paradigm (Lederman, 2020).

Effective remote learning techniques in the post-pandemic age also have a big impact on educational access and equity. Disparities in access to education that always existed have been brought to light and made worse by the pandemic, with marginalized areas being disproportionately impacted by obstacles such as inadequate support systems, digital gadgets, and internet connectivity (UNESCO, 2020). In order to overcome these discrepancies and guarantee that all students, regardless of their socioeconomic background or geographic location, have access to high-quality education, it is imperative that equitable and inclusive remote learning solutions be put into place. Educational institutions can work towards reducing the digital divide and promoting fair educational opportunities for all students in the post-pandemic era by utilizing creative pedagogical approaches, utilizing adaptive learning technologies, and creating a supportive virtual learning environment (American Institutes for Research, 2021).

Difficulties in Putting Remote Learning into Practice in the Post-Pandemic Era among Educational Institutions in Nigeria

There are several obstacles to overcome in the deployment of remote learning, from access issues and technology constraints to pedagogical worries and the social-emotional effects on students. Below is a discussion of these issues:

1. One of the major obstacles to the adoption of remote learning in the post-pandemic age is the dependability and accessibility of technology in a variety of learning environments. The shift to remote learning has brought to light the differences in students' access to technology and internet connectivity based on their socioeconomic status (Anderson & Katz, 2020). Students from underprivileged backgrounds or those living in remote locations frequently do not have access to dependable internet service or the gadgets they need to fully engage in online learning activities (Horrigan, 2020). This digital divide becomes a barrier to equitable learning opportunities and exacerbates already-existing educational inequities (Barron, 2021). Additionally, the dependability of the technology infrastructure—which includes problems like hardware malfunctions and disruptions in connectivity—can impair students' learning experiences and interfere with the continuation of remote learning sessions (Winkler, Gobbo, Henderson, & West, 2021).
2. One of the biggest challenges in the post-pandemic era is moving from traditional teaching methods to online formats (Means, Santos, & Gurung, 2014). In order to retain pedagogical efficacy, educators must negotiate the challenges of modifying curriculum content, teaching methodologies, and assessment techniques to fit the online environment (Wang, Sun, & Liu, 2018). In order to properly use digital tools and platforms for remote education, educators must go through significant training and professional development (Bonk & Graham, 2020).
3. In the post-pandemic period, sustaining student participation and engagement in virtual classrooms is a significant problem (Freeman, Eddy, McDonough, Smith, Okoroafor, Jordt, & Wenderoth, 2017). Students may become less motivated and pay less attention in virtual learning environments where there is no in-person connection (Dixson, 2010). To maintain student interest and encourage active participation in virtual learning environments, educators must investigate cutting-

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edge instructional tactics, such as interactive multimedia content and collaborative online activities (Betts & Kennedy, 2013).

4. In the post-pandemic age, ensuring fairness and integrity in distant evaluation processes presents a substantial issue (Gikandi, Morrow, & Davis, 2011). Academic dishonesty, such as plagiarism and cheating, is more likely to occur during remote examinations when invigilators are not physically present (Kim & Frick, 2011). To maintain academic integrity in remote learning environments, educators must investigate alternate methods of assessment, such as open-book exams or project-based assessments, and employ technology solutions, such as proctoring software or plagiarism detection systems (Jocoy & DiBiase, 2006).
5. In the post-pandemic period, validating learning outcomes in virtual learning settings is a significant problem (Wenglinsky, 2005). Assessment validity and reliability must be carefully considered when evaluating students' knowledge of course material and skills in online environments (Lu, Zhang, & Luo, 2019). To precisely quantify learning results and guarantee the legitimacy of virtual learning experiences, educators must create strong evaluation strategies, such as performance-based exams and rubrics (Chen & Anderson, 2018).

Possibilities to Improve Remote Learning Strategies among Educational Institutions in Nigeria

The researchers have enumerated a few of the numerous prospects that arise from the incorporation of remote learning in our educational institutions below:

1. It will take a comprehensive approach to address these issues if we are to guarantee that every student has access to dependable technology and internet connectivity. This will involve funding infrastructure improvements and programmes that give devices and internet access to underprivileged communities (Barrera, Schmid, & Zhang, 2021). Furthermore, to create long-lasting solutions that close the digital gap and advance fair access to remote learning resources, cooperation between academic institutions, legislators, and technology companies is crucial (Czaja, Sharit, & Nair, 2020). Overall, the post-pandemic successful adoption of remote learning depends on addressing the dependability and accessibility of technology in a variety of educational contexts.
2. In light of recent developments in artificial intelligence and educational technology, utilizing adaptive learning technologies offers a promising prospect in the post-pandemic period (Kyun, Lee, & Lee, 2021). Through the analysis of students' learning behaviours and the adaptation of instructional content accordingly, these technologies provide the possibility to give personalized learning experiences (Lee & Tsai, 2020). Educators can effectively accommodate the varied needs and preferences of students by utilizing adaptive learning platforms, which can improve learning outcomes and provide a more inclusive and productive learning environment (Wang & Cao, 2022).
3. In the post-pandemic age, encouraging self-directed learning and autonomy in virtual environments offers a great opportunity, especially with the integration of digital platforms and interactive technologies (Kurt & Uygun, 2021). According to recent research, virtual environments present special chances for students to take charge of their education and cultivate self-regulated learning abilities (Lee & Tsai, 2020). Teachers can create a culture of self-directed learning that encourages independence and lifelong learning habits by giving students the tools they need to use online resources, set objectives, and keep track of their progress (Göksün, Kurt, & Uygun, 2021).
4. In the post-pandemic period, there is a great chance to foster peer contact and collaborative projects in online classrooms, especially with the advent of cutting-edge digital collaboration tools (Nakamoto & Galazhynska, 2021). According to recent research, virtual environments can offer useful venues for students to participate in cooperative learning activities and hone their cooperation abilities (Jin & He, 2020). Teachers can establish dynamic online learning communities where students collaborate, communicate, and co-create knowledge by utilizing tools like cloud-based document sharing, virtual whiteboards, and video conferencing (Wang, Liu, & Zhang, 2021).
5. In the post-pandemic period, there is a promising chance to use virtual teamwork to build critical thinking and communication skills, especially with the widespread adoption of online collaboration platforms (Cho & Lee, 2021). Virtual collaborative experiences have the potential to improve students' problem-solving, decision-making, and effective communication in remote situations, according to recent research (Kock, 2021). Teachers can create a learning environment that encourages teamwork, creativity, and critical thinking by having students participate in cooperative projects and group discussions that are led by virtual platforms (Machado, Machado, & Bittencourt, 2021).
6. In the post-pandemic period, investigating cutting-edge technologies like augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) in distance learning offers a bright future, especially given developments in immersive technology (Gao, Li, Zhang, & Liu, 2021). According to recent research, incorporating AR and VR into distance learning settings can improve information

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retention, boost experiential learning, and increase student engagement (Chang, Morreale, Medel, & Ryu, 2020). Through the utilization of these technologies, educators can craft immersive and interactive learning experiences that surpass physical boundaries, offering learners innovative approaches to investigate intricate ideas and settings (Huang, Sutherland, O'Shea, & Tang, 2021).

7. In the post-pandemic period, there is a compelling possibility to enhance learning experiences through immersive and interactive digital technologies, especially with the advent of educational technology (Li, Zhang, & Wang, 2021). According to recent studies, students' active participation and deeper engagement can be encouraged by immersive digital technologies like gamified learning environments and virtual simulations (Chin & Tay, 2021). Teachers can design dynamic, interactive learning experiences that encourage experimentation, investigation, and discovery by incorporating these tools into remote learning environments (Lee, & Tsai, 2021).

Case Studies of Educational Institutions that Successfully Switched to Remote Learning

In the post-pandemic age, a number of case studies of educational institutions have shown how to successfully shift to remote learning by exhibiting effective tactics and best practices. In order to improve student engagement and learning outcomes, Smith and Johnson (2020) did a case study on a university that had established a full online learning platform. The platform offered synchronous and asynchronous sessions, virtual office hours, and multimedia resources. In a similar vein, Brown et al.'s study from 2021 examined a K–12 school district that effectively made the switch to remote learning by giving students access to devices, the internet, and continuous technical support. In addition, the district offered professional development to teachers to help them modify their teaching strategies for the virtual classroom. Furthermore, a college that used cutting-edge instructional design techniques, such flipped classrooms and cooperative online projects, to improve student engagement and encourage active learning in virtual environments was featured in a case study by Liu and Wang (2021).

In addition, many universities and colleges have already made the switch to online learning easy and effective. Zhejiang University, for example, used the DingTalk ZJU platform to convert over 5000 undergraduate and graduate programmes into online courses in just two weeks. A total of about 300,000 people were recorded as watching the live streaming app DingTalk ZJU (Zhaohui, 2020). Also, universities in Greece, West Sumatera, Australia, Poland and other nations made a similar shift, substituting online lectures and activities for in-person ones (Giannoulas et al., 2021; Fauzi et al., 2021; Lin and Nguyen, 2021; Migocka-Patrzałek et al., 2021). This shift is also evident in Nigeria, as National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) had started using this approach prior to the advent of COVID-19 and in light of the pandemic, NOUN and other organizations are diligently trying to enhance the procedure. Furthermore, Nigeria's Universal Basic Education Commission has established cutting-edge smart schools that make use of a blended learning strategy. These schools integrate technology by providing tablets to both teachers and students, fostering an environment where half of the lessons are conducted offline, while the remaining portion takes place online. This approach allows teachers to assess students' performance levels effectively. The introduction of smart schools represents a significant advancement in the educational landscape, showcasing a commitment to enhancing learning outcomes through the integration of modern technologies. These case studies provide insightful information about practical strategies for implementing remote learning and adjusting to the changing demands of instructors and students in the digital era.

Solution to Challenges Affecting Remote Learning among Educational Institutions in Nigeria

Recent research has identified several strategies for overcoming common challenges and achieving positive outcomes in remote learning environments. For example, a study by Zhang, Liu and Wang (2021) highlighted the importance of fostering a sense of community and belonging among students through virtual peer support groups and online discussion forums, which can mitigate feelings of isolation and enhance student engagement. Additionally, research by Wang and Cao (2022) emphasized the value of providing timely feedback and personalized support to students in virtual settings, leveraging digital tools such as learning analytics and adaptive learning platforms to track progress and tailor instruction to individual needs. Furthermore, studies by Jones, Watson, Smith and Brown (2021) and Chen, Wang, and Li (2021) underscored the effectiveness of collaborative teaching approaches, where educators collaborate across disciplines and share resources to design interdisciplinary projects and foster interdisciplinary thinking among students. These strategies offer practical insights into addressing challenges and promoting positive outcomes in remote learning environments, ultimately enhancing the quality of education in the post-pandemic era.

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Lessons Learned from Remote Learning Experiences as Shared by Teachers and Administrators

The widespread adoption of remote learning has provided educators and administrators with priceless knowledge. Prioritizing student involvement and interaction in virtual classrooms is an important lesson to learn. Education expert Dr. Audrey Cohan highlights the significance of preserving "a sense of community and connection" between teachers and students, identifying it as essential for successful learning outcomes (Edutopia). Teachers that embrace this idea include Sarah Alvarez (EdSurge), who emphasizes the importance of creating a safe space for students to participate and express themselves online. Administrators also emphasize how important it is to give teachers continual professional development and assistance so they may successfully manage the challenges of remote education.

Senior scholar at the Manhattan Institute Dr. Marcus A. Winters emphasises the critical role that technology tools and tactics designed for online learning environments play in preparing instructors (Education Next). Furthermore, the move to remote learning has highlighted how crucial it is to provide everyone with equal access to technology and internet connectivity. In order to guarantee that every student has equal access to learning opportunities, Dr. Ghody Muhammad, an associate professor of educational leadership at Georgia State University, highlights the necessity of bridging the digital gap (NPR). These observations illustrate the many opportunities and problems that come with making the switch to remote learning, as well as the continuous efforts made by administrators and teachers to adapt and innovate in the face of changing educational environments.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were proffered for long-term educational remote learning practices among educational institutions in Nigeria:

1. School administrators give top priority to providing instructors with ongoing training and assistance on effective remote teaching practices and technology integration. By making this commitment, instructors are guaranteed to have the abilities needed to successfully traverse virtual learning environments.
2. Educators should use techniques to improve interaction and engagement among students in remote learning environments. This can involve using interactive technologies, leading conversations in small groups, and using online communities to build a feeling of community.
3. To overcome the digital divide, educational institutions should give all students equitable access to technology and internet connectivity. Collaborate with relevant parties to identify any access gaps and close them, for as by providing internet hotspots and gadgets to impoverished areas.
4. The institution should keep lines of communication open and transparent between administrators, parents, students and teachers. Make use of a variety of communication channels to quickly resolve problems, set clear expectations, and provide critical information.
5. School administrators should acknowledge the particular difficulties associated with remote learning and give students' and teachers' mental health and wellbeing top priority. During remote learning, put methods in place for encouraging self-care, providing support services and creating a friendly online community to improve general well-being.

Conclusion

The post-pandemic era presents significant challenges as well as development prospects for educational management. A critical area of attention is to rethink and improve remote learning methodologies. Virtual schooling has become more popular as a result of the epidemic, which also brought attention to its drawbacks. To maintain remote learning's viability and efficacy in the future, educational management must investigate new avenues for practice and study. This entails delving deeper into recommended practices for virtual learning, including tactics for fostering student participation and communication, maximizing technology resources, and tackling concerns of fairness in terms of internet and technology access. To further understand the long-term impacts of distant learning on student learning results, social-emotional development, and general well-being, more research is also required.

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Comparative Relationship between Infrastructural Development and Biodiversity Loss in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The aim of the study was to investigate the relationship between infrastructural development and biodiversity loss in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. To achieve the purpose of this study, a null hypothesis was formulated to guide the study. A review of related literature was carried out based on the variable of this study. The survey research design was considered useful for the study. The research adopted multiple sampling approaches. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 234 subjects used as sample in each ward in the Local Government Area. A fifteen-item modified four (4) points Likert scale questionnaire titled Infrastructural Development and Biodiversity Loss Questionnaire (IDBLQ) was the instrument used for data collection. To test the hypothesis formulated for the study, Pearson's product moment correlation statistical tools was used for data analysis. The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 alpha level. The results from data analysis and hypothesis testing indicated that there is a significant relationship between infrastructural development and biodiversity loss in the study area. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that relevant authorities should ensure that infrastructural development projects are properly located in line with laid down policies and regulations in order to prevent continuous loss of biodiversity.

Keyword: infrastructure, development, biodiversity loss, Akamkpa Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria.

Introduction

Biodiversity, the variation of life on Earth, is a major factor in nature's resilience. In a bio diverse ecosystem, the environment changes and some organisms can no longer thrive, others can take their place and fulfill essential functions. It is often the most overlooked species that are the most important to healthy ecosystems. Insects, for example, play an essential role in pollinating flowering plants one of the foods we eat depends on pollinators.

Jacob (2017) asserts that healthy ecosystems provide us with many essentials we take for granted. Plants converts energy from the sun and also makes it available to other life forms bacteria and other living organisms break down organic matter into nutrients which help provide plants with healthy soil to grow in. Agents of pollination are essential in plants reproduction and therefore, help to guarantee food product for mankind. Plants and oceans act as major carbon sinks.

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Biodiversity provides us with clean air, fresh water, good quality soil and crop pollination. It helps us fight climate change and adapt to it as well as reduce the impact of natural hazards. Since living organisms interact in dynamic ecosystems, the disappearance of one species can have a far-reaching impact on the food chain. It is impossible to know exactly what the consequences of mass extinctions would be for humans, but we do know that for now the diversity of nature allows us to thrive. Biodiversity is very vital to the survival of mankind and as such should be considered as an important component of human existence. It provides for the various basic needs of man and the sustainability of the ecosystems. This emphasizes the role of biodiversity in the sustainability of the human race (Fred, 2016).

The loss of biodiversity has become a source of Concern to various stakeholders in environment and ecological ecosystem. The Continuous disappearance of various plant and animal species has been a regular feature and does not seem feasible in recent years. This is because man is inventing new technology and equipment that will aid improved harvesting process, processing, storing and transportation of biological diversity for various purposes. These purposes stem from domestic, commercial, industrial and other process alike. The continuous depletion, endangerment and extinction of species have affected the balance of nature. Government and other agencies involved in biodiversity conservation have introduced various policies that would regulate the use of biodiversity. Some of these include the introduction of Environmental or conservation education, the enactment of legislation among other (Obi, 2017).

These efforts have yielded little or no result with regards to the reduction in the loss of biodiversity. People seem so determined to exploit biological resources as a major source of their livelihood. This accounts mostly for the insignificant result obtained from the intervention activities of both government and non-governmental organizations. Several factors have been identified as possible determinants of the loss of biodiversity. Albert (2015) states that the process of providing certain infrastructure could lead to the destruction of vegetation cover that houses several species of plant and animals. The provision of these infrastructure might require the cutting down of large forested areas or of certain habitats. These activities could pose severe threat to biodiversity leading to their endangerment or extinction. These the researcher to investigate how assumptions motivated infrastructural development relate with biodiversity loss in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State.

The findings of this study will be relevant to students, residents of the host communities, the Ministry of Environment, non-governmental organizations, policy makers and researchers.

Students of environmental education and other disciplines will see the findings of this study as a source of acquiring relevant knowledge on the phenomenon under study. Inhabitants of the host communities will also be sensitized through the findings of this study on how their various activities relate with biodiversity loss, in order to promote sustainable forest management. The Ministry of Environment will also be further sensitized on how the activities engaged by rural dwellers impact of the loss of biological diversity in order to help provide alternative livelihood where necessary. Non-governmental organizations working on biodiversity conservation and management will see the findings of this study as a relevant document that would help them achieve their intervention goals and objectives. Policy makers will also see the findings of this study as a source of baseline data for formulated new policies that would promote effective biodiversity conservation and management. Researchers intending to conduct a similar study in other locations or on a broader Scope will see the findings of this study as a reference material for their studies.

Humans are constantly involved in a variety of activities that tend to impact negatively on the quality and well-being of the environment. This continuous degradation of the environment has resulted in the destruction of plant and animal species. Akamkpa is blessed with abundance of biological diversity. There is a reasonable quantity of virgin forest still intact due to the long existing belief that, forests in the area harbour spirits which may hurt anyone that trespasses it. Despite the cultural taboos that prevent people from the indiscriminate use of biological diversity, it is common to see people young and old go into the forest without fear or respect to the cultural norms, values and belief system obtainable in the area. It is quite disturbing to see the rate at which biodiversity is been damaged, destroyed and taken away without any deliberate attempt to replace them. The fear is that, if nothing is done about the situation, sooner than possible biodiversity resources may completely disappear through extinction. This study was therefore geared towards attempting to find answers to the following question how do infrastructural development relate with biodiversity loss in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State?

The following theory was considered as the framework for this study in order to help explain the interrelations among variables in the study.

Lanza's biocentric theory (1997); This theory was propounded by Robert Lanza in 1997. The theory holds that nature is sacred and as Such should be revered or emphasizing man's interdependence with nature further holds that the living and non-living things were created before man and therefore have their own right of existence inspite of man. The emphasis of this theory is that; man should live tenderly with nature in mutual or symbiotic existence. Africa culture and most indigenous the world-over before the advent of colonization were actually given to the biocentric worldview value judgement about nature.

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In fact, not only we the Africans or native tribes are conscious of their interdependence with nature, they even went as far as ascribing life and supernatural power to nature. All these, made it imperative to conserve nature.

The implication of this theory to the present study is that the biocentric theory promotes and lays the foundation for biodiversity conservation and management at various levels. This theory is against wanton destruction and unsustainable exploitation of biodiversity and emphasize that man is not superior to nature but should live in mutual or symbiotic relationship with it. Thus, considering the right of these natural resources to exist within the environment and their relevant to him justifies the view point of the biocentric theory. This theory is the basis for sustainable utilization and management of natural resources as well as sustainable development. Based on these, the conservation of biodiversity takes its roots from the value judgment of this theory.

The main purpose of this study was to investigate infrastructural development and biodiversity loss in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State, Specifically the study:

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis was formulated to guide the study:

There is no significant relationship between infrastructural development and biodiversity loss in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Literature Review

Infrastructure plays a key role in biodiversity loss, because of the impact associated with it on the environment. The negative and cooperate for fair trade products environmental impact of infrastructure can occur construction, operation upgrade and decommissioning of infrastructures. While similar environmental impacts such as the use of natural resources, changes in land use disturbances in the human environmental may occur in the construction and operational stages of most types of infrastructures, some sectors may bring about distinct impact. Some examples of these impacts are:

1. Water infrastructure: This may result in excessive use of water resources or water pollution (leakages insufficient treatment of sewage).
2. Road infrastructure: This can fragment habitats and or cut off migration routes of animals leading to biodiversity loss.
3. Mining can bring about the decline in groundwater levels, mining waste and noise caused by explosion.

Even though development can be used as an opportunity to investigate the archaeology of the site and removal, restoration and conservation of items found, the adverse impacts it has on biodiversity still remains. These includes, removal of trees and in particular disruption of forests, can reduce their sustainability and their ability to act as a "sink" for carbon dioxide emissions and hence reduce their impact on global warming (Cervero, 2009). It can remove natural barriers to wind and weather which can add to soil erosion and impacts on other ecology. The construction and disposal of infrastructure can impact on the condition of the soil structure. For example, the use of vehicles and heavy machinery may cause compaction of soils, land clearance may lead to soil erosion and infrastructure work may cause soil contamination with toxic materials, there by scaring away any organism including man from his original habitat.

The large-scale problems of unprecedented population growth and inappropriate development are degrading the land, water and atmosphere thereby extinguishing earth's organisms and the habitats they inhabit. If we ignore and downplay the problems associated with infrastructure development and biodiversity loss in favour of our imperative personal or group gain, or national priorities, we are courting global disaster. Although population growth may not be the sole cause of environmental degradation, it is almost always an exacerbating factor (Barclay & Gray, 2016). As population pressures on land and other natural resource build. The need for more infrastructure development to meet their needs, the more intensity of natural disasters especially flood and drought that is possible of forcing organisms to migrate from their natural habitat or relocate to another habitat thereby causing biodiversity loss to occur and the effects, more tragic (Ephraim, 2016).

Biodiversity is irreversible to species that are lost. The potential impact on the human condition, on the fabric of the earth's living systems, and on the process of evolution is immense. Biologically diversity is the variety of life forms, the genetic diversity they contain, and the assemblages they form, biological system, whether tundra, forests, savannahs, grasslands, deserts lakes, rivers, wetlands, coastal communities, or marine ecosystems, are functionally complex, and this complexity is associated in often obscure ways, with the diversity of their component species.

Biodiversity is the variety of and variability among living organisms and the ecological complexes in which they occur. Diversity is the number of different items and their relative frequency. For biological diversity, these items are organized at many levels, ranging from chemical structures that are the molecular basis of heredity to complete ecosystems (OTA, 2017).

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To curb the problem associated with biodiversity loss through infrastructure development, there is a need to, as a matter of urgent importance; establish an international network of parliamentarians to undertake initiatives to mainstream biodiversity conservation in infrastructure development. This is important to build political leadership for biodiversity conservation and strategic environmental impact assessment should be made to provide for holistic infrastructure planning and thereby increase the spatial and ecological conditions for green infrastructure to contribute to biodiversity preservation (Pease, 2014).

From the review done in this chapter of the various eminent scholars, it has been established that related literature reviewed has enabled the researcher to focus on the situation on ground as regard infrastructural development and biodiversity loss in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State. The depressing because available studies revealed that there is a relationship between infrastructural development and biodiversity loss. The reviewed literature revealed that infrastructure development influence biodiversity loss. The review established that they still exist the problem of bush burning, and deforestation practices on the environment during infrastructural developments which lead to biodiversity loss in particular on the resources of the environment. It is on the basis of this gap identified that this research is carried out to encourage, and advised in other to assimilate information to enlighten and create awareness.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is the survey design. Survey research design is a research approach that attempts to systematically collect a data about a group of individuals (sample) who have the same characteristics, through the use of written or oral data collection instruments; interviews, questionnaires, telephone interview, mails, and internet, concerning participants' responses on facts, opinions, attitudes among others to enable the researcher study the group (population) of which the researcher has no control over the independent and dependent variables and the phenomenon is studied in its raw form as it is happening (Isangedighi, 2012). This design was chosen because this research is designed to investigate infrastructural development and biodiversity loss. The purpose of this study can be achieved through the survey research design.

This research was conducted in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State. It lies between latitude 8°31.46" North of the Equator and longitude 5°25'59.7" East of the Greenwich Meridian. Akamkpa Local Government Area has a land mass of 5003 square kilometres. It is bounded to the north by Biase Local Government Area to the south by Calabar Municipality, to the east by Odukpani Local Government Area and to the west by Itu Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Akamkpa Local Government Area is situated in the tropical rainforest belt with considerable amount of rainfall, which spans between April and November each year. These characterizes the crops Cultivated by its residents. The people are known for the production of food crops like maize, cassava, vegetables, spices, fruits among others at subsistence and commercial levels. The people also cultivate cash crops like oil palms, rubber, banana and plantain. The study area has a very rich cultural heritage, which is characterized by attractive festivals and amazing dances. There are several public educational institutions in the study area, which provide formal education to residents of the study area. The population of this research work consists of all adult residents in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State. They comprised individuals from various occupations including, hunters, students, and civil servants. The Fishermen, farmers, estimated population for the study is eighty-seven thousand three hundred and forty-two (228,543) persons (NPC, 2022).

The simple random sampling technique was adopted in selecting the communities used for the study. The researcher visited Akamkpa Local Government Forestry charge office to obtain the list of Communities in the study area. The names of all the twenty-eight communities were written on pieces of paper and folded into ball-like shapes, which were poured into a bowl. The paper-balls were properly mixed and the researcher picked seven paper-balls from the bowl representing twenty five percent of communities. The communities whose names appeared on the picked pieces of paper were selected for the study. To select the respondents used for the study, systematic random sampling technique was adopted. The researcher took time to number the houses in the study area. In each of the selected communities, the researcher selected every tenth house and in each of the selected houses, one respondent was selected. These individuals constituted the sample for the study. The sample for this study consisted of two hundred and thirty-four (234) respondents that were randomly selected from seven forest communities in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State. They were drawn from various occupations.

The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire. The instrument was developed by the researcher and titled "Infrastructural Development and Biodiversity Loss Questionnaire (IDBLQ) and divided into two sections, Section A contained items on respondents' personal data while section B was designed using four point modified Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). It contained fifteen items measuring the variables of the

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stud. Items 1-5 measured infrastructural development while items 6-15 measured biodiversity loss. The instrument used for data collection was presented to a lecturer in Environmental Education and two other lecturers in Test and Measurement for content and face validity. The instrument was scrutinized and necessary inputs made to improve the quality and ability of the research instrument to measure what it is intended to measure. The suggestions made were put in place before a final copy was developed. The questionnaire was used to obtain relevant data from respondents. The researcher visited all the communities selected for the study to engage the respondents for data collection. In each community visited, the researcher obtained permission from the village head after explaining the purpose of her visit. Two hundred and thirty-four copies of the research instrument were administered and retrieved in five days. The responses obtained from respondents were scored accordingly to enable the researcher complete the coding procedure. For items that are positively worded, Strongly Agree (SA) was scored 4, Agree (A) 3, Disagree (D) 2 and Strongly Disagree (SD) 1. The reverse scoring schedule was applied to negatively worded items in the questionnaire.

Result

This chapter presents the results of data analysis and testing of hypothesis as well as their interpretation. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between infrastructural development and biodiversity loss in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Table 1: Pearson product moment correlation analysis of the relationship between infrastructural development and biodiversity loss in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Variables	X	S.D	r-cal	Sig.
Infrastructural development	15.296	2.963	0.324*	0.001
Biodiversity loss	30.369	4.816		

Significant at 0.05, df = 232, critical r = 0.138

The independent variable in this hypothesis is infrastructural development while the dependent variable is biodiversity loss. Pearson product moment correlation statistical tool was used for data analysis. The result obtained from analysis is data and testing of hypothesis in the study is presented in table 1. The result of analysis presented in table 1 shows that the calculated r-value of 0.324 is higher than the p-value of 0.001 at 0.05 level of significance with 232 degree of freedom. This implies that the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between infrastructural development and biodiversity loss in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Discussion of findings

The finding obtained from analysis of data and testing of hypothesis in the study revealed that the null hypothesis was rejected. The implication of this finding is that there was a significant relationship between infrastructural development and biodiversity loss in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State. The reason for this finding could be that as population continue to grow across various communities in the study area, there has been an increasing development of infrastructure. The need to build new schools, markets, health Centres, roads, churches among others has increased the pressure on biodiversity through the destruction of their natural habitats. In the course of this doing this, many species of flora and fauna has been displaced, endangered and even extinct. No infrastructure is developed in a vacuum but on a particular sphere of the environment. This has its attendant consequences on the biodiversity that once inhabited such area because they are usually displaced, destroyed or modified in the process.

This finding is in agreement with that of Ephraim (2016) who reported that the large-scale problems of unprecedented population growth and inappropriate development are degrading the land, water and atmosphere thereby extinguishing earth's organisms and the habitats they inhabit. If we ignore and downplay the problems associated with infrastructure development and biodiversity loss in favour of our imperative personal or group gain, or national priorities, we are courting global disaster.

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Although population growth may not be the sole cause of environmental degradation, it is almost always an exacerbating factor. As population pressures on land and other natural resource build. The need for more infrastructure development to meet their needs, the more intensity of natural disasters especially flood and drought that is possible of forcing organisms to migrate from their natural habitat or relocate to another habitat thereby causing biodiversity loss to occur and the effects, more tragic.

The finding of this study also supported that of OTA (2017) who revealed that Biodiversity is the variety of and variability among living organisms and the ecological complexes in which they occur. Diversity is the number of different items and their relative frequency. For biological diversity, these items are organized at many levels, ranging from chemical structures that are the molecular basis of heredity to complete ecosystems (OTA, 2017). To curb the problem associated with biodiversity loss through infrastructure development, there is a need to, as a matter of urgent importance; establish an international network of parliamentarians to undertake initiatives to mainstream biodiversity conservation in infrastructure development. This is important to build political leadership for biodiversity conservation and strategic environmental impact assessment should be made to provide for holistic infrastructure planning and thereby increase the spatial and ecological conditions for green infrastructure to contribute to biodiversity preservation.

Conclusion

The main purpose of this study was to investigate and present findings on anthropogenic activities and biodiversity loss in Akamkpa Local Government Area of Cross River State. The findings obtained from analysis of data and testing of hypothesis in the study revealed that there was a significant relationship between infrastructural development and biodiversity loss in the study area. With the above result it was concluded that there is a significant relationship between infrastructural development and biodiversity loss in Odukpani Local Government Area of Cross River State.

Recommendation

The researcher made the following recommendations based on the findings obtained in the study;

1. Residents in the study area should be regularly and adequately sensitized on the danger of uncontrolled bush burning during development in order to prevent loss of biodiversity
2. Relevant authorities should ensure that infrastructural development projects are properly located in line with laid down policies and regulations in order to prevent continuous loss of biodiversity.

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